

REPORT ON PRIORITIZATION OF ACTOR NEEDS AND CRITERIA FOR LIVING LAB/ LIGHTHOUSE IDENTIFICATION

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ABBREVIATIONS AND DEFINITIONS**ABBREVIATIONS:**

AE	Agroecology
ALL	Agricultural Living Lab
AELL	Agroecology Living Lab
AKIS	Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems
CS	Citizen Science
CSA	Collaborative Support Action
D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
EIP-AGRI	Agricultural European Innovation Partnership
ENoLL	European Network of Living Labs
EU	European Union
GIS	Geographic Information Systems
LH	Lighthouses
LL	Living Labs
LTER	Long-Term Ecosystem Research
MS	Member States
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
NUTS	Nomenclature of territorial units for statistics
POL	Product Oriented Living Labs
R&I	Research and Innovation
RI	Research infrastructure
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SH LL	Soil Health Living Lab
SMART	Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Realistic, Timebound
SMS	Soil Mission Support
SRA	Strategic Research Agenda
ULL	Urban Living Lab
UTL	Urban Transition Living Lab
WG5	(Temporary) Working Group 5 for the implementation of the Mission for Soil food and health (active in 2021)
WP	Work Package

DEFINITIONS:

Actor	Stakeholder who actively engages in land and soil management, so who really acts
Actor needs	That what increases the gains, or relieves the pains that an actor faces in his/her job to do
Citizens	The general public (i.e. non-scientists) (Buytaert et al., 2014)
Citizen science	The participation of citizens in the generation of new knowledge (Buytaert et al., 2014) and/or data
Co-creation / co-production / joint-fact finding	A process in which stakeholders with differing viewpoints and interests work together to develop data and information, analyse facts and forecasts, develop common assumptions and informed opinion, finally, use the information they have developed to reach decisions together (Ehrmann and Stinson, 1999) <i>(On the topic of this report, this process also leads to soil management practices)</i>
Ecosystem services	The services provided and the benefits people derive from these services, both at the ecosystem and at the landscape scale, including public goods related to the wider ecosystem functioning and society well-being" (Haines-Young and Potschin 2018)
Living Labs	"Soil health living labs" are defined as "user-centred, place-based and transdisciplinary research and innovation ecosystems, which involve land managers, scientists and other relevant partners in systemic research and codesign, testing, monitoring and evaluation of solutions, in real-life settings, to improve their effectiveness for soil health and accelerate adoption." These living labs are collaborations between multiple partners that operate at regional or sub-regional level and coordinate experiments on several sites within a regional or sub-regional area (or working landscapes) (EC, 2021)
Lighthouses	"Lighthouses" are defined as "places for demonstration of solutions, training and communication that are exemplary in their performance in terms of soil health improvement". They are local sites (one farm, one forest exploitation, one industrial site, one urban city green area, etc.) that can be included in a living lab area or be situated outside a living lab area (EC, 2021)
SMS expert group	Key actors who engage in SMS in the co-creation of the SMS roadmap for R&I on land and soil management
Soil Health	The capacity of soils to contribute to ecosystem services in line with the SDGs and the Green Deal. (EC, 2021)
Stakeholders	Those who are affected in their interest or concern by changes in land and soil management

SUMMARY

The EU Soil Mission “A Soil Deal for Europe”

Soil health is vital for a wide range of ecosystem services. The EU Soil Mission “A Soil Deal for Europe” (EC, 2021) accelerates the transition to healthy soils through ambitious actions in 100 Living Labs and Lighthouses within territorial settings, combined with an ambitious transdisciplinary R&I programme, a robust, harmonised soil monitoring framework and increased soil literacy and communication to engage with citizens, all of this in synergy with relevant EU instruments and policies.

This deliverable

The H2020 Soil Mission Support (SMS) project supports the implementation of the Soil Mission. This SMS deliverable reports the aspects of identification and prioritization of actor needs in relation to the Soil Mission and elaborates on criteria for Soil Health Living Labs and Lighthouses (SH LL & LH).

Actors are defined as stakeholders who actively engage in land and soil management, so who really act. Actor needs are defined as that what increases the gains, or relieves the pains that actors face in their job to do. Living labs are understood as user-centred, place-based and transdisciplinary research and innovation ecosystems between multiple partners established at regional or sub-regional levels. Each living lab includes several sites at which systemic research and codesign, testing, monitoring and evaluation of solutions take place. (EC, 2021). Lighthouses are rather understood as one site for demonstration of solutions, training and communication that are exemplary in their performance in terms of soil health improvement (EC, 2021).

LL & LH and actor needs very much interrelate. Living Labs are efficient instruments for actors to experiment in real life settings. Lighthouses have a real demonstrative potential to encourage and engage larger communities. Hence, identification of the actor needs towards soil health is crucial to enable their engagement in the activities of the “Soil Deal for Europe” i.e. to make the transitions needed to significantly improve European Soil Health.

Actor needs

SMS anticipated that in order to be able to engage actors, it is needed to know and then express ‘what is in for them?’ Therefore, SMS drafted value propositions tailored to different actor groups (D3.3, Brils et al., 2021). To further refine these propositions, the next step was to specify and prioritize the actor needs in relation to the objectives of the EU Soil Mission. Primary source of information for achieving insight in the actor needs was the SMS survey on actor needs. Furthermore, two workshops were held with actors to provide a supplementary source of information.

The SMS survey was prepared and sent to approximately 550 soil professionals, all over Europe. These professionals are expected to be knowledgeable about the topics that are raised in the survey. Thus, the survey was not sent to citizens/general public/consumers as a specific actor group. In total 93 respondents responded to the survey: 32 partly and 61 fully. Respondents were asked to complete the survey from the perspective of their organization. Responding organizations are active in most European Member States and in some non-EU countries. Most respondents were researchers, policy makers and governmental organisations. The lowest response came from the land-users, managers and owner’s actor group.

The workshops were held at the AquaConSoil conference, visited by service providers and researchers with an urban/industrial background; and one with the SMS Expert Group, consisting of representatives from relevant networks covering different actor and land use groups.

After a joint analysis and synthesis of the outcome of the survey as well as the workshops it is concluded that the generic actor needs – i.e. applicable to all the actor groups – in order of priority are:

1. **Funding:** This appears the number one need for all the actor groups, but they need it for different reasons, which are linked to their specific actor interests, e.g.: policy and governmental organisations need it for capacity; the research community needs it for R&I including (long-term) observation; landowners and private sector need it for the implementation of measures/infrastructure.
1. **Legislation/policy frameworks:** This appears the number two need for all the actor groups, but legislation/policy needs vary between the various actor groups, e.g.: Policy and governmental organisations need it to set clear boundaries and targets; Landowners and private sector need it to create a level playing field, receive guidance and act.
2. **Knowledge/R&I in order to inform policy and measures:** For some of the Soil Mission objectives there is a clear need expressed for knowledge/R&I to inform policy making (legislation/frameworks) as well as to inform the design or increase the effectiveness of measures (e.g. solutions, best practices to improve land management, restore carbon stocks etc.)
3. **Awareness raising and communication:** Different actor groups express different viewpoints regarding awareness raising and communication. In general, the involvement of citizens is regarded as very important for any actor interacting with society. Furthermore, reaching out to for example farmers and project developers is also regarded as an important need.

It is now recommended to combine these results with the results from D3.3 for designing of a theory of change or intervention logic for each specific Soil Mission objective. Important challenges that need to be address in the steps are: Changing needs in the different phases of the planning and implementation process; Being aware of short-term interests and long-term ambitions; Searching for comparable themes between the groups (can be cross-cutting themes such as how to organize, finance etc.). The results will be described and integrated in D2.4 which will provide an important basis to prepare and deliver the Soil Mission roadmap in October 2022 (D3.5).

Criteria for Soil Health Living Labs and Lighthouses

SMS has built upon previous work done for LL & LH (D3.1, Maring et al., 2021) and in interaction with Working Group 5 (WG5) of the Mission Board on Soil Health and Food, that elaborated on living labs and lighthouses for the EU Mission “A soil deal for Europe” and is in line with the recently published implementation plan (EC, 2021).

Soil Health Living Labs being place-based, user-centred, transdisciplinary in which different actors (practice, policy, science, citizens) codesign and cocreate approaches and measures in real-life settings to improve soil health. These Living Labs act on landscape or ecosystem level and consist of multiple sites; **Soil Health Lighthouses** are sites, with exemplary performance in terms of soil health improvement. They can already exist or be a emerge from a LL site.

The **list of current LL & LH** as collated by the Soil Mission Board and the SMS project has been further elaborated. The list contains LL & LH that qualify as SH LL & LH – following the definition in the implementation plan, but it also contains many initiatives that possibly better qualify as ‘awareness, education and exchange’ initiatives and some on R&I and monitoring. The list is currently further complemented e.g. georeferencing is included to be able to map LL & LH.

Validation of what qualifies as a Soil Health (SH) LL & LH is important for the Mission to setup 100 LL and LH. Therefore, a limited set of manageable **criteria**, linked to the categories “scale”, “aim”, “activities”, “participants” and “context” was proposed for both SH LL and LH. These validation criteria were elaborated along the **characteristics for SH LL and LH** as proposed in the “Soil Deal for Europe”. The actual full validation of the (SH) LL & LH list is not part of the Soil Mission Support project.

To **establish a network of SH LL & LH**, it is of importance to find locations (e.g. in member states, on a level fit for analyses to the basic regions for the application of regional policies (=NUTS2¹ level), covering a broad range of geographic and geophysical conditions including soil types and socio-economic conditions) and the topics (covering different land uses, EU Soil Mission objectives) where SH LL & LH can be located. The current overview of LL and LH as mentioned above needs to be validated first to see where suitable initiatives are located and which topics they cover. The overview needs to be crosschecked after a more thorough inventory of specific soil needs as will be performed by follow-up projects of SMS as set out in the SOIL-MISSION-2021 calls.

When setting up SH LL & LH, or a network of these, it is important that next to the characteristics / criteria some **success factors** are considered, such as the political context, available resources, a clear outcome and collaboration. This will contribute to viability, sustainability and continuity of the LL & LH. Continuity is part of a set of **principles** that can help **designing SH LL**. The other principles are openness, realism, empowerment/influence of the actors involved and spontaneity/adaptivity within LL & LH.

Within these characteristics/criteria, success factors and principles, the **role of actors and collaboration** is crucial. The necessary but still untapped link between the soil health needs of actors in different circumstances and SH LL & LH is therewith supported. Related to this is the question what effective **business models** for SH LL & LH are. These should be further elaborated.

Social and economic scientists (such as policy scientists, economists, innovation science and communication science experts) need to help to develop the connections between the operational goals (R&I, SH LL & LH, monitoring, soil literacy) of the EU Mission “A Soil deal for Europe”. They can help to increase the likelihood that activities of the EU mission will have **impact**, including that the results will be adopted by land users and the public.

Finally, the **governance and funding of a LL & LH network** should be further elaborated under the activities of implementing the EU Soil Mission aimed at setting up a network of SH LL & LH. Issues and questions to resolve are: How to deal with ‘existing’ LL & LH versus ‘new’ LL & LH?; How to **learn and exchange** between LL & LH?; How to **monitoring** progress on their impact, outputs, outcomes?; How to **upscale** both results as methods to setup successful LL & LH? Experiences from existing networks and initiatives can be helpful to answer these questions. This will be further covered by the follow up projects of SMS as set out in the SOIL-MISSION-2021 calls.

¹ NUTS: Nomenclature of territorial units for statistics

1 INTRODUCTION

Soil health is vital for the delivery of food, energy, and biomaterials, as well as climate change adaptation and mitigation, biodiversity below and above ground and wide range of further ecosystem services. Pressure on land and soil is growing due to competing demands for land and bio-based products. A sustainable soil management that satisfies the increasing demand and avoids soil degradation requires coordinated research and innovation (R&I), sound and integrated policies and involvement of a large diversity of actors, from producers to citizens. “A Soil Deal for Europe” will actively address the above in the coming years (textbox 1-1).

Textbox 1-1: A Soil Deal for Europe: 100 Living labs and lighthouses to lead the transition towards healthy soils by 2030 (Source: EC 2020, page 2)

A Soil Deal for Europe:

100 Living labs and lighthouses to lead the transition towards healthy soils by 2030

The Green Deal needs healthy soils that can provide the (ecosystem) services that are crucial for our planet and society. Degradational pressures, mostly because of human activities linked to consumer demand and industrial processes, affect the health of the soil through physical damage or the introduction of pollutants. In turn, these processes disrupt the capacity of soils to supply a range of ecosystem services, with significant economic, environmental and societal consequences. Recent floods in Europe have shown how the effects of climate change are exacerbated by unhealthy, i.e. compacted, sealed and eroded soils. According to an assessment undertaken by the JRC and the Mission Board, 60-70% of soils in Europe are in an unhealthy condition. It is time to act.

Soil health can be restored through a range of measures. While some require longer timeframes, many can have a rapid beneficial impact. Several of these restoration processes could be easily implemented but - to be effective - require a step up in the extent of application. This increase should be driven by a greater societal understanding, demonstration of best practices, developments in research and innovation, of the factors driving soil health. This is where the mission comes into play.

The mission will pioneer, showcase and accelerate the transition to healthy soils through ambitious actions in 100 living labs and lighthouses within territorial settings. This will be combined with an ambitious transdisciplinary R&I programme, a robust, harmonised soil monitoring framework and increased soil literacy and communication to engage with citizens. Together with the effects of EU instruments funded under the Common Agricultural Policy other EU instruments and wide societal engagement, these measures are expected to result in a step change improvement on how we manage and use soils for wide societal benefits.

Recent scientific assessments have confirmed the mission’s ambition and the viability of its goal to significantly increase the share of currently 30-40% of healthy soils to levels that are in line with Green Deal commitments and targets by 2030.

1.1 The Soil Mission Support project

The H2020 Soil Mission Support (SMS) CSA project employs an approach to create an effective framework for action in the wider area of soil health and land management by coordinating efforts and pooling resources, by developing a coherent portfolio of R&I activities and by identifying criteria for Living Labs (LL) and Lighthouses (LH) to enable experimenting solutions and codesign and cocreation by a variety of actors. Activities include the analysis of the needs for R&I on soil and land management as expressed through actor consultation and involvement and research projects, the identification of gaps, priority areas and types of action for intervention including Living Labs and Lighthouses. The action fields range from agriculture and forestry to spatial planning, land remediation, climate action and disaster control.

SMS outcomes and results include:

- An actor-based, co-created roadmap for R&I on soil and land management, contributing to the objectives of the EU Mission “A soil deal for Europe”;
- Improved coordination with existing activities in Europe and globally, thereby raising visibility and effectiveness of R&I funding.
- Identification of and learning from existing and potential Living Labs and Lighthouses for cocreating, prototyping, testing and demonstrating solutions in order to understand and explore opportunities and find solutions for competing demands of soil use.

With its activities, SMS supports the European Commission (EC) and the Mission Board of the Horizon Europe Mission in delivering the objectives and related targets of the “Soil deal for Europe (EC, 2021).

Figure 1-1: Soil Health drivers and impacts (centre of the figure), the four operational objectives and crosscutting dimensions of the EU Mission “A soil deal for Europe” (Source: EC, 2021)

1.2 Objectives of this deliverable

This deliverable 3.4 is part of SMS WP3 'R&I Roadmap co-creation', task 3.2 'Engaging with soil and land management actors'.

This deliverable has two **main objectives**:

- 1) **Prioritization of the “needs” or “interests” of actors** to be engaged in sustainable soil and land management: The objective here is to further define and prioritize the key actor needs / interests ('what is in for them') to engage in sustainable soil and land management. Knowing this will also help to engage them in the SMS activities, such as setting up the roadmap for sustainable land and soil management linked to the objectives of the EU Mission “A soil deal for Europe”, and its activities, such as engagement in the Soil Health Living Labs. The “prioritization in actor needs” builds upon D3.2 detailed actor analysis (László et al., 2021) and D3.3 actor engagement guide (Brils et al., 2021).
- 2) **Proposing criteria for the identification of Soil Health Living Labs (LL)/ Lighthouses (LH)**: The objective is to further elaborate characteristics, selection and success criteria for Soil Health Living Lab / Lighthouses to support the implementation of the LL&LH operational objective in Horizon Europe (Figure 1-1) which aims to set up a dense and European covering network of SH LL and LH to boost sustainable soil and land management in Europe. The “criteria for living lab/ lighthouse identification” builds upon D3.1 concept note on Criteria for setting up living labs and lighthouses (Maring et al, 2021).

Although these two objectives are reported separately in this deliverable, they very much interrelate. **Living Labs** (implemented in many domains such as ICTs, rural development and sustainable cities and now also in soil health) are efficient instruments for actors to experiment in real-life settings. **Lighthouses** have a real demonstrative potential to encourage and engage larger communities. Identifying the **actor needs towards soil health** is crucial to engage actors that directly or indirectly rely on healthy soils and land in LL and LH, but also in the other activities of the “Soil deal for Europe” (Figure 1-2) to make the transitions needed to significantly improving European soil Health.

1.3 Target group of this deliverable

The target group of this deliverable is, on the one hand, the partners engaged in the SMS project, to enable them to engage actors in the roadmapping process in task 3.3. On the other hand, it targets at those who are involved in implementing the four operational objectives of the Horizon Europe Mission “A Soil Deal for Europe”, i.e. to enable them to engage actor groups in this process and to set up the LL & LH network. There are also relations with e.g. the agroecology partnership working on AgroEcology Living Labs (AELL). To help the methodology, description of characteristics and criteria on LL and LH forward, information is actively shared.

1.4 Structure of this deliverable

The topics of actor needs and SH LL & LH are, although interrelated, quite separately reported in this deliverable. In chapter 2, the methodology of both the topic of actor needs and the topic of SH LL & LH are described. Chapter 3 focuses on the actor needs only, chapter 4 on the LL & LH (however, this chapter also contains elements of actor needs). Chapter 5 gives an outlook and some recommendations for both topics.

Table 1-3: Report structure of this deliverable (SMS D3.4)

chapter	actor needs	SH LL & LH
2 Methodology		
2.1 Prioritization of actor needs	X	
2.2 Criteria for LL & LH		X
3 Actor needs and their priority		
3.1 Outcome of the workshops	X	
3.2 outcome of the survey	X	
3.3 prioritized actor needs	X	
4 Characteristics and criteria for SH LL & LH		
4.1 Characteristics SH LL & LH		X
4.2 Selection criteria for SH LL & LH		X
4.3 Establishing a SH LL network		X
4.4 Setting up successful SH LL & LH (networks)	X	X
5 Recommendations/outlook		
5.1 Prioritization of actor needs	X	
5.2 Criteria for LL & LH		X

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Actor needs and their priority

2.1.1 The actor needs

It is assumed that the engagement of actors is a prerequisite for achieving the EU Mission “A Soil Deal for Europe” and its related objectives as actors bring in knowledge, have the power to make or to block policy decisions and management measures and can ensure the relevance and acceptance of outcomes (Brils et al. 2021). Furthermore, it is assumed that actors will only engage if they recognize benefits in engagement, or, in other words: see “what’s in for them”.

In order to reveal “what is in for them” and thus engage actors, the needs of the actor group must be clarified and prioritized. Actor needs are defined as that what increases the gains, or relieves the pains that actors face in their job to do.

Table 2-1: Selected actor groups for which their needs are related to the Soil Mission objectives.

Actor group	Examples
Policymakers and governmental organisations	Local authorities/municipalities, regional, national, European ministries, governmental agencies and parliaments
Researchers / research communities	Research institutes, universities
Research funding organisations	Foundations, agencies
Land users / managers / owners and related organisations	Farmers, forestry, estate owners and their organisations, managers of urban green spaces, urban gardens, parks etc
Private sector and industry	Production, utilities, (petro)chemical, agro-food, energy, forestry
Service provider / Consultant	Advisory services, contractor, laboratories, testing and verification centres, certification bodies
Non-governmental organisations (NGOs)	Educational-, environmental/nature-, youth organizations

To structure the actor needs analysis, the logic as described in D3.3 (Brils et al., 2021) was applied. The basic rule of this logic is: *the more complex the issue at stake, the broader the set of actors to engage* (table 2-2).

Table 2-2: Type of participation in workshops and needs assessment. For more background information see D3.3 (Brils et al., 2021)

dominant characteristic of the issue	simple	complex	uncertain	ambiguous
type of participation	using existing routines to assess the issue and possible ways to address them	maximise the scientific knowledge of the issue and of the ways to address them	engage all affected stakeholders to collectively decide best way forward and learn-by-doing	societal debate about the issue, its underlying implications and best way forward

This dominant characteristic of the issues also has consequences for the actors involved: for example, in *simple*, only the regulatory bodies and experts are consulted. While in *uncertain* next to the regulatory bodies and experts also external scientists / researchers and affected stakeholders are involved. We also used this logic in the selection of respondents to the survey and participants to the workshops.

This logic starts with the Soil Mission objectives and focussing on the different actor groups that have been identified by the SMS project (Table 2-1). Because we define the soil mission as a an *uncertain*² issue all the actor groups from Table 2-1 are relevant. Then for each actor group, the needs per objective of the EU mission “A Soil Deal for Europe” are identified and prioritized. Thus, the Soil Mission objective is linked to the actor needs.

Primary source of information for achieving insight in the actor needs was the SMS survey on actor needs. Furthermore, two workshops were held with actors. However, as these workshops only engaged a relative low number of actors compared to the survey, the results of the workshops are only used as supplementary source of information. The survey and workshops methodologies are further described hereafter.

² Uncertain: this refers to the uncertainty of what, and how effective management measures may be. This type of issue acknowledges the different kinds of uncertainty: that there is (and will always be) lack of knowledge on how different parts of the soil system work and interact, and how it will change in time. This calls for learning cycles through small steps (accompanied by well-designed and targeted monitoring).

Primary source of information: Survey on actor needs

A survey was designed (Annex VIII) which focusses on the actors needs and priorities related to achievement of the objectives of the Soil Mission (see Annex I). The survey contained both multiple choice and open-ended questions and was sent out:

- by a bulk email - with all email addresses under Bcc - to:
 - Over 500 stakeholders as listed by Laszlo et al. (2021) in D3.2 Detailed actor analysis;
- by individual emails to:
 - The European networks and organizations who provided a Letter of Support for the SMS project;
 - The SMS Expert Group (table 2-3);
 - The SMS Advisory Board;
 - When receiving the responses, additional people were invited representing urban and industrial soils (networks around the FP5 HOMBRE project³ and H2020 INSPIRATION⁴ projects) because this group tended to get underrepresented.

Figure 2-1: Statistics of actors to which the survey on actor needs was sent to. In this map, the global and European networks (n=71) are left out. Please note that no organisations (with contact details) in member states Croatia, Cyprus, Luxembourg and Malta were identified at the time that the survey was sent out.

³ www.zerobrownfields.eu

⁴ <http://www.inspiration-h2020.eu/>

The survey was **sent to networks** (textbox 2-1) and **professionals** who are expected to be knowledgeable about the topics that are raised in the survey. Thus, the survey was not sent to citizens/general public/consumers as a specific actor group – this is in line with the engagement logic described in the previous section of this deliverable. In the accompanying email the **respondents were asked to fill out the survey from the perspective of their stakeholder or actor group**. The survey ran from the 5th of August until the 29th of September 2021. It is difficult to state the exact number of professionals who received the invitation to complete the survey, as some of the email addresses appeared not accurate and because some respondents also forwarded the survey to other professionals in their networks. However, best estimate is that approximately 550 professionals received the invitation to fill out the SMS survey. The survey responses can be found in Annex IX.

Text box 2-1: Collation of the actor list. Source: (Laszlo et al., 2021)

The focus in the actor mapping was mainly on already organised, European networks, covering organisations in different European countries, for SMS relevant topics, land uses, actor categories (R&I, policy makers, etc.). This choice was consciously made because the capacities and duration of SMS do not allow for national and regional actor specification or setting up national actor networks or hubs. Existing hubs such as those in EJP SOIL, are only covering the agricultural networks, therefore not being suitable for the Soil Mission / SMS, where all land uses and their audiences should be covered. The European network approach was therefore a good solution, also because they are in many cases active for a longer time, their members cover multiple European countries, and have a good overview of (strategic) research needs. Through participation from SMS activities by a representative, SMS reaches a far broader audience than through engagement of single actors.

Supportive source of information: 2 workshops

Workshop at AquaConSoil (June 16th, 2021)

AquaConSoil is a leading international conference in the field of soil quality and water management. It started in 1985. Since then, the conference was organized every two years. AquaConSoil welcomes delegates from all over and outside Europe, with representatives from science, policy and businesses / industry. In the first decades the symposium was called ConSoil and was strongly focused on contaminated soils. In the last decade, the scope broadened and since the Barcelona conference in 2013, the symposium is called AquaConSoil. The name change represents the necessary systems-thinking for sustainable use and management of soil, water and sediments.

During the online 2021 AquaConSoil conference (14 to 18 June), SMS organized an online 1.5 hours workshop (June 16th) entitled “Co-creating the European Roadmap for Land and Soil Related Research and Innovation”. The workshop attracted at its peak approximately 10 professionals: researchers and service providers mainly on the topic of the conference: contaminated land (industrial and urban land use).

After a brief introduction to the SMS project and its scope, the workshop participants actively engaged in the workshop by responding to the following statements or questions:

- **Urban or industrial soil management is relevant for achieving of the Soil Mission targets**
Participants could score each specific Soil Mission target, scores ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).
- **Gains and Pains?**
Participants could fill out their answers in chat boxes – as many as they pleased – on two questions. Participants were asked to start their answer by indicating the actor group to which the answer belongs. Some participants also put themselves in the shoes of other actor groups. The two questions were:
 - What would you gain (is your benefit) from sustainably managed soil?
 - What pains (headaches) do you fear when soil is sustainably managed?

Workshop with the SMS Expert group (June 22nd, 2021)

A 3.5-hour online workshop entitled “Co-creating a European research and innovation roadmap on soils and land management” was held, engaging the experts from the SMS Expert group (table 2-3). These 12 experts from key European organizations represent different actor groups and land use sectors⁵. After a broad introduction to the SMS project and its scope, the workshop participants actively engaged in the workshop by providing written contributions to an online collaborative whiteboard platform. Besides specific suggestions related to the vision of the roadmap, also suggestions were provided related to their need, benefits and priorities.

⁵ Engaging representatives from: JPI FACCE Scientific Advisory Board; representative of the Ecosystem Service Partnership; Local Governments for Sustainability (ICLEI); NICOLE network; Copa-Cogeca; The Common Forum on contaminated Land; European Forest Institute (EFI); The European Environmental Bureau (EEB); European Landowners Organisation (ELO), IFOAM and EJP Soil

Table 2-3: Members of the dedicated actor group (n=12, from each of the organisations/networks there is 1 representative, from ELO there are 2 representatives)

Organisation / network	Land use sector	Category
JPI FACCE https://faccejpi.net	Agriculture	R&I
Ecosystem Service Partnership https://www.es-partnership.org	All	R&I, policy makers and practitioners
Local Governments for Sustainability (ICLEI)	Urban	Policy makers
Network for Industrially Co-ordinated Sustainable Land Management in Europe (NICOLE) nicole.org	Industrial land	Industry, R&I, service providers/advisors
Copa-Cogeca copa-cogeca.eu	Agriculture	Practitioners (farmers and agri-cooperatives)
The Common Forum on contaminated Land https://www.commonforum.eu	Urban and industrial land	Policy makers
European Forest Institute (EFI) https://efi.int	Forestry	R&I (and policy support)
The European Environmental Bureau (EEB) eeb.org	All	Civil society: environmental citizens' organisations
European Landowners Organisation (ELO) elo.org	Agriculture, nature, forestry	Land owners and managers
IFOAM https://www.ifoam.bio/	Agriculture	Organisation with members from practitioners (farmers), civil society, policy makers, R&I
EJP Soil ejpsoil.eu	Agriculture	R&I

2.1.2 The actor priorities

The actor priorities relate to:

- How they perceive the importance and urgency of the Soil Mission objectives; and
- What their most important needs are regarding these objectives.

Importance and urgency of the objectives of the EU Mission “A Soil Deal for Europe”

For each of the eight Soil Mission objectives (Annex I), the survey respondents were asked to indicate how important (of great significance or value) and how urgent they consider the specific objective for their organisation. Respondents had the option to tick one of the next boxes: very, fairly, neutral, slightly, not at all, not applicable or no opinion. Thereafter they were asked to briefly motivate their answer by ticking one of the indicated options in the survey (Annex VIII) and/or fill out some text.

Actor needs regarding the Soil Mission objectives

In the survey as well as in the workshops, the actors were asked to specify their needs regarding the Soil Mission objectives. These results were clustered per Soil Mission objective and – where feasible – under each objective also clustered per actor group. The most important actor needs were identified through a joint analysis and synthesis of the outcome of the survey as well as the workshops.

Both the survey and the workshop data sets have a qualitative nature. For example, we asked for specific needs per soil mission by means of open questions, to get a better understanding of the needs and whether there was a difference between actor groups. This makes a rigorous quantitative statistical analysis not feasible. Therefore, a word cloud instrument was used to support this analysis and synthesis by showing the most common terms in the responses. Some descriptive statistics on the actors that filled out the survey are provided however.

2.2 Criteria for living labs (LL) and lighthouses (LH)

The work on LL&LH continues the earlier work for D3.1 Concept note on Criteria for setting up living labs and lighthouses (Maring et al, 2021), which mainly consisted of literature review.

This deliverable has been elaborated in close interaction with the Mission board on soil health and food Working Group 5 on living labs and lighthouses (“WG5”) that worked in the same period on the implementation of the EU Mission “A soil deal for Europe” (EC, 2021) and that was published around the same moment that the deliverable was due. The WG5 contact person reviewed the work presented in this report. Also, the CSA ALLREADY was again involved in discussions and the review of this report. The literature review that started when drafting D3.1 was expanded and the different topics in this report were further elaborated by Deltares with the input of trainees. Finally: Relevant meetings/webinars on LL were attended:

- EURAGRI webinar - Living Labs on June 9th, attended by Deltares;
- Webinar "Living Labs for sustainable AKIS and innovation support and AKIS for sustainable Living Labs" on July 2nd, attended by Deltares;
- EUSO Stakeholder Forum (19-21 Oct), attended by Deltares, ATK, ZALF and EAA

Characteristics

SMS adapted the definitions and characteristics of LL and LH, according to the “new” definitions in the implementation plan (EC, 2021). Characteristics for soil health (SH) LL and LH were further described to ensure there is a common understanding about what they are and contribute to (section 4.1).

Selection criteria for single LL & LH

Based on the characteristics, a procedure for validation⁶ is developed to assess if a LL & LH would qualify as a soil health LL & LH under the EU Mission “A soil deal for Europe”, i.e. if it matches the proposed characteristics. The validation method is proposed based on literature and by expert knowledge (WG5 of the Mission Board for Soil health and food and SMS partners); students have tested the validation method on applicability on a sample of LL from the overall list of LL&LH (see underneath) This is reported in sections 4.2.

Establishing a network of LL & LH

An overall list of LL & LH was constructed by merging information of the updated LL&LH list from the Mission board for Soil health and food (updated list received by June 2021), LL and LH by SMS partners (Wall et al., 2021) and further additions based on own knowledge, literature / online research). The actual validation by means of direct interviews of or workshops with all LL&LH in the list cannot take place within SMS⁵. However, some of the listed LL&LH initiatives (Annex III) were individually contacted by SMS partners for further information and engaging them in the Soil Mission activities of the project. The follow-up projects under the mission that will elaborate activities on the mapping and/or setup of LL networks will be actively informed by the SMS project concerning the information available on LL/LH’s.

⁶ We cannot do the validation in SMS due to time and budget restrictions, future actions funded under the mission should take over.

The LL⁷ for Agroecology transition that were inventoried in December 2020 by the EC in the “*First screening of European agroecology living labs and research infrastructures initiatives*” are not added to this overall list because a deeper mapping will be undertaken in the following steps by the Horizon 2020 CSA projects “ALL Ready⁸” and “AE4EU⁹” and it would be better to merge initiatives at a more mature stage to avoid double work in screening, validating etc...

Additional fields were added to the LL&LH overall list to be able to further classify, select and map the LL & LH. These fields were (partially) filled by the available information in literature and online sources. In Annex III, the original and additional fields that were used in the overview are given and explained as well as the actual list of LL and LH (version September 2021). Additional checking and adding information, such as georeferencing, and mapping the LL & LH on an interactive map, in cooperation with the JRC soil observatory, is done under SMS WP 4 (Annex IV).

Criteria for establishing a network of SH LL & LH were to be elaborated in line with the mapped examples: which are existing, where do we see gaps, and is based on 1) location / where and 2) topic. The list was analysed to find gaps in location and topic.

Because the overall list does contain a lot of “noise” (entries that cannot be classified as SH LL & LH when following the selection criteria) it was unsuitable for the purpose of identifying gaps in this stage. For that reason, additional literature and the implementation plan “A soil deal for Europe” (EC, 2021) were consulted to add to the criteria for setting up a network of SH LL& LH. The results are given in section 4.2.

Setting up successful SH LL & LH (networks)

Success factors and principles for LL and LH were based on (scientific) literature and reviewing of online sources.

Examples were elaborated from different land use / production systems along their characteristics, to find relevant differences and points of attention to feed in the success criteria. The examples are presented in Annex IV.

Actor engagement is an important factor of success for LL & LH. SMS already elaborated draft value propositions for different actor groups (D3.3, Brils et al., 2021) and identified stakeholder needs in this deliverable (section 2.1 and chapter 3). Important aspects for actor engagement in SH LL & LH were based on this exercise, together with the review of some literature sources.

About governance and funding of the SH LL & LH network, several points of attention were added to what the implementation plan of the Soil Mission proposes, based on expert judgement and literature.

The above points are reported in section 4.4.

⁷ AE4EU: European Commission survey on agroecology living labs and research infrastructures: <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/FirstScreeningAELLRI2020#>

⁸ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101000349>

⁹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101000478>

3 ACTOR NEEDS AND THEIR PRIORITY

3.1 Survey results

3.1.1 The responding actors

The survey methodology is described in section 2.1. The complete survey results are presented in Annex IX. In total 93 respondents filled out the survey: 32 partly and 61 fully. The distribution of the respondents over the different actor groups is displayed in figure 3-1. Most respondents are working for an organization that is a part of the *research community*, followed by *policy makers and governmental organisations*. The least represented category is *land users, managers and owners*. The category *other* includes (as specified by the respondents): JPI, farmers and agricultural cooperatives, living labs, network on soil data, agricultural sector society.

Figure 3-1: In what actor group would you place the organisation that you are working for? [multiple answers are possible] (n = 91)

The organizations of the respondents are active in a diversity of EU countries but also in several non-EU countries (figure 3-2). In the category *other* the following countries were mentioned: China, the United States of America, Colombia, Singapore and Japan.

Figure 3-2: In which country/countries is your organisation most active? (n=90)

The organizations of the respondents are related all sectors and the largest sector represented is agriculture/horticulture (figure 3-3).

Figure 3-3: Which of the following areas or sectors relate to your organisation? [multiple answers are possible] (n=88)

3.1.2 The actor needs regarding the Soil Mission objectives

A summary of the specific needs per Soil Mission objective as expressed by the actor group respondents is presented below. The report is starting with the 1st and ending with the 8th and last Soil Mission objective. For each Soil Mission objective, the results are summarised in a word cloud, which shows the most common terms given by all actors together, within the survey answers on needs for that objective. Then, below each word cloud, a summary of the specific needs that were mentioned by the different actor groups are presented in a table. Finally, descriptive statistics on the respondents are shown. The complete survey results are presented in Annex IX.

Soil Mission objective 1: Reduce land degradation, including desertification and salinization

Figure 3-4a: Word cloud of survey results on needs for the objective: Reduce land degradation

The generic needs most mentioned by all actor groups point out that a policy framework is needed as well as point to the importance of knowledge. Elements of such a framework are legal and financial support, but also a clear image of the roles and responsibilities of the different public/governmental organizations (figure 3-4a). More specific needs per actor group are presented in table 3-1.

Table 3-1: Specific needs mentioned by actor groups for the objective: Reduce land degradation

Actor group	Specific needs – examples
Land users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legal and financial support in order to allow farmers and farming cooperatives to actively work on this issue; preserving the resource most precious and essential to their activities. Without genuine support and guidance, then change cannot occur as the farming community cannot put their own livelihoods at risk and impoverish themselves.
Policymakers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge: identification of areas concerned by desertification and salinization (where and when?) • Including oversea territories.
Researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adequate funding of research and innovation activities. • Acceptance of innovation and reduce reluctance from regulatory bodies • Political drivers from legislators. • A general shift from "Business as Usual" with economic growth as an excuse to not take the measures needed. • Encourage society to be a vector of environmental and social trends.

Actor group	Specific needs – examples
Research funding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> R&I and funding.
Private sector & industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -
Service provider	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Soil protection and restoration requires a whole-of-government approach in relevant policies Strong linkages of soil management with other major goals of the EU Green Deal require a convergence and alignment of soil policies with the connected policy areas. EU endorsed key performance indicators (e.g., for nature-based solutions, Green City Accord (GCA), EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, Urban Greening Plans) should take into account soil and land degradation. Strive for mainstreaming Land Degradation Neutrality (LDN) in territorial planning in EU via EU Goal on LDN and policy alignment; multi-level governance structures, EU standards and integration in EU commitments e.g. Green City Accord, Local Green Deals. Legislative mandate and budgetary capacity for local and regional governments to make decisions related to soil health and land-use without having to give way to powerful (real-estate) developers or other urban development priorities.
NGO's	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific knowledge summarised and translated to be easily "digestible" and usable in a policy context (e.g. as done by the European Court of Auditors in their report on desertification).

Statistics on the background of the respondents

The number of respondents that filled out their needs was N = 58. Below their organisational backgrounds, countries and sectors (that they are active in) are displayed in figures 3-4b, 3-4c, 3-4d.

Figure 3-4b: Organisational backgrounds of the respondents that reacted on objective 1

Figure 3-4c: Countries in which the respondents who reacted on objective 1 are active in

Figure 3-4d: Sectors in which the respondents who reacted on objective 1 are active in

Soil Mission objective 2: Conserve (e.g. in forests, permanent pastures, wetlands) and increase soil organic carbon stocks

Figure 3-5a: Word cloud of survey results on needs for the objective: conserve and increase soil organic carbon stocks

The generic needs most mentioned by all actor groups circle around: knowledge, policy, funding/financial report, awareness raising and a legal framework (figure 3-5a). More specific needs per actor group are presented in table 3-2.

Table 3-2: Specific needs mentioned by actor groups for the objective: conserve and increase soil organic carbon stocks

Actor group	Specific needs – examples
Land users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • From theory into practice: independent advice based on scientific results, • Appropriate rewarding mechanisms both supported by an adequate policy framework
Policymakers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge and technology transfer of good practices
Researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy to measure and cost-effective indicators. Digital platform for follow-up • Political focus on monitoring soil degradation and soil health
Research funding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • R&I and funding
Private sector & industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • --
Service provider	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better information about 'behaviour' of different pools of organic matter and organic inputs in the soil • R&I, knowledge, technology, legal support, forms of organization • The following is needed: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Mobilisation of adequate financial resources and effective incentive mechanisms. ○ Technical knowledge: municipal capacity for SOC management and monitoring (i.e., human resources, technical knowledge and efficient tools) ○ Standardised key performance indicators and monitoring protocols as well as easily accessible and affordable monitoring technology ○ Evidence to support decision-making and priority setting for SOC stocks in view of many other development priorities ○ Best practices in urban SOC stock restoration and management
NGO's	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy choices, there are contradictions between manure legislation and soil protection (organic matters) • Legal framework (EU and national policies and programmes, e.g. CAP) to <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ provide incentives for farmers who maintain and/or increase soil carbon by practicing sustainable agriculture (such as organic farming and agroecology) while disincentivising practices that deplete soil carbon stocks; financial support for advocacy activities to further advance organic farming and agroecology in Europe,

Actor group	Specific needs – examples
NGO's	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ build capacity of the organic sector to engage in R&I and enable knowledge exchange amongst all farmers in Europe and beyond, e.g. through digital knowledge reservoirs, farmer-field schools, demo farms, innovation hubs, peer-to-peer learning etc.

Statistics on the background of the respondents

The number of respondents that filled out their needs was N = 65. Below their organisational backgrounds, countries and sectors (that they are active in) are displayed in figures 3-5b, 3-5c, 3-5d

Figure 3-5b: Organisational backgrounds of the respondents that reacted on objective 2

Figure 3-5c: Countries in which the respondents who reacted on objective 2 are active in

Figure 3-5d: sectors in which the respondents who reacted on objective 2 are active in

Soil Mission objective 3: No net soil sealing and increase the re-use of urban soils for urban development.

Figure 3-6a: Word cloud of survey results on needs for the objective: No net soil sealing and increase the re-use of urban soils for urban development

The generic needs most mentioned by all actors draws the focus on legal support and policy (figure 3-6a). More specific needs per actor group are presented in table 3-3.

Table 3-3: Specific needs mentioned by actor groups for the objective: No net soil sealing and increase the re-use of urban soils for urban development

Actor group	Specific needs – examples
Land users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Budget from the government to build awareness and to show good practical instruments and demonstrate these in lighthouses
Policymakers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stricter regulations and more funding, awareness raising, mobilisation of politics and politicians
Researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stimulation of Living labs development of Societal Business cases in which 'green inclusive' measures are not hindered by bureaucracy. Open and transparent platforms to share knowledge and support to explore existing successful stories.
Research funding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> R&I, demand from citizens
Private sector & industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> --

Service provider	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Knowledge, Innovation and Technology (KIT), legislation and pro-active approach of large industry (supported by their stakeholders)
NGO's	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Funding to support implementation of green measures in cities, legal support.

Statistics on the background of the respondents

The number of respondents that filled out their needs was N = 45. Below their organisational backgrounds, countries and sectors (that they are active in) are displayed in figures 3-6b, 3-6c, 3-6d.

Figure 3-6b: Organisational backgrounds of the respondents that reacted on objective 3

Figure 3-6c: Countries in which the respondents who reacted on objective 3 are active in

Figure 3-6d: Sectors in which the respondents who reacted on objective 3 are active in

Soil Mission objective 4: Reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration

Figure 3-7a: Word cloud of survey results on needs for the objective: Reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration

The generic needs most mentioned by all actors are diverse and circle around: knowledge, policy, funding/financial report and a legal framework (figure 3-7a). More specific needs per actor group are presented in table 3-4.

Table 3-4: Specific needs mentioned by actor groups for the objective: Reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration

Actor group	Specific needs – examples
Land users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Because of the decentralization of soil tasks, there is a need for capacity building, funded by the government. This should include practical instruments to demonstrate how contaminated land can be controlled/managed or remediated. • Only legislation can force stakeholders to improve the situation
Policymakers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organization in charge of orphaned contaminated site management, human and financial • Resources oriented on securing, increasing means could allow to fully restore polluted sites and develop prevention actions.
Policymakers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legal support to harmonize prevention of soil pollution, • Integrative legal framework to prevent soil pollution and define a national soil quality target. • European Soil Directive. • Targeted funding reducing barriers and psychological fears
Researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial support to our R&D projects to highlight and develop technology and knowledge, to avoid and to remediate this soil pollution, legislative actions from the authorities to prevent this deterioration.
Research funding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • R&I, continuous research funding and transfer infrastructure
Private sector & industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Toolbox with solutions and more insights

Actor group	Specific needs – examples
Service provider	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "Substantial capacity building for cities. This includes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Adequate financial resources and investments in the remediation of polluted sites. ○ Effective toolkit to build technical capabilities for municipal staff. ○ Urban, landscape and architecture planning expertise to consider and reduce soil sealing.
NGO's	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Independent research being carried out and its findings brought to policy circles. • Awareness raising among farmers to convince of the need to act.

Statistics on the background of the respondents

The number of respondents that filled out their needs was N = 52. Below their organisational backgrounds, countries and sectors (that they are active in) are displayed in figures 3-7b, 3-7c, 3-7d.

Figure 3-6b: Organisational backgrounds of the respondents that reacted on objective 4

Figure 3-7c: Countries in which the respondents who reacted on objective 4 are active in

Figure 3-7d: Sectors in which the respondents who reacted on objective 4 are active in

Soil Mission objective 5: Prevent erosion

Figure 3-8a: Word cloud of survey results on needs for the objective: Prevent erosion

The generic needs most mentioned by all actor groups circle around: legal support, funding and R&I (figure 3-8a). More specific needs per actor group are presented in table 3-5.

Table 3-5: Specific needs mentioned by actor groups for the objective: Prevent erosion

Actor group	Specific needs – examples
Land users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> --
Policymakers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Awareness raising, funding and supporting of measures, agricultural practices Pilot project with nature-based solutions We need: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Human and financial resources: our organization is not able to cover these actions meanwhile our organization is in charge of soil protection. Knowledge: identification of areas concerned. Legal support: National soil framework and European Soil Directive.
Researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Some technical solutions exist already to reduce erosion, they must be promoted through legal support. Continuous funding for working with farmers to test small and larger improvements to their management and machinery to prevent erosion.

Researchers	There was an interesting project, but then the funding ends and the work with farmers cannot be continued anymore. These matters need continuous action and attention.
Research funding	• --
Private sector & industry	• Dialog with & awareness at land owners and authorities
Service provider	• EU Soil strategy embedded in every country, balance strategy with agricultural and nature sectors
NGO's	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legal framework (EU and national policies and programmes, e.g. CAP) to • provide incentives (subsidies etc.) for farmers to practice (adopt/maintain) sustainable forms of agriculture prevent erosion, such as organic farming and agroecology, while disincentivising harmful forms (methods, techniques, practices) of land management; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ provide financial support for advocacy activities to further advance organic farming and agroecology in Europe and ○ enable awareness raising and knowledge exchange among all farmers, land owners and managers, e.g. through digital knowledge reservoirs, farmer-field schools, demo farms, innovation hubs, peer-to-peer learning etc.

Statistics on the background of the respondents

The number of respondents that filled out their needs was N = 48. Below their organisational backgrounds, countries and sectors (that they are active in) are displayed in figures 3-8b, 3-8c, 3-8d.

Figure 3-8b: Organisational backgrounds of the respondents that reacted on objective 5

Figure 3-8c: Countries in which the respondents who reacted on objective 5 are active in

Figure 3-8d: Sectors in which the respondents who reacted on objective 5 are active in

Soil Mission objective 6: Improve soil structure to enhance habitat quality for soil biota and crops

Figure 3-9a: Word cloud of survey results on needs for the objective: Improve soil structure to enhance habitat quality for soil biota and crops

The generic needs most mentioned by all actors draws the focus on knowledge, research, funding and monitoring (figure 3-9a). More specific needs per actor group are presented in table 3-6.

Table 3-6: Specific needs mentioned by actor groups for the objective: Improve soil structure to enhance habitat quality for soil biota and crops

Actor group	Specific needs – examples
Land users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Operational instruments, budget and a reduction of the total nitrogen deposition on nature areas. Also, in agricultural land the benefits of biodiversity are clear.
Polymakers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Human and financial resources, organization not able to cover these actions meanwhile our organization is in charge of soil protection - knowledge: identification of areas concerned- legal support: national soil framework and European Soil Directive. Improved monitoring, more knowledge on the effect of current practices on soil life, knowledge transfer to farmers...
Researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Continuous R&I and work with farmers. Cost effective and accurate indicators (e.g. based on remote sensing) to detect problems with soil structure and compaction. Running research and promoting remedial measures in agriculture: liming, recycling of residual materials from society as plant nutrients and organic substances, promoting increased biological life in soils.
Research funding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Soil monitoring and guidelines for farmers
Private sector & industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regulation Funding
Service provider	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> More awareness of the importance of Soil as Natural Capital by all stakeholders (policy - industry - citizens). Align with agriculture and nature sector (from the perspective of environmental and infrastructure approach). Running research and promoting remedial measures in agriculture: liming, recycling of residual materials from society as plant nutrients and organic substances, promoting increased biological life in soils.
NGO's	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Binding, comprehensive and integrated legal framework (EU and national policies and programmes, e.g. CAP) to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> provide incentives for farmers to practice (adopt/maintain) regenerative agricultural practices that enhance soil structure, including organic farming and agroecology, while disincentivising harmful forms of land management; provide financial support for advocacy activities to further advance organic farming and agroecology in Europe and enable awareness raising and knowledge exchange among farmers, e.g. through digital knowledge reservoirs, farmer-field schools, demo farms, innovation hubs, peer-to-peer learning etc. Knowledge and financial support to implement the good practices

Actor group	Specific needs – examples
NGO's	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU soil protection framework and linkages to other EU initiatives Farm to Fork CAP reform

Statistics on the background of the respondents

The number of respondents that filled out their needs was N = 54. Below their organisational backgrounds, countries and sectors (that they are active in) are displayed in figures 3-9b, 3-9c, 3-9d.

Figure 3-9b: Organisational backgrounds of the respondents that reacted on objective 6

Figure 3-9c: Countries in which the respondents who reacted on objective 6 are active in

Figure 3-9d: Sectors in which the respondents who reacted on objective 6 are active in

Soil Mission objective 7: Reduce the EU global footprint on soils

Figure 3-10a: Word cloud of survey results on needs for the objective: Reduce the EU global footprint on soils

The most generic needs mentioned by all actor groups circle around: knowledge, clear frameworks – internationally embedded – based on international standards and legal support (figure 3-10a). More specific needs per actor group are presented in table 3-7.

Table 3-7: Specific needs mentioned by actor groups for the objective: Reduce the EU global footprint on soils

Actor group	Specific needs – examples
Land users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practical information to build awareness at the general public and other stakeholders. • Budget from the government to execute such a program.
Policymakers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge: methodologies to assess, international standardization • Legal support at an international level, WTO • Action oriented and intersectoral coordinated EU policy, in many aspects the EU policies are in contradiction • Practical information to build awareness at the general public and other stakeholders and budget from the government to execute such a program.
Researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • R&I, knowledge
Research funding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • R&I, legal support (EU/National policies), financial support, citizen awareness/demand
Private sector & industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness & sense of urgency
Service provider	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We operate in a European context, so our aim is also to reduce the EU global footprint on Soils. There is a need for an overall approach (policy - industry - citizens).
NGO's	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More and easily accessible data about our land footprint outside the EU, what is driving it (what is that land being used for), how is it affecting local populations in those countries...

Statistics on the background of the respondents

The number of respondents that filled out their needs was N = 45. Below their organisational backgrounds, countries and sectors (that they are active in) are displayed in figures 3-10b, 3-10c, 3-10d.

Figure 3-10b: Organisational backgrounds of the respondents that reacted on objective 7

Figure 3-10c: Countries in which the respondents who reacted on objective 7 are active in

Figure 3-10d: Sectors in which the respondents who reacted on objective 7 are active in

Soil Mission objective 8: Increase soil literacy in society across Member States

Figure 3-11a: Word cloud of survey results on needs for the objective: Increase soil literacy in society across Member States

The generic needs most mentioned by all actors draws the focus on communication, knowledge, awareness and education (figure 3-11a). More specific needs per actor group are presented in table 3-8.

Table 3-8: Specific needs mentioned by actor groups for the objective: Increase soil literacy in society across Member States

Actor group	Specific needs – examples
Land users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A genuine education of the importance of soil and their properties at primary, secondary, and university levels in all EU member states. • The understanding of the role of soil in the future of adapting and mitigating climate change is not adequately provided, and as a result can be the cause of regular misunderstanding and propaganda. • While the role of soil has been lauded only recently as one of the main saviours from climate change; there is still a largescale mis appreciation for the importance of this natural resource.
Policymakers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Human and financial resources, • Knowledge transfer • Legal support: a national and integrated policy to enhance soil literacy in society (education, communication, training, awareness, participative science and observatories...)
Researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some funding to improve the communication between the research agencies/university, etc and the general public is key. • Improve knowledge level of soil health and food productivity conditions throughout whole society.
Research funding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Events on world soil day, lectures, R&I, stakeholder involvement • collaboration between the soil and climate research communities towards joint communication
Private sector & industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regulation and funding

Service provider	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication, education and public awareness raising initiatives should highlight the underestimated importance of soils and their functions to drive soil conservation and restoration action with concrete messages and options for action for the diversity of stakeholders (e.g. from developers, to local policy-makers, to planners and architects as well as local CSOs). • It all starts with insight / understanding of the importance of a healthy soil. There's a need of a long-term vision. There is a must of a wholeheartedly support by the politicians (policy > legislation > enforcement) as well as a pro-active industry. A dialogue is vital in order to change the ESG course of companies (dialogue between industry and politicians and between industry and their stakeholders).
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NGO's	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial support for advocacy and communication activities to raise awareness among policy makers, farmers, industry and civil society/citizens in general of the importance of soil and sustainable soil management for food, environmental services etc. through (social) media, knowledge platforms, events, workshops, personal meetings etc
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Statistics on the background of the respondents

The number of respondents that filled out their needs was N = 44. Below their organisational backgrounds, countries and sectors (that they are active in) are displayed in figures 3-11b, 3-11c, 3-11d.

Figure 3-11b: Organisational backgrounds of the respondents that reacted on objective 8

Figure 3-11c: Countries in which the respondents who reacted on objective 8 are active in

Figure 3-11d: Sectors in which the respondents who reacted on objective 8 are active in

3.2 Workshop results

The complete outcome of the AquaConSoil and the SMS Expert Group workshops is presented in Annex VII. The number of people participating in both workshops was small compared to the number of survey respondents. However, the workshop set-up and lower number allowed for more in-depth discussion.

The **AquaConSoil workshop participants** expressed that urban and industrial land is most relevant for achieving the soil mission targets on: 1) Restoration of polluted sites; increasing the rate of soil reuse; better understanding of soil system functioning; 2) Restoring degraded land beyond land degradation neutrality¹⁰ and reducing carbon losses in peatlands and 3) No net soil sealing.

When looking at the R&I needs (as displayed in ANNEX VII) the workshop participants suggest focussing on fate and transport of pollutants / degradation and on the missing links between social, economic and environmental studies in soil. Another R&I gap is seen with respect to the social, legal and economic context in which they work, such as better insights in the influence from market chains on sustainability and the influence on subsidies and regulation to avoid trade-offs in objectives.

¹⁰ In this workshop, the relation between degraded land and desertification was not specified. However, given the AquaConSoil audience it may be assumed that the audience has interpreted degraded land as polluted/contaminated land.

When soils are managed sustainably the workshop participants suggested different gains for different actor groups:

- *For the research community:* their benefit will be the increase in impact of their work i.e. enabling sustainable use and management, resulting in clean water and soil and this will increase soil and human health;
- *For service providers:* it is mentioned that there will be more room for innovation when soils are managed sustainably;
- *For land users* (incl. private sector and industry) they may have as benefits that: the long-term productivity potential increases; less money needs to be spent on clean-up / mitigation; and increased resilience to climate extremes;
- *For citizens* the benefits that are mentioned are: sustained long-term wellbeing; a cleaner planet; and that less tax money needs to be spend on protection and clean-up when we make steps on towards achieving of the mission goals.

The **SMS Expert Group workshop participants** expressed that there are very clear benefits for every sector, however translating these benefits to R&I needs is more complex and needs to differ between regions. A summary of the needs that were expressed by the group:

- *Agriculture:* Need for effective policy incentives directly rewarding farmers for good soil management and carbon sequestration (not carbon markets with high transaction costs where consultants make most profit);
- *Forestry:* Need for analysis of the improvement potential (baseline) and overview of impact of potential measures;
- *Urban areas:* Need for safe and strict standards for soil contamination in urban (as well as soils in nature and agricultural area);
- *Industry:* Need for ecosystem services-based management (looking at trade-offs and synergies);
- *Protected areas:* Need for ecosystem services-based management (looking at trade-offs and synergies).

From both workshops it can be concluded that the participants could easily indicate for all actor groups benefits from, and needs related to sustainable soil management. However, the remaining challenges are to:

- Translate these benefits in to a R&I agenda and concrete activities on how to enhance the benefits (i.e. increase the gains and/or lower the pains);
- Prioritise the needs in terms urgency and timing as each actor group will perceive this differently¹¹;

¹¹ This was also the experience of the INSPIRATION process developing a Strategic Research Agenda (SRA) for land and soil, a final step in the process was aimed at prioritizing the topics to be included in the SRA with the ambition to keep only the most relevant. The result of an online-consultation – with a broad representation of different kinds of actors from different European countries, was that no significant difference between the relevance of identified topics was found – all were regarded as important or most important so that all were kept for the final phase (Bartke et al., 2018).

- Balance trade-offs (pains and gains between actors) as any change in land and soil management will result in a different provision of ecosystem services.

3.3 Actor priorities

3.3.1 Importance and urgency of the Soil Mission objectives for actors

A summary of how urgent and important the respondents perceive each Soil Mission objective for their organization, is presented in figure 3-12. The figure only displays the percentage of the survey respondents – all actor groups pooled together – who perceive a specific Soil Mission objective as very urgent and very important. The complete results, including a diversification per actor group, are presented in annex IX.

Figure 3-12: Percentage of the survey respondents who perceive specific Soil Mission objectives (numbered 1 to 8) as very urgent and very important

The results of the survey show that the respondents for each Soil Mission seem to value ‘importance’ and ‘urgency’ more-or-less equally, except for Soil Mission objective “6. *Improve soil structure to enhance habitat quality for soil biota and crops*” which 58% of the respondent rate as ‘very important’, while only 24% of the respondents rate it as ‘very urgent’.

The results of the survey also show that the respondents value the specific Soil Mission objectives differently. Based on ‘importance X urgency’ the decreasing order of the Soil Mission objectives is:

- nr 1. Objective 2 - Conserve (e.g. in forests, permanent pastures, wetlands) and increase soil organic carbon stocks.
- nr 2. Objective 1 - Reduce land degradation, including desertification and salinization
- nr 3. Objective 4 - Reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration
- nr 4. Objective 5 - Prevent erosion
- nr 5. Objective 7 - Reduce the EU global footprint on soils
- nr 6. Objective 3 - No net soil sealing and increase the re-use of urban soils for urban development.
- nr 7. Objective 8 - Increase soil literacy in society across Member States
- nr 8. Objective 6 - Improve soil structure to enhance habitat quality for soil biota and crops

Looking at the different actor groups (Annex IX), some differences can be observed, but the overall priority of the objectives remains the same among the different actor groups.

The main reasons that were mentioned for both urgency and importance for *all* the soil objectives were '*Social and environmental responsibility*' closely followed by '*Current activities of my organisation*' or '*Ambitions of my organisation*'.

Next to these three dominant reasons for each Soil Mission objective, the 4th reason mentioned per Soil Mission objective showed some differences:

1. Reduce land degradation, including desertification and salinization:
High costs for restoration or irreversibility of the matter (and related costs) (the same for both importance and urgency).
2. Conserve (e.g. in forests, permanent pastures, wetlands) and increase soil organic carbon stocks:
Demands from the soil user(s) (concerning importance) *Demands from the general public* (concerning urgency)
3. No net soil sealing and increase the re-use of urban soils for urban development: *Demands from the general public* (the same for both importance and urgency)
4. Reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration:
Legislation/regulation (the same for both importance and urgency)
5. Prevent erosion:
Demands from the soil user(s) (the same for both importance and urgency)
6. Improve soil structure to enhance habitat quality for soil biota and crops:
Demands from the soil user(s) (the same for both importance and urgency)
7. Reduce the EU global footprint on soils:
Demands from the general public (the same for both importance and urgency)
8. Increase soil literacy in society across Member States:
Demands from the soil user(s) (concerning importance) *Demands from the general public* (concerning urgency)

3.3.2 Actor needs priority

When looking at the needs of the actors in relation to the different Soil Mission objectives, it appears that there are many similarities in general, but also that the needs are concentrated when it comes to the specific objectives. After a joint analysis and synthesis of the outcome of the survey as well as the workshops it is concluded that the generic actor needs – i.e. applicable to all the actor groups – in order of priority are:

1. **Funding:**

This appears the number one need for all the actor groups, but they need it for different reasons, which are linked to their specific actor interests, e.g.:

- policy and governmental organisations need it for capacity,
- the research community needs it for R&I including (long-term) observation,
- landowners and private sector need it for the implementation of measures/infrastructure.

2. **Legislation/policy frameworks:**

This appears the number two need for all the actor groups, but legislation/policy needs vary between the various actor groups, e.g.:

- Policy and governmental organisations need it to set clear boundaries and targets,
- Landowners and private sector need it to create a level playing field, receive guidance and act.

3. **Knowledge/R&I in order to inform policy and measures:**

For some of the Soil Mission objectives there is a clear need expressed for knowledge/R&I to inform policy making (legislation/frameworks) as well as to inform the design or increase the effectiveness of measures (e.g. solutions, best practices to improve land management, restore carbon stocks etc.)

4. **Awareness raising and communication:**

Different actor groups express different viewpoints regarding awareness raising and communication. In general, the involvement of citizens is regarded as very important for any actor interacting with society. Furthermore, reaching out to, for example farmers and project developers, is also regarded as an important need.

Next to these generic needs, there are specific needs per actor group. These have been touched upon in the previous paragraphs. The longlists of needs per actor group is presented in Annex IX (Survey results) and Annex VII (Workshop results).

4 CHARACTERISTICS AND CRITERIA FOR (SOIL HEALTH) LIVING LABS AND LIGHTHOUSES

The Soil Mission sees living laboratories (LLs) and lighthouses (LHs) as instruments to accelerate the creation and uptake of solutions to meet the specific objectives across farms, forest, landscapes and urban settings in a diversity of geographical and socio-economic contexts (EC, 2021). This chapter on LL & LH continues the earlier work in SMS on this topic (as reported in D2.2 *Initial collection of living labs and lighthouses in the field of soil and land management* (Wall et al., 2021) and D3.2 *Concept note on Criteria for setting up living labs and lighthouses* (Maring et al., 2021)). The work is building upon and performed in interaction with Mission Board on soil health and food's Working Group 5 ("WG5") for the implementation of the Mission for Soil health and food and is in line with the recently published implementation plan "A Soil Deal for Europe" (EC, 2021). The main objective is to support the preparation to setup a dense network of soil health Living Labs and Lighthouses (SH LL and LH) in Europe to boost sustainable soil and land management in Europe. The contribution of soils to deliver ecosystem services is a central concept for the SH LL & LH as described in the Mission Goal (EC, 2021, page 14)

A Soil Deal for Europe:

100 living labs and lighthouses to lead the transition to healthy soils by 2030.

Soil health has been defined as **"the continued capacity of soils to support ecosystem services"**.

4.1 Characteristics of SH LL and LH

There are different types of LL described in literature (Annex V), and we elaborate here the so-called Soil Health LL (SH LL) & LH as proposed under the Mission for Soil health and food. While LL have many descriptions and definitions, LH are described poorly in literature. Therefore, we start with the definition / description of SH LL&LH as proposed in the implementation plan of the EU Mission "A soil deal for Europe" (EC, 2021, page 28):

"Soil health living labs" are defined as **"user-centred, place-based and transdisciplinary research and innovation ecosystems, which involve land managers, scientists and other relevant partners in systemic research and codesign, testing, monitoring and evaluation of solutions, in real-life settings, to improve their effectiveness for soil health and accelerate adoption."** These living labs are collaborations between multiple partners that operate at regional or sub-regional level and coordinate experiments on several sites within a regional or sub-regional area (or working landscapes);

"Lighthouses" are defined as **"places for demonstration of solutions, training and communication that are exemplary in their performance in terms of soil health improvement"**. They are local sites (one farm, one forest exploitation, one industrial site, one urban city green area, etc.) that can be included in a living lab area or be situated outside a living lab area.

Table 4-1 contains the scale, envisioned activities and performance in terms of soil health improvement for LL, the experimentation sites in LL and LH.

Table 4-1: Living Labs, Sites at which demonstrations takes place and Lighthouses (Source: adapted after EC, 2021, page 29)

	scale	Activities	Performance in terms of soil health and related ESS
Living lab	(sub)Regional / landscape	Orchestrate (sets of) experimentations + relation between actors	In progress at landscape scale
Living lab experimentation site	Local (one farm, one urban site, one forest exploitation)	Co-create knowledge, and experiment innovations	In progress on the site
Lighthouse	Site (one farm, one urban site, one forest exploitation)	Experimentation and demonstration	Demonstrated high performance

Figure 4-1: Living Labs, Sites (S) at which demonstrations takes place and Lighthouses (Left), in relation with activities under other operational objectives (Right)

According to definition by the implementation plan of the Mission for Soil health and food (EC, 2021, page 29).

A difference with literature (ENoLL, McPhee et al., 2021) and SMS D3.1 (Maring et al., 2021) is that the implementation plan states that a SH LL always consists of multiple sites, forming together the SH LL. In McPhee et al. (2021), describing Agroecosystems Living Lab (AELL), there are some examples of multi-sites LL, which are named “archipelago of LL”. Steen and van Bueren (2017), working on Urban Living Labs (ULL), name such constellations “Living Lab platforms”.

That SH LL should consist of multiple sites is linked to the requirement to operate at landscape / ecosystem scale, which necessarily comes together with several sites, as it is hard to envisage one site that would cover the whole ecosystem. In the Proposed Mission “Caring for soil is caring for life” (EC, 2020) the focus in a LL was estimated on 10-15 units (farms, forests, industrial areas and urban settings) to be able to cover the landscape or watershed level. In the implementation plan (EC 2021), the number and exact character of sites is not predefined (e.g. fields of a farm or entire farm, industrial area or single site in this area), nor is the exact amount and composition of the involved actor group. This depends on the objective/aim and nature of the LL, the pursued impact and innovations and the specific tasks in the LL, which will differ e.g. between agricultural, urban and forestry LL. Some examples are given below. The definition of the objective/aim and nature should be part of the initial phases of the LL (e.g. the Preparation & Exploration phase and Problem structuring & Envisioning phase as described by Roorda and Wittmayer, J. (2014) for urban transition management and applied on Urban Transition Lab (UTL) & Product Oriented Living Labs (POL) by Neef et al 2017.)

LL Example 1 - agricultural, rural and forestry – multiple communities and sites focusing on a central question in different geophysical, socio-economic conditions and in different geographic regions

The DESIRA Living Labs¹² are 20 networks of stakeholders established across Europe and selected to represent a variety of agricultural, rural and forestry domains. They are constituted around a focal question (e.g. How to reduce the risk of forest fires?) and will co-develop ideas, scenarios, digital storytelling outputs, and socio-technical solutions related to digitalisation. Interaction in the networks will be based on both face-to-face and online activities.

LL Example 2 – urban -multiple cities with urban sites focusing on a central challenge: sustainable transformation using ecosystem services

The Vertical Green 2.0 example¹³ (not yet taken up in the LL/LH list in Annex III) fosters transformations of cities (Vienna - AT, Berlin - DE, Ljubljana - SL) to sustainable, resilient spaces by re-thinking, re-designing and re-managing vertical greening as progressive food-water-energy nexuses. Vertical greening is interpreted and designed as a biological-technical system in an architectural-technical context with a substantial capacity to implement multiple ecosystem services like passive cooling, flood alleviation, bioenergy and possibly food production, biodiversity, noise reduction and it could be consistently installed as a part of the built environment especially in dense city districts.

LL Example 3 - urban – multiple cities focusing on a central challenge, due to similar circumstances, e.g. subsidence in urban areas

The existing Living Lab “strong city on weak soils” Gouda in the Netherlands¹⁴ could be expanded with other cities in peat areas (e.g.: other peat areas in the Netherlands, Germany and Scandinavian countries) to exchange, elaborate and upscale experiences and innovations to different locations with more or less the same circumstances. Although the LL Gouda has as an objective to obtain knowledge for other cities as well, the expansion to other locations within Europe has not been made. This could be a great opportunity to enrich this one city LL and increase its impact.

¹² desira2020.eu

¹³ <https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/vertical-green-2-0/>

¹⁴ <https://www.bewustlevenmetwater.nl/klimaatverandering-rijnland/praktijk-voorbeelden/living-lab/>

LL Example 4 – forestry - four countries collaborating on landscape level

The Living lab is anchored in the Greater Luxembourg forest¹⁵, covering 2,375,000 ha across four countries (Luxembourg, Belgium, France and Germany). A large portion (over 40%) of this forest is privately owned and poorly maintained, thus returning to a wild state with positive (biodiversity) and negative impacts (spread of illness, fire risk). Biodiversity is also affected by monocultures of non-endemic species like spruce which dominate parts of the forest. To tackle these challenges, the living lab has explored all the dimensions of sustainability, i.e., environmental, social and economic, with various stakeholders and through two complementary projects.

The lighthouse as such is not sharply defined; it is mentioned only in a few instances online and in literature¹⁶. For Soil Health, it is described as a successful outcome / result / demonstration on a single site, which can act as an example, a place where people can learn from (EC 2021). In theory, each site in a SH LL can become a lighthouse. In practice however, some LL can be too specific, or do not have the capacity to be demonstrators, trainers, and communicators. In that case they still may act very well to improve SH locally. Some lighthouse examples are given below.

LH example 1 -The Grand Farm¹⁷ – Austria on organic farming

Mr Alfred Grand who was in the Soil Mission Board runs an exemplary research and demonstration farm of 90 hectare arable field focusing on soil-health, agroforestry and market gardening. It demonstrates low-tillage methods to maintain and improve the soil; on-farm research projects support the development of agroforestry, the livestock sector and a market garden; advancing vermiculture and vermicomposting – composting with the help of earthworms, long crop rotations, Etc. In 2015, a cooperation with Rodale Institute (USA) was established, to carry out trial sand research in organic no-till methods. In 2019 Alfred established GRAND GARTEN, where a team of young university graduates is producing all year-round organic vegetables for the regional market and doing research and demonstration activities.

¹⁵ <https://ercim-news.ercim.eu/en121/special/a-living-lab-approach-for-sustainable-forest-management>

¹⁶ Baumgartner, 2019 retrieved the definition of lighthouses from Wikipedia in his article: Lighthouse = a model project that aims, besides its original purpose, to have a signal effect for numerous follow-up projects as they look towards it for inspiration and guidance. The term is mentioned in the article of Keesstra et al., 2016 on soils and SDGs in more or less the same way: inspiring and exemplary cases, but no exact definition is given. WUR and the related Global network of lighthouse farms use the term “lighthouse farms”. WUR online in an article: “A lighthouse farm is an existing, commercially operating farm in the real world, that is ‘already in 2050’, and it is used in providing sustainably produced food and ecosystem services” The UNCCD describes lighthouse activities (for climate change actions) as the “most inspiring and transformational mitigation and adaptation activities”.

¹⁷ <https://www.lighthousefarmnetwork.com/lighthouse-farms/grand-farm>

LH example agroforestry - ACKERBAUM¹⁸ Germany

The Agroforestry Research and Model Project from of the University for Sustainable Development in Eberswalde is located in the Löwenberger Land, about 50 km north of Berlin. The experimental area comprises approx. 30 hectares (approx. 10 hectares each of agroforestry, zero area, short rotation plantation) of an agriculturally used area. The owner's motivation is to counteract compaction, evaporation, impoverishment, loss and sealing and to provide protection against wind and water erosion and to build up soil fertility by establishing agroforestry systems. His top priority for the design is to convince the tenant, furthermore, he wants the project area to have a radiating effect and to encourage imitation. Students from all faculties of the university work together in the project on an interdisciplinary basis. The topics include biodiversity, soil, climate, plant health, marketing and public relations. The aim of the long-term scientific study is to use the findings gained to show how a complex agroforestry system can be structured. The system should remain practicable and motivate many farmers to invest. In this context, the economic profitability should also be taken into account.

The implementation plan of the EU Mission “A soil deal for Europe” (EC, 2021) proposes a set of criteria, or rather characteristics, to describe SH LL & LH (figure 4-2 for the main criteria/characteristics and Table 4-2 for the extended criteria/characteristics). They are categorized in: AIMS, ACTIVITIES, PARTICIPANTS, CONTEXT (Steen and Van Bueren, 2017, McPhee et al, 2021). A suggestion can be to add the “orchestration” of the different experiment sites within the SH LL (always consisting of multiple sites) as an additional activity to the LL.

Figure 4-2 draft criteria/characteristics for the selection and set-up of living labs and lighthouses

Source: EC., 2021, page 31

¹⁸ <https://agroforst-info.de/portfolio-item/ackerbaum/>

Aims	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovation and co-creation. • Formal learning. • Contributing to societal challenges, sustainability, and resilience. • Improving soil health and ecosystem services, thereby achieving the soil mission objectives in a holistic manner (minimising trade-offs) in the specific context of the region in which it operates.
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Outreach and facilitation of engagement of the land users. • Co-design/co-development/co-creation of innovations focused on improving soil health and ecosystem services, in major soils and land use systems in a given region/area. • Experimentation of innovative practices and solutions using transdisciplinary, multi-actor, systems approaches, in real-life settings, seeking to adapt scientifically-proven solutions to local conditions (on real farms, forest exploitation or urban soil management sites). • Measurement/monitoring/evaluation of impact of innovative practices/approaches on soil health and related ecosystem services at site and landscape levels, involving research and innovative measurement technologies (data management, sensing, monitoring, assessment modelling). • Evaluation of socio-economic impacts and behavioural drivers and lock-ins related to the adoption of the innovations by soil managers. • Contributing to networking and knowledge exchange with other sites/LL/LH & EIP-AGRI. • Testing, validating and improving the comprehensive soil and ecosystem monitoring system through co-creation (including assessment, training and education on tools). <p>For sites that have reached a high level of performance (lighthouses):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstration, dissemination and promotion to soil managers, the public and the policy arena, at landscape scale and beyond, of land-use systems that satisfy criteria for sustainable development, in particular in terms of soil health and related ecosystem services. • Reaching out to the policy arena linking results of the LH's to environmental rules and regulations. This in line with science based policy support and governance.
Participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public-private-people partnership involving if possible four groups: science, policy, practice, citizens. • Active engagement in co-development and experimentation of the multiplicity of users having an impact on the achievement of the societal goals. • Users of primary importance to achieve the soil mission objectives: soil managers (farmers, advisors, foresters, city greens managers, allotment holder, industries with impacts on soils etc.) and researchers. They would have the responsibility early in the process to connect with other interests such as: associations and organisations with an interest in soil health and related ecosystem services, local or regional government, scientists from a variety of fields outside soils (natural sciences, social and behavioural sciences etc.). The list of users may depend on the specificities of the places and challenges that are specific to that place. • For demonstration activities: target audiences include soil managers, the public arena and relevant networks such as for example EIP-AGRI.
Context	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transdisciplinary and participatory approach. • Multi-method approach. • Place-based; well defined system boundaries (e.g. farm, (sub)-watershed, neighbourhood, NUTS region, value chain) of relevance to soil challenges. This relates to specific regions and sectors. • Real-life context = real farms/forest or urban/industrial sites, seeking to go beyond current practice. • Long-term set-up. • Openness, communication and dissemination and connection with networks. • Multiple dimensions: technical, economic, social. • Robust scientific set-up for ecosystem assessment.

Table 4-2: draft criteria/characteristics for Soil Health Living Labs and Lighthouses

Source: EC., 2021, page 74

4.2 Selection criteria for Soil Health LL and LH

When discussing selection criteria, we can distinguish between criteria that each single LL & LH needs to meet to qualify as a SH LL or LH (section 4.2), and criteria for selecting LL to establish a network of SH LL over Europe (section 4.3).

4.2.1 Selection criteria for soil health living labs

A procedure for validation¹⁹ is proposed here to assess if a LL would qualify as a Soil Health Living Lab (SH LL), i.e. if it matches some overarching or the “most important” characteristics as proposed in Table 4-2. “Most important” is here quite arbitrary, the exercise also considers what information on existing LL and LH can be retrieved within a reasonable amount of effort, to perform this validation. For example, in “context”, the multiple dimensions that should be covered (technical, economic, social) are quite important to determine if the LL has a sufficiently broad approach, but it will be hard to find this information in many of the public descriptions, which in many cases just mention the topics that are covered in the LL. In this case, it is presumed that this aspect is already sufficiently reflected by the other fields such as “activities” and involved “participants”. Another point of attention is that the “selection criteria” for SH LL and LH are not always very SMART. The person who performs the validation needs understanding of the topic and in some cases additional information of involved participants to make a good assessment. But with the procedure as proposed, a validator is given tools to get started with this task. The effort of the validation of course also depends on the way the validation is performed (as a desk study, which is most feasible when first assessing the existing overview of LL, or in interaction with the LL actors), availability of information and the language in which is reported on how easy this job will be.

¹⁹ We cannot perform the validation of the overall LL / LH list in the SMS due to time and budget restrictions, a follow up project to support the Mission should take over this activity

Table 4-3: Validation / selection criteria for Soil Health Living Labs as selected from figure 4-2 / table 4-2 and tested on a sample from the overall LL list

SCALE	Multiple experimenting or test sites ; orchestration of the LL sites is conducted on regional/landscape scale	
AIMS	Aimed at achieving societal and environmental impacts / benefits in relation to the soil mission objectives by means of co-creation or co-design processes	
ACTIVITIES	Co-creation/co-design/co-development of research and innovation in a transdisciplinary and multi-actor approach and robust setup	
	Monitoring/evaluation on soil health /ESS of the research / innovation influence/	
PARTICIPANTS	Multiple participants in a public-private-people partnership, including real users	
CONTEXT	Participatory and open approach in a real-life context (place-based) and within a context familiar to the users (agricultural, urban, forest)	
	Living Labs are conducted on the (middle to) long term	

Scale

The scale of living labs is debated in literature. Living Labs can take on a wide range of geographical scales: from a delimited, small-scale individual locations to a region-wide scale (Følstad, 2008). The criterion for a Soil Health Living Lab (EC, 2021) is that the innovation is pursued on **multiple experimenting or testing locations** within a **regional or landscape scale**. So, the SH LL do consist of multiple locations, where the Living Lab itself is set up as overarching programme to orchestrate/coordinate these experimentations. The reason for that is that only on this scale, the human and the natural system interaction can be truly demonstrated.

Aims

Different sources (e.g. Følstad, 2008, Steen and van Bueren, 2017, McPhee et al., 2021) discuss that Living Labs can pursue various aims or purposes (see also the examples in section 4.1 and 4.4.3, under “funding / business models for LL”). LL are a powerful instrument for transition and change making. However, the overall aim of LL is to achieve societal and environmental benefits in a cooperative way. For the SH LL in the EU Mission “A soil deal for Europe” (EC, 2021) this can be linked to the objectives and targets set to achieve soil health and battle pressures on soils in the EU (Annex I). Therefore, the aims of Living Labs are divided into two criteria. First, Living Labs are aimed at **obtaining** societal and environmental benefits **in light of the soil mission objectives**²⁰. Secondly, Living Labs aim to conduct this by means of co-creation or co-design processes.

²⁰ Soil Mission objectives: 1. Reduce land degradation relating to desertification, 2. Conserve and increase soil organic carbon stocks, 3. No net soil sealing and increase the reuse of urban soils, 4. Reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration, 5. Prevent erosion, 6. Improve soil structure to enhance habitat quality for soil biota and crops. 7. Reduce the EU global footprint on soils and 8. Increase soil literacy in society across Member States (EC, 2021)

Activities

Because Living Labs can serve multiple purposes for which open-innovation will add business and social value and produce accessible knowledge, various activities can play a role within Living Labs. Leminen and Westerlund (2017) detail a variety of innovation tools and activities available for living lab practitioners. Where the content of the activities vary, a central element of Living Labs is that they deal with certain challenges by developing solutions or innovations by processes of **co-design, co-creation or co-development**. This takes place in a **transdisciplinary and multi-actor approach**, covering technical, economic and social aspects. Also, the **monitoring and evaluation** of achieved soil health / ESS performance for the SH Living Labs are important. These two activities, aimed at the SH LL objectives, are proposed as main criteria for SHLL. Monitoring activities can also be conducted by citizen participation or Citizen Science (CS) (Veeckman & Temmerman, 2021), which can at the same time contribute to soil literacy (figure 4-1, right). More about upscaling results of a LL to other actors and regions is found under section 4.4.3.

Participants

A central element of Living Labs is the user-integrated approach aimed at certain challenges and transitions (Liedtke et al., 2015). This means that a broad range of stakeholders, or participants can be part of Living Labs. Living Labs can for example concern the land owner or manager, researchers, people from NGOs, consumer organisations, experts from businesses, various future users or funding agencies. For SH LL, they concern all parties that have a certain interest in the contribution of soil health and related ecosystem services to societal challenges and needs (e.g. food production, biodiverse and liveable cities, climate change adaptation etc). Sometimes the role of soil health to fulfil the societal need or tackle the challenge is very direct (e.g. when talking about food production) and in some cases the link to soil health is more implicit, and the potential LL participants should be made aware of this link (for example by using the value propositions as mentioned in section 2.2). Mostly, there are four central parties that are part of living labs: **science, policy, practice and civil society**. Ideally, these actors work together in a public-private-people partnership and all actors involved have decision-making power. Also, considering the broader effect that Living Labs can have afterwards (through for example upscaling, section 4.4.3), literature shows that involvement of a large network of stakeholders is key for the successful implementation of the living labs and the experimentations they are aiming to do (Ceschin, 2012). For SH LL a core criterion for the mission board is that **real soil managers should be at the centre of the innovation process** (EC, 2021). While SH LL can have various aims and purposes, this also has effect on the stakeholder composition. For example, a living lab aimed at soil health improvement techniques for large-scale farming may not systematically concern the average citizen, while urban farming projects could be of interest to residents. Therefore, the participants composition does not always have to include stakeholders from every part of society. It is about finding and assembling a stakeholder composition consisting of the relevant ones, considering the living lab's aim. More about actor involvement and setting up successful LL and LH can be found in section 4.4.

Context

One of the 3 principles on which LL are founded, beside co-creation, the involvement of users and openness, is that they are “in Real Life”. It may even mean that they are in a **real-world context** (Bergvall-Kareborn & Stahlbrost, 2009). For SH LL this is a core criterion (EC, 2021). Følstad (2008) adds to this that Living Labs are mostly conducted in contexts that are familiar to the users that are involved in the Living Lab. This also distinguishes Living Labs from other experimentation tools or environments. They are conducted in the physical environment where the challenge occurs, or the transition / innovation is needed. In case for SH LL, this means locations where a specific land uses is conducted (agricultural, urban, forestry). Additionally, because of their set up, Living Labs are mostly seen as **middle- to long term** user’s involvement tools (Ogonowski, et al., 2013). Although multiple dimensions (technical, economic and social) should be considered under “context” it is proposed not to add this here as extra selection criterion, because it is already covered under “activities”.

4.2.2 Selection criteria for soil health lighthouses

A procedure for validation²¹ is proposed here to assess if a LH would qualify as a Soil Health Lighthouse (SH LH) under the mission, i.e. if it matches the (additional) characteristics as proposed in Table 4-4.

Table 4-4: Validation / selection criteria for SH lighthouses

SCALE	Site: farm, cooperation of number of farms, urban site, forest exploitation, etc.	
AIMS	Aimed at demonstrating exemplary performance in terms of soil health and ecosystem services in relation to the soil mission objectives	
ACTIVITIES	Activities aimed at demonstration, dissemination and exploitation of a high-performance (e.g. overall management system) to other parties (soil managers, public, policy arena)	
PARTICIPANTS	PPP partnerships and active engagement of potential future users and target audiences	
CONTEXT	Place-based and well-defined system boundaries in a real-life demonstrative context	

Scale

Soil Health Lighthouses are understood as a **site** (which can be a (field of a) farm, or cooperation of a number of farms, an urban site, a forest exploitation etc) that demonstrates exemplary performance when it comes to soil health and ecosystem services. This site functions as demonstration site for a set of practices that lead to this exemplary performance (see also the examples in section 4.1). Although lighthouses can be involved in experimentation and co-creation in the context of living labs, they can also be active on their own.

²¹ We cannot do the validation in SMS due to time and budget restrictions, follow up activities under the EU Mission “A soil deal for Europe” should take over

Aims

The lighthouse is aimed at **demonstrating a developed and tested performance** in terms of soil health and ecosystem services in relation to the soil mission objectives. According to Baumgartner (2019), a lighthouse aims, besides its original purpose, to have a signal effect for numerous follow-up projects as they look towards it for inspiration and guidance. This means that it has a demonstrated high performance. The focus of the lighthouse is to disseminate this performance a set of practices/approaches towards future users or the broader society. Therefore, lighthouse projects can instrument broader upscaling.

Activities

The activities in lighthouses are aimed **demonstration, dissemination and exploitation activities**. This can include active networking, organising demonstrations or active external ambassadorship activities by participants of the lighthouse project. Exploitation is the use of results for commercial purposes or in public policymaking. Experimenting and innovation activities are likely to be resumed in this demonstration phase. For example, by means of participatory monitoring, potential future users can be involved in the process of monitoring the effect of a set of practices / approaches. In this way, they still further develop and can be refined, while the effects are at the same time demonstrated to a larger audience (Holte-McKenzie, Forde & Theobald, 2006).

Participants

The composition of participants that is involved in lighthouses can be comparable living labs, but in most cases the partnerships within a LH will be smaller and less complex. The partnership can e.g. also consist of just a land owner and researchers (as in the example in section 4.1). Next to that, the focus is more on demonstrating the positive effects to the **future users or target audiences** that are likely to potentially use the exemplary practices / approaches in practice or policy.

Context

The context of lighthouses is, comparably to living labs, formed by a **place-based** project that operates within a **real-life** demonstrative context. However, lighthouses operate within clearly defined and more strict system boundaries than living labs.

4.3 Establishing a SH LL network

4.3.1 Criteria for establishing a SH LL network

Next to the aims, objectives, activities, participants and context for each single SH LL, as described in section 4.2.1, there are also additional criteria to establish the dense network of S HLL & LH. The implementation plan of the mission (EC 2021) states that it will support co-creation of innovations that target the **achievement of specific objectives 1 to 6¹⁴**, prioritising those of greatest relevance to **each area** in which a living lab is developed. The process of selecting living labs will ensure that all these specific objectives are covered by the activities of several labs.

The main questions when establishing this network are therefore: 1) **where** to select or setup LL & LH to have a good coverage over Europe and different circumstances. And 2) which **topics** to cover.

1) Where

- In **different Member States** and associated countries
- **NUTS2 level**²² – when performing socio-economic analyses, this level is suited for (analysing) the application of regional policies. there are 283 regions at NUTS 2 in 2021.
- Broad range of geophysical conditions including soil types and socio-economic conditions
- In different geographic regions (environmental zones in Europe)

The “where” part can be easily investigated by a GIS (Geographic Information Systems) exercise when overlapping LL&LH locations with background maps using administrative boundaries, (European) soil maps²³ and biogeographical²⁴ or environmental zones²⁵. For example, 2nd pillar CAP measures, which are customized towards regional specific objectives, can here be tested and monitored for their success in a co-design approach. Synergies between Horizon Europe and the CAP initiatives can thereby be achieved in LL.

Important is the landscape level criterion for SH LL. A SH LL operates at ecosystem level with several sites within that ecosystem / agroecosystem / landscape. This will be a requirement for new SH LL. Most of the already mapped “existing LL” (see also section 4.3.2 and Annex III for the LL/LH list) do not fulfil this scale criterion. In many cases the LL in the list consist of a single site, which can be still valuable in terms of a scientific or societal contribution. When they prove to yield effective / successful methods, we can consider them as SH LH and learn from them / use them as demonstration sites.

2) Topics

- **Various types of land uses** (farms, forests, nature, industrial areas and urban settings)

The type of land use is easy to discover in most cases. It is part of the description of existing LL & LH and will be part of the calls for “new” SH LL. A good division over all land uses can be steered upon. This is not necessarily an even division over all land uses, e.g. it can be based on % land cover in Europe²⁶ and/or on priorities based on soil threats²⁷ as covered by the mission’s objectives, or land use changes²⁸.

- Contributing to the different **Missions objectives** (focus on 1-6, see table 4.5) and covering different knowledge domains (see also Annex X)

Ecosystem services (ESS) provided by soils are a central concept for the SH LL. However, to use the soils contribution to ESS as a criterion to select SH LL in the network will be too complex, both to “measure” and to communicate to actors. Therefore, it is recommended to use the objectives of the EU Mission “A soil deal for Europe” (Annex I) as a selection criterion for new SH LL, as they show a clear goal to work on and cover multiple ecosystem services.

²² <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/nuts/background>

²³ Corine European soil database version 2 <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/soil-type>

²⁴ Map with the biogeographical zones in Europe: <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/biogeographical-regions-europe-3>

²⁵ Map with the environmental zones in Europe: <https://www.wur.nl/en/ResearchResults/Research-Institutes/EnvironmentalResearch/Projects/EBONE/Products/EuropeanEnvironmental-Stratification.htm>

²⁶ Corine database: Europe’s land cover has remained relatively stable since 2000, with about 25 % covered by arable land and permanent crops, 17 % by pastures, 34 % by forests. Artificial surfaces cover less than 5 %.

²⁷ land degradation (desertification), loss of soil organic carbon; soil pollution; erosion; declining soil structure

²⁸ E.g. losses in agricultural land by urban expansion, this links to objective “no net soil sealing”, but it will be hard to cover this topic in a LL setup

Due to the described characteristics of single LL & LH (section 4.2.1 and 4.2.2) it is almost inevitable that SH LL / LH cover different “knowledge types”²⁹ as defined by the SMS project. We recommend that we do not use these knowledge types as an additional criterion for identification and selection of existing or new SHLL for the network. Of course, when in a later stage the actors having an interest in soils discover that there is an urgent and important gap and need on one of these knowledge types, it can be added as a selection criterion for LL in the network as well.

Table 4-5: Mission objectives related to LL and LH

Mission objectives (EC, 2021)	Potential to investigate this objective in a LL setting	examples (Annex III)
1. Reduce land degradation relating to desertification, 2. Conserve and increase soil organic carbon stocks, 5. Prevent erosion, 6. Improve soil structure to enhance habitat quality for soil biota and crops.	While many of these objectives contain processes that take place on a landscape scale, and while they are linked to land management they are very suitable to be (one of the aims) in a LL/LH setting. Methods and innovations can be developed to contribute to these objectives.	There are many examples in the current list in Annex III, addressing one or multiple objectives, such as many of the EIP-AGRI-projects that can be considered as LL/LH or the LL in the Agrilink example (Annex VI)
3. No net soil sealing and increase the reuse of urban soils 4. Reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration,	It can be hard to investigate transformation from agricultural land to urban/infrastructural land in a LL, due to its temporary character (a project instead of long-term LL), although innovation towards more sustainable, climate resilient (planning and technical) methods in urban transformation itself can be a good study object. The desealing and decontamination of soils, reuse of urban and industrial land are however suitable topics to investigate in a Living Lab or Lighthouse setting, where soil health can be a major topic.	1) In France, in 2021 a LL “Life Artisan” has started with local experiments on desealing soils and renaturation with the aim to test new remediation techniques/new land planning management activities ³⁰ 2) Not in the LL list yet: Smart-U-Green ³¹ (JPI urban Europe) investigates urban transformations in France, Italy and the Netherlands with input from other countries. The project is performed with local governments, local businesses, citizen initiatives and NGOs.

²⁹ The SMS project uses a “knowledge matrix”, combining “knowledge themes” that can be linked to the SDGs and EU Mission “A Soil Deal for Europe” objectives, and “knowledge types”, which are overarching aspects and are defined as: Technical, economic and social innovation; Data management, sensing and monitoring; Assessment and modelling; Awareness, training and education; Science based policy support; Institutions and governance. See also Annex X.

³⁰ <https://www.nature2050.com/projet/friche-kodak/>, http://www.urbanisme-puca.gouv.fr/IMG/pdf/sequence_2_auchel.pdf, <https://www.actu-environnement.com/ae/news/projet-life-artisan-OFB-dix-territoires-pilotes-solutions-fondees-nature-adaptation-climat-36622.php4>

³¹ <https://www.smartugreen.eu/results/>

Mission objectives (EC, 2021)	Potential to investigate this objective in a LL setting	examples (Annex III)
7. Reduce the EU global footprint on soils	This objective covers many different topics, from consumer behaviour and trade to regulation and subsidies. There is no clear definition of the global soil footprint yet, but good examples exist for other footprints (land footprint, water footprint, carbon footprint). In any case, the global footprint mechanisms are rooted in global product price relationships. A LL or LH setting would thus be related to a certain product life cycle rather than to specific locations. It can be useful to determine the footprint and to monitor effects of measures within Europe.	None in the current list. An example could be to investigate the effects of the European ban of neonicotinoids in crop (canola) production, which might lead to an increase of such use in other areas of the world. Another (positive) example could be fair trade of e.g. tea or coffee, which guarantees social and environmental standards for production outside EU through consumption inside EU.
8. Increase soil literacy in society across Member States	This should always be part of the objectives of a LL and LH but should not be the only objective. In that case the activity can be categorized better under the Soil Mission operational objective 4: “Engage with the soil user community and society at large” (“Soil literacy, communication and citizen engagement”) (EC, 2021)	in the list in Annex III a lot of examples are given that actually are better categorized as soil literacy activities (indicated in red). They are for example not really place-based but are awareness or pedagogical activities, or soil networks aimed at exchanging experiences and information

4.3.2 Observations from the current list of LL&LH

An overall list of existing LL&LH is collated by the Mission board for Soil Health and Food and the SMS project. This overview gives some insights to how many LL & LH are listed (figure 4-3), in which regions and for what kind of land uses (agricultural, forestry, urban, etc.). In total the list contains 241 entries (version September 2021)³². It should be noted that there is still a lot of “noise” in this overall list, while the entries have not been validated according to the criteria as proposed for SH LL & LH in section 4.2. It can be assumed, that many people that have marked their initiative as a LL or LH and that have ended up in this list, have a different understanding on definitions. (e.g. workshops, networks, farmer adviser initiatives, citizen science projects, pedagogical and educational activities, guidelines for best practices, (laboratory) training courses, etc. are entered.)

³² The amount of entries in the list (Annex III) is increased, while when making the revision of this report (March-April 2021) additional LL are being added by a trainee in “missing” member states (Cyprus, Greece, Malta, Slovakia) and some urban LL from JPI Urban Europe are being added. They could not yet be added to Annex III. For the mapping exercise, also entries will be added while each single site (in a LL, or in a (EU) project with multiple LL in different countries) needs to be represented in a different row, to allow for adding georeferencing data. See also Annex IV

Many of the entered initiatives can be better linked to the Soil Mission’s operational objective 4 on soil literacy, 1 on R&I or 3 on monitoring, instead to operational objective 2 on SH LL & LH (table 4.5 and Annex III).

Figure 4-3: Amounts of LL, LH and combined LL/LH initiatives in the overall list of LL/LH

Coverage over country: as can be seen from the division of initiatives per country, (Figures 4-4 and 4-5) a bias can be seen due to additions made by people from a specific country, (e.g. Spain, Austria, Germany, France, Ireland, Netherlands). Some countries show an under- or overestimation of LL and LH. Although countries are mentioned, the initiatives are not georeferenced. Within SMS, a mapping exercise is being performed (Annex IV) including the georeferencing of initiatives. This exercise can help cleaning up the list because all entries that are not place-based (e.g. the guidelines for good practice, workshops etc) could be marked as “not qualifying as a SH LL or LH”.

Figure 4-4: Geographical division of LL, LH, LL/LH initiatives in Europe. (Plus 9 initiatives spread over different European locations, + 11 outside Europe (not shown on the map))

Figure 4-5: LL, LH, LL/LH initiatives per country (only European)³³

Coverage over land uses: Figure 4-6: LL, LH, LL/LH initiatives per land use group shows that the amount of LL & LH initiatives of agricultural land uses (arable and livestock farming) is much higher than the other land uses. This is potentially an overrepresentation due to the people (mainly with an agricultural background) who added initiatives. Some extra effort could be paid at searching urban and forestry initiatives that have a link with soils.

Figure 4-6: LL, LH, LL/LH initiatives per land use group (note that LL & LH that have no specified land use group are missing from this table)

³³ LL in “multiple countries” contain the following combinations: Austria, France, Germany, Italy and Slovenia, Liechtenstein, Switzerland; Belgium, France, Luxembourg, Netherlands, UK; Germany, Sweden, Spain, France, Romania; Hungary, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, Switzerland, France and Slovenia; Italy, Latvia, Spain, Romania, Norway, The Netherlands and Belgium; Luxembourg, Belgium, France, Germany

Coverage over Topics: Although the overview of LL / LH gives some information (Short Description) on the content of the initiative, it does not have any information yet towards which Soil Mission objectives these LL & LH contribute. This lacking information is a restriction for the usability of this list to determine if these LL / LH could fit in the European network.

4.4 Setting up successful SH LL and LH (networks)

The EU Mission “A soil deal for Europe” (EC, 2021) has set several impact, outcome and output indicators related to operational objective 2: Co-create and upscale place-based innovations. An important aspect is to establish actives LL&LH and the broader adoption of results leading towards improved soil health by practitioners. Therefore, this section goes into some aspects of setting up LL in a sustainable and successful way.

4.4.1 Success factors/barriers/principles for LL

In Maring et al., 2021, many criteria, principles, tips and tricks and additional characteristics for LL to ensure that they are set up in a **sustainable way** (viable), and that they will **reach impact** (outputs, outcomes) were listed from different networks (eg ENOLL³⁴), projects and literature.

Neef et al. (2017) sum up in a more structured way **success factors/barriers for LL**³⁵ from literature:

- **Political context** concerns political, social and legal preconditions for the creation and functioning of a living lab. E.g. a higher policy priority helps when starting a LL. Also, arrangements such as subsidies for certain innovation improve the rate of success for LL as well as existing support for collaboration between policy makers and citizens.

However, the LL should be able to act independently from local political context and should have the liberty -to a certain extent- to experiment outside existing rules and regulation.

- **Resources** point to the importance of users, time, money and institutions in the functioning of living labs. Without time and budget there is insufficient space for an effective learning process. The amount of time to spend for the involved actors should be realistic.

Another point of attention is that the actors should be relevant and representative to the issue addressed and that actors should be attracted AND removed when necessary during the LL process (being able to be adaptive).

- **Outcome** factors endorse the correct approach towards aims, results, monitoring, expectations, roles and statements during the living lab process. Unclear aims and expectations can frustrate the LL actors. A clear scope is of key importance to future success and necessary to set a framework to monitor results. The latter being of importance to implement the LL results in practice / policy or regulations. At the same time, it should be possible to change set aims and results, in a reasoned way, to elaborate unforeseen but valuable opportunities and directions for research and innovation (being able to be adaptive).

³⁴ Tips & tricks: https://enoll.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/07/finalcards_tt_print-1.pdf

³⁵ They have also tested 3 Dutch LL (LL spatial adaptation (climate adaptation); LL firm city on soft soil (soil subsidence) and LL InnovA58 (infrastructure) on how they score on these success factors and barriers

- **Collaboration** concerns the quality, differences, support, motivation (sense of ownership) and adverse incentives that can stimulate or undermine success during the lab. It is a challenge to keep all actors on board. Continuous motivation, trust between actors, and coordination are therefore important success factors. The role of a process manager is important, for example to bridge differences in knowledge capacity and interests between involved actors, to avoid that they focus on individual gains instead of the group process and aims of the LL.

Continuity (as also mentioned underneath under “principles”) can be a result of the above success factors, that are in a sense the enablers for continuity of a LL or LH.

Principles for LL

To support the above success factors / barriers, the principles underneath can be taken along when setting up SH LL & LH. These principles are generally applicable on LL and were elaborated by Bergvall-Kareborn et al. (2009) for managing innovation processes, Humble (2014) for LL in dementia care and by Van Well (2018) in the EVOKED ERA-NET project on climate services.

- **Continuity:** Durable relations between stakeholders so there can be a long-term process in which knowledge is continuously shared.
- **Openness:** Representative stakeholders functioning in a transparent setting that provides options for co-production and learning
- **Realism:** Involve real users in a real-life setting based on identified needs, while keeping an optimistic and realistic view. When orchestrating the process and combining and customising methodologies, the purpose of the living lab is better refined and there is a set-up for external actors to participate and add to valid outcomes.
- **Empowerment (or influence):** Encouraging and enabling users to engage in the innovation process, not limiting this to validation but as ownership of the process itself.
- **Value:** results are concrete and measurable, are attractive and added value for the users, involvement of users is cost- and time-effective
- **Spontaneity:** Detecting and analysing emerging needs and ideas of users.
- **(Sustainability: activities are performed in an ecologically, socially, and environmentally sustainable way. This aspect is not so much a boundary condition for success, as well as an important value to take along in the LL setup and activities)**

Examples

We elaborated 3 examples from our LL / LH list, agricultural land (The Horizon 2020 project AgriLink, different European countries), forestry (Des hommes et des arbres, France) and urban land (The Living Labs of the Amsterdam Institute for Advanced Metropolitan Solutions, AMS, The Netherlands) along their characteristics (scale / aim / participants / activities / context), as described in section 4.1, and the principles (Continuity, Openness, Realism, Influence (Empowerment), Value, Sustainability) as described in section 4.4.1. The aim was to find relevant differences and points of attention in terms of success factors. The elaborated examples are presented in Annex VI. Among the many observations a few are highlighted underneath in textbox 4-1.

Textbox 4-1: Observations from 3 LL examples (Annex VI)

Continuity:

- The **funding** of LL is key to determining continuity of a LL. Funding for a specific period on a **project basis** (e.g. for the agricultural LL and the urban LL) can both enable and threaten continuity and steer the development of products and outputs. If funding is restricted and inflexible, this can hamper the spontaneity, and the flexibility to change set aims and results towards promising opportunities and directions for research and innovation (success factor outcomes). However, in AgriLink, the provision of funding for the LL provided impetus for stakeholders to engage in a more open innovation process leading to successful outcomes.

Openness, Empowerment (or influence):

- In the agricultural example, external influences, or the **social** and **political context** were found to be significant. This wider context can hamper or encourage openness of projects and influence the outcomes of, as well as the collaboration within the LL.
- For the forestry example the **large scale** of the LL was the reason to set up an association with different levels of membership, which can influence the openness and empowerment of actors. They can differ for different actors. As long as this is clear to all actors and there is a correct orchestration of the process and a good process manager, this does not have to be a problem.
- **Ownership** and empowerment of the actors be very important for the success and continuity of LL (this aspect is mentioned under the success factors “collaboration”). Although this comes from the AgriLink example, it is likely that this is valid for all kinds of LL. The sense of ownership also influences other principles, such as continuity and realism.

Realism, value

- The setup of all described LL was done in such a way, that realism and value is ensured. The **real-life setting** is used and involvement of end-users in the **cocreation** process are mentioned as boundary conditions. However, the **orchestration of the process and the role of a process manager** are important to keep actors looking at the same direction.

Soil health / actor needs:

- For the forestry and agricultural examples, the link to soil is easy to make, although the objective of soil health needs a translation towards more direct and perhaps shorter-term objectives linked to the LL situation and actor-needs. For the urban living lab, soil (health) is a much more implicit aspect within the complex urban issues. It would be good to highlight the role of soils the larger challenges and objectives such as climate change adaptivity, circularity, etc... *(Note: in some cases, such as the urban LL Breda³⁶ and urban LL on soil subsidence in Gouda³⁷, both in the Netherlands, the link with soil is easier to make while urban agriculture resp. soil subsidence are main topics in the LL setup)*

³⁶ <https://urbanlivinglabbreda.nl/>

³⁷ <https://www.slappobodem.nl/projecten/110/gouda-stevige-stad>

4.4.2 Actor engagement in SH LL and LH

Although much has been said about involving actors in LL in the sections above, it is important to state that to engage actors in soil health LL, they should have an incentive, or angle to engage in land and soil management topics. This is not always part of the main activities of actors. Even farmers, who are very directly connected to soil for its production function, have different ideas about soil health or can find it a vague or long-term objective and are not triggered by it.

SMS already elaborated draft value propositions for different actor groups (table 2-1; reported in Brils et al., 2021) to see where their gains and pains lie and what soil and land can offer them (why should they engage). SMS has elaborated actor needs as reported in chapter 3 (and Annex VII and IX) of this deliverable. The specification of actor needs and value propositions can be a valuable tool to engage the actors in SH LL. The survey and workshops performed are a first step helping to link the mission objectives to the main actor needs and potential topics that can be addressed in the LL.

Related to actor needs, it is important to consider the social-cultural circumstances in which a LL is set-up, to be successful (as already described in Maring et al., 2021). Actor, but also specifically citizen engagement is important in LL and especially in SH LL as foreseen under the EU mission “A Soil deal for Europe”. Hague et al. (2016) describe materialistic and post-materialistic values and how they apply to the level of engagement from citizens. Materialistic values are basic needs such as economy (having a job and food), safety and health. These values occur when citizens are uncertain or scared about their situation. Next to this, post-materialistic values are linked to the “new way of living” when the basic needs are fulfilled. Stakes that then become more important are for example dealing with climate change and citizen participation. When the materialistic needs aren’t fulfilled, citizens are less likely to have post-materialistic needs. Why care for urban biodiversity when you don’t have a job or food. When raised in poverty, someone will be likely to keep value to materialism, even when the needs are fulfilled. Values occurring during youth are hard to change. When linking these materialism and post-materialism values to the different degrees of potential actor / citizen participation in LL it is needed to search for the above-mentioned angles (already at the very onset of the LL e.g. in codesign/cocreation workshops) to get and keep actors involved and pay attention to the different success factors and values when setting up the LL.

4.4.3 Governance and funding of a LL and LH network

When developing this deliverable, it is too early to give solutions or very concrete recommendations for setting up a governance structure and funding (business model) plans for SH LL & LH networks, next to what the implementation plan for the Mission for Soil health and food (EC, 2021) is proposing. However, some points of attention are given.

In the implementation plan for the Mission activities for setting-up a core-network of LL and LH are given. For SH LL & LH an EU support structure will be set up that will:

- prepares the ground at regional and local level for the setting-up of LLs and LHs;
- undertakes networking activities and interface with other relevant activities such as the EJP Soil, EIP AGRI, other missions and partnerships;
- makes use of regional and national structures established under the CAP including the European Network for Rural Development.

Next to that, it is recommended that the support structure for LL&LH seeks synergies with objectives and instruments of relevant policies and regulation such as:

- the CAP, in particular 2nd pillar measures including cooperative, result-based and knowledge transfer activities such as LEADER and EIP-AGRI for aligning environmental and climate protection performance with agricultural production,
- Soil Strategy and upcoming Soil Health Law, in particular related to the common objectives around Soil Health,
- Horizon Europe instruments that allow for setting up and supporting LL such as LIFE, INTERREG (see also section 5.3.1 of “A Soil deal for Europe” (EC, 2021)).

Activities need to take place in all member states/associated countries and address a range of land uses and topics and, build upon the current landscape of LL and LH). Different instruments under Horizon Europe can be employed to setup the governance of the LL network and to setup and run the LL & LHs (figure 4-7).

Figure 4-7: The phases of the creation of the European network of SH LL (EC, 2021, page 30 text, page 31 figure)

The EU support structure for the SH LL / LH network should consider different points when developing a **governance structure and funding**. Several points of attention here given below:

Existing LL versus new LL:

The existing overview of LL gives many examples that already fit in an existing governance structure but do not meet the SH LL characteristics. It will be very hard to “fit” these many existing LL in a new structure when it is too demanding. The criterion to work in a LL consisting of multiple sites, orchestrated at landscape scale is until now not seen very much. Also, the transdisciplinarity can be challenging, while a lot of initiatives have mostly natural sciences on-board and focus not so much on social and economic sciences yet. But these aspects are precisely what raises the ambition, hence the attention of the Mission board to these criteria. Advice is to work out several scenarios to deal with existing LL, for example:

1. An elaborated scenario where funding and support is found for existing LL to fulfil the SH LL criteria and fit in the governance of the SH LL network
2. A network with a core circle (with SH LL) and another –outer- circle with the existing structures (some of which not qualifying as LL, but with useful results and experience) that would be there as stakeholders for exchange, communication, dissemination and exploitation
3. A very light effort scenario: a practical choice can be to focus solely on a “new” LL network, nicely covering the topics, locations as foreseen by the mission. However, a lot of ‘LL capital’ is missed in this scenario.

Existing LH versus new LH?

For lighthouses, the criteria to qualify as a SH LL are less demanding. They are sites of high performance in the light of soil health and the mission objectives. In the existing overview of LL and LH, many of the LL entries would actually not qualify as a SH LL, but they would fulfil the criteria for a SH LH. Also, there are some existing LH in areas that may not succeed in developing a SH LL and are therefore very interesting to keep the actors in those areas involved and use these LH and their actors as demonstrating sites and ambassadors for soil health, with as added value to raise interest in the LL approach. While the term LH is not widespread until now (except for the global network of lighthouse farms and the UNCCD lighthouse activities for climate change actions), building this SH LH network can be an interesting starting point and have high added value in demonstrating activities and approaches improving soil health.

Learning and exchanging between LL

A SH LL itself already has a governance, while it is consisting of different sites with science, policy, practice involved. When a European network of LL is set up, not only on different topics, but also over different land uses, which all involve very different communities (e.g. the urban community is different from the agricultural community) and cultures (languages), it can become an unworkable situation. We propose to keep it as simple and practical as possible. Joint learning and exchanging on specific land uses (e.g. forestry); in specific regions (e.g. alpine regions); or on specific topics (e.g. climate change, mission objectives, disciplines/techniques or other components such as monitoring. In this way, the communities meet, but keep the relation with their own interests. The promotion of best practices can be done through the lighthouses, and the overall abstraction of lessons learned a communication, dissemination and exploitation plan should be set up to effectively reach the right target groups. Experiences from networks as ENoLL, EIP-AGRI or European Research Infrastructure (RI) (such as the existing LTER - Long-Term Ecosystem research in Europe) can help here.

Monitoring progress

The EU Mission “A soil deal for Europe” aims with SH LL & LH at different outcomes:

- **Improved awareness by land managers** of soil health challenges (objectives 1-6) and **uptake of innovative solutions** (...);
- **Measurable improvement of soil health** (...) see also Annex I;
- **Increased social capital** (norms, networks, relations between actors) (...), triggering further positive long-term developments in soil health and ecosystem services related domains;
- **Improved citizen awareness** (...) (EC, 2021 page 33)

“Rigorous monitoring will assess progress and allow the planning to be adapted during the mission’s lifetime” (EC, 2021 page 19). This is also the reason for the different phases in setting up the LL & LH (Figure 4-7). These subsequent phases allow for learning by doing and improvements in defining relevant characteristics, success factors and principles for SH LL & LH (figure 5-1).

Of course, there is a need for indicators to perform the monitoring on the above outcomes. In Annex II, an intervention logic model for the operational objective on LL is given, together with (tentative) impact, outcome and output indicators for soil health and the mission’s operational objectives are given as proposed in the implementation plan (EC, 2021). These include specifics for the operational objectives, including the one on SH LL & LH. The Soil Mission also envisions a mid-term review in 2025, an assessment after 2027 as part of the overall Horizon Europe monitoring and evaluation and a final review in 2030 to assess the Mission’s performance. These reviews and assessment will include the progress of LL & LH.

Upscaling and replication

For upscaling LL & LH approaches and practices³⁸ to areas beyond the areas in which the living labs are established, a point of attention is to consider next to the technical dimension also other dimensions such as the institutional, economic, social dimension as is mentioned under the SH LL characteristics (table 4-2, under CONTEXT). However, for upscaling also the difference between the LL environment (“real-life setting”) and the actual real-life are of importance. In a LL situation, activities can sometimes under some constraints be performed more or less independently from the local political context and have the liberty to experiment outside existing rules and regulation (see also “political context” under the success factors). The technical dimension concerns upscaling an innovation or practice from a parcel to a system, or from a street to a city. But when the activities are to be implemented from the LL environment in the actual real-life situation, they will not always fit to the daily practice of organizations or fit in the way how things are normally arranged. So, for successful upscaling the constitutional boundary conditions need to be investigated and considered. This is described more in depth in the “pilot paradox” of Van Buuren et al., 2018. The pilot paradox describes the important factors for both *internal success* of a pilot and the *external success* of a pilot. The internal success of a pilot has to do with the extent to which the pilot successfully realize its main ambition. The external success can be seen as the wider impact of a pilot. We define this success as the matter to which the output of a pilot also results into more enduring change within the policy regime (by changing policies, visions, rules and standards et cetera) and whether its findings or results are also applied in other contexts, in a larger area, time span or set of problems.

³⁸ Next to the upscaling of LL / LH approaches and practices, the process through which these innovations were generated in the LL can be also used and upscaled to new LL initiatives.

This also holds if the pilots demonstrate that a certain solution does not work at all or under certain conditions (Van Buuren et al., 2018). Below the factors for both *internal* and *external* success are displayed. To address the pilot paradox and thus improve the chance on upscaling and replication, it is important to pay attention to both the internal and external success factors.

Figure 4-8: The factors for internal and external success of pilots (based on Van Buuren et al., 2018)

The pilot paradox also applies to *Lighthouses*. These Lighthouses can be helpful for upscaling approaches and practices to other locations, because they have demonstrated high performance and showcase it on a (cooperative of) farm(s), urban, forest or natural site.

The predominant mode of thinking about scaling (of pilots, LL and the innovations they bring forth) has emerged over the past decades: a systems perspective (see Schut et al., 2020, and Woltering et al., 2019). As Giller (2022) describes: *“In the conceptual thinking of scaling from a systems perspective progress has been made from a mere technical replication of pilots and a very singular idea of adoption/non-adoption, to the constellation of a system and how there can be sustainable change at the level of a system rather than counting the number of adoptees”*. This more systemic view on upscaling and replication is also relevant for the Living Labs and Lighthouses of the Soil Mission.

Funding / business models for LL

Next to the EC as a funding mechanism of LL, different business models should be elaborated to be able to set up (medium to) long term LLs. European funding (Horizon Europe, LIFE, Cohesion policy etc) lasts in many cases several (4-5) years, while soil is a slow medium and LL should ideally have a longer lifetime. In some countries, there can be national schemes supporting LL (these can be traditional funding schemes or more open and innovative funding schemes that are less focused on a fixed result, such as the LL in “Des hommes et des arbres” in France). It can be helpful to collaborate between EU and national schemes; the EU giving the seed money to set up the SH LL in the right way, while national funding supports the LL afterwards.

Also, other mechanisms can be found, related to the aim and nature of the LL. For example, **education** can be a strong incentive to setup a durable LL. In the urban LL of Breda educational organisations work together with business, government and the city of Breda on urban issues (under which urban farming including robotics) with education as the main driver and the LL is integrated in the educational setup. The policymakers are not funding but contributing in kind.

For land users, developing new **techniques/methods** together with science, and business can be a valuable approach. The implementation plan (EC, 2021) support this: “Living labs and lighthouses under the mission will provide ample opportunities for business to work together with land managers, advisors and other stakeholders to test and establish soil health techniques”. For example, farmers can cocreate new techniques and methods to **improve yields on the long-term or their business model** (e.g. obtain better income by sustainable products). Other options can be to make a “**problem**” the main driver for the LL setup, such as a long-term remediation. The so-called never-ending remediation sites, where isolation, maintenance and monitoring / controlling takes place, could be interesting sites for LL research and innovation. Or soil subsidence in an urban setting such as LL “firm cities on soft soils” in Gouda as already mentioned under section 4.1. Also, a **shared ambition** can be a driver for stakeholders (organizations or individuals) to support a LL in terms of contributing in budget or in kind to activities, an example is the forest LL in “Des hommes et des arbres” in France. Setting up interesting business models for LL links very much to the actor needs as described in this deliverable (why should actors engage with soil health / soil and land management).

5 CONCLUSIONS / RECOMMENDATIONS / OUTLOOK

As a general recommendation: the link between the topics actor needs and SH LL and LH, and for the other operational objectives (figure 1-1) should be elaborated in the next activities under the EU Mission “A soil deal for Europe”.

5.1 Prioritization of actor needs

Both the survey and the workshops provided valuable input to update the value propositions and the expected engagement of the actor-groups as described in D3.3. Due to the more qualitative nature of both the survey and the workshop results, quantitative statistical analyses are not feasible, but a good overview of needs per objective, including the background of the respondents and the countries and sectors that they are active in was produced.

The recent publication of the Soil Mission implementation plan indicates that the timing is right for this. Regarding the prioritization of actor needs, it is proposed to link these closely to the urgency *and* importance of the different Soil Mission objectives as perceived by the different actor groups.

It is now recommended to in close cooperation with WP2 of the SMS project use the results from this deliverable together with the results from D3.3 for designing of a theory of change or intervention logic for each specific Soil Mission objective. Important challenges that need to address in the steps are:

- Changing needs in the different phases of the planning and implementation process,
- Being aware of short-term interests and long-term ambitions,
- Searching for comparable themes between the groups (can be cross-cutting themes such as how to organize, finance etc..).

The above will be integrated in D2.4 which will report on soil and land management needs and gaps as input for the Soil Mission Roadmap. This will be done by updating of the value propositions per actor group as presented in D3.3 and mirror these propositions on a theory of change per Soil Mission objective resulting in a better insight in the role and (levels of) engagement in relation to the needs of the different actor groups. This output will be validated and adjusted by 1-on-1 or focus groups interviews and in the SMS expert group meeting in December 2021. In the same period a crosscheck of R&I gaps with stakeholders will be executed. A final validation with stakeholders will be done in February 2022. The results will be described and integrated in D2.4 which will provide an important basis to prepare and deliver the Soil Mission roadmap in October 2022.

5.2 Criteria for living labs and lighthouses

Characteristics and Selection criteria of SH LL and LH

- The definition or **characteristics** of SH LL and LH are at the stage that the implementation plan has been published quite mature and manageable. The only recommendation to make for is that before the calls to setup the LL & LH network, they should be definite.
- Concerning the **selection criteria**: The set scale of LL: requiring SH LL to consist from multiple sites can lead to a disqualification of existing LL to call themselves SH LL. A recommendation is to find a solution for this, that can be done by not applying the characteristics too strict for existing LL, or by “transforming” them (with support in terms of budget etc.) to the “new” SH LL setup.

Setting up successful SH LL and LH (networks)

- To change behaviour and values of actors involved, and to really make an impact on soil health and related ecosystem services at sites and landscape levels through the living lab approach, the design of the LL should consider the characteristics, success factors and principles carefully when setting up SH LL.
- Figure 5-1 sums up the main **characteristics, success factors and values** for SH LL (the characteristics differ for SH LH, see figure 5-2) as proposed and elaborated in chapter 4. They are in many cases interlinked and are important to consider in the different phases of LL. A recommendation is to further specify these factors and principles for SH LL and LH and to apply them in the calls for the SH LL. Also, the interaction and connection between LL and LH should be elaborated further. How can LL benefit from LH and the other way around e.g. in terms of definition of emerging needs, promotion, successful upscaling and making the concept of LL more accessible and attractive for actors to engage in them.

Figure 5-1: Main characteristics, success factors and principles for (SH) LL

Figure 5-2 + main characteristics for (SH) LH

Establishing a SH LL & LH network

- **Usability current LL overview:** There is still a lot of “noise” in the overall list of LL & LH, while the entries have not been validated. Many of the contributions to this list do not qualify as SH LL & LH when using the criteria as set in section 4.2, or as a LL at all following other criteria such as the ENoLL principles. For example, Communities of Practice, network and farmer advice activities are also found in the overview. These initiatives are actually more linked to operational objective 4 “engage with the soil user community and society as a whole” than with the operational objective 2 concerning SH LL & LH: “co-create and upscale place-based innovations to improve soil health in all places” of The EU Mission “A soil deal for Europe. Also, many of the already mapped existing LL do not follow the landscape approach, in many cases the proposed LL in the list exist from a single site, which can be still valuable in terms of a scientific contribution. When they prove to yield effective / successful methods, we can consider them as SH LH and learn from them / use them as demonstration sites.
- The recommendation is to start **validating the entries in LL & LH list** (Annex III) to qualify as SH LL & LH and then:
 - **add information** following Annex III (Used fields) to this list to see which land uses and topics (soil mission objectives) are covered
 - A next step is to **perform a GIS exercise** to see where the LL and LH that qualify as SH LL / LH are located. Do they cover the member states and associated countries? Are they covering different biogeographical / environmental zones?
 - These analyses show both the **existing SH LL & LH and the gaps** (location, land uses, topics (linked to Soil Mission objectives)) that should be covered. For the gaps, an additional literature research/survey on land uses and topics that seem under-represented can be done or new LL & LH can be attracted within the next Horizon Europe calls.
 - Additionally, it should be further investigated how LL and LH can address the Soil Mission objective to **reduce the EU footprint on soils outside the EU**. This objective covers many different topics, from consumer behaviour and trade to regulation and subsidies. It should be investigated if it is possible to have LLs and LHs in associated or other countries outside the EU to define and measure the footprint on soils and effects of measures within Europe.
- For the **existing, suitable SH LL & LH** a next step is to ensure that they are **willing and able to contribute and commit** to the European SH LL & LH network. For this, the specific objectives and governance of this network, the demands to and added value for (existing and new) LL and LH should be further elaborated by the LL network support structure together with the network members in the following steps under the EU Mission “A soil deal for Europe”.
- It can be recommended to connect this new network of SH LL & LH to the **existing ENoLL** network. This European network can facilitate outreach to a broader audience and the LL can benefit from the networks experience and research.
- For the actor engagement, the **actor needs** - why would they engage in SH LL & LH- need to be elaborated. The SMS project will make some further steps in this direction. These actor needs can also influence / **prioritize the** (most important and urgent) **topics** (linked to the mission objectives) that should be covered.

- The **governance structure** for the SH LL & LH network should be further elaborated, taking into account points of attention such as: **Existing LL & LH versus new LL & LH; Learning and exchanging between LL; Monitoring progress on their impact, outputs, outcomes; Upscaling and replication.** For the latter, it is important to keep the systemic view of upscaling on the radar of the Soil Mission. Also, when discussing the governance of the SH LL & LH network, experiences from the ENoLL network, Global network of lighthouse farms and UNCCD experiences on lighthouse activities related to climate adaptation, EIP-Agri and European research infrastructures and other relevant networks and initiatives can be helpful.
- The links between the different Horizon Europe **instruments and policies** (such as CAP or the Soil Strategy) and national funding / policy schemes should be further elaborated and made explicit how they can contribute to setting up and supporting LL & LH.
- Finally, the **business models** should be further elaborated. This is very much interrelated with the aspect of actor needs. Some incentives are mentioned section 4.4.3 but further substantiation with examples and prove is necessary.

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ANNEX I: SOIL MISSION SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES, TARGETS AND SOIL HEALTH INDICATORS

Table 1: soil mission specific objectives and related targets and soil health indicators

Source: The EU Mission “A soil deal for Europe” (EC, 2021 page 16-17)

Mission Goal: 100 living labs and lighthouses to lead the transition towards healthy soils by 2030			
Objectives	Mission targets in line with EU and global commitments	Baseline (see 8.A)	Soil health indicators
1.Reduce land degradation relating to desertification	T 1.1: Halt desertification to help achieve land degradation neutrality and start restoration ----- In line with SDG 15.3	25% of land in Southern, Central and Eastern Europe at risk of desertification.	All eight soil health indicators
2.Conserve and increase soil organic carbon stocks	T 2.1: Current carbon concentration losses on cultivated land (0.5% per year) are reversed to an increase by 0.1-0.4% per year T 2.2: the area of peatlands and wetlands losing carbon is reduced and the natural sink is significantly increased to help meet GHG reduction targets by 2030 and the Climate law goal by 2050. ----- In line with the Fit for 55 Climate Energy Package (Climate Law, revised LULUCF regulation) and the Paris Agreement 4 per mille initiative.	Area of land with low and declining carbon stocks = 23%. Area of degraded peatland = 4.8%	Soil organic carbon stock Vegetation cover
3.No net soil sealing and increase the reuse of urban soils	T 3.1: increase urban recycling of land beyond 13% and switch from 2.4% to no net soil sealing as a contribution towards meeting the target of no net land take by 2050. ----- In line with Roadmap to a resource efficient Europe, and Biodiversity Strategy including upcoming nature restoration targets	Area of land affected by soil sealing = about <1% of EU, but can be as high as 2.4%, Current rate of recycling of urban land for development: 13%	Soil structure (incl. soil bulk density, absence of soil sealing, erosion and water infiltration) Vegetation cover
4.Reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration	T 4.1: reduce the overall use and risk of chemical pesticides by 50% and the use of more hazardous pesticides by 50% T 4.2 reducing fertilizer use by at least 20% T 4.3: reduce nutrient losses by at least 50% T 4.4: 25% of land under organic farming T 4.5: Reduce microplastics released to soils to meet 30% target of zero pollution action plan T.4.6 Halt and reduce secondary Salinization All to be achieved by 2030 to contribute to meeting the target by 2050 that soil pollution is reduced to levels no longer considered harmful to health and natural ecosystems. ----- In line with the Biodiversity strategy, the Farm to Fork Strategy and the Zero Pollution Action plan.	27% - 31% of land with excess nutrient pollution Soil contamination: 2.5% (non-agricultural), 21% (conventional arable), ca. 40-80% of land from atmospheric deposition depending on the pollutant. Farmland under organic agriculture: 8.5% (2019)	Presence of soil pollutants, excess nutrients and salts

Objectives	Mission targets in line with EU and global commitments	Baseline (see 8.A)	Soil health indicators
5.Prevent erosion	<p>T 5.1: reduce the area of land currently affected by unsustainable erosion from 25% to sustainable levels</p> <p>-----</p> <p>In line with the Roadmap to a resource efficient Europe</p>	Area of land with unsustainable soil water erosion is 25%, with 70% of this being agricultural land.	<p>Soil structure, absence of soil sealing, erosion and water infiltration</p> <p>Vegetation cover</p> <p>Landscape heterogeneity</p> <p>Forest cover</p>
6.Improve soil structure to enhance habitat quality for soil biota and crops	<p>T 6.1: Reduce compaction of soils to go significantly below current levels of 23% - 33%</p> <p>-----</p> <p>As for forest soils: in line with the new EU Forest Strategy</p>	Area of land with critical levels of soil compaction = 23-33%, 7% of which is outside agricultural area.	<p>Soil structure, absence of soil sealing, erosion and water infiltration.</p> <p>Vegetation cover</p> <p>Landscape heterogeneity</p>
7.Reduce the EU global footprint on soils	<p>T 7.1: Establish the EU’s global soil footprint in line with international standards</p> <p>T 7.2: The impact of EU’s food, timber and biomass imports on land degradation elsewhere is significantly reduced without creating trade-offs</p> <p>-----</p> <p>In line with the Zero Pollution Action Plan</p>	Baseline to be created by mission activities	Food, feed and fibre imports leading to land degradation and deforestation
8.Increase soil literacy in society across Member States	<p>T. 8.1: awareness of the societal role and value of soil is increased amongst EU citizens, including in key stakeholder groups, and policy makers</p> <p>T. 8.2: soil health is firmly embedded in schools and educational curricula, to enable citizens’ behavioural change towards the adoption of sustainable practices both individually and collectively.</p> <p>T 8.3: citizen involvement in soil and land-related issues is improved at all levels</p> <p>T 8.4: practitioners and stakeholders have access to appropriate information and training to improve skills and to support the adoption of sustainable land management practices.</p>		All eight indicators (on a long term)

ANNEX II: INTERVENTION LOGIC FOR OPERATION OBJECTIVE 2 ON LL

This figure shows the (tentative) intervention logic for operation objective 2 on LL and additionally gives examples of impact, outcome and output indicators for soil health and the operational objectives of the EU Mission “A soil deal for Europe”.

Figure 1: The intervention logic related to operational objective 2: Cocreate and upscale place-based innovations to improve soil health in all places (Source: The EU Mission “A soil deal for Europe” (EC, 2021 page 27))

Table 1: proposed impact, outcome and output indicators (Source: The EU Mission “A soil deal for Europe” (EC, 2021 page 58-59))

	Impact indicators
<p>Mission goal: 100 living labs and lighthouses leading the transition towards healthy soils by 2030</p> <p>8 specific objectives to which specific indicators have been assigned (see table 1 in section 2.1)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Presence of soil pollutants, excess nutrients and salts - Soil organic carbon stock - Soil structure including soil bulk density and absence of soil sealing and erosion - Soil biodiversity - Soil nutrients and acidity (pH) - Vegetation cover - Landscape heterogeneity - Forest cover
	Outcome indicators (examples)
Operational objective 1: Build capacities and the knowledge base	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Level of access to knowledge on soil health issues and solutions - Uptake of knowledge and solutions by land managers as shown by changes in management practices (land use monitoring, surveys) - Product information about global soil footprint
Operational objective 2: Co-create and upscale place-based innovations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rate of awareness of land managers with regards to soil health challenges (survey based) - % of land managers having changed or adopted one or more of their practices in a direction improving soil health (in the living lab areas and outside) - Level of soil health indicators and ecosystem services <u>in</u> the living lab areas - Level of social capital (norms, values, networks, governance) in living lab areas (using quantitative and qualitative methodologies documented in literature)
Operational objective 3: Develop an integrated soil monitoring system	<p>Number of</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - active soil monitoring programmes in Member States - EU reporting making use of up-to-date and harmonised reporting - Member States introducing a soil health certificate
Operational objective 4: Engage with the soil user community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Level of awareness of citizen and key stakeholder groups with regards to societal role and value of soil (survey based) - Level of access to information and trainings to improve skills and to support the adoption of sustainable land management practices.

	Output indicators (examples)
Operational objective 1: Build capacities and the knowledge base	<p>Number of</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - publications on knowledge in relation to the mission's specific objectives and soil health indicators - roadmaps developed per specific objective - infrastructures, platforms and other resources for experimentation and ready-to use knowledge on solutions for soil management t - land managers and other "users" of soil health services involved in R&I activities - best practices and solutions developed and tested in relation to specific objectives and land uses (e.g. apps, techniques for reduction of contentious inputs and remediation)
Operational objective 2: Co-create and upscale place-based innovations	<p>Number of</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - living labs, lighthouses and experimental sites, active and present on the interactive map - stakeholders involved in the living labs - innovative soil management technologies or practices developed/adopted in the living lab area/adopted in other areas - demonstration/upscaling/training activities undertaken, number of participants in these demonstration activities - reports, scientific publications, professional articles and media articles on lessons learnt in the living labs R&I activities (in particular focused on systems approaches, transdisciplinarity, socio-economic, behavioural and cultural drivers of change). - knowledge exchange activities conducted between living labs, indicators qualifying the intensity of community exchange (e.g. through social media) - cooperation activities with living labs and lighthouses outside Europe
Operational objective 3: Develop an integrated soil monitoring system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Availability of targets and thresholds for each soil health indicator - Level of harmonisation of monitoring protocols and reporting across Member States - Extent of operability of data sets across Member States - number (existence) of tools for self-assessment of soil health
Operational objective 4: Engage with the soil user community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rate of soil awareness amongst citizens (survey based); - Number of national school curricula on soil related subjects, number of tool-kits, and of good practices (school gardens, vegetable gardens, composting spaces, digital tools); - Existence of a 'best of resources' repository on soil communication, education, and engagement with high-quality materials for different target groups (measured by number of visits); - Number of municipalities and regions pursuing citizen-identified soil related objectives; - Number of businesses and companies developing strategies for valorising of soils in their production and supply chains; - Number of trainings for advisors and practitioners; - Number of people involved in soil related art-science-society events

ANNEX III: LL & LH USED / PROPOSED FIELDS AND OVERALL LIST WITH LL&LH

The overall list consists of the SMB overview of LL, SMS added LL and potentially AELL LL. Although it is a living document, for this deliverable the version of September 2021 was used.

USED / PROPOSED FIELDS

Uncoloured fields originate from the list as provided by the mission board for soil health and food, yellow fields were added by SMS for the sake of the LL mapping exercise and proposed "validation" method for LL&LH.

Table 1: (Proposed) fields in the overall LL & LH overview (sept 2021)

(proposed) Field	Explanation
source data	
"author" <i>not presented in list underneath</i>	who added the LL (name of the person when available), <i>when exchanging the list this field can be removed.</i>
Source <i>merged with a "comments" field in list underneath</i>	project / mapping initiative eg: SMB (soil mission board) or SMS (SMS project) <i>when exchanging the list this field can be removed.</i>
general info	
LL/LH	classification in LL or LH or both (links to the validation method for SH LL & LH)
EU <i>not presented in list underneath</i>	in EU or elsewhere (global)
Country / countries	could be plural, when a LL consists of multiple sites as is described for SHLL
Project / LL /LH name	
Overarching LL name or project name when Living lab created as a result of e.g. a Horizon project <i>not presented in list underneath</i>	selection method for series LL as defined in 1 project, or different sites under 1 overarching LL. (Each site needs its own "row" for georeferencing purposes)
Short Description	including AIM, ACTIVITIES, PARTICIPANTS, CONTEXT as compulsory aspects
weblink	to more info
contact person / email address <i>not presented in list underneath</i>	GDPR: hide when sharing / presenting
characterisation	
Land use	we proposed to split this further up in

(proposed) Field	Explanation
<p><i>merged to 1 column in list underneath</i></p> <p>originally the SMB used 3 columns with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Arable and livestock farming • Forest systems • Urban, peri-urban fringe 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agriculture / horticulture • Forestry • Urban • Protected areas • Industry • Infrastructure • Other <p>you might need to select multiple land uses when having combined LL sites</p>
<p>Which Soil Mission objectives are addressed?</p> <p><i>not presented in list underneath</i></p>	<p>the choice was made not to refer to (soil related) ecosystem services (ESS) or soil functions or SDGs that are addressed, but to link to the Soil Mission Objectives. This information is currently missing but can be easier be obtained than scoring a long list with soil-related ESS or the very overarching SDGs.</p> <p>SM objectives (EC, 2021) are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1.Reduce land degradation relating to desertification • 2.Conserve and increase soil organic carbon stocks • 3.No net soil sealing and increase the reuse of urban soils • 4.Reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration • 5.Prevent erosion • 6.Improve soil structure to enhance habitat quality for soil biota and crops • 7.Reduce the EU global footprint on soils • 8.Increase soil literacy in society across Member States
<p><i>potentially an additional field is needed to characterize LH (not implemented yet)</i></p>	<p><i>For LH, we are looking at sites that achieved and can demonstrate exemplary performance in terms of ecosystem services and soil health. Hence, it's a different column that you would need that could say something like "High ESS/SH value"? We are likely not to have the information to fill it (and criteria/thresholds would need to be specified) but this can be an important part of the tool for the future. The columns above on (SDG/ESS) Soil Mission objectives could be a good start. This is clearly something that can be specified in future calls.</i></p>

georeferencing	
geographic coordinates <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Georef- lat • Georef – lon <i>not presented in list underneath</i>	this information is being added for the mapping exercise. Not all entries will have a location, because they are not place-based (and therefore do not qualify as a SH LL/ LH) and in some cases just a “global” location is given, e.g. when a region or city is mentioned as the location. In that case a central point will be chosen to pinpoint the location
SH LL/ LH criteria	
Scale 1-Mono-Site (one farm, one urban site, one forest) 2-Multi-site (regional / landscape) <i>not presented in list underneath</i>	a SH LL has ideally always a multi-site scale (regional/landscape) while a LH is based on 1 site
Display [Y/N] <i>not presented in list underneath</i>	we have chosen not to add the validation criteria (in aims, activities, participants, context, see section 4.2 of this report) in separate columns because the table will be too complex. We propose to add these as compulsory aspects in the “short description” (for new entries) so a validator can use the info to assess if the LL or LH qualifies as a SH LL or LH. If YES, the entry will be displayed. If NO, the entry won’t be thrown away, but will not be displayed in the mapping as a SH LL/ LH.

LL & LH LIST

Version September 2021. The list of LL & LH was constructed by merging information of the updated LL&LH list from the Mission board for Soil health and food (updated list received by June 2021, indicated with SMB (soil mission board) in column “source”), LL and LH by SMS partners (D2.2 Wall et al., 2021) and further additions based on own knowledge, literature / online research). The list is sorted on 1) country; 2) LL/LH and 3) comments (when it is merely a soil literacy instead of a LL/LH example, these entries are marked in red font) 4) land use.

In the above table it is indicated which fields are presented in the list below and which fields have been removed because they do not contain data yet (georeferencing / Soil Mission objectives) or author / contact person due to GDPR. Please note that all entries outside Europe have been removed.

The full list can be made available on request by the report’s author.

SMS Soil Mission Support

LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
LH	Austria	Grand Farm - Austria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • organic farming & vermiculture • organic farm applying low-tillage methods to maintain and improve the soil • on-farm research projects support the development of agroforestry, the livestock sector and a the market garden • frontrunner in advancing vermiculture and vermicomposting – composting with the help of earthworms • 90 hectare arable field research and demonstration farm focusing on soil-health, agroforestry and market gardening • in the long crop rotation, lucerne, winter wheat, maize, hemp, soybeans, rye-vetch mixes and more are produced • in 2015, a cooperation with Rodale Institute (USA) was established, to carry out trial sand research in organic no-till methods • in 2019 Alfred established GRAND GARTEN, where a team of young university graduates is producing all year round organic vegetables for the regional market and doing research and demonstration activities 	https://www.lighthousefarmnetwork.com/lighthouse-farms/grand-farm	Agriculture	SMB
LL	Austria	AGES long-term field experiments	The Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES) and its precursor organisations carry out long-term field experiments since more than 60 years. The main research sites are Fuchsenbigl (Marchfeld), Grabenegg (Alpenvorland), both Lower Austria, and Ritzlhof (Upper Austria). They are representative of productive soils managed as arable land.	http://www.ages.at/themen/umwelt/boden/forschung/	Agriculture	SMS, Del 2.2
LL/LH	Austria	"Neu Leopoldau" - From Industrial Area to Housing for All	Hard work characterized the site of the former Leopoldau gasworks in Vienna for decades. At the same time, it also offered places of community for workers. Being an abandoned brownfield site for a long time a project to revitalise and build up a new city quarter under the name of "Neu Leopoldau" is implemented. The redevelopment process started by an urban design ideas competition and complemented by a participatory neighborhood process. In 2016, the IBA Vienna commissioned a research project on the subject of "Young Housing in Neu Leopoldau". The process of coordination and realization of children- and youth-friendly spatial design is the focus in Neu Leopoldau. Particular attention is paid to outdoor space planning, adapted forms of housing, and spaces for physical activity specially designed for children and young adults. Following an in-depth analysis of soil risks for establishing an integrated concept for safe environmental conditions the entire construction phase and each site for new buildings gets audited to finally certify "good soil conditions". Revitalised and upcycled the "Neu Leopoldau" welcomed its first new residents by summer 2019.	https://www.iba-wien.at/en/projekte/projekt-detail/project/neu-leopoldau	urban	SMB

SMS Soil Mission Support

LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
LL/LH	Austria	Humus balancing for farmers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Humus balancing allows farmers to calculate for themselves whether their cultivation and crop rotation increases the organic matter content of the soil or reduces soil organic matter in the long term. • Humus balancing courses for farmers (site-adapted humus balancing method) are offered and operated by Bio Forschung Austria since nine years and have been attended by around 1100 farmers. • For additional information visit: www.bioforschung.at/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/Humusbilanzierung_22_25-BLW_01-2020.pdf 	www.bioforschung.at/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/Humusbilanzierung_22_25-BLW_01-2020.pdf	not specified	SMB
LL/LH	Austria	Multi-purpose hedges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hedges protect the soil from wind erosion and ensure that the fertile topsoil is preserved. Multi-purpose hedges contain wild fruit, nut trees, precious woods or woody plants for energy production, which raise the owner`s income. The possibility of use increases the incentive for farmers to plant such hedges. • Additional information on multi-purpose hedges as best practice for an agro-ecological measure is available here: www.bioforschung.at/projects/mehrnutzungshecken/ 	www.bioforschung.at/projects/mehrnutzungshecken/	not specified	SMB
LL/LH	Austria	Hand-held soil determination brochures for forest soils	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • These brochures are part of a training project for foresters which is financially supported by the ministry • They contain e.g. general information about forest soils and humus, a simple key based on 6 questions to determine the soil type, comprehensive descriptions of the different soil types including information about the management (tree type, biomass withdrawal etc.) ... • These brochures are used e.g. in forest schools, for trainings of foresters etc. • At the moment a similar product for agricultural and grassland soils incl. an App is under development • For additional information visit: https://www.waldwissen.net/wald/boden/bfw_waldbodenfaecher/index_DE 	https://www.waldwissen.net/wald/boden/bfw_waldbodenfaecher/index_DE	not specified	SMB
LL/LH	Austria	Selected national and international projects related to Soil Health	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Several projects under EIP-AGRI and national funding are carried out in order to improve soil management, soil knowledge, awareness raising and soil protection. For example in the national project “AustroPOPs” a monitoring of persistent organic pollutants in Austrian soils is carried out to identify possible pollution by emerging pollutants (https://www.bodeninfo.net/projekte/austropops/) 	https://www.bodeninfo.net/projekte/austropops/	not specified	SMB
LL/LH	Austria	Selected national and international projects related to Soil Health	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in several projects under HORIZON 2020 with focus on multistakeholder information, such as “Agridemo” (www.agridemo-h2020.eu) and “Landmark” (www.landmark2020.eu). 	www.agridemo-h2020.eu www.landmark2020.eu	not specified	SMB

SMS Soil Mission Support

LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
LL/LH	Austria	Selected national and international projects related to Soil Health	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> One example for an international project is e.g. the “Links4Soils” Project (https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/links4soils/en/home). This project which ends 2020 aims at overcoming existing gaps by linking Alpine soil knowledge and experts, elaborating sectoral soil information and creating best-case practices and promoting soil management. This is guaranteed by founding the Alpine Soil Partnership (https://alpinesoils.eu/soil-partnership/) and establishing an alpine soil information and decision platform (https://alpinesoils.eu/). 	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/links4soils/en/home https://alpinesoils.eu/soil-partnership/ https://alpinesoils.eu/	not specified	SMB
LL/LH	Austria	Selected national and international projects related to Soil Health	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “Impuls4Action” is an ARPAF project that builds on results of on-going projects such as “Links4Soils” and aims to trigger actions to support sustainable development on all levels by providing appropriate tools, raising awareness and finding new models for sustainable soil protection in the Alps: https://www.alpine-region.eu/projects/impuls4action-intelligent-land-use-sustainable-municipalities-0 	https://www.alpine-region.eu/projects/impuls4action-intelligent-land-use-sustainable-municipalities-0	not specified	SMB
LL/LH	Austria	Selected national and international projects related to Soil Health	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In the H2020 project “Landsupport” an integrated web-based Land Decision Support System is being developed aiming to support the implementation of policies for agriculture and environment in EU member states such as Austria (https://www.landsupport.eu/) 	https://www.landsupport.eu/	not specified	SMB
LL/LH	Austria	Selected national and international projects related to Soil Health	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fruit- and Winegrowers in the project “Leader” learnt how to use a regionally adapted spray technology that is gentle on the soil, with reduced use of herbicides, minimal spray drift, low noise and low fuel consumption. Participating fruit- and winegrowers got individual training sessions. https://obstwein-technik.eu/891/LEADER-Projekt 	https://obstwein-technik.eu/891/LEADER-Projekt	not specified	SMB
LL/LH	Austria	AGES-Sortenfinder	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To facilitate a feature-based, comparative and fast variety selection - based on regional yield data - the AGES recently launched an interactive variety finder. This makes the Federal Office for Food Safety in cooperation with AGES, alongside CETIOM, the first European approval institution to offer such a tool to the agricultural sector for winter wheat, winter barley, grain maize, potato, sugar beet and winter grain rape. For additional information visit: https://sortenfinder.agrarcommander.at/ 	https://sortenfinder.agrarcommander.at/	not specified	SMB
LL/LH	Austria	Plant Protection Alert System	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In Austria, plant protection products undergo a comprehensive science-based testing and risk assessment process during the authorization process. The prerequisite for the approval of a plant protection product is minimizing the risk to human, animal and environmental health. The Plant Protection Alert System in Austria with its monitoring and forecasting models is an efficient and modern tool for optimizing crop protection measures. This tool offers an alert service for diseases and pests in 	https://warndienst.lko.at/	not specified	SMB

SMS Soil Mission Support

LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
			the areas of crop farming, vegetable gardening, fruit growing and viticulture across all crops and nationwide. The Alert Service offers 28 prediction models and 24 monitoring maps. The monitoring maps provide farmers important information, recommendations and warnings on the current plant health situation. The aim of the alert service is to inform farmers in time about the occurrence of diseases and pests. This platform enables the compliance of the good plant protection practice and the proper use of plant protection products in time and in accordance with the warnings and forecast models.			
LL/LH	Austria	Pesticide Reduction Programme (PRP)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More than 15 years ago the Pesticide Reduction Programme (PRP) was initiated by REWE Int Group in cooperation with GLOBAL 2000 with the aim to constantly and sustainably reduce pesticide residues on fresh fruit and vegetables (https://www.global2000.at/pestizidreduktionsprogramm). Its success is based on the following 4 pillars: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. binding standards for producers and suppliers 2. regular monitoring 3. close exchange with producers and suppliers 4. public relations • Every week, fresh fruit and vegetable samples are taken following a risk-oriented schedule and analyzed by accredited laboratories. As soon as the results become available, all producers and suppliers are immediately informed about residues on their produce. Regarding transparency as a consumers right, all results are published on the publicly accessible websites of the supermarkets Merkur and BILLA. Results are evaluated by GLOBAL 2000 according to following standards: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o maximum residue levels according to law (MRL) o acute reference dose (ARfD) o verification of not containing prohibited substances o PRP-maximum residue level (based on values of Acceptable Daily Intake = ADI) o Sum of exposure (considering „cocktail effect“) o Endocrine Disrupting Chemicals (=EDCs) • Over the years, the PRP can look back on many achievements regarding pesticide reduction, for example: In 2003, residues of chlorpyrifos, a highly poisonous insecticide, could be found on 80% of all apples tested. Due to a close cooperation and hard work of apple producers and the PRP alike, residues of chlorpyrifos have been eliminated by 2017. • Intensive exchanges with producers and suppliers are a key element to success. Only by working together, common solutions can be developed and realised. 	https://www.global2000.at/pestizidreduktionsprogramm	not specified	SMB

SMS Soil Mission Support

LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • With many future challenges lying ahead, the PRP cannot rest on its laurels. Especially EDC (Endocrine Disrupting Chemicals) are a great concern in regards to safe and high quality food. Minor residues of these substances can negatively influence the endocrine system of humans and animals alike. Thus, future goals of the PRP include the reduction and elimination of EDCs in fresh fruit and vegetables, as well as further generally reducing pesticide exposure via fruit and vegetable consumption. 			
LL/LH	Austria	Training course on "pesticide certificate of competence"	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • According to the Plant Protection Products Ordinance 2011, when selling plant protection products, personnel holding a certificate from the Federal Office for Food Safety must be available to provide information on the risks to human health and the environment and safety instructions for risk management for the products concerned. • The following contents are taught in the course: Legal basics - national and EU law, product definition, authorisation and licensing of plant protection products, plant protection product register, placing plant protection products on the market, integrated pest management and organic farming, toxicology and user protection, plant protection product residues and consumer protection, basics for the protection of the environment & groundwater Measures for risk reduction & loss prevention • Target group: staff of trading companies selling plant protection products, consultants 		not specified	SMB
LL/LH	Austria	AGES long-term field experiments	AGES carries out arable field experiments since 1954. The topics range from different tillage treatments and different kinds and amounts of organic/mineral fertilisation to the effects of long-term crop residue management (removal and incorporation) on soil parameters and crop yields and quality.	Heide Spiegel, Taru Sandén, http://www.ages.at/themen/umwelt/boden/forschung/	Agriculture	SMB
LL/LH	Austria	Soil.Pioneers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involves 20 light house pioneer farms (mainly from the Farmers Alliance www.bodenistleben.at) that are compared to standard management for determination of the potential of innovative farming systems for closing soil organic carbon deficits of arable soils. • Key management principles are revealed that drive soil organic carbon storage in stable SOC pools (aggregate-occluded, mineral-bound). • Investigation of processes such as microbial diversity that underly the SOC storage increase in pioneer farming systems a. • Development of management sensitive indicators for soil organic carbon monitoring • Development of on-farm tools for soil fertility assessment. 	https://www.bodenistleben.at/	not specified	SMB

SMS Soil Mission Support

LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Field days and courses for farmer to promote management adaption for soil organic carbon and soil health improvement. 			
LL/LH	Austria	KLIWA (Climate resilience through water-saving organic farming)	In Eastern Austria, an operational group(OG) consisting of 7organic farmers, consultants and scientists was established. The aim of the group is to test strategies to adapt to climate change in arable farming. Machinery and adapted farming strategies utilizing the cover crop based organic rotational no-till system (CCORNT) will be tested in maize and soybean trials, and cut & carry systems with legume transfer mulch will be investigated in maize and potato trials, all under on-farm conditions. The OG will study the influence of these strategies on yield, soil and crop water demand. Additionally, within a long-term monitoring project on an organic farm east of Vienna, the effects of different organic fertilisation and tillage systems (plough vs chisel) on plant and soil traits will be further investigated. The aim of the OG is to develop and test farming strategies valuable in adapting to climate change.	https://boku.ac.at/fileadmin/data/H03000/H93000/H93300/AG_Boden/Projekte/KLIWA/Publikationen/Booklet_template_WS_Cropping_for_the_future_Gollner_KLIWA.pdf	not specified	SMB
LL/LH	Austria	Training for Soil Practitioners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This Training for farmers is offered and operated by Bio Austria (an union of organic farmers) since far more than 10 years and is financially supported by the ministry • The nine training days (81h) are broken up through the whole year and provide theoretical and practical sessions for the soil related topics; there are two different types of training for arable land and for grassland • The training is also open for conventional farmers • At the moment the content is revised and updated • For additional information visit: https://www.bio-austria.at/bio-bauern/beratung/pflanzliche-erzeugung/boden/ausbildung-zum-bodenpraktiker/ 	https://www.bio-austria.at/bio-bauern/beratung/pflanzliche-erzeugung/boden/ausbildung-zum-bodenpraktiker/	not specified	SMB Soil literacy example
LL/LH	Austria	Training for farmers in the framework of ÖPUL 2015 - the Agri-environmental Programme until 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Preventative ground-water protection” – courses. Between 2017 and 2018 alone, around 1500 people took part in over 50 events. • E-Learning: “Nitrogen in agriculture” - content: Nitrogen in agriculture, Nitrogen and management, Nitrogen fertilization in practice (23 arable crops), Nitrogen and environment • E-Learning: “My soil knowledge” – content: soil formation, soil functions, soil composition, soil structure, soil types, soil structure, humus, erosion, catch crop cultivation • The courses and E-Learnings were implemented in cooperation with the rural training institutes and the AGES. The target group are farmers. • For additional information visit: https://oe.lfi.at/onlinekurs-mein-bodenwissen-wir-gehen-dem-boden-auf-den- 	https://oe.lfi.at/onlinekurs-mein-bodenwissen-wir-gehen-dem-boden-auf-den-grund+2500+1609901 https://oe.lfi.at/onlinekurs-stickstoff-im-ackerbau+2500+1798801 https://www.bmlrt.gv.at/english/agricultur	not specified	SMB Soil literacy example

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LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
			grund+2500+1609901 https://oe.lfi.at/onlinekurs-stickstoff-im-ackerbau+2500+1798801	e/Rural-development/-pul2015until2020.html		
LL/LH	Austria	Painting with the Colours of the Earth	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This international activity is carried out since 2007 under the responsibility of the government of Lower Austria • The aim of this ongoing project is societal education, soil awareness and sustainability • The target groups are farmers, schools and other educational institutions, municipalities and all interested people • Various national and international projects with CZ, SK, HU, RO - e.g. successful painting competitions with soil colours in schools have reached more than 80.000 persons until now • The basis is a painting box "with the Colours of the Earth". These colours of course differ according to the regions and soils which are used for the production of these colours • The concept "soilart for you(r planet)" enables regions/local bodies to extract and use soil colours of their won – in production together with social enterprises • For additional information visit: http://www.soilart.eu/ 	http://www.soilart.eu/	not specified	SMB Soil literacy example
LL/LH	Austria	Pedagogical and educational activities towards soil awareness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A summary of all current and past soils awareness raising activities guided and advised by the Austrian Soil Science Society (ÖBG – Österreichische Bodenkundliche Gesellschaft) has been compiled in the article "Bodenbewusstseinsbildung und Bodenpädagogik in Österreich": https://www.researchgate.net/publication/331037176_Bodenbewusstseinsbildung_und_Bodenpädagogik_in_Osterreich_Ein_Streifzug_durch_ausgewahlte_Beispiele 	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/331037176_Bodenbewusstseinsbildung_und_Bodenpädagogik_in_Osterreich_Ein_Streifzug_durch_ausgewahlte_Beispiele	not specified	SMB Soil literacy example
LL/LH	Austria	Pedagogical and educational activities towards soil awareness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In 2014, the Austrian ministry for Education has requested a summary of the Austrian pedagogical offer related to soil for kids of all ages and for adults. This summary is available here: https://www.oekolog.at/static/fileadmin/oekolog/dokumente/Schwerpunkt/Natur_erleben_im_Schulumfeld/OnlineversionLernmoeglichkeitenBoden_IK2.pdf 	https://www.oekolog.at/static/fileadmin/oekolog/dokumente/Schwerpunkt/Natur_erleben_im_Schulumfeld/OnlineversionLernmoeglichkeitenBoden_IK2.pdf	not specified	SMB Soil literacy example

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LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
LL/LH	Austria	Pedagogical and educational activities towards soil awareness	· Several research institutes offer workshops for schools under the name “Boden macht Schule” (https://bfw.ac.at/rz/bfwcms.web?dok=9821)	https://www.umweltbundesamt.at/seminare-schulungen/boden-und-bildung	not specified	SMB Soil literacy example
LL/LH	Austria	Pedagogical and educational activities towards soil awareness	· Österreichisches Bodenbündnis (Soil alliance) (https://www.bodenbuendnis.or.at/) offers every year a seminar for communities. This seminar aims at raising soil awareness within the communities.	https://www.bodenbuendnis.or.at/	not specified	SMB Soil literacy example
LL/LH	Austria	Pedagogical and educational activities towards soil awareness	· University for Life Sciences and Natural Resources (BOKU) offers the possibility for communities to ask for a visit of a soil bus (https://boku.ac.at/humusplattform/boku-mobil). The aim of this project is to bring soil knowledge to the people.	https://boku.ac.at/humusplattform/boku-mobil	not specified	SMB Soil literacy example
LL/LH	Austria	Pedagogical and educational activities towards soil awareness	· In the projects “TeaTime4Schools” and “TeaTime4App” (https://teatime4schools.at/en and https://teatime4schools.at/en/teatime4app/), the Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES) has engaged over 150 school classes in order to raise awareness about the importance of soil, soil functions and their interrelation with the climate. All school classes have conducted the Tea Bag Index (TBI) experiment, which measures the rate of organic matter decomposition with the help of tea bags. The data was submitted to the global TBI database (http://www.teatime4science.org/data/map/). Moreover, the educational TBI app was developed, which comprises different hands-on methods to explore soils, e.g. Texture by feel method, Spade test, Soil animals observation, and the TBI experiment.	https://teatime4schools.at/en https://teatime4schools.at/en/teatime4app/ http://www.teatime4science.org/data/map/	not specified	SMB Soil literacy example
LL/LH	Austria	Pedagogical and educational activities towards soil awareness	· Video TBI method: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=A_MFpo50bhI&t=20s (German)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=A_MFpo50bhI&t=20s	not specified	SMB Soil literacy example
LL/LH	Austria	Pedagogical and educational activities towards soil awareness	· Video TBI app: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IIICrWm84Ck (German)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IIICrWm84Ck	not specified	SMB Soil literacy example

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LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
LL/LH	Austria	Pedagogical and educational activities towards soil awareness	· The project "Soil Book" is an interactive tool to create awareness for the variety but also for the endangered status of soils (www.soilbook.info). Different soil profiles and soil-insights from 8 countries around the world can be viewed in spectacular 3D images. A selection of Austrian soil profiles in 3D can be found here: https://www.bodenoekologie.com/bodenprofile/	www.soilbook.info https://www.bodenoekologie.com/bodenprofile/	not specified	SMB Soil literacy example
LL/LH	Austria	Pedagogical and educational activities towards soil awareness	· The initiative "Natur im Garten" (Nature in the garden) promotes the greening of gardens and green spaces in Lower Austria and beyond. The core criteria of the "Nature in the Garden" movement stipulate that gardens and green spaces are and will be without chemical-synthetic pesticides and fertilizers and without peat sequences. (https://www.naturimgarten.at/)	https://www.naturimgarten.at/	not specified	SMB Soil literacy example
LL/LH	Austria	Soil networks	· Good established soil networks like "advisory forum for soil protection and soil fertility" (https://www.bmlrt.gv.at/land/produktion-maerkte/pflanzliche-produktion/boden-duengung/Bodenschutz.html) and the "soil forum" (https://www.bodeninfo.net/termine/bodenforum-oesterreich/) are active in Austria. They provide a regular information exchange between famers, farm advisers, researchers and administration.	https://www.bmlrt.gv.at/land/produktion-maerkte/pflanzliche-produktion/boden-duengung/Bodenschutz.html https://www.bodeninfo.net/	not specified	SMB Soil literacy example
LL/LH	Austria	Soil networks	· A new farmer's society has been founded in 2019 which already has around 200 members (www.boden-leben.at). Their aim is to improve the collaboration between farmers and researchers and to raise awareness for several aspects of soil protection. They are very active and have already organized a lot of successful field days, events ...	www.boden-leben.at	not specified	SMB Soil literacy example
LL/LH	Austria	Soil networks	· European Land and Soil Alliance (ELSA) is the largest European city network dedicated to the protection of soil. More than 250 municipalities and districts within 9 European countries, as well as a variety of regional NGOs and other organisations, are members of ELSA. The European agency, coordinating the network, is based in Osnabrück (D), which is supported by national coordination units in some countries (http://www.bodenbuendnis.org).	http://www.bodenbuendnis.org	not specified	SMB Soil literacy example
LL/LH	Austria	Soil networks	· EU Strategy for the Danube Region (EUSDR): The area includes 9 EU Member States, 3 Accession Countries and 2 Neighbouring Countries. It stretches from the Black Forest (Germany) to the Black Sea (Romania-Ukraine-Moldova) and is home to 115 million inhabitants. The topic of soil is represented within Priority Area 6 "Biodiversity, Landscapes and Air & Soil Quality". Lower Austria is member of the Steering Group of PA6 and responsible for the Task Force "Soil Strategy Network in the Danube Region" (SONDAR). For additional information: https://nature.danube-region.eu/	https://nature.danube-region.eu/	not specified	SMB Soil literacy example

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LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
LL/LH	Austria	Laboratory Practice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES) offers in a practice-oriented advanced training series "Laboratory Practice": Laboratory training courses for the detection of residues and pathogens as well as for the confirmation of the quality of food, feed and raw materials, among others. • Our laboratory training courses on the analysis of residues of veterinary drugs, on genetically modified organisms (GMO) or e. g. on the determination of elements comprise more than 20 course formats. • AGES operates 61 National Reference Laboratories, 21 National Reference Centres and 11 State Laboratories with Special Tasks and the Drug Control Laboratory for the analysis of food, feed, agricultural raw materials and operating materials, the detection of pathogens in humans, animals and plants. Every year 700,000 samples are processed using 1,350 accredited methods. • Within the laboratory training courses you learn about: relevance of sampling, sample processing, Analytics, infrastructure/equipment, qualification of the staff, QM, reporting, Utilization of the test results • Examples for trainings are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Analysis of Pesticide Residues in Plant Based Food and Animal Feed o Genetically modified organisms (GMOs) – Screening, Identification and Quantification o Heavy Metals in Food Contact Materials o Residue Analysis of Hormones and Hormonally Active Substances in Animal Matrices o Species Identification o Veterinary Drug Residues Analysis o Detection of Radioactivity with HPGe System in Food and Water o Determination of Mycotoxins in Food and Animal Feed • For additional information visit: https://www.ages.at/en/service/ages-academy/laborpraxis/ 	https://www.ages.at/en/service/ages-academy/laborpraxis/	not specified	SMB Soil literacy example
LL/LH	Austria	FutureSoils	<p>Project Futuresoils: In school workshops and on experiment days, children and young people are made aware of the subject of soil, landtake and nutrition, as well as professions related to soil.</p> <p>Their own nutrition, the space required for it in connection with the plants grown on it, the importance and properties of the soil as well as different cultivation systems with and without soil, up to "vertical" agriculture are professionally worked out.</p>	https://projekte.ffg.at/projekt/3757231	Agriculture; urban	SMB Soil literacy example
LL/LH	Austria	Advanced training courses offered by the	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To ensure food safety and food quality, the AGES offers countless courses every year. • A selection of the offered courses 		not specified	SMB Soil literacy example

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LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
		Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Principles of risk assessment and their practical application to food - Basic knowledge of risk analysis and risk assessment of contaminants and chemical substances in food; stages of risk assessment: hazard identification, hazard characterisation, exposure assessment, risk characterisation; derivation of health-based guide values; assessment bases for single-sample risk assessment and expert opinions on food law; current regulations and guidelines o Food law for businesses - European and national food law, product classification and legal positioning, food labelling and product description, communication measures around the product o Food labelling - Legal regulations - most frequent reasons for complaints and penalties, European Food Information Regulation - current requirements, basic knowledge about further regulations, labelling requirements o Hygiene training courses <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Target group: Experts, food inspectors, manufacturers, Trade, gastronomy, private persons, Teachers 			
LL/LH	Austria	AGES-Field-Days	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The AGES-Field-Days are a combination of theoretical and practical input for farmers. Current knowledge on site-adapted variety selection is combined with information on soil cultivation, soil management and soil analysis. • For additional information visit: www.ages.at/akdemie 	https://www.ages.at/service/ages-akademie/le-14-20-fort-und-weiterbildung/	not specified	SMB Soil literacy example
LL/LH	Austria, France, Germany, Italy and Slovenia, Liechtenstein Switzerland	Soil networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU Strategy for the Alpine Region (EUSALP) concerns 7 Countries, of which 5 EU Member States (Austria, France, Germany, Italy and Slovenia) and 2 non-EU countries (Liechtenstein and Switzerland), and 48 Regions. The topics of soil and food are represented by Action Group 6 “To preserve and valorise natural resources, including water and cultural resources”. Representatives of the administrations of Carinthia, Lower Austria, and Tyrol are members of AG6. For additional information: https://www.alpine-region.eu/action-group-6 	https://www.alpine-region.eu/action-group-6	not specified	SMB Soil literacy example
LH	Belgium	Ferme Henricot à Corbais	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alternatives to inorganic fertilisers • Reduced use of inputs and control chemicals • No tillage • Cover crops • Increased diversity / rotation of crops/ mixed cropping • agro-sylvo-pastoral system • Composting 	https://www.serres-henricot.be/	Agriculture	SMB
LL	Belgium	Project Hansbeke Agro-Ecology / ILVO	The theoretical principles of agroecology are put into daily practice, and through experiments, field trials, innovative techniques and intensive scientific monitoring, researchers quickly gain insight into the best systems and practices.	https://www.ilvo.vlaanderen.be/language/	Agriculture	SMB, SMS

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LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
		Living Lab Agrifood Technology (Belgium)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alternatives to inorganic fertilisers • Organic farming, no use of control chemicals • No tillage • Mulching • Cover crops • Increased diversity / rotation of crops/ mixed cropping • Agroforestry • Composting • Seed coating with microorganisms 	nl-BE/NL/Pers-en-media/Alle-media/articleType/ArticleView/articleId/5849/Eerste-grootschalig-AGRO-ECOLOGISCH-PROEFPLATFORM-in-Vlaanderen-gelanceerd-Versnelde-kennisopbouw-mbt-duurzame-landbouwpraktijk.aspx#.X2sTpJMzbGI		
LH	Belgium, France, Luxembourg, Netherlands, UK	FABulous Farmers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • pilot-project operating in different regions around the world • European project designed to support farmers in the transition to more agro-ecological practices on their farms • project aims to reduce the reliance on external inputs, like chemical fertilisers and pesticides, by encouraging the use of methods and interventions that increase the farm's Functional AgroBiodiversity (FAB) • targeted measures of biodiversity in and around the field to improve pollination, pest management, soil and water quality on the farmland • 12 pilot areas are spread over 5 countries • in each area the farmers can choose from a list of 10 FAB-solutions to implement on their field • The pilot areas are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • De Merode (Belgium) • Het Pajottenland (Belgium) • Pays de la Loire (France) • Ouest et Brocélian Bretagne (France) • Eure Normandie (France) • Stausee Ouwersauer (Luxembourg) • Hoeksche Waard (The Netherlands) • West-Brabant (The Netherlands) • Zeeland (The Netherlands) • East of England (United Kingdom) 	https://www.nweurope.eu/projects/project-search/fabulous-farmers/#tab-1	Agriculture	SMB

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LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pembrookshire (United Kingdom) • South West (United Kingdom) 			
LH	Bulgaria	Agrilink National Agricultural Advisory Service	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced use of inorganic fertilisers by performing soil analyses and providing recommendations to farmers • Assessment and advice on how to implement Statutory management requirements in a farm in way which improve soil health • Solutions to reduce erosion and land degradation • Positive impact from performing rotation of crops • Optimized and balanced fertilization • Use of environmentally friendly agricultural production methods contributing to the protection of soil and water resources • Non-plowing and conversion into arable land, minimum and zero tillage, measures to limit harmful soil acidity and soil salinization • Prevention of soil compaction • Activities to improve the organic composition of the soil on which permanently grassed areas are located, based on an analysis of the determined humus from the soil samples taken 	https://www.agrilink2020.eu/countries/bulgaria/	Agriculture	SMB
LL/LH	Bulgaria	Agrilink National Agricultural Advisory Service	<p>Bulgarian HUB under Horizon 2020 NEFERTITI* project Network 7 (Improved nutrient use efficiency in horticulture) is a group for sharing innovations, technologies and best practices on plant nutrition, with purpose to increase the efficiency of nutrient use and environmental protection. The HUB is on national level.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstration of good practices of reduced use / alternatives to inorganic fertilisers • Solutions to reduce erosion and land degradation • Knowledge exchange and presentation of specific knowledge to farmers through soil and leaf diagnostics, how to make the nutrient balance at farm level - ecological and economic effect. The system of recommendations for fertilization based on the concept - the "reasonable" fertilizer in the reasonable standard, by the reasonable time and at reasonable way • Presentation of technological solutions for environmentally friendly fertilization of different varieties of one kind of vegetable crops • Demonstration of innovative practice in vegetable nutrition - aquaponics, hydroponics - efficiency and environmentally friendly 	https://www.agrilink2020.eu/countries/bulgaria/	Agriculture	SMB
LH	Czech Republic	Pro Silva Bohemica	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • how to start the conversion to the uneven-aged forests • forest adaptation to climate change – testing new silvicultural models • reducing clearcuts, soil erosion, etc. 	www.prosilvabohemica.cz	forestry	SMB

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LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • local, regional and national policy making – lobbying for legislation changes, support of non-profit forest functions • local, regional and national policy making – lobbying for legislation changes, support of non-profit forest functions • education of foresters • increasing biodiversity • improving forest health • improving soil & ecosystem water retention and micro-climate 			
LL/LH	Czech Republic	Mendel University in Brno – University Forest Enterprise (UFE)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • forest adaptation to climate change – testing new silvicultural models • continuous cover forestry and uneven-aged silviculture • reducing of clearcuts, soil erosion, etc. • increasing biodiversity • improving forest health • improving soil & ecosystem water retention and micro-climate • forest aesthetics for recreation – natural springs, grassy clearings, ponds, arboretum, interesting trees, etc. • forest education 	www.slpkrtiny.cz	forestry	SMB
LL/LH	Estonia	Soil sampling automation using mobile robotic platform - Estonia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • land based drone technology has considerable potential for usage in different areas of agriculture • here a novel robotic soil sampling device is being introduced • unmanned mobile technology implementation for soil sampling automation is significantly increasing the efficiency of the process • the automated and remotely controlled technology is enabling more frequent sample collection than traditional human operated manual methods • universal mobile robotic platform is adapted and modified to collect and store soil samples from fields and measure soil parameters simultaneously • the platform navigates and operates autonomously with dedicated software and remote server connection • mechanical design of the soil sampling device and control software is introduced and discussed 	https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/financial-connect/projects/autonomous-mullaproovide-kogumise-seadme	Agriculture	SMB
LL	Europe	Desira Project-Network	DESIRA Living Labs are 20 networks of stakeholders established across Europe and selected to represent a variety of agricultural, rural and forestry domains. They are constituted around a focal question (e.g. How to reduce the risk of forest fires?) and will co-develop ideas, scenarios, digital storytelling outputs, and socio-technical solutions related to digitalisation. Interaction in the networks will be based on both face-to-face and online activities.	https://desira2020.eu/living-labs/	Agriculture; forestry	SMS, Del 2.2

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LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
LH	Finland	Qvidja farm	<p>Qvidja farm is the most important intensive study site for Carbon Action. Qvidja is a test farm on regenerative agriculture and a field site for several interdisciplinary research projects (https://www.qvidja.fi/en/about-us/research-projects/), located in Parainen. Qvidja is also used actively for demonstration and dissemination, for different kind of stakeholder visits – for example the Finnish EU Presidency had a kick-off at Qvidja</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increasing photosynthesis by increasing vegetation cover, lengthening the period of growth and selecting crops and strains that increase yields • Management of soil structure and health • Reduced tillage • Increasing soil organic matter content by addition of manure, recycled fertilizers and soil amendments • Diversified crop rotation and crop diversification 	https://www.qvidja.fi/en/front-page/	Agriculture	SMB
LL	Finland	Carbon Action	<p>Carbon Action is a Finnish platform that develops and researches ways of accelerating soil carbon sequestration and how to verify the results scientifically. It also introduces climate-friendly, regenerative farming practices to Finnish farms.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increasing photosynthesis by increasing vegetation cover, lengthening the period of growth and selecting crops and strains that increase yields • Management of soil structure and health • Reduced tillage • Increasing soil organic matter content by addition of manure, recycled fertilizers and soil amendments • Diversified crop rotation and crop diversification • In addition : Carbon Action co-operation with the city of Helsinki has started on urban green areas : ‘Transforming lawns into flower fields and urban farms’ https://omastadi.hel.fi/processes/osbu-2019/f/173/results/22?locale=en 	https://carbonaction.org/front-page/	Agriculture	SMB
LL	Finland	Lahti LAB	<p>The Lahti LAB university of applied sci-ence LL was established in 2020 and focuses on topics: sus-tainability, innovations, design and health. There is an exchange program with the Dutch urban Living Lab Breda</p>	https://lab.fi/en/studying/why-lab/lahti-finland	urban	SMS
LL	Finland	Agro Living Lab Seinäjoki	<p>agri-machinery The Agro Living Lab project in Finland was a user-centred platform bringing together end-users and companies in order to improve the usability and acceptability of new ideas and solutions in machinery used in agriculture and forestry. Agro Living Lab has been admitted membership to ENOLL</p>	https://enrd.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/assets/pdf/research-and-innovation/8.AgroLiving-Lab-in-Finland_en.pdf &	Agriculture; forestry	SMS, McPhee, 2021

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LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
LL	Finland	Suurpelto Urban Living Lab	Suurpelto is a new urban area located between major traffic routes in the city of Espoo in southern Finland. In Finnish, Suurpelto means "great fields": the area originally consisted of 325 hectares of uninhabited, park-like forest. Following development of the area, the first inhabitants moved in during the fall of 2010. The City of Espoo's planning process, which took place over a period of 10 years, was unique in terms of combining inputs from various stakeholders, such as building companies, land owners, and city representatives. According to the vision, Suurpelto would be an ecological city that is close to everything. Homes, workplaces, culture, and pastime services would all be within walking distance. The intention of the plan is to promote wellbeing for people at all stages of life as well as to encourage ecological sustainability and opportunities to smoothly connect work, family, and leisure activities. Suurpelto would also serve as a living lab for novel technology and new ways of living.	https://timreview.ca/article/742	urban	SMS, McPhee, 2021
LH	France	Call GESIPOL from the French EPA (ADEME)	Demonstration sites where new assessment and decontamination (phytotechnologies) techniques are used to characterise and remediate contaminated land (e.g. projects MISCHAR, TRIPODE) aims: test new assessment and remediation techniques activities: Develop and test, communicate participants: Scientist, students, municipalities, local planners...	https://mischar-43.webself.net/ https://www.axelera.org/fr/actualite/GESIPOL-2-projets-finances-et-1-sur-liste-d-rsquo-attente-8211-Zoom-sur-le-projet-Tripode	industrial (contaminated land)	SMS/Minsitry of Environment FR
LH	France	Local experiments on de-sealing soils and renaturation	Demonstration sites where soils are de-sealed/de-impermeabilized to regrow nature (e.g. friche Kodak, ancienne gare routière d'Auchel, Life Artisan) aims: test new remediation techniques/new land planning management activities: Develop and test, communicate participants: to be clarified (projects just selected, no information yet - Sept 2021)	https://www.nature2050.com/projet/friche-kodak/ http://www.urbanisme-puca.gouv.fr/IMG/pdf/sequence_2_auchel.pdf https://www.actu-environnement.com/ae/news/projet-life-artisan-OFB-dix-territoires-pilotes-solutions-fondees-nature-adaptation-climat-36622.php4	industrial (contaminated land)	SMS/Minsitry of Environment FR

SMS Soil Mission Support

LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
LL	France	Des hommes et des arbres (part of Living Labs under the "Territoires d'Innovation" Scheme)	Des Hommes et Des Arbres is a regional project based on an unprecedented alliance of some 100 public and private actors from the South of Lorraine and the Northern Vosges Within the framework of an ambitious territorial project ("Des Hommes et des Arbres"), we implement a living lab approach, supported by LFLL know-how. The first results are presented in a pioneer PhD project, specifically focused on the design of innovation systems to improve wood mobilization in small private forests while conciliating all ecosystem services. These results concern especially co-created practical tools (Swoted "PESTEL", forest owners personas, etc.) useful for project facilitators. Living lab approach should complement or support existing schemes designed by French forest policies as "Plans de Développement de Massif" (Massif Development Plan), "Chartes Forestières de Territoires" (Territorial Forest Charters) or "Groupements d'Intérêt Economique et Environnemental Forestier" (Forest Economic and Environmental Interest Grouping).	https://www.deshommesetdesarbres.org/	forestry	SMB, SMS
LL	France	Lorraine Smart Cities Living Lab (LSCLL)	It covers 5 Issues for innovative territories (Details to come) The Man / Nature Relationship The Digital Transition The Energy and Ecological Transition The Art of Living and Moving Health and well-being at all stages of life	https://lf2l.fr/projects/lorraine-smart-cities-living-lab/	urban	SMS
LL	France	"Dijon, Sustainable Food and Farming 2030" (part of Living Labs under the "Territoires d'Innovation" Scheme)	Since 2017, Dijon Metropole has been working with its public and private partners to shift towards a sustainable food system. In 2019, the project "Dijon, Sustainable Food and Farming 2030", has been the winner of the French government prize "Territoires d'innovations". The Living Lab, coordinated by Dijon Metropole, implements a range of actions aiming at a) improving food and environment quality b) Citizens' diet and health and c) the relationship between farmers and citizens. Aim: "Transforming the agricultural system at the territorial level by experimenting a new consumption model for : - Better food and health for the population - Secure farmers (help with production transformation, training) - Improve the nutritional and environmental quality of local agricultural production - Better preserve the environment and biodiversity through innovative agroecology - Facilitate access to local quality products through innovative applications - Increase local agricultural production consumed by the inhabitants	https://www.metropole-dijon.fr/Grands-projets/Un-systeme-alimentaire-durable-pour-2030	Agriculture	SMS

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LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
			<p>- Certify and guarantee the production by creating the ""Dijon Agroecological"" label and an indicator to evaluate the growth in the consumption of local products</p> <p>activities: "This project is based on both :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the creation of a new model of agroecological production with high environmental performance and - the virtuous sharing of resources between the city and the agricultural world." <p>participants: An approach involving all the actors in the production, exchange, processing, distribution and consumption activities of a territory. Context: With its innovative players in this field (research, companies) and its reputation for its heritage and gastronomy, Dijon metropole has the ambition to become, within 10 years, the demonstrator of a sustainable food system that will serve as a model for national and international metropolises.</p>			
LL	France	Occitanum (part of Living Labs under the "Territoires d'Innovation" Scheme)	<p>The Occitanum project aims to mobilise digital technologies to accelerate the agro-ecological transition, enable farmers to earn a living and offer people access to local and sustainable food. The Occitanum living-lab is an original open innovation system that relies on a collective intelligence approach associating local players: companies, local authorities, farmers and giving a central place to the user in order to better innovate, here in agriculture.</p> <p>Aim: An exemplary agriculture, feeding the 1st food circuit in France</p> <p>Activities :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To create in Occitania a field of experimentation and full-scale demonstration of the contribution of digital technologies to agriculture and territorial economic development - Accelerate the agro-ecological transition - Enable farmers to recover their income - Enable people to have access to local and sustainable food" <p>Participants: To implement this innovation project, Occitanum has set up a consortium that brings together all the stakeholders in innovative projects: local authorities, users (farmers, cooperatives, citizens), innovation facilitators, agricultural development players, AgTech companies and research and transfer players.</p>	https://occitanum.fr/Occitanum-c-est/Le-Projet	Agriculture	SMS
LL	France	Terre et cité	<p>The aim of the association is to perpetuate, promote and develop quality agriculture on the Plateau de Saclay and its valleys.</p> <p>This objective is associated with the desire to preserve and enhance the associated heritage: natural, forestry, built, hydraulic, cultural... Support for the</p>	Terre & Cité Préserver et développer l'agriculture sur le	Agriculture	SMS

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LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
			<p>diversification and processing of local products, the improvement of the logistical aspects of local circuits and the installation and transmission of farms in the area.</p> <p>Participants: Terre et Cité provides a space for exchange between farmers and other actors in the area and carries out concrete projects. The association is made up of four colleges - farmers, elected officials, associations and citizens - and works in close collaboration with the local planners, namely the Établissement Public d'Aménagement Paris-Saclay (EPAPS) and the research community. Beyond the Plateau de Saclay, Terre et Cité collaborates and implements numerous projects (PAT, living lab, etc.) with neighbouring agglomerations, communities and associations.</p> <p>Research projects are performed in partnership between farmers and researchers; e.g.: (i) Greening of agriculture via waste products and legumes to improve ecosystem services. (ii) Dynamics of biodiversity and ecosystem services during peri-urban development.</p>	plateau de Saclay (terreetcite.org)		
LL	France	Syppre	<p>The Syppre project aims to support farmers in developing new production systems that meet the challenges of agriculture and the expectations of society by 2025.</p> <p>The cropping systems resulting from the Syppre project should provide more quality agricultural products, while being economically efficient and environmentally friendly.</p> <p>The Syppre project is based on a range of original methodological tools, involving farmers in the design and dissemination of the cropping systems developed.</p> <p>The Syppre project has a national dimension and relies on the expertise and partnership of the three technical institutes for field crops.</p> <p>The aim is to solve a complex equation, i.e. to produce more, to offer quality products, to work in environmentally friendly conditions and to be economically efficient.</p> <p>activities:"The Syppre project is based on an original method that combines an observatory, experimental platforms and farmers' networks.</p> <p>participants: Provides a space for exchange between farmers and technical institutes for co-creation</p>	https://syppre.fr/syp-pre-en-bref/	Agriculture	SMS
LL	France	Dephy network	<p>The aim of the DEPHY network is to test, develop and deploy agricultural techniques and systems that are economical in the use of plant protection products and economically, environmentally and socially efficient, based on a national network covering all French plant sectors. The DEPHY network</p>	https://ecophytopic.fr/dephe/carte-interactive-dephy	Agriculture	SMS

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LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
			mobilises all the stakeholders in agricultural development, teaching, research and agricultural transfer.			
LL	France	Un vignoble au service du vivant - le Laboratoire d'Innovation Territorial des Vignerons de Buzet	Using a Living Lab approach, this initiative is to implement the agroecological transition of the territories based on the innovative pathway, which is the cooperative' DNA. To do so, it first aims at (i) reviving the cooperative mind within the cooperators. This collaborative approach is necessary to (ii) demonstrate the resilience of the farming model embodied by Nous, les Vignerons de Buzet. Thus, they will (iii) broadcast their state of mind across territories and farming value chains.	https://www.nouslesvigneronsdebuzet.fr/	Agriculture	SMS, Del 2.2
LL	France	Living Labs under the "Territoires d'Innovation" Scheme	In 2010, France initiated the "Investissements d'Avenir" program, through which the French government invested in science, education, and public-private partnerships to: (1) accelerate a transition to sustainability and resilience through ecological principles, (2) base competitiveness on innovation, (3) build a state for the digital age, and (4) create foundations for a knowledge based society. The latest call for projects, "Territoires d'Innovation," was launched in 2019 and devotes €450 million to large regional innovation projects for six different "transitions": digital, sustainable energy, clean mobility, skill adaptation in an evolving labor market, the evolution of health systems, and the transformation of agricultural systems through agroecological practices. Among the 24 projects selected, 10 (Terres de sources, Sesame, des hommes et des arbres (elaborated in a separate line), dijon alimentation durable 2030, Ouesterel, Vitirev, Occit@num, Biovallée, Ambition Pyreénées, LITTORAL+) are oriented toward agroecological transitions and are expected to benefit more than 12 million people.	https://doi.org/10.3390/su13041718	Agriculture; other	SMS, McPhee, 2021
LL	France	Laboratoire d'Innovation Territoriale Grandes Cultures (Auvergne, France)	The Territorial Innovation Laboratory (LIT) for field crops in Auvergne is based on a new innovation approach in agriculture: the Living Lab method. This open, participatory and agile method makes it possible to co-create innovations with the users of the territory, in real conditions. innovations, bringing together a broad community, participatory ecosystem approach.	https://www.lit-gca.com/	Agriculture	SMS, McPhee, 2021
LL	France	Ateliers des territoires - Mieux aménager avec des sols vivants	Call from the Ministry of Environment (DGALN) to support the development of local dynamics that integrate soil as a resource to be preserved, recycled, regenerated. This call is addressed to actors working in collaboration mode, at the crossroads of multiple disciplines, to develop territorial projects based on land sobriety. Fives municipal areas were selected in Normandie (Lisieux),	http://www.atelier-territoires.logement.gouv.fr/session-nationale-mieux-amenager-avec-des-	Agriculture; forestry; urban	SMS/Ministry of Environment FR

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LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
			Guadeloupe (Cap Excellence), Occitanie (Avant-Monts), Centre VAI de Loire (Tours) and Paris. All projects include land planning issues, agricultural/forest and urban land uses, soil protection. aims: Introduce soil issues in land planning management at local level activities: to be clarified (projects just selected, no information yet - Sept 2021) participants: to be clarified (projects just selected, no information yet - Sept 2021)	sols-a171.html Atelier-des-territoires.ad1.dhup.dgaln@developpement-durable.gouv.fr		
LL	France	4pmille - Carpentras	Network of farms with different landuses (e.g. market gardening, olive growing, wine, field crops, an equestrian center and a goat farm) testing several practices to store C in soils (e.g. cover crops, permanent meadows, use of legumes, addition of organic matter, hedges...) aims: Testing new practices to store C in soil activities: Diagnose and help farms to improve C storage in soils participants: Several farms and agricultural chambers	https://www.jediagno.stiquemaferme.com/initiative-4-pour-1000-mise-en-place-dun-reseau-de-parcelles-en-provence-alpes-cote-dazur/	Agriculture	SMS/Ministry of Agriculture FR
LL	France	Dige'O - Obernai - methane digestate	Testing the use of methane digestate on soils and develop reference aims: Testing the use digestate on soils and crops activities: Diagnose, test, analyze and deveop references participants: Scientist, students, agricultural chambers...	https://adt.educagri.fr/exploitations-et-ateliers-technologiques/en-direct-des-exploit/grand-est/obernai-agronomie-methanisation.html	Agriculture	SMS/Ministry of Agriculture FR
LL	France	Observatoire de la santé des sols Rovalterra	Soil health observatory in several municipalities aims: Develop a tool for long term territorial monitoring of soil health activities: Diagnose, test, analyze and deveop references for a set of soil health indicators participants: Scientist, students, municipalities...	https://www.grandrovaltain.fr/rovalterra.html https://www.grandrovaltain.fr/files/Documents/Contrat%20Vert%20et%20Bleu/Prese ntation%20ROVALTER RA%20Juillet%202020.pdf	Agriculture; forestry; urban	SMS/Ministry of Agriculture FR
LL	France	Réseaux des lycées agricoles (network of agricultural high schools)	In several agricultural high schools, teachers may have part of his/her time for experimental work or for networking. Several are involved in actions with researchers and students on soil issues. The aim is to promote better soil management techniques	We got a report from the Ministry of Agriculture with weveral experiments but no web site	Agriculture	SMS Soil literacy example

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LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
			activities: Teaching and testing (see page 32 for an experiment in Belleville, page 41/47 in Albi) participants: Teachers	(report : https://adt.educagri.fr/fileadmin/user_upload/pdf/tiers_temps/s Emm2020/analyse_rapports_TT_2020_19_11-comprese.pdf)		
LL	France	Participatory Observatory of Earthworms	<p>This project benefits both the work of scientists through the accumulation of a large set of data, and also the education of citizens by raising awareness on scientific issues. It has several purposes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> to offer, through earthworm assessment, a simple tool for soil biodiversity evaluation in natural and anthropic soils, to provide simple sampling protocols, accessible to a wide range of citizens and adapted to the targeted public (farmers, territory managers, gardeners, pupils), to build a databank of reference values on earthworms: participants can enter the data online and in return is given an individual report of results, to offer trainings to farmers, to propose providing for example earthworm identification guidelines, general scientific background on earthworm ecology and the impact of agricultural practices. <p>This project benefits both the work of scientists through the accumulation of a large set of data, and also the education of citizens by raising awareness on scientific issues. It has several purposes: to offer, through earthworm assessment, a simple tool for soil biodiversity evaluation in natural and anthropic soils, o provide simple sampling protocols, accessible to a wide range of citizens and adapted to the targeted public (farmers, territory managers, gardeners, pupils), to build a databank of reference values on earthworms: participants can enter the data online and in return is given an individual report of results, to offer trainings to farmers, o propose providing for example earthworm identification guidelines, general scientific background on earthworm ecology and the impact of agricultural practices.</p>	https://ecobiosoil.univ-rennes1.fr/OPVT_accueil.php	not specified	SMS, Del 2.2 Soil literacy example
LL/LH	France	RegGAE: Natural regulations on field crops with agroecological practices - France	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • REgGAE aims to provide farmers guidelines for reducing their reliance on pesticides for pest management <p>The project combines several types of innovations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • agroecological, through the identification of on farm management options enhancing the biological regulation of pests and weeds • educational by active learning in concrete situations (training in observation, 	https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/financed-connect/projects/reggae-regulations-biologiques-en-grandes-cultures	Agriculture	SMB

SMS Soil Mission Support

LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
			in diagnosis and in actions) and through the development of pedagogic tools to be disseminated in training institutions across France			
LH	Germany	RUN - Germany	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • nutrient communities for sustainable agriculture • the aim of the RUN project (for Rural Urban Nutrient Partnership) is to close nutrient cycles between urban and rural regions • to achieve this, RUN combines the development of new and innovative technologies, the analysis of material flow models, systemic scenario analyses, and social science participatory methods • nutrients from biowaste and wastewater streams will be recovered and used for the production of safe and effective design fertilizers for agriculture • the core element is that nutrient communities are formed between farmers and urban dwellers, which have the potential to anchor a sustainable cycle closure in society • a living lab for experiments under real-time conditions: • in the course of the project, the construction of a large-scale pilot plant in an urban residential area in Heidelberg is planned • new technologies will be tested under real-time conditions and with the participation of different actors • the aim of the pilot plant is to demonstrate the implementation of nutrient recovery from the city in a short cycle into agriculture • an additional experience room will be set up to make RUN research tangible and understandable for citizens 	https://www.run-projekt.de/	urban	SMB
LH	Germany	BonaRes Funding Initiative	<p>The BonaRes funding initiative consists of 10 separate collaborative projects which all conduct research on sustainable soil use and management including stakeholder engagement.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Optimization of soil functions (productivity, carbon sequestration, nutrient cycling, water filtering and storage, habitat for biological diversity) • alternatives to inorganic fertilisers • optimization of nutrient use efficiency • increased diversity / rotation of crops • agroforestry • reduction of soil compaction • overcoming replant disease 	www.bonares.de	Agriculture; forestry	SMB
LH	Germany	Biohof-Lex - Bockhorn, Germany	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • since 1980 an ecologically managed agricultural enterprise, which was able to develop its own marketing with its small farm shop and with its quality awareness a customer base • family business that has been operating according to the guidelines of organic 	https://lex.typo3n.de /	Agriculture	SMB

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LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
			<p>farming for over 30 years</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • farm is located about 40km east of Munich near Erding • work is based on the guidelines of the Naturland organic farming association, of which they have been a member since its foundation • today the farm has a functioning marketing and takes on social responsibility by organising the school class programme "Explore the DIVERSITY on an organic farm" • in this programme pupils are introduced to the topic "biological diversity" in connection with organic farming and healthy nutrition in a playful way • Demonstration farm for organic farming 			
LH	Germany	Competence Network Organic Agriculture and Plant Production North East Brandenburg - Cropping School	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the "Organic Farming Region Southern Uckermark" is considered one of the largest organically cultivated arable farming regions in Europe and a nationwide "lighthouse region" for sustainable development of rural areas • in view of constantly changing such as climate change and the agricultural and soil market, maintaining this "lighthouse character" is a major challenge for organic farms in the region • promising approach is seen in the establishment and coordination of a regional competence network for organic agriculture and plant production with supra-regional cooperation between land use, educational and scientific actors • through this network, a new quality in the cooperation between (organic) farmers is to be achieved, which in the long term should result in a self-supporting cultivation ring structure over the long term. • network will work in a clearly defined spatial setting to solve inter-farm arable farming problems, which will be concretised and prioritised by the farms themselves 	https://www.hnee.de/de/Fachbereiche/Landschaftsnutzung-und-Naturschutz/Forschung/Forschungsprojekte/Aktuelle-Projekte/Cropping-School/Kompetenznetzwerk-kologischer-Acker-und-Pflanzenbau-Nordost-Brandenburg-Cropping-School-E9527.htm	Agriculture	SMB
LH	Germany	ADAPTER project Research Centre Juelich, IBG-3 (Agrosphere) and GERICS (HZG - Climate Service Center Germany)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge transfer and citizen science approach to : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide information to increase resilience to extreme weather events especially droughts e.g. : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • monitor and forecast soil moisture • monitor and forecast seepage water and groundwater recharge • implement observation network • Provide information to increase resilience to climate change e.g. : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • changes in average and extreme conditions of relevant parameters e.g. temperature & heat waves & precipitation & droughts • future optimal climate regions for given plants e.g. spatial shift 	https://adapter-projekt.de/	Agriculture	SMB
LH	Germany	ACKERBAUM - The Agroforestry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the Agroforestry Research and Model Project of the University for Sustainable Development in Eberswalde is located in the Löwenberger Land, about 50 km north of Berlin -the experimental area comprises approx. 30 hectares (approx. 	https://agroforst-info.de/portfolio-item/ackerbaum/	forestry	SMB

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LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
		Research and Model Project in the Löwenberger Land from the University for Sustainable Development in Eberswalde	<p>10 hectares each of agroforestry, zero area, short rotation plantation) of an agriculturally used area</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • students from all faculties of the university work together in the project • the project was offered for the first time in the winter semester 2017/2018 and represents an innovative form of teaching and learning (ILL) in which research is not only carried out across faculties but also on an interdisciplinary basis • the topics include biodiversity, soil, climate, plant health, marketing and public relations • the aim of the long-term scientific study is to use the findings gained to show how a complex agroforestry system can be structured • the owner's motivation is to counteract compaction, evaporation, impoverishment, loss and sealing by establishing agroforestry systems • his top priority for the design is to convince the tenant • furthermore, he wants the project area to have a radiating effect and to encourage imitation • the system should remain practicable and motivate many farmers to invest • in this context, the economic profitability should also be taken into account • agroforestry system may provide protection against wind and water erosion in particular; an effect which it can already begin to notice by planting roadside trees • also a goal is to building up soil fertility 	https://www.pflanzenforschung.de/de/pflanzenwissen/journal/baeume-als-schutzwall		
LH	Germany	Agroforestry Experiment Gladbacher Hof, Justus Liebig University Giessen	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Solutions to reduce erosion and land degradation • Improving soil fertility and soil biodiversity • Increasing above ground biodiversity and agro-biodiversity • Exploring new agricultural value chains from agroforestry • Implementating carbon sinks on agricultural land 	https://www.uni-giessen.de/faculties/f09/research/asrf/overview/gladbacherhof?set_language=en	urban	SMB
LH	Germany	Frisch vom Dach - Berlin, Germany	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "Frisch vom Dach" is planning to build the world's largest aquaponic roof farm on the roof of the Berliner Malzfabrik in order to practice sustainable agriculture and fish breeding all year round • mission is the construction, planning and operation of aquaponic farms in the city • the vision is year-round organic farming with a neutral CO2 balance • the Frisch vom Dach team is pursuing a clear goal: agriculture and fish breeding in the DACHFARM should contribute to sustainable nutrition through minimal water consumption and the elimination of transport routes 	https://www.gabot.de/ansicht/projekt-die-groesste-aquaponic-dachfarm-der-welt-220400.html	urban	SMB

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LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
LL	Germany		In Germany there is a big network on Urban living labs.	https://www.ioer.de/ioer-im-ueberblick/beschaefigte/wolfram/	urban	SMS multiple LL&LH, To be selected in terms of relevance for soils
LL	Germany	SUSALPS (BonaRes Project)/TERENO Observatory	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Best management practice to optimise yields, soil health, nutrient use efficiency and biodiversity • Adaptation to climate change • Adaptation to legislation 	www.susalps.de/en/	Agriculture	SMB
LL	Germany	Living Labs—A Concept for Co-Designing Nature-Base Solutions	paper	https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/13/1/188/pdf	forestry	SMS this paper contains some Living Labs in literature, check them for relevance
LL	Germany	Model region for sustainable bioeconomy	Fossil based energy production is phasing out till 2038 in the Rhineland. To promote the development of regional bio-based value chains and business models, BioökonomieREVIER is establishing 14 living labs at the interfaces of bioeconomy, digitalization and energy. These labs are designed e.g. as field labs or shared IT facilities to provide state-of-the-art development and test sites. They grant access for SMEs, farmers or local communities to co-design new concepts with researchers.	https://www.biooekonomievier.de/	Agriculture; urban	SMS, Del 2.2
LL	Germany	Global Change Experimental Facility (GCEF)	The GCEF is a field experiment located in Bad Lauchstädt, which allows the investigation of the effects of future climatic conditions on ecosystem processes under different land use scenarios. Especially higher temperatures and altered precipitation pattern in Central Germany are simulated on five different land use types. The facility is equipped with 50 plots having a size of 16 m x 24 m. The long-term experiment started in 2014 and is planned to be conducted for at least 15 years.	https://www.ufz.de/index.php?en=40038 ,	Agriculture	SMS, Del 2.2
LL/LH	Germany	NOcsPS – Landwirtschaft 4.0 ohne chemisch-synthetischen	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • in NOcsPS - Agriculture 4.0 without chemical synthetic plant protection, scientists want to analyse agricultural systems that do not use any chemical synthetic plant protection - but do use mineral fertilisers • the project, which is coordinated by the University of Hohenheim, hopes to combine the strengths of conventional and ecological agriculture 	https://nocps.uni-hohenheim.de/	Agriculture	SMB

LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
		Pflanzenschutz - University of Hohenheim	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • both farming systems have their shortcomings: While conventional farming aims to reduce the use of chemical pesticides, organic farming is not sufficiently productive to feed the world's population. • agricultural system located between the two systems: "The most modern automated and digitally networked technologies are used that follow biological principles" • "The aim is to achieve comparatively high yields with high-quality products while at the same time maintaining soil fertility, also through the use of mineral fertilisers" • before the system is later tested nationwide on farmland by farmers, there will first be test plants at the project partners of the University of Hohenheim in Baden-Württemberg and the Julius Kühn Institute in Brandenburg • the NOcsPS cultivation systems require a different crop rotation from stalk and leaf crops, with winter and summer crops • in addition to cereals and maize, protein plants such as pea, bean and lupin as well as catch crops are also integrated. This serves preventive plant protection and humus formation in the soil. • in the fields, the researchers investigate the effects of the cultivation method (e.g. effect on pollinating insects and on the soil) • the project partners are also carrying out laboratory tests, life cycle assessments, farm analyses and surveys, because the aim is to record and analyse the entire value chain in terms of sustainable production • NOcsPS cultivation systems can develop as a new agricultural system with a high potential to adapt to future conditions. They can thus support sustainable production of food and renewable resources and inspire the conventional and organic farming systems established to date 			
LL/LH	Germany	GreenGrass - University of Goettingen	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "Ruminants back to pasture" is the aim of the joint project GreenGrass - Innovative Use of Grassland for a Sustainable Intensification of Agriculture on a Landscape Scale, coordinated at the University of Göttingen • the project aims to reverse a trend that has negative effects on biodiversity and climate: livestock housing associated with the intensification of livestock farming, including feeding with silage and concentrated feed • many farmers have abandoned pasture farming because the conditions on the pasture fluctuate and are difficult to reconcile with high milk yields. Instead, the grass of the former pastures is cut and fertilised by machine four to five times a year. Only a few plant species can cope with this, many grasses and herbs disappear from the scar. • Insects, birds and small mammals lose their habitat. And because pastures are 	https://www.uni-goettingen.de/de/forschung/524575.html#GreenGrass	Agriculture	SMB

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LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
			<p>cultural landscapes, flora and fauna are not better off if the land is left alone for cost reasons: The former willows are becoming overgrown with bushes, grasses and herbs are disappearing here too.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • in order to bring the cattle back to the pastures, pasture farming must become economically attractive again. GreenGrass wants to achieve this goal by technological means. Using satellite and drone based remote sensing technologies, farms are to receive spatially and temporally precise information about the available quantity and quality of fodder on their pastures. This will enable them to meet the current nutrient requirements of their cattle exactly and at the same time boost plant growth, because targeted grazing will improve the distribution of animal excrement. • virtual fences (collars with GPS transmitters for positioning, combined with an advance warning signal and a subsequent aversive stimulus to direct the animals to certain parts of the pasture or to keep them away from certain areas for a while) • can be set flexibly in space and time via mobile apps • in combination with efficient and sustainable pasture management, this promotes both the regeneration of forage plants in the pasture areas and the preservation and optimisation of habitat structures and species diversity 			
LL/LH	Germany	Mulching vegetables - Economic vegetable cultivation in a natural mulching system - Germany	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mulch systems could make a contribution to sustainability of food by dispensing with pesticides or promoting humus formation • the OG combines the transfer and In-situ to a combined mulching process • an innovative planting machine, the MulchTec Planter, is intended to compensate for the work involved in mulch planting • the aim is to produce high-quality, regional vegetables with ecological added value at prices similar to those of common vegetables. Farms in 'non-vegetable regions' should also produce sustainable vegetables 	https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/financial-connect/projects/mulchgem%C3%BCse-hessen-wirtschaftlicher-gem%C3%BCseanbau	Agriculture	SMB
LL/LH	Germany	Cultivation of legumes for humus cultivation on dry sandy soils - Germany	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the project is intended to demonstrate the cultivation of fodder and grain legumes as the basis of humus cultivation in two crop sequences and to test new species in exact experiments for cultivation suitability for the present site conditions (dry sand soils) • by the cultivation of previously mixed mixtures with legumes (horn clover and / or Sicheluzerne with redhorn), a new culture for the crop rotation on sandy soil is to be established • the cultivation of the alternative legumes and their possible effects for the cultivation of humus have so far not been tested on these extreme sandy soils with low rainfall supply in practice cultivation 	https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/financial-connect/projects/anbau-von-leguminosen-zum-humusaufbau-auf	Agriculture	SMB

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LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
LL/LH	Germany	Practical innovation for the improvement of soil fertility and sustainability in stockless organic farms - Germany	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specialization, a lack of profitability and further reasons such as vegetarian diet of the manager leads to a growing number of organic farms that have no or only a low number of animals • farms with are mainly placed in regions which have a high share of cropland and spezial crops • this limits the possibility of importing organic fertilizer through fodder-manure-cooperation • the aim of the project ist to guarantee long term soil fertility of stockless organic farms which increases their sustainability 	https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/financial-connect/projects/mit-betrieblichen-innovationen-bodenfruchtbarkeit	Agriculture	SMB
LL/LH	Germany	Leibniz Institute for Agricultural Engineering and Bioeconomy (ATB)	<p>Issues being tested / demonstrated / innovated</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • On-the-go digital soil mapping using multiple proximal sensor systems • Sensor data fusion using machine learning for modelling high resolution soil property maps • Decision support system for site-specific, variable-rate determination of lime and fertilizer requirement • Precise and effective use of agrochemicals a modern, resource-efficient and yield-optimized agricultural production 	https://www.atb-potsdam.de/en/	Agriculture	SMB
LL/LH	Germany	Anhalt University of Applied Sciences, Department of Agriculture, Ecotrophology and Landscape Development, Institute of Bioanalytical Sciences (IBAS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced use / alternatives to inorganic fertilisers • Reduced use of control chemicals • Application of biological pathogen control • Solutions to reduce erosion and land degradation • Increased diversity / rotation of crops • Analysing rhizosphere microbiomes (prokaryotes, fungi, oomycetes) • Microbe mediated nutrient cycling in agricultural soils • Nutrient use efficiency • Mixed and intercropping, catch-crops • Agro-ecosystems resilience • Soil carbon (C-sequestration) • Digitisation and remote sensing • Combination of plant-derived bioactive substances and plant beneficial microbes (development and consultancy) 	https://www.hs-anhalt.de/en/start-page.html https://www.bioanalytik-anhalt.de/	Agriculture	SMB
LL/LH	Germany	AgroScapeLab Quillow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Solutions to reduce erosion and land degradation • Solutions to increase soil organic matter and soil fertility • Increased crop diversification/rotation of crops • Increase biodiversity through reshaping landscape structures • Reduce pesticide inputs by identification of disease hotspots at field scale (Agriculture 4.0) • Joint research platform for inter- and transdisciplinary research 	http://www.zalf.de/de/struktur/eip/Seiten/AgroScapeLab.aspx	Agriculture	SMB

SMS Soil Mission Support

LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
LL/LH	Germany	patchCROP	<p>The experimental site is part of the agricultural enterprise Komturei Lietzen GmbH which is located in Eastern Brandenburg.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased agricultural diversification by crop rotation and structural field elements • reduced use of chemical-synthetic pesticides • Design of future cropping systems through new field arrangements • Agricultural digitalization through successful use of automated and sensor-controlled technology • Agricultural system research including increasing shares of co-design and co-innovation and multidisciplinary research activities 	https://comm.zalf.de/sites/patchcrop/SitePages/Homepage.aspx	Agriculture	SMB
LL/LH	Germany	Bodenallianz Pfaffenhofen	<p>The municipal level is not responsible for agricultural issues in Germany. This makes Bodenallianz - as a municipally funded project - unique. Pfaffenhofen is providing €1 million for soil and species protection, the expansion of organic farming and re-uniting city residents and farmers. The farmers who participate in the project (currently ~ 80) are supported in order to provide all the ecosystem services linked to organic farming by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Close coordination between project management and a steering group of farmers • Ground courses - Internationally recognized experts provide free practical advice for farmers, duration: 3 years. • Marketing support - whether international or regional. • "BODEN.KLIMA" - Cooperation with the Bioland Foundation to investigate the storage of greenhouse gases in the soil. Duration: 3 years • "Fokus Natur Tag" - Specialist consultants take a close look at nature on the farm - what is done, what can be done in addition • Strengthening the organic/local supply - Farmers, processors and consumers are brought together • Linking the agricultural challenge to other municipal programs - Climate protection concept, climate adaptation strategy, Agenda 2030 • Citizens' Workshop and Sustainability Day - How can the people in the city contribute to the land alliance through their behavior? 	https://pfaffenhofen.de/artikel/solidaritaet-sprojekt-bodenallianz/	Agriculture	SMB
LL/LH	Germany	Citizen Science project on soil health and soil awareness as part of the Science Year	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • as part of the Science Year 2020 Bioeconomy, a nationwide Citizen Science Action on Soil Health is to be carried out • a large part of plant biomass is produced on soils, this means that soils are at the very beginning of many bioeconomic value creation chain • in order to ensure the sustainable and responsible use of soil as a resource with all its functions, it is necessary i) to have the most accurate information possible on the condition of the soil and ii) to increase public awareness of the 	https://forschung-sachsen-anhalt.de/project/citizen-science-projekt-bodengesundheit-23954	Agriculture	SMB Soil literacy example

SMS Soil Mission Support

LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
		2020 Bioeconomy	relevance of soil for humans and the environment • these are the two central objectives of the planned Citizen Science action			
LL	Germany, Sweden, Spain, France, Romania	SoilMan	Network of 5 Long Term Observation sites (LTOs) driven by universities and field sites belonging to real farms. Aims for a deeper understanding of the interrelationship between farm based soil management practices and soil biodiversity in view of improving soil health and soil fertility. provide knowledge on how soil biodiversity in turn feeds back into soil functions and ecosystem services as factors for agricultural productivity and sustainability.	https://soilman.eu/project/case-study-regions Center of Biodiversity and Sustainable Land Use, University of Göttingen, Germany	Agriculture	SMS, Del 2.2
LL	Hungary	ÖMKI Research Institute for Organic Agricultural Practices	The “on farm” system was created by organic farmers, of growing various crops, such as the spelta wheat, grow as novel and highly value wheat variety. Other crops as tomato, potato, other vegetables and The most intensive research are focused for the grape varieties and the organic bio-wine industry. Other project is focusing for the honey-bee, and the preparation of honey, prepared from local and national plants, as the Robinia pseudoacacia, grown in large territories and can give special value of honey. All the products have an ecological certificate from Biocontrol Ltd. that meets international biological-ecological standards • Ecological farming • Compost use and composting technologies • Ecological crop varieties in Hungary • closed-loop sustainable farming	https://www.biokutatas.hu/hu/page/show/onfarm https://biokutatas.hu/hu/page/show/meheszeti-on-farm-kutato-i-halozat	Agriculture	SMB
LL	Hungary	Homokháti Living Lab	agriculture and tourism	https://www.sed.inf.u-szeged.hu/content/homokhati-small-area-living-lab-benefiting-agricultural-sector-hungary & https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Hans-Schaffers/publication/230730354_Living_Labs_for_Enhancing_Innovation_and_Rural_development_Metho	Agriculture	SMS, McPhee, 2021

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LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
				dology_and_Implementation/links/5cc95be5a6fdcc1d49bc64fb/Living-Labs-for-Enhancing-Innovation-and-Rural-development-Methodology-and-Implementation.pdf#page=111		
LL	Hungary, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, Switzerland, France and Slovenia.	Restoring Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services in Agricultural Landscapes (REAL)	Prototype sensors for monitor soil biology diversity.		not specified	SMS, Del 2.2
LL	Ireland	Long-term Grazing Platform at UCD Lyons Farm	<p>The UCD Lyons Farm Long-term Grazing Platform (UCD LGP) provides a long-term platform to assess and develop the sustainability of Irish grass-based agricultural systems through investigation of the interactions between pasture types, animal production, the environment, labour and farm economics. A pasture systems approach is necessary to address the greatest challenges facing pasture-based agricultural systems:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) pasture resilience (ii) animal productivity, health and welfare (iii) food quality from farm animals (iv) environmental and social sustainability (v) labour, human capacity and financial sustainability. <p>Critical research questions that can only be addressed through a long-term experimental platform include:</p> <p>The productivity and stability of a range of pasture types under farm animal grazing systems.</p> <p>Effect of pasture type on the health and productivity of grazing animals.</p> <p>Effect of farm systems on soil carbon sequestration, soil quality and fertility, water quality, greenhouse gas emissions and biodiversity.</p> <p>Long-term economic performance, labour and knowledge requirements of pasture-based farm systems.</p>	https://globalfarmplatform.org/lyons-farm/	Agriculture	SMB

SMS Soil Mission Support

LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
			This is a farm systems experiment with 3 pasture types (perennial ryegrass, perennial ryegrass and white clover, and a grass, legume, forage herb mixture), each with 4 replicate 2 ha hydrologically isolated units, arranged in 8 paddocks, and grazing 20 livestock units. French drains to achieve hydrologic isolation were installed in Autumn/Winter 2018 and pasture types were established in 2019.			
LL	Ireland	Dooary Forest Ecosystem Research Platform	UCD's Forest Ecosystem Research Platform at Dooary Forest, Co. Laois has developed extensive capabilities to monitor tree and stand growth dynamics in high detail in relation to climate factors. Given that the site is strategically located in a commercially managed forest (by Coillte who are collaborators), the research findings are of direct relevance to the forest industry in Ireland. The research site was developed by a series of DAFM-funded projects and has been running since 2002. There is a substantial emphasis on understanding the interaction between climate and above- and belowground productivity. In particular there are long-running experiments into soil respiratory responses to climate, climate warming and forest productivity.	https://www.ucd.ie/carbifor/chronosequence.html	forestry	SMB
LL	Ireland	NEC Indicators	Indicators of air pollution effects on ecosystems. EPA project 2019-CCRP-LS_3. Long-term monitoring sites are part of a forthcoming National Ecosystem Monitoring Network being established by Ireland's Environmental Protection Agency, monitoring freshwater, natural, semi-natural and forest ecosystems for effects of air pollution, including flora and soil effects.	https://nemn.ucd.ie/	forestry	SMB
LL	Ireland	University College Dublin Lyons Farm Long-term Grazing Platform (UCD LGP)	The UCD LGP aims to develop the sustainability of pasture-based agricultural systems through investigation of the interactions between pasture types, animal production, the environment, labour and farm economics. 3 pastures (perennial ryegrass, grass/clover, and a grass/legume/herb mix), 4 replicate 2 ha hydrologically isolated units, each grazing 20 livestock units. Infrastructure in place to monitor soil fertility, nutrient losses to water, greenhouse gas emissions, soil C sequestration, pasture composition and resilience, biodiversity, animal health and performance, food quality and profitability. Additionally, blocks of land have been retained in arable (crop) production and planted with mixed tree species for comparison over time. As a farm systems experiment UCD LGP integrates research and innovation in a real-life setting, from soil to farm product. Management decisions and practices for each of the 3 sward-based systems must be optimised; an iterative process of communication and learning involving the researchers and a much wider group of stakeholders.	https://www.ucd.ie/lyonsfarm/research/long-term-pasture-based-productionsystemsresearch/	Agriculture	SMB
LL	Ireland	Marine Institute Newport laboratory and	• Laboratory and catchment with long-term fisheries and ecosystem research history (1955 to current) based in the Burrishoole catchment, Newport Co. Mayo. A catchment with 45km of streams, freshwater lakes (~450ha) and a	http://burrishoole.marine.ie	Agriculture; forestry	SMB

SMS Soil Mission Support

LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
		Burrishoole Catchment	tidal lagoon lake (141ha) (see deEyto et al 2020; Chapter13.2 in <i>Ireland's Rivers</i> , edited by Kelly-Quinn & Reynolds, UCD Press, 496pp) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In-situ immersive Ecosystem monitoring • Aquaculture and innovation development • Interested in promoting the facility as a gateway with NPWS for study on wilderness & rewilding, biodiversity conservation, Mayo dark skies, energy awareness (possible application for UNESCO World Heritage Site) • Cross sectoral research programme • Data integration for ecological forecasting • Long term ecological monitoring allowing for climate change attribution, aquatic carbon dynamics, water quality and diadromous fish population dynamics research • Collaboration with third level Institutions, State Agencies, community groups, schools, stakeholders and general public 	https://www.marine.ie/Home/site-area/infrastructure-facilities/newport-catchment-facilities/newport-catchment-facilities?language=en		
LL	Ireland	Farm Zero C	A world first for agriculture, Carbery and its collaborators led by BiOrbic have undertaken an interdisciplinary programme of work targeting soil and grassland; animal diet and breeding; biodiversity; life cycle analysis and renewable energy as a direct response to the challenge area. This presents a holistic view of the farm to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and increase the health and resilience of the farm. Farm Zero C is attempting to achieve a new sustainable business model for farming.	Our Farmer Suppliers - Carbery	Agriculture	SMB
LL	Ireland	Signpost Farm Programme	The Signpost programme will be a multi-annual campaign to prompt climate action by all Irish farmers, and achieve early progress in reducing gaseous emissions from Irish agriculture (while also improving water quality, maintaining and in some cases improving) biodiversity and creating more profitable and sustainable farming enterprises. To lead and support the transition of Irish farming towards more sustainable farming systems; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To reduce agricultural emissions, specifically, • To reduce GHG emissions to the range 17.5 – 19.0 MtCO₂ eq. by 2030; and • To reduce ammonia emissions by 5% below 2005 levels, currently estimated at 5 kT NH₃, also by 2030; • To reduce other negative environmental impacts of agriculture (specifically, to improve water quality and to improve biodiversity)two elements to the programme. Central to the programme will be a network of Signpost Farms, which will act as demonstration farms for the programme and sites for carbon sequestration measurements. These will point the way forward towards climate smart farming, and will be central to the second element, the Signpost Advisory 	https://www.teagasc.ie/publications/2020/the-signpost-programme.php	Agriculture	SMS, Del 2.2

SMS Soil Mission Support

LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
			campaign, which will engage with all farmers and support them to move towards more sustainable farming systems.			
LL	Ireland	Urban Farm	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dublin based organisation, encourages creation, education and experience in urban farming, • STEM school outreach, public urban gardens in the city, various projects dealing mostly with sustainable food production and nutrient management 	www.urbanfarm.ie	urban	SMS, Del 2.2
LL	Ireland	All Ireland Permaculture	Permaculture Ireland is a group of like-minded individuals working together to support one another, offer events, courses and promote permaculture across the island of Ireland. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Network of 11 garden and enclosed field sites where permaculture concepts and practices are used and demonstrated. 	https://permaculture.ie/	urban	SMS, Del 2.2
LL	Ireland	Agricultural Catchments Programme	A combined research & KT programme evaluating the impact of Agriculture on water quality, gaseous emissions and carbon sequestration across six small river catchments. The six catchments cover a range of soil types and farming enterprises. The support of the 300 farmers in these catchments allow monitoring of soils, weather, farming practice, ground and surface water. Farm economic performance and social factors influencing behavior is also key to the programme.	www.acpmet.ie https://www.teagasc.ie/environment/water-quality/agricultural-catchments/	Agriculture	SMS, Del 2.2
LL	Ireland	Connecting Nature	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 30 partners within 16 European countries • develop an urban planning process that will ‘burst open’ silos, enrich and nurture social, business and governance innovations and focus on the scaling-up of nature-based solutions in cities; • develop a new master planning process that accelerates the scaling of nature-based solutions in cities by connecting policy and market needs and turning barriers into opportunities for innovations; • develop a guiding process for identifying funding and financial mechanisms that establish nature-based solutions as evidenced valid solutions for sustainable and resilient cities that are climate prepared; and to valorise knowledge and market mechanisms of nature-based solutions’ scaling for stimulating the market for new innovation; • showcase, and share learning from, the scaling-up, replication and integration of nature-based solutions for city-making within front-runner cities; • Implement resourced masterplans in the fast-follower cities, that is collaborative, employing sharing of good practice, working examples and quantifiable evidence, interdisciplinary work and stakeholder engagement; • engage the fast-follower cities in capacity-building and experiential learning building on effective knowledge sharing and mentoring between front-runner cities and fast-follower cities and the use of proven curatorial planning 	https://connectingnature.eu/what-connecting-nature	forestry	SMS, Del 2.2

SMS Soil Mission Support

LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
			<p>processes;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • secure adequate funding to realise fast-follower city accelerator masterplans for scale up of nature-based solutions in the fast-follower cities; • develop sustainable support for innovation, exploitation and enterprise development building on selected and promising new nature-based solution exemplars from the front runner cities and other solutions co-created to better suit the specific environmental, organisational and funding scenarios of the fast follower cities; • experiences and knowledge gained will be fed back into the reference framework for nature-based solutions. 			
LL/LH	Ireland	RBAPS in Ireland - County Leitrim & Shannon Callows	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 31 farmers participating in the project in Ireland: 13 in County Leitrim and 18 in the Shannon Callows • these participants have entered almost 120 hectares of farmed habitats across 106 land parcels • in County Leitrim our participants have two measures available, Species-rich Grassland and Marsh Fritillary butterfly Habitat; on the Shannon Callows the options available to Farmers are Species-rich Flood Meadow and Wet Grassland suitable for Breeding Waders • for all RBAPS measures for each management unit (land parcel/field) entered under an RBAPS measure is assessed and given marks out of 10 based on the ecological quality of the habitat; payments are based on the annual scores 	https://rbaps.eu/pilot-areas/rbaps-measures-in-ireland/	Agriculture	SMB
LL/LH	Ireland	A Sustainable Agricultural Plan for the MacGillycuddy Reeks - Conservation and restoration of Upland Habitat in the MacGillycuddy Reeks - Ireland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • project aims to improve the economic viability of farming in the MacGillycuddy Reeks through the development of practical, achievable actions and innovative solutions to address the issues facing farmers on the Reeks <p>The following objectives will be pursued:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • develop, in collaboration with landowners, innovative management interventions for the preservation, restoration and enhancement of upland habitats in a farmed, HNV landscape. • provide a mechanism to create a positive outreach programme and to prevent further habitat damage due to increasing recreational pressures on the Reeks through the formation of a landowner ranger system, and trail maintenance and definition works 	https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/fin-d-connect/projects/sustainable-agricultural-plan-macgillycuddy-reeks	Agriculture	SMB
LL/LH	Ireland	The agricultural catchments programme	The Agricultural Catchments Programme (ACP), with a remit to evaluate the Nitrates Action Programme (NAP) under the EU Nitrates Directive (ND), commenced in 2008. It has amassed a unique environmental, agronomic and socio-economic data set unrivalled around the world. The same experiment has been run over the course of the programme in six catchments covering a range of landscape/soil/farming combinations. Thus the combination of data sets -	https://www.teagasc.ie/environment/water-quality/agricultural-catchments/	Agriculture	SMB

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LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
			soils, groundwater, surface water, weather, ecology, farm practice, farmer attitudes, topography and economic returns – over 10 successive years, 300 farmers located in six widely divergent but agriculturally productive sites renders the programme archives invaluable in the context of meeting the sustainable food production challenges. The programme has focused on producing high resolution temporal and spatial dataset on water quality, aquatic biology and more recently on greenhouse gas emissions. The programme continues to expand to investigate sustainable farming practices across a wide range of farmers and catchment types.			
LL/LH	Ireland	The long term carbon flux site at Johnstown Castle	A long term eddy covariance CO2 and H2O flux site has been established on an intensively managed grazed grassland dairy farm since 2002. The site has been evaluating the effect of a range of farm management practices on soil carbon sequestration for almost 20 years. Eddy covariance N2O was added to the site in 2017. Currently the site is being upgraded to meet ICOS class 2 standards and will be officially Ireland only class 2 agricultural site in ICOS.	https://www.teagasc.ie/environment/climate-change--air-quality/soil-carbon/gary.lanigan@teagasc.ie	Agriculture	SMB
LL/LH	Ireland	multi-species grazed grasslands for sustainable dairy production	A dairy systems trial is running in Johnstown Castle to investigate sustainable dairy production using multispecies swards to reduce chemical nitrogen use, improve biodiversity, carbon sequestration, water quality. To increase the climate resilience of the grazed fodder in particular to drought and to weed infestation. This long term light house farm also incorporates diverse hedgerows and wild flower margins.	https://www.teagasc.ie/publications/2020/grassland-re-seeding-how-to-establish-multi-species-swards.php	not specified	SMB
LL/LH	Ireland	climate neutral and biodiverse beef production	A new farming system is being established to investigate the benefits of agroforestry for the production of beef and a range of other environmental goods and services. Mature and new rows of forestry rows will be established and the areas of multispecies swards planted between the trees rows will be grazed by beef cattle. The farming system will maximise carbon capture, biodiversity, soil quality while improving water quality and producing high quality beef.	contact: karl.richards@teagasc.ie ian.short@teagasc.ie	Agriculture; forestry	SMB
LL/LH	Ireland	The Devenish Lands at Dowth	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To optimise essential nutrients and their flow from soils, into plants, into animals, into humans, while enhancing the environment, to deliver a One Health Solution, from Soil to Society • To produce carbon neutral beef and lamb by 2025 by driving GHG mitigation, improving efficiency, accelerating carbon sequestration and communicating our journey through the production of a Net Annual farm Carbon Balance Sheet • To rejuvenate physical, chemical and biological properties of a spent mineral soil, under grassland being grazed by ruminants and reporting progress through repeat measuring and recording of key management decisions. • To ascertain the effectiveness and economics of using multispecies swards to 	https://www.lighthousefarmnetwork.com/lighthouse-farms/lands-at-dowth	Agriculture	SMB

SMS Soil Mission Support

LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
			<p>improve soil, sward, animal and human health, simultaneously</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To explore how silvopasture, coppicing and pollarding of hedgerows and woodlands can accelerate carbon sequestration while maintaining biodiversity • To ground truth the accuracy of using digital survey technologies, such as LiDAR to measure change in the amount of above ground carbon ; and in the highlighting of routes of overland flow of excessive rainfall which carries soil and nutrients into our water courses • To ascertain the trade off point between managing our woodlands for Ireland's top mammal, wild red deer, and accelerating our journey to sequester more carbon from our woodlands and hedges • To demonstrate that a World Heritage Site can become a working, living landscape, while maintaining and enhancing our extraordinary heritage, for the benefit of the breadth of society • To facilitate, engage and demonstrate to the breadth of society that ruminant farming can produce more nutritious food, reduce its environmental footprint, while enhancing an UNESCO World Heritage Site, simultaneously 			
LL/LH	Ireland	The sign post farms programme	The Signpost programme is a multi-annual campaign to lead climate action by all Irish farmers, and achieve early progress in reducing gaseous emissions from Irish agriculture (while also improving water quality, halting biodiversity loss and creating more profitable and sustainable farming enterprises. It will also act as a test bed for on-farm carbon sequestration measurements. It is a collaborative programme, led by Teagasc and including all relevant agriculture industry partners and state agencies. There are two elements to the programme. A network of up to 100 demonstration farms (the "Signpost Farms") are central to the programme, and these will point the way forward towards climate smart farming, and will be central to the second element, the Signpost Advisory campaign, which will engage with all farmers and support them to move towards more sustainable farming systems.	https://www.teagasc.ie/publications/2020/the-signpost-programme.php	Agriculture	SMB, SMS
LL	Ireland	Irish National Agricultural Soil Carbon Observatory	The carbon observatory consists of a network of eddy covariance stations will be established across a range of sites to establish land-use and soil type specific soil carbon sequestration emission factors. The sites will measure and enable the reporting of Tier 2 carbon sequestration emissions factors and inclusion in the national inventory. The observatory will investigate soil type and land-use effects on carbon sequestration and provide farmers with the ability to monetise carbon farming. The 'National Agricultural Soil Carbon Observatory' contribute to EU research on carbon sequestration and enable Ireland to: Better quantify and model carbon emissions from soil and sinks from agricultural land.	http://agriculture.infoagro.com/news/2020/ireland-creates-the-national-agricultural-soil-carbon-observatory/	Agriculture; urban	SMS, Del 2.2

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LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
			Allow mitigation measures to increase carbon sequestration to be included in the national inventory. Participate in the EU ICOS (Integrated Carbon Observation System) network.			
LH	Italy	Agrilombicoltura a Terra Viva	Alessandro Gandolfi, Giulia Caramaschi, Davide Gemelli and Maurizio Vincenzi from Pegognaga (Mantova) are four young dairy cow farmers who have applied the principle of the circular economy in agriculture, in the name of sustainability. They started from the problem of nitrate excess and turned it into an entrepreneurial opportunity thanks to vermicomposting that enhances livestock residues in a totally natural way. They have in fact created an earthworm farm and through the action of these animals they are able to transform, in a totally natural way, the manure produced by their cows into organic, ecological and 100% natural humus, suitable for organic and biodynamic agriculture. In addition, manure from farms is partly sold to biogas plants for energy production. About fifty other farms in the area are also involved in this project, united in a local cooperative.	http://www.agrilombicolturaaterraviva.it/	Agriculture	SMB
LL	Italy	Municipality of Ferrandina – Università della Basilicata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improvement of soil fertility (soil structure; water holding capacity; mineral element availability along soil profile) and reduction of mineral fertilization input; • Reduction of soil erosion processes; • Improvement of plant productivity and commercially valuable fruit parameters; • Improvement of farmer’s income and consequent social and environmental advantages (reduction of migration, control activity on the territory by the olive farmers, landscape conservation, etc.). 	http://portale.unibas.it/site/home.html	Agriculture	SMB
LL	Italy	Metapontino area - Università della Basilicata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction of annual irrigation volume • Definition of specific Kc to be adopted • Improvement of water use efficiency • Involvement of farmers in the use of new technologies for monitoring soil moisture • Reduction of environmental impact (nitrate and salinization) • Improved knowledge of irrigation issues by technician of farmers’ associations 	http://portale.unibas.it/site/home.html	Agriculture	SMB
LL	Italy	Forcatella	Aquasoils is a SME who produces, stores and distributes water for irrigation by tertiary treating the effluent of Fasano, a 50.000 PE town in South-Eastern Italy. When the local demand is low, water is infiltrated into the ground (Soil Aquifer Treatment) to contrast seawater intrusion and salinization of the local groundwater. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduce/eliminate the effluent discharge on shore • Exploit a water resource having better quality than the conventional 		Agriculture	SMB

SMS Soil Mission Support

LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
			<p>groundwater (e.g. salinity, nutrients)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluate the effects of different water qualities on land and crops (conventional vs reclaimed, or blends of the two) • Groundwater recharge and contrast to seawater intrusion • Promote more sustainable crops production 			
LL	Italy	Santa Chiara Lab - university of Siena	<p>Santa Chiara Lab at the University of Siena is already working as a living laboratory .</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This Lab is a place for dialogue and hybridization of knowledge, a facilitator of relationships between university and business, and a space for sharing knowledge and innovative solutions aimed at supporting the transition to a sustainable society and to solve issues linked to rural territory <p>https://santachiaralab.unisi.it/scope/agroalimentare, https://www.barillacfn.com/it/pubblicazioni/fixing-the-business-of-food/, https://agrifoodnext.it/</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Projects of research and technology transfer are promoted by the Lab, https://sienafoodlab.it/it/, as well as activities of training and education and programmes of outreach and engagement, https://www.sdsn-mediterranean.unisi.it/mooc-sustainable-food-systems-a-mediterranean-perspective-2/ • At the same time, the Santa Chiara Lab is collecting good practices in the agrifood sector that are implemented by several farmers and land managers, https://primaobservatory.unisi.it/it/homepage <p>These farms are similar to LH, as they are places for demonstrations of innovative and sustainable solutions provided in the field.</p>	https://santachiaralab.unisi.it/	Agriculture; urban	SMB
LL	Italy	AgriLink - Rebuilding a local food community starting from sustainable farming and collective actions - Italy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the aim of this living lab is that of catalysing the creation of services and tools able to provide support to a demographically and professionally diverse group of farmers and other stakeholders in the consolidation of a wheat value chain that is rooted in the cooperative management of common land • create a food supply chain based on wheat production and processing, and as a consequence try to help mitigating farming abandonment, as well as preserving rural landscapes, reducing soil depletion and pollution and, at the same time, producing local and sustainable food • the majority of farmers involved are small to medium farm holders, most of which are part time or hobby farmers • local municipalities and citizens are also involved in the management of the land 	https://www.agrilink2020.eu/living-labs/rebuilding-a-local-food-community-starting-from-sustainable-farming-and-collective-actions-2/	Agriculture	SMB

SMS Soil Mission Support

LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
LL	Italy	AGRI-FORESTER Guidelines for sustainable management, enhancement of ecosystem services and carbon sequestration in the Emilia-Romagna forest system - Bologna	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • estimate the storage of organic carbon in forest soil • monitor the basic parameters and the apparent density of the soil • carry out specific analyzes aimed at improving the quantitative and qualitative knowledge of the organic substance • emphasize the role of organic matter in the soil • evaluate the organic soil quality index • monitor and enhance the ecosystem services of the partner companies forests • identify the silvicultural practices that lead to the favoring of carbon sequestration in the soils by creating specific "Guidelines for sustainable management, the enhancement of ecosystem services and carbon sequestration in the Emilia-Romagna forest system" 	https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/fin d-connect/projects/agri-forester-linee-guida-la-gestione-sostenibile	forestry	SMS, Del 2.2
LL/LH	Italy	Optimization of conservation agricultural systems through better management of cultivation techniques - Italy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • main objective of the project was the protection of natural resources that support the production of food, especially soil conservation • the path chosen to achieve this objective involved the application of conservation crop systems through the introduction of agronomic techniques and practices (no-tillage (NT) and cover crops), which favored the accumulation of soil organic matter (SOM) in the soil and the increase of soil fertility (chemical, physical and biological) • plowing and conventional management (CT - conventional tillage) represented the control 	https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/fin d-connect/projects/ottimizzazione-dei-sistemi-agricoli-conservativi	Agriculture	SMB
LL/LH	Italy	Renewal crops valorization in Tuscany to tackle up the future climatic changes (VARITOSCAN-Clima) - Italy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • aim of the project is the implementation of a Pilot Project for the identification of varieties / populations of maize and millet adapted to Tuscan pedoclimatic environments and the development of a low-input agronomic management model that reduces the necessary water supply to these crops and conserve soil fertility • the product obtained will also be characterized by high nutraceutical-organoleptic qualities and characterized by a strong territorial link, a combination that will allow the insertion of specific niches in the national and international agri-food sector 	https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/fin d-connect/projects/valorizzazione-delle-colture-da-rinnovo-ambienti	Agriculture	SMB
LL/LH	Italy	Maize & Vegetables using Hemp as trap crop. Reduction of cropping inputs also with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • chemical input control in low impact agriculture is strictly connected to water and environmental health • MACARENA aims at reducing the use of agrochemicals via crop rotation with ancient varieties and the use of hemp as corn borer trap crop both on maize and pepper <p>The three year project is structured as it follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordination and cooperation; 	https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/fin d-connect/projects/maize-canapa-frumenti-e-ortive-la-riduzione-degli	Agriculture	SMB

SMS Soil Mission Support

LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
		Triticum spp. - Bologna	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning to insert hemp and ancient grains; • Indicators selection and set up of monitoring procedures; • Plan execution in the field; • Prototype development; • Dissemination; • Training of the participants on the cropping stage as well as on the cultivation, harvesting and stocking of hemp 			
LL/LH	Italy	Biodiversity and Sustainable Precision Agriculture in Sannio - Italy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preservation of cereal biodiversity through sustainable precision production processes • Production of semolina and flour with important nutritional and nutraceutical properties • Genetic characterization of cultivars and development of the traceability model • Introduction of precision cereal farming models and diffusion of innovative techniques (vertical seeding on semisode) • Introduction of precision agriculture and soil fertility conservation techniques with cover crops through innovative mechanization • Monitoring of production performance and health conditions (Phytopathies) • Introduction of the most suitable raw material storage and milling techniques to reduce mycotic contamination • Molecular evaluation of kernels, flours and semolina 	https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/financial-connect/projects/biodiversit%C3%A0-e-agricoltura-sostenibile-di	Agriculture	SMB
LL/LH	Italy	AGRI-FORESTER Guidelines for sustainable management, enhancement of ecosystem services and carbon sequestration in the Emilia-Romagna forest system - Bologna	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • estimate the storage of organic carbon in forest soil • monitor the basic parameters and the apparent density of the soil • carry out specific analyzes aimed at improving the quantitative and qualitative knowledge of the organic substance • emphasize the role of organic matter in the soil • evaluate the organic soil quality index • monitor and enhance the ecosystem services of the partner companies forests • identify the silvicultural practices that lead to the favoring of carbon sequestration in the soils by creating specific "Guidelines for sustainable management, the enhancement of ecosystem services and carbon sequestration in the Emilia-Romagna forest system" 	https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/financial-connect/projects/agri-forester-linee-guida-la-gestione-sostenibile	forestry	SMB
LL	Italy, Latvia, Spain, Romania, Norway,	AgriLink	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AgriLink established six Living Laboratories in which scientists, advisors and farmers work together to develop new advisory techniques in response to particular industry issues 	https://www.agrilink2020.eu/our-work/living-labs/	Agriculture	SMB

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LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
	The Netherlands and Belgium		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> the approach is focused on the processes of knowledge exchange, through facilitating communication between all the involved actors 			
LH	Latvia	AS Ziedi JP - Latvia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> comprises of 4000 ha of land where 1000 dairy cows are being kept to produce biogas biogas installation, which runs on slurry, generates 45 MW per day; the digestate is used as fertilizer the surplus heat generated by the engine is used to warm up water, that is transported to the adjacent fish culture, producing eel and sturgeon caviar example of circular economy operates in the following segments: crop production, animal feedstuff production, dairy farming and beef cattle farming and sales, biogas operations from biomass, fish farming, services provision 	https://www.lighthousefarmnetwork.com/lighthouse-farms/as-ziedi-jp	Agriculture	SMB
LL/LH	Latvia	Family owned join-stock company "AS Ziedi JP"	<p>Sustainable circular bioeconomy case. Production cycle</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> grain/rapeseed and feedstuff production from agricultural land feedstuff for > 2000 cattle manure and feed residues go to biogas station (2 MW per year) biogas station produces electricity for sale and heat; heat from biogas station go to fish production (Sturgeon, eel and caviar); biogas station produces digestate; digestate goes to the field and replace synthetic fertilizers 		Agriculture	SMB
LH	Lithuania	Valentinas Genys Organic Farm	<p>Farmland (organic) about 900 ha. Main crops: winter rye, spelta wheat, oat, caraway, flax, timothy grass, peas, etc.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Solutions to reduce erosion and land degradation Sustainable soil tillage No-tillage technology Increased diversity / rotation of crops Strategies of organic fertilization Use of cover crops Local varieties Legume management 		Agriculture	SMB
LH	Lithuania	AUGA group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Delivering organic food with no cost to nature Building a new operational model, called Sustainable Organic Food Architecture (or SOFA) Closed-loop sustainable farming model (manure in the cycle, in its secondary role, utilised both for fertilisation, and as a source for the production of biofuel) Biogas infrastructure Specialised feed technology to reduce methane emissions from ruminants 	http://augaorganics.com/global/en/about-us/	Agriculture	SMB

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LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regenerative crop-rotation with a share of cereals substituted with leguminous grasses that have carbon sequestration and nitrogen fixation capabilities • Reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions 			
LH	Lithuania	Martinėlių ūkis	<p>Martinėliai farm grows cereals and Highland cattle. The main goal is to grow and present the highest quality products.</p> <p>The farm grows spelta wheat, oats, peas and buckwheat. The products have an ecological certificate from EkoAgros and a DEMETER International certificate that meets international biological-dynamic standards.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biodynamic farming • Composting • Biodynamics preparations • Closed-loop sustainable farming 	https://www.martinel-iuukis.lt/	Agriculture	SMB
LL	Luxembourg	Institute of Organic Agriculture Luxembourg (IBLA)	<p>IBLA itself does not have farmland, but we perform the variety trials, exact field trials and on-farm field trial on farmers farmland</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organic Agriculture • Alternatives to inorganic fertilisers • Alternatives to the use of control chemicals • Increased diversity / rotation of crops • Reduce imports of soybean by cultivating regional grain legumes • Sustainability assessment • Variety testing • Improvement of soil fertility 	https://ibla.lu/en/ibla/	Agriculture	SMB
LL	Luxembourg, Belgium, France, Germany	Greater Luxembourg forest	<p>Our living lab is anchored in the Greater Luxembourg forest, covering 2,375,000 ha across four countries (Luxembourg, Belgium, France and Germany). A large portion (over 40%) of this forest is privately owned and poorly maintained, thus returning to a wild state with positive (biodiversity) and negative impacts (spread of illness, fire risk). Biodiversity is also affected by monocultures of non-endemic species like spruce which dominate parts of the forest. To tackle these challenges, the living lab has explored all the dimensions of sustainability, i.e., environmental, social and economic, with various stakeholders and through two complementary projects</p>	https://ercim-news.ercim.eu/en121/special/a-living-lab-approach-for-sustainable-forest-management	forestry	SMS
LH	Netherlands	Agrilink - Looking differently at sustainable maize cultivation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • strip cropping farming • private organic agriculture company • strives to invest in a healthy, fertile Flevoland soil and to realize a large yield of tasty organic products • largest private organic farm in the Netherlands • cultivated surface constitutes about 1800 ha 	https://www.erfbv.nl/nl	Agriculture	SMB

SMS Soil Mission Support

LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
		together - Netherlands & Belgium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • is growing around 20 organic arable and vegetable crops • to combine landscape biodiversity and sustainable production, the company has started experimenting with various kinds of mixed cropping systems and crop diversity in time and space • large production scale allows for the introduction of modern techniques in the cultivation as well as in the processing of the products • production sites are mainly located at city borders -> citizens can witness food production without being burdened by the use of synthetic pesticides • company plays a leading role in the development of sustainable food production • experiments with various kinds of innovative mechanization and production techniques 			
LL	Netherlands	AMS Urban Living labs: Marine terrein Amsterdam	The Amsterdam Institute for Advanced Metropolitan Solutions is a collaboration between the municipality of Amsterdam, several universities and business organisations. The living labs are located in Amsterdam at different transformational locations (Currently: Marineterrein Amsterdam, Buiksloterham) and cover topics: smart mobility, energy transition, climate resilience, metropolitan food system, digitization, circularity	https://www.ams-institute.org/how-we-work/living-labs/	urban	SMS
LL	Netherlands	AMS Urban Living labs: Buiksloterham	The Amsterdam Institute for Advanced Metropolitan Solutions is a collaboration between the municipality of Amsterdam, several universities and business organisations. The living labs are located in Amsterdam at different transformational locations (Currently: Marineterrein Amsterdam, Buiksloterham) and cover topics: smart mobility, energy transition, climate resilience, metropolitan food system, digitization, circularity	https://www.ams-institute.org/how-we-work/living-labs/	urban	SMS
LL	Netherlands	Urban Living Lab Breda	This urban living lab was initiated by educational organisations in the city of Breda. In it, they collaborate with the municipality, province and involve citizens along the following program lines, of which the first pro-gram line concerns land and soil use 1) livable city; incl energy transition and (robotized) urban agriculture (food supply, biodiversity) 2) City as community; social cohesion and digitalizing 3) New economy new urban LL in the region are currently set up in Tilburg and Den Bosch. There is an exchange program with the Finnish Lahmi LAB	https://www.urbanlivinglabbreda.nl/	urban	SMS

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LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
LL	Netherlands	Living Lab Schouwen Duiveland	<p>In this LL, policymakers, science, and practice search for solutions to societal challenges in the field of water, food, education and institutions/policy. The aim of the Living Lab is to work on innovative solutions in practice and to test them, on the way to a circular economy in Schouwen-Duiveland. Innovative solutions found at Schouwen-Duiveland can also offer prospects for other coastal areas, governments and educational institutions.</p> <p>Ambitions Searching for increasing freshwater availability and innovations for a sustainable water supply, finding answers to dehydration and salinization of agricultural soils through alternative fresh, saline and saline crops on land; Developing ecologically responsible seaweed and food production outside the dykes in the Oosterschelde and Grevelingen that also offers added value for flood risk management and recreation; Developing and testing new methods for connecting government (including incentives for faster and supported decision-making by governments); Developing Schouwen-Duiveland as an innovative island for a resilient and adaptive delta.</p> <p>Research Themes fresh, saline, saline crops and freshwater supplies for agriculture on land; food production outside the dikes (including seaweed and algae cultivation) in the water; binding governance, administrative innovation and connection; educational innovation, mutual connections and practice-oriented education.</p>	https://livinglabschouwen-duiveland.nl/over-living-lab	Agriculture; other (water)	SMS
LL	Netherlands	CASTOR (CAatchment Strategies TOwards Resilience)	<p>CASTOR is all about the sandy-soil landscapes of the east and south Netherlands. These have a wide range of agricultural, recreational and natural functions and are at risk with climate change. Using a living lab approach, the CASTOR project identifies climate-robust landscapes for the future, and together with government and societal partners they design pathways towards these.</p> <p>The CASTOR project focuses on how future stable landscape configurations can contribute to resilient societies and on the pathways towards these futures. With this, the CASTOR project addresses some of the grand challenges societies will face regarding future landscaping, ecology and the food-water-energy-land nexus. These challenges require interdisciplinary expertise of different scientists and engineers, and cooperation with practitioners.</p>	https://www.4tu.nl/resilience/news-and-events/news/green-light-castor-project/	Agriculture; urba; protected areas	SMS
LL	Netherlands	Zegveld	<p>Knowledge transfer center on peat / soil subsidence, KTC Zegveld is the perfect location to research, test and share innovations for stakeholders such as entrepreneurs, businesses, policymakers and administrators. Valuable data sets are being built up and continued on the experimental farm in areas such as underwater drainage, measurements on soil subsidence, water quality and</p>	https://www.ktczegveld.nl/	Agriculture	SMS, Del 2.2

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LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
			phosphate balanced fertilization. Some of these experiments have been running for more than 10 years and thus provide a unique dataset. In addition to the ongoing experiments at its own location, KTC also offers its expertise and facilities for the construction and maintenance of test fields in the region focusing on themes such as soil, water, crop production and nature management.			
LL	Netherlands	Green Circle Cheese and Soil Subsidence (Groene Cirkel Kaas en Bodemdaling)	As a result of subsidence, the characteristic peat meadow landscape of Alblasserwaard has come under pressure. The same goes for the economic position of the farming community in the area, and for biodiversity. Species-rich grasslands, meadow birds and biodiverse ditches have become scarce. Six parties have joined hands for a climate-proof and biodiverse future of this archetypal Dutch landscape, in which farmers find new ways to earn a living.	https://www.greencircles.nl/cheese-and-subsidence https://www.wur.nl/en/article/Green-Circle-deals-with-subsidence-in-Alblasserwaard.htm	Agriculture	SMS, Del 2.2
LL	Netherlands	Living Labs Climate adaptation Dordrecht & Overijssel (Zwolle, Kampen, Zwartewaterland, Enschede, Hengelo en Almelo)	The living labs in dordrecht and in 6 cities in the province Overijssel (Zwolle, Kampen, Zwartewaterland, Enschede, Hengelo en Almelo) were funded in 2016-2017 by the Dutch Delta programme. In the LL urban climate adaptation was the central point, the LL were elaborated with science, policy, citizens. unknown how large the role of soil health was in this LL, although the natural system played a role.	https://klimaatadaptatienederland.nl/overheden/sra/living-labs/dordrecht/ https://klimaatadaptatienederland.nl/overheden/sra/living-labs/overijssel/	urban	SMS, Neef et al., 2017
LL	Netherlands	Living Lab strong city on weak soils (stevige stad op slappe bodem) Gouda	living lab in Gouda in which a coalition of governments, business, knowledge institutions and citizens develop, test and deploy together in a real-life pilot area measures against subsidence	https://www.bewustlevenmetwater.nl/klimaatverandering-rijnland/praktijk-voorbeelden/living-lab/	urban	SMS, Neef et al., 2017
LL	Netherlands	Living Lab INNOA58	amongst others the vitality and multifunctionality of roadsides (ecosystem services, water retention and purification, biodiversity etc)	https://innova58.nl/innovatie/living+lab/default.aspx	Infrastructure	SMS, Neef et al., 2017
LL/LH	Netherlands	EIP-AGRI-project Soil, Biodiversity &	• testing, scientific underpinning and further development of promising nature-inclusive measures aimed at the application of mixed crops, the incorporation of legumes into the rotation plan and the use of more organic manure on the farm	https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/fin-d-	Agriculture	SMB

SMS Soil Mission Support

LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
		Region Nature inclusievewanting and being able to; substantiate pioneering measures - Netherlands	and investigating the effects of these in the Oldambt practice <ul style="list-style-type: none"> investigate the effects of the measures on biodiversity, prudential feasibility and adaptability in business operations and / or new CAP 	connect/projects/bodem-biodiversiteit-regio-natuurinclusief-willen		
LL/LH	Netherlands	EIP-AGRI-project Integrated sustainability of seed potato cultivation in Groningen - Netherlands	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> aim of the project is to make the seed potato cultivation on the Hogeland in Groningen more sustainable in this project, cultivation measures are being investigated in a new collaboration between seed potato growers however, these measures are no longer seen separately; measures to increase biodiversity are now combined with measures to improve soil quality in this way the group wants to work on greening and developing soil management more sustainable with measures in the field of (soil) biodiversity, organic matter management, building plan, crop rotation and agricultural nature management to further develop this innovation and to adapt it to regional needs, a plan of action is developed and promising measures are tested, monitored and evaluated in practice 	https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/fin d-connect/projects/integrale-verduurzaming-van-de-pootaardappelteelt-1	Agriculture	SMB
LL/LH	Netherlands	EIP-AGRI-project Soil, Biodiversity and Region - Netherlands	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> objective is to test, scientifically support and develop in the daily practice of the Oldambt promoting nature inclusive measures aimed at the application of mixed crops, fitting legumes into the crop rotation and using more organic fertilizer on biodiversity, economic feasibility and adaptability in business operations and / or new CAP 	https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/fin d-connect/projects/bodem-biodiversiteit-regio	Agriculture	SMB
LL/LH	Netherlands	EIP-AGRI-project Reduce surface compaction - Netherlands	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> contract workers and farmers are aware of the measures to prevent soil compaction and are able to bring this to the attention of their customers this proactive attitude contributes to an awareness process that is reflected in a service in which care for soil quality is an integral part in this project, contractors and their customers (mainly dairy farmers) together enter a knowledge and development process that is aimed at preventing and eliminating soil compaction 	https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/fin d-connect/projects/verminderen-ondergrond-verdichting	Agriculture	SMB
LL/LH	Netherlands	EIP-AGRI-project Towards profitable soy cultivation in	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> in this project the cultivation of soy in the Veenkoloniën is brought to a level that the crop has a fixed value in the rotation and that in a substantial size this serves a market that supports its profitability in addition, a leguminous crop is introduced in the rotation that captures 	https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/fin d-connect/projects/naa	Agriculture	SMB

LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
		the Veenkoloniën - Netherlands	<p>atmospheric nitrogen and thus makes a sustainable crop rotation in the Veenkoloniën possible</p> <p>Activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Breeding and cultivation research: each variety is most suitable for the Veenkoloniën in order to meet the requirements as best as possible; precocity, protein and moisture percentage, quality, yield per hectare etc. • Market and chain research: it is important to increase and diversify market access. In order to get the business case positive, the focus will first be on human sales channels (soy drinks, meat substitutes etc.). Then we look at sales channels for animal feed. • Knowledge gathering and knowledge sharing: During the entire project (international) knowledge is gathered and shared with other growers. To make steps, it is necessary to bring knowledge from other countries inside. 	r- een-rendabele-sojateelt-de-veenkoloni%C3%ABn		
LL	Netherlands /Belgium	Agrilink's Dutch Belgian Living Lab - Looking differently at sustainable maize cultivation together - Netherlands & Belgium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the aim of the Dutch Belgian living Lab is to contribute to more sustainable maize cultivation, creating awareness among farmers with respect to nitrate leaching and the individual influence of each farmer and enabling farmers to improve their maize cultivation • working together with farmers, advisors and contractors to develop and test advisory support has provided more detailed insights in the dynamics around agricultural advisory system on sustainable maize cultivation • main stakeholders in the Living Lab are farmers, advisors and contractors involved in maize cultivation in the south east of the Netherlands 	https://www.agrilink2020.eu/living-labs/support-sustainable-maize-cultivation-looking-differently-at-maize-cultivation-together/	Agriculture	SMB, SMS
LL	Norway	Agrilink - Crop rotation between farms: Developing innovation support services and tools - Norway	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the objective of the Norway Living Lab is to support development of an advisory service supporting cooperation between farmers in order to build a shared diverse rotational system in production, including different species of grain, ley (i.e. grass), potatoes and/or vegetables - and thereby improve the agronomical practice • a diverse crop rotation is expected to improve soil fertility, plant health and yields, reduce the need of fertilizers and pesticides, and consequently improve the economic benefit for the farmer compared to a crop rotation with e.g. barley only • the fact that neighbor farms, each producing grain, grass or vegetables only, are narrowly located, more diverse crop rotations may potentially be achieved by co-operation between the farms • the grass producing farmer may, by such co-operation, grow his/her grass on the neighbor field for a certain period, whereas the neighbor grows potatoes or barley on the grass farmers' fields during the same period 	https://www.agrilink2020.eu/living-labs/crop-rotation-between-farms-developing-innovation-support-services-and-tools/	Agriculture	SMB, SMS

SMS Soil Mission Support

LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> through this measure, the Crop Rotation project and the Lab aims at improving agronomic knowledge and practice, leading to increased produce per hectare, reduced costs, and hopefully more climate-friendly grain farming 			
LL	Poland	Institute for Ecology of Industrial Areas Experimental Fields Poland, Upper Silesia Region, Bytom City	<p>Agricultural land contaminated with heavy metals due to the smelting activity in the past, different energy and industrial crop cultivation experimental field</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Energy crop cultivation at heavy metal contaminated soil Industrial crop cultivation at heavy metal contaminated soil Biomass quality valorisation Resilience of energy crops to abiotic stress (contamination, drought, etc) Biomass tested for different use (i.e. renewable energy production) 	https://ietu.pl/en/	Agriculture	SMB
LL	Portugal	Charneca Landscape Observatory, an agroforestry mediterranean Living Lab	<p>The Charneca Landscape Observatory(CLO) is centred in an estate in the lower Tagus region of Portugal, high nature value agro-forestry production system, including annual crops and sheep. Good agriculture practices are applied as organic farming and forest certification FSC, building on ecosystem services. It uses a bottom-up approach involving landscape researchers, practitioners and the local community</p>	www.opc-paisagem.pt , https://opc-paisagem.pt/en/	Agriculture; forestry	SMS, Del 2.2
LL	Portugal	Vineyard living lab for longer-term experimentation	<p>7ha vineyard</p> <p>Evaluate the performance and the variability the biodiversity under the changing climate conditions to ascertain the best cultivars that can better adapted for these changing conditions.</p> <p>Vineyard can be also used to test and demonstrate novel techniques and machinery in a partnership with the private sector.</p>		Agriculture	SMS, Del 2.2
LL	Portugal	Terra Alta	<p>Permaculture site involved in public education including: composting techniques, vermiculture, boosting soil health, managing nutrient cycling, agroforestry, local economy food production, earthworks and earth building, encouraging connectoin to soil</p>		forestry	SMS, Del 2.2
LL/LH	Portugal	Increasing the viability of sown biodiverse pastures through optimization of phosphate fertilization - Portugal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demonstration of the applicability of precision agriculture technologies in the optimization of phosphorus fertilization, with implications on the profitability of sown biodiverse pastures and their multiple environmental benefits 	https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/fin-d-connect/projects/viabiliza%C3%A7%C3%A3o-de-pastagens-semeadas-biodiversas	Agriculture	SMB

SMS Soil Mission Support

LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
LL/LH	Portugal	Conservation Agriculture - Portugal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> conservation agriculture system used on the farm soil as the main engine of the "industry" combined crop and beef production no-till, crop rotation (wheat x forrage x wheat x Lupinus), manure (from beef production include rice husk and wheat straw from beds) and permanent prairies 	https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/content/conservation-agriculture	Agriculture	SMB
LL/LH	Portugal	Interaction between manure and mineral fertilizer applications in conservation agriculture - Portugal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> aim of this project is to study the interaction between manure and mineral fertilizer applications under a conservation agriculture system in a crop rotation of wheat x forragge (ray grass x clover) x wheat x Lupinus luteus testing different levels of mineral fertilizer applications in different levels of manure applications 	https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/fin-d-connect/projects/interaction-between-manure-and-mineral-fertilizer	Agriculture	SMB
LL/LH	Romania	Results-Based Payments for Biodiversity: A New Pilot Agri-Environment Scheme for the Tarnava Mare and Pogány Havas Regions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a "results-based" agri-environment scheme which is targeted at High Nature Value hay meadows, rewarding practical management that produces good quality hay and protects wild species project aims: to test the suitability and practicality of results-based agri-environment schemes to maintain the broad range of species and habitats in two Bio-geographical regions (the Târnava Mare and Pogány Havas Regions) in Romania's extensive High Nature Value farmed landscapes objectives: use HNV areas in Transylvania, Romania, as pilot sites: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> to test design, development and use of result-based remuneration schemes; to conserve and enhance biodiversity; to increase the understanding of factors that contribute to the success or failure of such schemes; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> to identify opportunities and conditions for increasing the use of such schemes in Romania and in the EU more widely, especially in future Rural Development programmes of the CAP; to demonstrate the potential of these schemes to achieve ecological targets, using monitoring of indicators in pilot measure participant and control grasslands; to increase the understanding of the benefits of results-based remuneration schemes within the rural community; to promote results-based remuneration schemes within the MECC and MARD, based on results achieved 	https://fundatia-adept.org/projects/rbaps-results-based-payments-for-biodiversity/	Agriculture; forestry	SMB

SMS Soil Mission Support

LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
LL	Serbia	PA4ALL / BioSense - Serbia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BioSense Institute is a public research and development institution which cross-fertilizes two most promising sectors in Serbia but also globally: ICT and agriculture • Research and innovation at BioSense is developed in a close interaction with farmers and the agrifood sector, government bodies, entrepreneurs and business community, international researchers, and citizens • create a new generation of open innovations which will be readily used and which will bring benefits across the entire value-chain • as a meeting place for all relevant stakeholders, we have established PA4ALL – the Living lab for precision agriculture • this is the first living laboratory in Serbia and the first one in Europe to focus on precision agriculture • PA4ALL takes full advantage of inter-sectoral cross-fertilization of ideas and offers possibilities to test ideas and prototypes in the real-world setting. • multidisciplinary research is performed in the fields of micro and nano-electronics, communications, signal processing, remote sensing, big data and artificial intelligence, robotics and biosystems, with a common goal to support the development of sustainable agriculture • challenge: to discover new ways of supporting and increasing the use of it in the agricultural field • challenge was based on the fact that the institute operates in the field of precision agriculture and strives to implement these new technologies in the agriculture sector of Serbia 	https://siscodeproject.eu/pa4al/ https://biosens.rs/?page_id=7697&lang=en	Agriculture	SMB
LL	Serbia	PA4ALL	<p>precision agriculture</p> <p>BioSense Institute is a public research and development institution which cross-fertilizes two most promising sectors in Serbia but also globally: ICT and agriculture. Multidisciplinary research is performed in the fields of micro and nano-electronics, communications, signal processing, remote sensing, big data and artificial intelligence, robotics and biosystems, with a common goal to support the development of sustainable agriculture. The Institute founded and hosts one of the first European Living Lab focused on Precision Agriculture – PA4ALL, an open innovation ecosystem that promotes the development of user-driven precision agriculture.</p>	https://siscodeproject.eu/pa4al/	Agriculture	SMS, McPhee, 2021
LH	Spain	La Junquera - Spain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • organic farm and village that is being transformed into a beacon of regenerative agriculture according to the four returns principles of Commonland in Southern Spain • the farm is based in Caravaca de la Cruz, Murcia, Spain which is on the border of the desert and as such faces many challenges related to soil erosion, water 	https://lajunquera.com/	Agriculture	SMB

SMS Soil Mission Support

LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
			<p>shortages, irregular rain events, unemployment, graying, and lack of possibilities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • La Junquera focuses on building silt traps, swales, composting, limited tilling, and the restoration of natural areas • these practices not only help to reduce erosion, improve fertility and increase water infiltration but also help to increase biodiversity • the Regeneration Academy helps to make this transformation to regenerative agriculture 			
LL	Spain	Prionfreesoils	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Focus on two animal prion diseases with zoonotic potential: Scrapie in sheeps and goats, prevalent for centuries in Europe, and Chronic Wasting Disease (CWD) in cervids, recently introduced in our continent. · Seeks to explore the potential role of both the soil and gut microbiota in the transmission of those prion diseases. · Aims to create synthetic devices that enable bacterial microbiota as a robust and economic biosensor of harmful amyloids that are persistent contaminants of soils and other natural environments (as plants and waters). · Will also generate devices built-in bacteria for the clearance of amyloids from contaminated environmental resources. 	http://www.cnb.csic.es/index.php/en/investigacion/departamentos-de-investigacion/biologia-microbiana/amiloides-bacterianos-sinteticos	Agriculture	SMS
LL	Spain	Las Dehesillas Nut farm. Almond and Pistachio	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Agriculture farms devoted to the nut tree crops (Almond and Pistachio). It is an irrigated farm with water uptaken from underground - Saving water and improving water use efficiency - Increasing soil fertility and improving soil organic matter - Solutions to reduce erosion and land degradation 	(Not available)	Agriculture	SMS
LL	Spain	Fundación Lucio Gil de Fagoaga. Finca el Cerrito	<p>Agriculture farms devoted to grape for wine making production. the farm is in part irrigated and vines trained with vertical shoot positioning and some other part is rainfed and vines trained with open-vase system.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Saving water and improving water use efficiency - Increasing soil fertility and improving soil organic matter - Improve grape composition and wine quality 	(Not available)	Agriculture	SMS
LL	Spain	AgriLink	INTIA's LL wants to improve the current advisory service by bringing innovation closer to farmers and involving advisors and farmers in the design of this service.	https://www.agrilink2020.eu/why-agrilink/	Agriculture; forestry	SMS
LL	Spain	LIVERUR	Living Lab Vega del Segura: Rural Living Lab in cultivation activities with short supply of water and technological penetration	https://liverur.eu/project/	Agriculture; forestry	SMS
LL	Spain	DESIRA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In Andalucía, the Living Lab will deal with how to reduce the risk of forest fires, with the involvement of public administrations, local civil protection agency and fires fighters. - In Aragon, the Living Lab will address how technology can help enhance the 	(Not available)	Agriculture; forestry	SMS

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LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
			attractiveness of the territory, boosting local economy and finding solution to already identified challenges, while preserving the natural resources and environment of the rural areas of Maestrazgo and Gúdar-Javalambre.F13			
LL	Spain	ROBUST	Experimental collaboration that emphasizes co-creation in a real-world setting. Policy-makers, researchers, businesses, service providers, citizens and other stakeholders work together to develop and test new ways to solve problems in a specific geographic region. Includes 11 Living Labs that represent typical rural-urban settings throughout Europe. Click on the images below to explore what is happening in each ROBUST Living Lab	https://rural-urban.eu/living-lab/valencia	Agriculture; forestry; urban	SMS
LL	Spain	VALENCIA LIVING LAB	The University of Valencia and the Valencian Federation of Municipalities and Provinces (FVMP) will collaborate with other regional and local stakeholders in this Living Lab to analyse some of the region's exceptional experiences to illustrate the importance of implementing rural-urban territorial processes, particularly as they pertain to business and labour markets, public infrastructure, and sustainable food systems. They will also explore how shifting from a sectoral-based, short-term view to a territory-based, comprehensive long-term view could help the region better manage challenges in the future.	(Not available)	Agriculture; forestry; urban	SMS
LL	Spain	GANADERÍA EXTENSIVA.- Operational Group to achieve extensive precision livestock adapted to climate change.	The main objective of the project is the modernization of the extensive livestock sector in the Peninsular Southwest through the application of validated technologies in precision agriculture and livestock. This is to achieve more efficient and sustainable management of farms and to value their enormous contribution to the sustainability of the rural and natural environment.	https://innogestiones/	Agriculture; forestry	SMS
LL	Spain	FUTURE FARMING LAB.- Operational Group for Precision Agriculture in Cereals and Almonds	Promote the implementation of "precision agriculture" through "living lab" methodology, among cereal and almond farmers, as a solution to increase its use on a large scale.	https://www.usj.es/ https://campag.es/el-cluster-de-maquinaria-agricola-impulsa-la-creacion-del-future-farming-lab-para-la-agricultura-de-precision/	Agriculture; forestry	SMS

SMS Soil Mission Support

LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
LL	Spain	LABIOLIV.- Living Lab for sustainable olive oil production through intelligent control of olive grove cultivation and the application of bio-treatments	Monitoring and biological control of olive crops through the application of a technological solution for the olive farming sector that will improve farm management and increase their competitiveness. This system will allow to achieve better conditions for cultivation, avoiding the spread of pests and favouring resource efficiency, thus achieving a greater profitability of the olive grove. It is about reducing the use of pollutants and using greener ones instead, as well as improving the specificity of olive treatments, which will reduce the risk of cross-reaction and soil microbiota imbalance. These actions promote more efficient and ecological agriculture.	(Not available)	Agriculture; forestry	SMS
LL	Spain	GESVAC4.0.- Operational Group Management 4.0 of the Beef Sector: Collaborative platform of advanced management for improving the profitability of livestock farms through their Digital Transformation.	Development of an advanced management platform, through the implementation of the Living Labs methodology, to improve the profitability of livestock farms through their digital transformation. The project focuses on horizontal aspects including animal feed, farm management, non-ecological differentiated quality, increased value added and digitization and big data. In this regard, the innovative project will develop an information capture and management system based on digitization and Big Data that will generate a business intelligence system, in order to improve the economic and environmental efficiency and social sustainability of meat farms	http://gesvac.org/	Agriculture	SMS, EIP AGRI OG
LL	Spain	ISAB.- Operational Group incorporating information for the improvement of animal health and welfare in	The focus of the project will be the dairy cattle population in Spain. The activities focus on the development of an additional information collection, digitization and processing system that has been routinely collected within the dairy performance control and morphological qualification for integration into the breed improvement programme, including the collection of animal health and welfare characteristics, as well as the genotyping of animals with new data to enable the selection in the future of disease-resistant animals, generating a LIVING LAB around animal health and welfare data from dairy cattle farms. The	https://www.conafe.com/	Agriculture	SMS, EIP AGRI OG

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		the Spanish dairy cattle sector	project is therefore part of the livestock thematic area and the type of product for ministry purposes is dairy cattle within the animal production sector.			
LL	Spain	RESINLAB.- Operational Group Network of territories of participatory experimentation to create innovation appropriate to the real needs of the resin sector	The project is proposed as a network of experimentation territories where the different actors in the resin value chain can co-create innovations to ensure user-centric innovation and a clear sociocultural return, environmental and economic investment based on bioeconomy and maintenance of ecosystem services (forest and rural development). The focal area priority is to restore, preserve and improve ecosystems related to agriculture and selviculture.	http://www.cesefor.com/tags/grupos-operativos	not specified	SMS, EIP AGRI OG
LL	Spain	TRAZAMIELLAB.- Operating Group Technologies of authenticity and traceability of honeys to improve the protection and sustainability of the entire value chain	It is proposed as an adequate space to integrate the processes of participation within the honey value cycle from the producer to the consumer, through packaging and marketing, as well as by the Government Administration and control laboratories. It is meant as a methodology for the development and validation of authenticity and traceability technologies, considered to improve protection, safety, competitive and sustainability of the entire honey value chain.	https://www.uvigo.gal/	Agriculture; forestry	SMS, EIP AGRI OG
LL	Spain	Living Lab Rurales.- Operational Group for the promotion of circular agro-forestry systems and the improvement of ecosystems in the counties of	It focuses on the most characteristic agricultural products of the counties in which its main actions will be carried out. In this sense, we can find as main crops almond, irrigated and dry olive trees, walnut, other fruit trees in less proportion, aromatic plants and cereals. Likewise, many of these farms obtain forest by-products such as firewood or scarcely wood, leaving forest management more delegated to the conservation of biodiversity that improve the presence of kinetic activity or complement the ecosystem benefits so necessary for the different ecological functions. In this way, the main theme area is rural development and the promotion of social innovation.	https://ruralbridge.es/	Agriculture; forestry	SMS, EIP AGRI OG

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LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
		the Iberian Mountains of Southeast				
LL	Spain	Rural Bridge.- Operational Group for the development and interconnection of three Living Labs for the co-development of innovative solutions to promote the digital transition of the rural environment	To accelerate the development of innovative solutions in rural areas. Main goal is to achieve a real impact in economic and social terms, ensuring this output through the inclusion of all relevant actors from the beginning in the innovation process. Therefore, the definition itself fits into the objective of promoting practical, faster application and implementing innovative solutions, which is achieved through shortening the distance between the research scientific offer and the needs of the agricultural sector and the other actors involved, in order to finally achieve an agricultural sector that is economically viable, productive and competitive. Focus crops are olive, almond, pistachio, fruit, garlic and onion.	http://www.akisinternational.com/	Agriculture; forestry; urban	SMS, EIP AGRI OG
LL	Spain	INNPROLABS.- Operational Group for the promotion of innovation among the stakeholders in the agri-food meat processing industry through Living Labs.	The overall activity is to drive innovation along the value chains of the agri-food sector. The focus is on the agri-food industry and mainly on meat processing. Consequently, the thematic areas it will address are mainly the meat industry.	http://tecnara.es/org/anigrama/	Agriculture	SMS, EIP AGRI OG
LL	Spain	ECOREGION .- Operational Group to promote agro-ecological food, intelligent management systems and	The main objective of this project is the creation of a Living Lab, a supra-Regional Economic Community of Organic Foods that, through the training of promoters of the Sustainable Economy and the development and implementation of new technologies of digital transformation and industry 4.0, will promote the creation of an innovative agroecological value chain, involving production , distribution, marketing and services.	https://ecoregio.cat/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/Candidatura-MicroEcoRegio%CC%81-2021_ES.pdf https://www.agroeco	Agriculture; forestry; urban	SMS, EIP AGRI OG

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		their logistics, technologies applied to the Sustainable Economy and Social Innovation, training and university field. (see also this Project in the "ESP Agroecology" class)		logia.net/ecoregiones /		
LL	Spain	MECAZAFRAN .- Operational Group for the integral mechanization of saffron production.	The project is aimed at the integral mechanization of saffron production, which in turn will promote the expansion of this crop. Main objective is to obtain prototypes of machinery and equipment for different tasks, ranging from planting to saffron processing. The goal is to facilitate the viability of the sector, as well as to improve current production techniques through such mechanization as well as the transfer of knowledge related to agricultural best practices and more sustainable in this crop.	http://www.ofiset.es/	Agriculture	SMS, EIP AGRIOG
LL	Spain	GESVIÑA.- Operational Group on open innovation ecosystems and validation of sustainable strategies in the management of the Atlantic vineyard.	The project falls within the scope of plant production-woody crops-vineyard. Specifically, the objective is the grape for winemaking, through sustainable production in the environment of Atlantic viticulture. All this in line with the growing demands of consumers of wines produced with more environmentally friendly techniques, and aimed at meeting the objectives of the European strategy "Farm to Fork".	https://www.feuga.es/en/casosexitonac/ge/svina/	Agriculture; forestry	SMS, EIP AGRIOG
LL	Spain	HIGOS.- Operational Group for the design of innovative strategies in the	The project consists of the implementation of a Living Lab model through open community involving all users of the dry fig production and processing chain to determine, in real environments, the maturity and degree of acceptance in the application of different innovative and sustainable techniques that ensure the hygienic-health quality of this product , especially in terms of insect-related contaminations and toxic moulds.	https://gohigos.adismonta.com/	Agriculture; forestry	SMS, EIP AGRIOG

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LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
		production of dry figs with the highest hygienic-sanitary quality in Spain.				
LL	Spain	BIOLIVING.- Operational Group for the development of sustainable and circular processes for obtaining biofertilisers and aquaculture feed from agri-food waste.	The project is based on the use of waste and waste from the food industries of processing marine products and aquaculture effluents for direct use or through extraction/production of intermediate products (yeasts, insects, microalgae, water lentil), for the manufacture of biostimulant-capacity biofertilisers and for use as ingredients for the formulation of aquaculture feed. That is, a high added value orientation today.	http://www.anfaco.es/es/index.php	Agriculture	SMS, EIP AGRI OG
LL	Spain	GOPINO.- Operational Group Network of innovative forestry laboratories for the integrated management of forest pathologies in commercial coniferous forests.	The Project, whose product is the living forest plant of coniferous species for repopulation, aims to contribute to the improvement of conifer forest plantations through the practical application of advances in genetic material innovation. With the introduction of this improvement, wood production will be more sustainable in the face of pests and diseases and will face climate change.	https://asociacionforestal.gal/#	not specified	SMS, EIP AGRI OG
LL	Spain	TRIGOLABINNO VA.- Organic production of cereals of traditional varieties for the	Strengthening dry organic farming through the efficient use of water by wheat varieties adapted to dry conditions and with greater capacity to use water resources, due to the increased development of its root system. The use of these varieties contributes to making the agricultural sector dedicated to cereals more resilient to climate change (CC), thanks to its agronomic and physiological characteristics, as well as strengthening the benefits of organic agriculture by being adapted to conditions closer to these production systems,	https://www.ecovalia.org/index.php	Agriculture	SMS, EIP AGRI OG

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		agri-food industry	thus contributing to the conservation and restoration of the natural resources of agricultural systems.			
LL	Spain	AUREUS.- Implementation of a Digital Advisory System (DATS) tool and system that allows veterinarians to apply more efficient and sustainable treatments against Staphylococcus aureus	It responds to the need of rabbit-breeding farmers and veterinarians to monitor the presence of pathologies caused by Staphylococcus aureus. The focus is on more effective treatments at the first moment that a possible outbreak is detected. These sanitary incidences are the main cause of elimination of breeding females and very often responsible for the fall in global production.	http://e-imasde.eu/language/en/home-6/	Agriculture	SMS, EIP AGRI OG
LL	Spain	LIVLAB-IN.- Validation of the methodology in real environment of the use of plant by-products through insect culture for the increase in productivity and sustainability of agro-industrial farms.	Residues and waste from the food industries, from its generation in the primary sector to those generated in agro-industrial activities, will be used, highly valued in its main use: animal-prepared foods (proteins, amino acids, fats and components of high food added value for livestock, aquaculture and pets).	https://eurecat.org/en/	Agriculture	SMS, EIP AGRI OG
LL	Spain	TUBERLAB.- Living lab for increasing the resilience of the	Strengthen the value chain of the Spanish truffle sector through a strategy of meeting the different actors in an open space, meeting and joint generation such as a trufa living-lab. The aim is to lay the groundwork for increasing the resilience of a sector that is already a European leader in terms of production, but not in the generation of added value of the product	https://www.cesefor.com/	Agriculture; forestry	SMS, EIP AGRI OG

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LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
		truffle sector in Spain				
LL	Spain	TICsANI.- Incorporation of TICs in extensive livestock: development/digitization of the Iberian Black-Avileña breeding center	The objectives set out are: (i) - Improve the sustainability of production models by improving the use of food, health and animal welfare; (ii) Establish a protocol to monitor stress and assess its impact on productive and reproductive aspects of immunity; (iii) Search, validate and define new indicators of animal welfare adapted to the extensive exploitation system of the Iberian Black-Avileña breed.	https://es.figroup.com/	Agriculture	SMS, EIP AGRI OG
LL	Spain	ANTI- INVASORAS.- Living Lab for fighting invasive species in irrigation waters	The overall objective is the development of technological tools appropriate to the needs regarding the problem of invasive species within irrigator communities. Specifically, the project attacks a large-scale problem at national and European level: the proliferation of invasive species (the best known being zebra mussels) in inland waters and their detrimental effects on irrigation systems. This creation of solutions will involve the different stakeholders offering scenarios where technological prototypes are developed and tested using the LIVING LABS methodology, to meet those needs.	https://pamagroup.es /	Agriculture	SMS, EIP AGRI OG
LL	Spain	BEETEAM.- Development of a BIG DATA technology for the control of the Asian hornet in Spain	Improve existing management, control and eradication techniques against invasive alien species, as one of the main causes of biodiversity loss in the world. In this case, the project focuses on the control of <i>Vespa velutina</i> , mainly because of its negative impact on beekeeping and the socio-economic consequences that this entails. Efforts will focus on minimizing damage, mainly associated with the large number of nests that can coexist in the same area. If population control is achieved and the number of nests and/or their size is reduced, the damage caused will also be greatly reduced.	https://itagraformacion.com/	Agriculture	SMS, EIP AGRI OG
LL	Spain	Agroecosystem History Lab UPO	Agro-Ecosystems History Laboratory brings together researchers from different universities and academic disciplines. Its main objective is to promote an improved understanding of the function of agro-ecosystems in a historical perspective. This history is discussed as a form of applied knowledge that enables us to describe the ecology of traditional farming systems and thus the possibility to build more sustainable agriculture for the future.	https://www.lha.es/en	Agriculture; forestry	SMS, 1st screening of EU agro-ecology LL and RI
LL	Spain	COPLACA Avocado C Islands	Sustainable production of avocado and mango fruits with a minimal amount of pesticides	https://coplaca.es	not specified	SMS, 1st screening of EU agro-

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LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
						ecology LL and RI
LL	Spain	COPLACA Banana C Islands	Sustainable production of banana fruits with a minimal amount of pesticides	https://coplaca.es	not specified	SMS, 1st screening of EU agro-ecology LL and RI
LL	Spain	ECOPIONET	It aims to promote organic production among farmers, providing them with the necessary tools for their conversion to organic and promoting their channeled associationism through a producer organisation. They deal with extensive arable crops in the provinces of Salamanca, Toledo and Guadalajara	https://pionerosecologicos.net/ecopionet-english/	Agriculture	SMS, 1st screening of EU agro-ecology LL and RI
LL	Spain	ECOREGIONS	Transition to reach local sustainable, ecological food systems in the region of Mallorca, Malaga and Valencia	www.agroecologia.net	Agriculture; forestry; urban	SMS, 1st screening of EU agro-ecology LL and RI
LL	Spain	PROMOTION OF AGROECOLOGY AND TRANSITION TO ORGANIC PRODUCTION	Methods for pest control under organic management and pest early detection, organic fertilization, soil health, rotation schemes, mulching and variety selection. Dedication to major food crops diseases as soil and seed diseases on cereals, downy mildew on grapes and potato and grey mould on grape and horticultural crops.	https://www.euskadi.eus/gobierno-vasco/plan_programa_proyecto/plan-de-fomento-de-la-produccionecologica-fope/	Agriculture	SMS, 1st screening of EU agro-ecology LL and RI
LL	Spain	OPERATIONAL GROUPS OF COOPERATION TO PROVIDE A LOCAL OFFER OF QUALITY LEGUME-FORAGES FOR LIVESTOCK FARMERS (IMINE) AND CONTINUOUS	Agricultural farms: Promotion of legumes and crop rotation approaches, as well as the utilization of compost instead of non-organic fertilizers. In addition, we also try to promote reduced tillage techniques. Livestock farms: Benefits of grazing planning and the implementation of rotational grazing, not only to enhance feed self-sufficiency, but also to improve soil health, to fix huge amounts of carbon in the soil and to foster other ecosystem services associated to the soil (biodiversity, water retention capacity, etc.). We also advise on the existence of local alternatives to the utilization of soya and palm oil in animal feeding, such as the utilization of rapeseed or sunflower cakes and oil for livestock feeding. The development of short food supply chains (direct selling, farmer's markets, etc.) is also presented to farmers.	https://neiker.eus/es/proyecto/imine/	Agriculture	SMS, 1st screening of EU agro-ecology LL and RI

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LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
		SUPPLY OF ORGANIC BEEF MEAT FOR THE BASQUE MARKET (HAREKO).				
LL	Spain	INCREASING FERTILITY AND SOIL QUALITY BY USING BENEFICIAL MICROORGANISMS	Application of fungal species and mycorrhizal inoculation in vivo to increase soil fertility and biodiversity. The general purpose is to ameliorate the quality of crops in the Canary Islands.	WWW.icia.es	Agriculture; forestry	SMS, 1st screening of EU agro-ecology LL and RI
LL	Spain	AGROLAB PROJECT - OPEN AGRICULTURE LABORATORIES, PROMOTED BY THE MADRID REGION GOVERNMENT	This hands-on project relies on living labs that efficaciously create, evaluate and test various innovative agricultural practices, from products, services and business ideas, to market expansion and new technologies. Mainly focused on agricultural activities in orchards, including fruit trees, berries and cereal cultivation. The ultimate goal is to assist, empower and educate local inhabitants, encouraging them to develop commercially resilient agro-ecological production.	https://agrolabmadrid.com/ https://12fwd.com/news/2145-agrolab-madrid	Agriculture; forestry; urban	SMS, 1st screening of EU agro-ecology LL and RI
LL	Spain	LIVING LAB LA VEGA DE GRANADA	Agroecology / Enhance organic agriculture and farming in the Granada Region, Andalusia	https://www.otragranada.org/IMG/pdf/Plan_Estrategicode_Agricultura_Ecologica_de_LA_Vega_Granada.pdf	Agriculture; forestry; urban	SMS, 1st screening of EU agro-ecology LL and RI
LL	Spain	MAKING OLIVE AND OTHER WOODY CROPS CULTIVATION MORE SUSTAINABLE	Reconciling practices in olive groves that are profitable and sustainable, considering the protection of the environment and avoiding the overexploitation of natural resources. Thus, the general objective of SUSTAINOLIVE is to promote the sustainability of the olive oil sector through the implementation and promotion of innovative and sustainable solution sets in management practices, based on agroecological concepts and in effective and active exchange of knowledge in the main actors of the sector.	https://sustainolive.eu/general-objective/?lang=en	Agriculture; forestry	SMS, 1st screening of EU agro-ecology LL and RI
LL	Spain	LIVING LAB FOR THE AGROECOLOGICAL TRANSITION	Reconnecting rain-fed cropping systems with extensive livestock through introducing traditional food and feeding management, crop and legumes varieties	https://www.lha.es/en/PORTADA/ https://ecovalia.org/	Agriculture; forestry	SMS, 1st screening of EU agro-

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LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
		OF RAIN-FED CROOPING SYSTEMS IN ANDALUSIA REGION				ecology LL and RI
LL	Spain	Agro-Lab (Madrid, Spain)	participatory farming lab as a space to reactivate the agrarian sector in rural and periurban areas of Madrid, ecosystem services	https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/11/4/1181	Agriculture	SMS, McPhee, 2021
LL	Spain	FUNDACION INSTITUTO DE AGRICULTURA ECOLOGICA Y SOSTENIBLE (FIAES)	Various training activities are organized in agroecology, defense of food sovereignty, local resources, sustainable rural development and gender equity. Activities are materialized in three ways: online courses, face-to-face courses and field training.	www.multiversidad.es https://www.ull.es/titulospropios/masterpropio-agroecologia-soberania-alimentaria/	Agriculture; forestry; urban	SMS, 1st screening of EU agroecology LL and RI Soil literacy example
LL	Spain	SEAE, SPANISH SOCIETY FOR ORGANIC FARMING AND AGROECOLOGY, JOINING TOGETHER FOR THE TRANSITION	Joining the efforts of farmers, technicians, scientists, and civil people, to promote the improvement and dissemination of knowledge about the production of quality food based on agroecological and sustainable rural development.	www.agroecologia.net	Agriculture; forestry; urban	SMS, 1st screening of EU agroecology LL and RI Soil literacy example
LL	Spain	LL ON LOCAL AGROECOLOGICAL FOOD SYSTEMS IN THE SUBBETIC REGION	Promoting organic production and consumption, going back to recognise the value of working in the fields, dignifying the profession of agriculture through fair and stable prices, supporting artisanal production and normalizing ecological consumption. A mutual support network helps us to promote local, close and humanized trade in the Andalusian Region (Jaen, Cordoba, Sevilla and Malaga).	https://subbeticaecologica.com/	Agriculture; forestry; urban	SMS, 1st screening of EU agroecology LL and RI Soil literacy example
LL/LH	Spain	4 Returns, restoration of degraded soils. Implementation of soil regeneration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> the project's mission is to halt land degradation caused by almond monoculture and aggressive agricultural use of the land and the environment, which leads to the disappearance of organic matter and the consequent loss of fertility and biodiversity in the soils of the rural areas of Los Vélez, Alto Almanzora, Altiplano Granada and Guadix, in the provinces of Almeria and Granada 	https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/fin-d-connect/projects/4-retornos-restauraci%C3%B3n-de-suelos-degradados	Agriculture	SMB

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LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
		techniques in the territory formed by Los Vélez, Altiplano Granadino, Gu - Spain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> the largest production of organic, rainfed almonds in the world is concentrated in these regions (100,000 hectares of almonds and 45,000 of them are organic) 			
LL/LH	Spain	RBAPS - Mosaic Perennial Crops, Navarra	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> the pilot area is located in the upland part of the Mediterranean High Nature Value Farming area of Navarra for the he pilot, a test area of 6154,62 hectares was selected, forming part of the municipalities of Viana, Aras and Bargota, in the west central Navarra the mosaic of land uses in the area of the municipalities of Aras, Viana and Bargota, creates a landscape of high heterogeneity which is the support of a wide range of flora and fauna species that are related to low intensity farming practices Perennial crops, olive groves, almonds and vineyards, with and without herbaceous cover, herbaceous crops, pastures, scrublands and trees are the main elements of the landscape the area has a very small parcel size and a high boundary density (km/ha), ideal to test Results Based Agri-environment measures for heterogeneous extensive farming systems the overarching goal of the project in Navarra is to maintain this mosaic farmed landscape 	https://rbaps.eu/pilot-areas/navarra-spain/mosaic-farmed-habitats-navarra/	Agriculture; forestry	SMB
LL/LH	Spain	Degrades soils restoration, Alvelal-Aland	We aim to stop soil degradation caused by monoculture and aggressive uses and practices with soil and environment leading to a reduction of organic matter, soil structure, etc. causing the loss of fertility and soil health. The main practices that we carried out are: reduction of labour, promotion of green fertilizers, establishment of plant casings, contributions of organic amendments, pruning crushing, and revaluation of by-products. We work in both public natural areas and in natural areas of agricultural farms. All this is rigorously and technically evaluated. The execution area is home to 1,000. 000 hectares between Andalusia and Murcia. In short, it is a land and landscape regeneration project that promotes in turn, the creation of sustainable business cases.	https://www.alvelal.net/ https://4retornos.es/ https://almendrehesa.es/	Agriculture; forestry	SMS, EIP AGRI OG
LL/LH	Spain and Ireland	RBAPS Project - Spain & Ireland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> developing Results Based Agri-environmental Payment Schemes in Ireland and Spain the RBAPS project was a three and a half year project in Ireland and Spain working with farmers and stakeholders developing ways to reward farmers for delivering biodiversity on their lands key element of results-based method of delivering payments is that the 	https://rbaps.eu/	Agriculture	SMB

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LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
			amount of money paid to the farmer, reflects the quality of wildlife (biodiversity) that is delivered on their farmed land			
LH	Switzerland	Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL): several long-term field experiments	FiBL runs long-term field experiments addressing systems (organic vs. conventional), tillage (reduced vs. plough) and fertilization (manures/digestates vs. mineral) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced use / alternatives to inorganic fertilisers • Reduced use of control chemicals • Re-use of wastes • Reduced soil disturbance during soil preparation • Increased carbon sequestration, reduced climate impact • Maintain biodiversity 	www.fibl.org	Agriculture	SMB
LL	Switzerland	Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL): On-Farm Research	large network of organic and conventional farms in Switzerland for on-farm research on mechanical weed control without herbicides, precision farming/robotics, conservation tillage, variety and fertilizer testing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced use / alternatives to inorganic fertilisers • Reduced use of control chemicals • Mechanical weed control • Reduced tillage • Increased biodiversity / diverse rotations / agroforestry • Re-use of water/wastes 	www.fibl.org	Agriculture	SMB
LL	Switzerland	Progrès Sol	Field cropping systems, conventional and organic agriculture, conservation agriculture, soil protection <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Solutions to reduce soil degradation • Increased diversity / rotation of crops • Solutions to reduce soil compaction • Increase to self-fertility of soil, and farm • Solutions for carbon sequestration • Prevent side-effects of intensive mechanical weeding • Choice of cover crops • Moving from diagnosis to solutions in soil fertility enhancement • Developing farmers' autonomy in soil fertility management 	www.progres-sol.ch	Agriculture	SMB
LL/LH	Switzerland	Bodenfruchtbarkeitsfonds der Bio-Stiftung Schweiz	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • values the commitment of farmers to maintain and develop the fertility of soils in the long term • what they do has charitable value and deserves understanding and financial support from society • through the soil fertility fund, concrete measures that lead to the preservation and development of soil fertility on agricultural land are supported 	https://www.bodenfruchtbarkeit.bio/	Agriculture	SMB

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LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • after all, fertile soils are the basis for healthy nutrition in the present and the future and at the same time counteract global warming by storing more CO2 than conventionally cultivated soils 			
LL/LH	Switzerland	Sounding Soil (Acoustic Ecology Lab, Zurich University of the Arts)	<p>Influence of soil types, human land use and climate change on the soil soundscape.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First-time exploration of soil soundscapes • Investigating acoustic indicators of soil fauna activity and diversity • Comparison of effectivity of acoustic and conventional probing • Automatic acoustic identification of soil animals • Citizen science: Does hearing the soil raise awareness? • Arts : Are media arts capable of initiating a public discourse about soil health and land use? • Arts : How can a soil ecosystem be rendered acoustically experienceable? • Development of an autonomous soil recorder, market-ready 	<p>https://blog.zhdk.ch/marcusmaeder/ https://www.soundin-gsoil.ch/en/</p>	Agriculture; forestry; urban	SMB
LL	Tenerife (Spain)	Guidelines for the production of organic avocado in arid environments	<p>Coplaca is an Organization of Producers of Fruits and Vegetables that, in addition to bananas, have tropical crops. To explore and disseminate the sustainable management guidelines, it is in charge of the direct management of two farms of 9 ha in total in the south of Tenerife, where avocado and mango cultivation is carried out from a vacant land, under the regulations European organic farming.</p>	<p>https://coplaca.es/vidEOS/ https://coplaca.es/2020/06/04/estrategia-farm-to-fork-hacia-2030/ https://youtu.be/ZwnC1H4FRt0</p>	not specified	SMS, Del 2.2
LL	UK	Producing efficient high-quality humified compost - Land Gardeners Controlled-Aerobic-Compost group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • investigating the Controlled-Aerobic-Composting method of producing a compost that is fully nutrient and crumb stabilized, in the form of clay-humus-complexes and long-chain humic acids, as well as other high quality humus substances, within 6 - 8 weeks 	<p>https://innovativefarmers.org/field-lab?id=411b95f5-0833-e611-80c9-005056ad0bd4</p>	Agriculture	SMB
LL	UK	Increasing nutrient efficiency from anaerobic digestate - Agri-Tech East	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • this field lab is investigating how to stabilise N and reduce loss in AD • this includes improving absorption and soil structure using cover crops 	<p>https://innovativefarmers.org/field-lab?id=8fb224cb-df5c-e711-8149-005056ad0bd4</p>	Agriculture	SMB

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LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
		Anaerobic Digestate group				
LL	UK	Management practices to increase deep burrowing earthworm numbers, crop rooting depth and yields - Deeper Rooting Group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> this field lab will study how crop yield, root depths and earthworm numbers are impacted by additions of organic matter in no-till, strip-till and conventional cultivation 	https://innovativefarmers.org/field-lab?id=89a5798b-b76d-ea11-8181-005056ad0bd4	Agriculture	SMB
LL	UK	Less Toil, Better Soil - Scotland Market Gardening Group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> this group will explore the effectiveness of under-sowing kale crops with green manures and intercropping with salads 	https://innovativefarmers.org/field-lab?id=6f9da1d4-482c-e811-816d-005056ad0bd4	Agriculture	SMB
LL	UK	Biochar for soil and livestock health - Biochar Group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Biochar is a potentially useful soil and feed amendment for increasing yield and health of livestock, crops and soil this group of farmers are interested in looking at the effects of small-scale produced biochar on their farming systems 	https://innovativefarmers.org/field-lab?id=0a0868eb-8fe1-e711-816a-005056ad0bd4	Agriculture	SMB
LL	UK	Amendments for soil health in top fruit - GREATsoils Fruit group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> this field lab aims to investigate how the addition of different soil amendments affects soil health in fruit production systems 	https://innovativefarmers.org/field-lab?id=c6bb2819-56d3-e611-80ce-005056ad0bd4	Agriculture	SMB
LL	UK	Intercropping in arable systems - DIVERSify Intercropping Group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> interest in Intercropping has been growing amongst conventional and organic farmers for some time this field lab will look at how farmers can use intercropping to make their arable systems more sustainable and productive the group will explore opportunities for intercropping and companion cropping in arable systems 	https://innovativefarmers.org/field-lab?id=29e46613-5899-e711-8168-005056ad0bd4	Agriculture	SMB
LL	UK	Sward improver: Nitrogen-free soil treatments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> this field lab will investigate the use of two nitrogen-free soil treatments to improve seasonal productivity of grasslands, with the aim of improving livestock gross margins as well as improving the drought resistance of these drought-prone landscapes 	https://innovativefarmers.org/field-lab?id=e897db86-	Agriculture	SMB

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LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
		for grassland productivity - Eastern South Downs Farmer Cluster		35ca-e911-8176-005056ad0bd4		
LL	UK	Cover crop management for improved soil biology - England	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • it is recognised that different cover crop management strategies could have different impacts on soil biology, both positive and negative • the operational group is seeking to compare the impact of different methods of cover crop management on soil biology • the outcome will be the better information on how to best manage cover crops for improving soil biology • this is the first time this approach and solution has been explored in England. 	https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/financial-connect/projects/cover-crop-management-improved-soil-biology	Agriculture	SMB
LL	UK	SUSDRAIN - Derbyshire Street Pocket Park	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • interest in nature based solutions, • use of SuDS (Sustainable Drainage Systems) so all surface water naturally drains away and no surface water would enter the combined sewer system • Create a space that can be used for community and art events • use native and nectar rich plants and plant edible herbs and fruit trees in an attempt to spread the word of “grow your own” • use recycled materials 	https://www.susdrain.org/case-studies/case_studies/derbyshire_street_pocket_park_london.html	urban	SMS, Del 2.2
LL	UK	UK Soils LL	uk-soils is an ambitious new initiative that aims to kickstart a nationwide appreciation and understanding of the economic, societal and ecological importance of soil health to support action and research. We will enable better access to robust, independent information, and provide a space for new proactive communities to share their knowledge and experiences of actions to improve soil health. We are a growing group of scientific, campaigning and awareness raising organisations, all with a specialist knowledge of soil health. Founding members are UK representatives on the EU Mission for Soil Health and Food and its Assembly (the UK Centre for Ecology and Hydrology, Earthwatch Europe, University of Sheffield) and the Sustainable Soils Alliance. The group will continually seek new partners to expand the initiative’s reach and engagement and is delighted to have been joined most recently by Scotland’s Rural College (SRUC). We launched on the 4th December 2020 as our contribution to World Soil Day.	https://uksoils.org/living-labs-lighthouses	Agriculture	SMS, Del 2.2
LL/LH	UK	Biodiversity Management in Shetland - United Kingdom	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • aim of the project is to empower the farming/crofting community to take a leadership role in managing its environmental resources for the benefit of biodiversity and the wider community • focus on trialling farmer participation in the monitoring of the impact of land management practices on breeding waders 	https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/financial-connect/projects/biodiversity-	Agriculture	SMB

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LL/LH	Country	LL name	Short Description (incl aims, activities, participants and context)	Link	Land use	Source / comments
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> the information collected by participants will be used to identify beneficial practices and create best-practice guidance, to support land management for waders at the landscape scale in the long-term the Shetland Agri-Environment Group stakeholders will also work together to develop a Wader Habitat scoresheet, setting a standard for measuring habitat quality on farmland 	management-shetland		
LL	UK (Northern Ireland)	the Sustainable Agriculture Land Management Strategy for N. Ireland Pilots	41,644 ha of predominately grass production in three river catchments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> To secure and record positive change in soil management To improve water quality To empower individual farmers to accelerate positive change by giving them personal data on their own farm’s soil fertility and highlight locations where soil & nutrient runs off during extreme rainfall events To evaluate the use and analysis of precision technologies such as GPS soil sampling and LiDAR Aerial surveys in giving farmers and policy makers robust and transparent baselines from which better and more informed land management decisions can be made To evaluate how best to provide training and communicate this precision data with individual farmers and land managers To provide evidence of positive change to allow a business case to be built for funding to secure a futher roll out of the pilots to other parts of N. Ireland 	https://www.daera-ni.gov.uk/articles/sustainable-agricultural-land-management-strategy	Agriculture	SMB
LL	Europe	different LL&LH, to check relevance for soil		https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/urbanlivinglabs/Projects JPI Urban Europe (jpi-urbaneurope.eu)	urban	SMS, AB, JPI urban Europe multiple LL&LH, To be selected in terms of relevance for soils

ANNEX IV: MAPPING EXERCISE LL & LH

As part of WP4, a selection of Living Labs and Lighthouses are shown on a map. This map, which is still under development, can be accessed at <https://www.soilmissionsupport.eu/outputs/map>. On this website it is possible to distinguish between living labs and lighthouses. In addition, thematic filters such as "Agriculture/Horticulture", "Forestry", "Urban", "Protected Areas", "Industry", "Protected Areas", "Industry", "Infrastructure" and "Other" can be set to display the selection of specific living labs and lighthouses. The results are shown on a map using OpenstreetMap as an open source map. Detailed information can be accessed by clicking on the flags. Likewise, the hits are also displayed as a list.

In a preliminary version there is a form for authorized users to add new Living labs and lighthouses.

It is planned that the map with the Living Labs and Lighthouses will be hosted by SMS on the web server of the project partner "Environment Agency Austria" during the project period (on the SMS website <https://www.soilmissionsupport.eu/outputs/map/>). After the end of the project, the maps will be transferred to the servers of the JRC.

Figure 1 - Screenshot of the interactive LL / LH map as available on the SMS website

ANNEX V: TYPES OF LL

When we start to work with LL, it is important to understand that different types of LL can be distinguished which can have different starting points, in aims, activities, participants, context.

Labeling LL in types can be useful for analysis of LL, to learn from them and improve their effectivity and impact. Underneath we give some different typologies from literature, to show the diversity.

McPhee et al., (2021) give some ways to categorize LL in types in their article.

“1 Sector: The most common way to categorize different types of living labs is by sector, thematic domain, or area of application. For example, ENoLL uses sectors to categorize its membership: Health & Wellbeing, Smart Cities & Regions, Culture & Creativity, Energy, Mobility, Social Inclusion, Social Innovation, Government, Education, and Other. (Within this typology, certain living labs could be described as “agriculture living labs,”” (...)

2. Purpose or function: Efforts to distinguish living labs by their purpose or function have been part of an overall effort to clarify the living lab concept and separate out distinct clusters of “living labs” that all use this common label to represent somewhat different applications (e.g., European vs. American approaches or ICT innovations vs. engineering testbeds.

3. Driving actor: Actors can play varying roles within a living lab, and various coordination, management, and governance structures are possible within living labs. (...)” See above: utilizer-driven, enabler-driven, provider-driven, and user-driven.

“4. Processes and approaches: Researchers have also based typologies on their coordination approach and participation approach. This approach has been combined with a platform of dimension to categorize living labs as different types of collaborative innovation networks There is a related typology proposed based on the innovation processes and tools used in living labs.

McPhee et al., also distinguish “ULLs” and “rural living labs” as “types without a typology”. This makes it even more important to elaborate the characteristics and criteria of these labs as done in section 4.2.

Method 3 (driving actor) was the typology as was used in D3.1 (Maring et al., 2021), to describe the different existing types as shown in the tables underneath:

Table 1: Types of Living Labs

(source: adapted from Schuurman et al., 2013, p.5)

Original ‘American’ Living Labs (Type 1)	Living Labs as extension to testbeds (Type 2)	Living Labs supporting context research and co-creation (Type 3)	Living Labs for collaboration and knowledge support activities (Type 4)
Laboratory made to resemble the real-world, smaller scale, data capturing, can also be in-house research on a small scale focusing on ethnographic methods	Environments within which users and stakeholders can collaborate in the creation and validation of (ICT) services	Environments aimed to support innovation processes focusing on the early development phases of needs analysis and early design	Multi-stakeholder collaboration, focus on collaborative platforms, knowledge sharing and community development
Provider-driven	Provider-driven infrastructure with Utilizer-driven projects	Utilizer-driven	Enabler-driven
<i>Examples are: the testing of climate related soil measures in urban areas to improve drainage capacity.</i>	<i>Examples are: measures aimed at reducing soil subsidence / mineralisation of peatlands to reduce greenhouse gas emission.</i>	<i>Example are: precision farming or test of alternative (no tillage) ways of agricultural production; the reuse of urban soils for urban development.</i>	<i>Examples are; solidarity or community initiatives on urban farming, climate adaptation, no tillage (no-dig)</i>

Type 4, the LL for collaboration and knowledge support activities, matches most to the SHLL according to the description of the Mission for Soil health and food. (And, in addition to that, it is good to add that according to the “new” definition, the SH LL are a combination of different sites on a landscape level). But it is good to be aware that there are many existing LL on soil topics found under the other types. The LL & LH mapping exercise (as described in Annex IV) also contains many examples that could rather be described as (extended) testbeds, than LL.

ANNEX VI: EXAMPLES OF LL

From the LL overall list as collated in SMS, 3 examples with different land uses were elaborated along their characteristics (scale / aim / participants / activities / context, as described in section 4.1), and the LL principles (Continuity, Openness, Realism, Influence (Empowerment), Value, Sustainability as described in section 4.4.1).

- agricultural land - The Horizon 2020 project AgriLink, different European countries,
- forestry - Des hommes et des arbres, France
- urban land - The Living Labs of the Amsterdam Institute for Advanced Metropolitan Solutions (AMS), The Netherlands

The aim was to find relevant differences and points of attention in terms of “success factors”. The conclusions are given in 4.4.1 and the examples are elaborated in this Annex.

An important caveat to the following examples is that this exercise is based on desk research and only the AgriLink example was checked by the involved actors. This means that not all information was available on the all examples to elaborate the LL characteristics and principles. When this is the case, this is mentioned in the text. Additionally, the descriptions in this annex can contain inaccuracies and deviate from the real situation and experience by actors as the available information online was limited.

Furthermore, the LL principles within this analysis are applied in such a way that they link to the context of soil health. Please note that the principle “Spontaneity” and “sustainability” are not elaborated in the examples underneath.

Agriculture: Horizon 2020 project AgriLink

Short description

The EU Horizon2020 project AgriLink³⁹ (Agricultural Knowledge: Linking farmers, advisors and researchers to boost innovation) is a multi-actor project designed to facilitate an active dialogue on innovative farm advisory tools and approaches that surpass classical boundaries between research, policy and practice. To this end, a Living Labs approach was used within a total of six cases located in seven countries (The Netherlands/Belgium, Italy, Norway, Latvia, Spain and Romania). In table 1, these Living Lab locations are described regarding scale, aim, participants, activities and context.

Between the different living labs there are noticeable difference. In terms of the scale / participants: The Living Lab in the Netherlands/Belgium has a stakeholder group of 6 farms, whereas in Romania it is a cooperative of 150 members. Regarding the aim of the Living Labs: these differences are not as large. Within the aim there lies a focus on current and future needs regarding information, advice, knowledge and awareness amongst farmers. Due to the overall aim of the project this is however not surprising. A similar observation can also be made regarding the kind of participants, as these are primarily farmers and advisors.

For activities and context: The LL are situated in place-based locations and focus on co-creation, research and innovation and experimenting. In some LL, this also encompassed demonstration, awareness raising and advice /education (linking more to a LH than a LL concept). The differences are not always evident in the literature review.

³⁹ <https://www.agrilink2020.eu/>

Table 1: Overview of the Living Lab locations in regard to scale, aim, participants, activities and context

Country	Scale	Aim	Participants	Activities	Context
Italy ⁴⁰	Parcel of land around the city of Udine	Catalyzing the creation of services and tools able to provide support to a demographically and professionally diverse group of farmers and other stakeholders in the consolidation of a wheat value chain that is rooted in the cooperative management of common land.	Farmers, citizens, local municipalities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Interviews with stakeholders - Stakeholder meetings - Organized events 	This initiative started five years ago when a group of farmers and citizens started to manage cooperatively a parcel of common land in the surroundings of the city of Udine.
Latvia ⁴¹	Unclear	Improving the engagement of farmers and producers with the resources and facilities of the agricultural advisory system in Latvia.	Fruit farmers, advisors, researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development of an online platform for users - Meetings 	An increasing number of public, private and third sector organisations are involved in providing advice to farmers, and there is little evidence of widespread coordination among them. Few AKIS members perceive the Latvian AKIS as a coherent and unified system. Consequently, there are currently different methods of instruction and knowledge-dissemination in Latvia that allow farmers and horticultural producers to acquire the requisite knowledge to produce processed fruit or vegetable products. Nonetheless, many farmers and entrepreneurs do not have the time or skills to navigate the advisory system, while others do not always have a clear understanding of their professional needs and where they can get help.
Norway ⁴²	Farmer cooperative	To support development of an advisory service supporting cooperation between farmers in order to build a shared diverse rotational system in production, including different species of grain, ley (i.e. grass), potatoes and/or vegetables - and thereby improve the agronomical practice.	Farmers, advisors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development of an advisory service - Dialogs between advisors and farmers 	The LL was part of a larger, existing project which required careful and extended negotiation as to the specific aims and role of the LL.

⁴⁰ <https://www.agrilink2020.eu/living-labs/rebuilding-a-local-food-community-starting-from-sustainable-farming-and-collective-actions-2/>

⁴¹ <https://www.agrilink2020.eu/living-labs/making-it-easier-for-farmers-and-entrepreneurs-to-find-the-right-information-and-advice/>

⁴² <https://www.agrilink2020.eu/living-labs/crop-rotation-between-farms-developing-innovation-support-services-and-tools>

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Country	Scale	Aim	Participants	Activities	Context
Netherlands/ Belgium ⁴³	6 farms as practice demonstration	Contributing to more sustainable maize cultivation, creating awareness among farmers with respect to nitrate leaching and the individual influence of each farmer and enabling farmers to improve their maize cultivation.	Farmers, University of Wageningen, advisors, contractors	- Developing innovation support tools -Interviews with stakeholders - Stakeholder meetings	In the region, agriculture consist of intensive livestock production with some dairy farming in combination with arable farming and horticulture. In this context maize is an important feed crop in dairy farming. Many dairy farmers use contractors to take care of the cultivation of maize. Advisory services on maize cultivation are provided by independent advisors and contractors.
Romania ⁴⁴	Cooperative of vegetable producers of about 150 members	The aim of the Romanian Living Lab is to develop innovative support services and tools that improve access to reliable, timely [financial & marketing] information for small scale Romanian farmers, cooperatives and Local Action Groups in Romania.	Vegetable producers, advisors	- Needs assessment - Meetings - Assisting farmers	In the absence of a functional advisory services system, farmers, mostly small ones (the great majority of them being less than 1 ha), are feeling the urgency to push for changing and adapting to their more specific needs, the legal financial procedures and to get more practical information for marketing activities and better access and position themselves on the market. Due to these rapid developments, the cooperative is struggling to keep up with growing administrative burdens, complexity and changing financial legislation.
Spain ⁴⁵	Unclear	Improving the current advisory service by bringing innovation closer to farmers and involving advisors and farmers in the design of this service.	Farmers, advisors, researchers	- Meetings - Peer to peer mentoring - Workshop	In a context in which farmers are trying to adapt themselves to new laws, changes in consumers' demand and new challenges and needs regarding sustainability, researchers and experimentation experts are trying to develop tools and solutions to help farmers. Experts are the main users of the tools and the knowledge is transferred to the farmer through the advisor. To make a more efficient advisory service, it is necessary to involve all actors in the transference of knowledge: involve experimentation experts who work on the development of solutions and also advisors and farmers who get familiar with the use of these tools and solutions in the field, organise demonstrations in farmers' plots to enhance peer to peer learning and try to promote a collaborative use of the Pest Monitoring and Warning system and other tools to improve the decision making process in the field.

⁴³ <https://www.agrilink2020.eu/living-labs/support-sustainable-maize-cultivation-looking-differently-at-maize-cultivation-together/>

⁴⁴ <https://www.agrilink2020.eu/living-labs/small-farmers-receive-better-fiscal-information-in-a-confusing-informational-landscape/>

⁴⁵ <https://www.agrilink2020.eu/living-labs/rebuilding-a-local-food-community-starting-from-sustainable-farming-and-collective-actions/>

The Living Lab principles

Continuity

For the aspect of continuity, the Living Labs (LL) differ per case. The project in general has a positive point that it makes use of existing networks and actor relationships (between advisors and farmers which without the project also would be cooperating to some degree though perhaps for different means and ends). This makes continuity after the LL and project have finished more realistic and likely. However, at the same time we also see the use of other projects as vehicle to 'hop on' as LL (e.g. in the Dutch/Belgian case) which can lead to competition between the LL and the projects, which might lead to a situation where the LL is not getting enough attention and visibility or independence. This may threaten the continuity of the project after AgriLink finishes, or could, conversely, ensure impetus is maintained if the LL is seen to be valuable. Additionally, information from the Latvian case also shows that the LL has had to constantly refine and narrow down its ambition in order to come up with something that could work and continue to exist after the project has concluded. The Spanish LL also adds that the attitude of end-users towards the LL affects the potential continuity as well. The Norwegian case did report that before COVID-19, the project was running well, but that continuation of the project might potentially be threatened. For the Italian case no further data was available, but since it was based on an existing network, the potential for continuity might be positive. Finally, in Romania, the continuity of the project is good as other networks are planned to be used to further replicate the Living Lab approach in other parts of the country. It is important to note that continuity is not an end in itself. A LL which has completed the work needed, as determined by its stakeholder community, can be dissolved by collective agreement and that this dissolution can be a very strong indication of its success.

Openness

Regarding the openness within the LL environment of the AgriLink-cases, this was a key design principle for all of the LL. It is evident that the cases portray what an ideal or 'good' LL should be in terms of this principle. Within the project there was space for LL participants to be able to give their opinion during meetings and workshops. Additionally, the input from these meetings was also used to co-create services and tools that can then be used by the end-users. However, this openness also has had downsides as the Dutch/Belgian case portrays that individual interests can also threaten the co-creation process (see success factor/barrier "collaboration" from section 4.4.1). A LL needs to be able to recognise and engage with these types of issues which may involve careful and skilled facilitation. Unfortunately, the website source does not provide further information on how this issue was handled. The Romanian case also mentions the importance of the aspect of openness for a good LL. Within the LL experience, the participants had the chance to openly talk about the challenges they faced, ensuring the tools and services that were developed more fitting to the context and needs.

Realism

For a LL environment that aims at developing tools and services for end-users to use in their day-to-day practice, realism is an important principle (see success factor/barrier "outcome" from section 4.4.1). As the services and tools are developed through a process of co-creation, realism is an important aspect in this LL. However, by the website description it seems that the process of co-creation at the same time could affect realism.

An explanation can be that short-term/immediate information needs were seen as more important by participants than soil health, as a more unspecified, long-term objective. Unfortunately, there are no further details available and each LL handled this differently.

Empowerment / Influence

The principle of empowerment/influence is very well incorporated in this LL. This is since the co-creation process utilized in the LL allows for a high degree of influence from the participants. This also ensures that the end-products are more tailored to the needs of the end-users. At the same time, not all influence on the process lies within the control of the LL itself. For example, in the Netherlands, considerable influence regarding the project is located outside the LL in the form of external factors such as legislative changes (success factor/barrier “political context” from section 4.4.1). This can limit the influence of the LL participants. The influence of individuals (versus or outside the group) may also affect the end-products as collaborative aims and individual interests might clash (success factor/barrier “outcome, collaboration” from section 4.4.1). Within this principle, the element of ‘ownership’ that participants felt towards the LL was mentioned (success factor/barrier “collaboration” from section 4.4.1) as a crucial aspect. When participants do not feel connected to the project, co-creation will become more difficult. This in might also lead to reduced realism as defining user needs then becomes more difficult. Additionally, ownership also affects continuity after the LL period within a project has ended. When participants feel insufficiently connected to it, the will to keep the LL alive is also gone as soon as the project itself or the connected finances end.

Value

The value principle within the LL is based on the value that it brings to its users and how it fits to their needs. On this principle, the LL score well. Based on the descriptions provided by the LL, it can be stated that the end-products were well received by the users and that the process on its own was also of value for the users. (success factor/barrier “outcome” from section 4.4.1).

Conclusion

Based on the principles mentioned above, it can be stated that the LL in the AgriLink EU Horizon2020 project can be considered a good example of what a LL should entail. Also, some lessons can be learned from their experience. Regarding the context in which the LL takes place, it does show that in day-to-day practice long-term soil health objectives can be difficult to incorporate explicitly. However, the AgriLink LLs do demonstrate that shorter term activities can be situated within a wider context of farm viability and environmental improvements. A key element is that the focus of the LL should also be perceived as a ‘pressing and complex problem’ which requires further exploration by the LL participants.

Forestry: Des hommes et des arbres

Short description

“Des Hommes et Des Arbres⁴⁶” is a regional project based on an unprecedented alliance of some 100 public and private actors from the South of Lorraine and the Northern Vosges (France). This area encompasses 4 departments, 1.132 municipalities and about 1 million inhabitants. Within the framework of the project, a LL approach was implemented. The results concern co-created practical tools for end users. The aim of the LL approach is that it should complement or support existing French forest policies⁴⁷. The scale of the LL is an alliance of about 100 public and private actors within the region (consisting of a wide range of actors involved in for example training and research, communities, cities, nature parks, private companies, architects and planners). The LL has the shared ambition of transforming the area over a period of 10 years, through innovative actions that develop and enhance the place of trees in the well-being of populations, the preservation of the environment, resilience and prosperity of the area in resonance with societal expectations, future climate changes and a reasoned valuation of local resources. The different actions (28 as of now and increasing in the future) are carried out by a combination of different actors, and can be divided within 5 different focus areas related to forestry:

- Ecosystem Services provided by the forest - Better understand and promote the services provided by trees, in urban area, the forest and in the countryside, to encourage their inclusion in our economic and political choices. Without underestimating the risks associated with them (e.g. Lyme disease);
- The ecosystem - Foster sustainable and resilient tree ecosystems, support their adaptation to climate change, and make good management, operation and renewal practices accessible;
- Industry - Improve the valuation of local wood resources, accelerate innovation in the service of a sustainable, honest, efficient and creative forest-wood sector, and experiment with new techniques for valuing biomass from trees, new uses of wood and plant, substitution and recycling;
- Living environment and well-being - Develop the use of wood and plants in construction, development, pollution control, design, etc. and promote the therapeutic and social benefits of wooded areas.;
- The ‘augmented factory’ - Mobilize citizens and users, to involve them in the implementation of the project and accelerate innovations, as close as possible to societal expectations. Encourage and support co-construction initiatives at all levels, particularly with local industries.

⁴⁶ The information for this Living Lab was obtained from the website <https://www.deshommesetdesarbres.org/>. The information is originally given in French and was translated to English by using the translate page option in google chrome. There is a risk that translation errors did occur.

⁴⁷ Such as “Plans de Développement de Massif” (Massif Development Plan), “Chartes Forestières de Territoires” (Territorial Forest Charters) or “Groupements d’Intérêt Economique et Environnemental Forestier” (Forest Economic and Environmental Interest Grouping).

The Living Lab principles

Continuity

The LL scores well on continuity. The participants of the LL are grouped around common visions (trees are an essential asset in urban land, the forest, the countryside & getting to know, preserve and enhance the value of the services they provide us is a source of well-being, innovation, prosperity and ecological transformation). Additionally, by using existing actors and relationships, there is a strong basis for continuity within the LL. Within the LL, in order to further ensure this continuity, an association was created to ensure collective governance in the long-term as well as the sustainability and deployment of the project. Within this association, stakeholders (organizations or individuals) that share the ambition of the project may choose to become a member to support the project. Additionally, these members may also become active members (shareholders) by contributing to the project in the form of activities. Finally, another aspect that affects the continuity of the LL in a positive sense is the fact that the French national government also finances the LL for several years, making it easier to continue it without depending on a sort-term limited project budget.

Openness

It is unclear what the score is for openness for all actors within the LL environment, as no detailed information was presented in the website. The Living Lab works with an association located at the heart of the LL. In order to gain a voice with the project, actors need to contribute in the form of submitting an activity. Additionally, within the association, there is an executive committee elected from founding and contributing members. The level of participation and potentially some of the principles might differ between the different kinds of members in this tier-system. What we can learn from this case is that the large scale of this project also necessitates an organisation form such as the association (or similar structure) to steer the LL.

Realism

For a LL environment that aims at developing tools and services for end-users to use in their day-to-day practice, realism is an important principle. This is also the case for this LL. When taking the ambition of the Living Lab into account (*“transforming the territory over a period of 10 years, through innovative actions that develop and enhance the place of trees in the well-being of populations, the preservation of the environment, resilience and prosperity of the territory in resonance with societal expectations, future climate changes and a reasoned valuation of local resources”*) it can be said that this ambition is well embedded in practice and realism. Especially this connection to the practice of forestry, its different areas of interest, and the involvement of practitioners makes that the LL scores high on realism.

Empowerment / Influence

As for principle Openness, it is unclear what the score is for Empowerment / Influence for the different kind of members within this LL environment, as no detailed information on this aspect was presented in the website.

Value

The LL scores high on value as the actions are directly connected to practitioners. Therefore, the LL results and outcomes have a lot of value for the participants.

Additional principles mentioned

An additional principle that can be sign of a 'good' LL is the shared ambition between the different participants. When this is present, it creates a shared identity and a 'Rally around the Flag' feeling. To a degree this therefore also relates to the principle of continuity, but it can also be seen as a kind of 'red thread' that runs through the LL and connecting the different actors. In doing so, it also connects to the idea of 'ownership' mentioned in the Agrilink LL.

Conclusions

The Living Lab in general scores good on the different principles. There is a good sense of continuity within the LL due to a reliance on existing actors and relationships. Additionally, also the inclusion of an association to steer the LL in its general directions can be seen as a good addition as well as that the Living Lab has national funding. The activities that are based in practice on performed with practitioners, make the LL to score good on the principles of realism and value. Because there is not enough information available online, it is unclear what the tiered system to participate at this LL means regarding the openness for and the influence of all participants in overall decision-making. Due to the large scale of the LL, it can also be argued that a tiered structure with different levels of engagement can be necessary to keep the LL operational.

Urban: The Amsterdam Institute for Advanced Metropolitan Solutions

Short description

The Amsterdam Institute for Advanced Metropolitan Solutions⁴⁸ is a collaboration between the municipality of Amsterdam, several universities and business organisations. The LL are located in Amsterdam at different transformational locations (Currently: Marineterrein Amsterdam, Buiksloterham) and cover topics: smart mobility, energy transition, climate resilience, metropolitan food system, digitization, circularity

The goal within the urban Living Labs is to make impact by developing new products on a small scale – be it an object, a service, a technology, an application, or a system – and to find solutions that can be implemented on a larger scale. This is done in a real-life and co-creating setting in which different stakeholders give shape to the innovation process. The actors are users, private and public actors, as well as knowledge institutes. In the process, the feedback gathered from use and evaluation of the product is used to accelerate further development. As the product is implemented in a real-life setting and validated by the involved actors, it is more likely to be adopted smoothly and swiftly by all involved actors, and subsequently have a large and rapid impact in the city.

Regarding the scale of the LL, it can be stated that these can be considered small. There is one larger area (Marineterrein Amsterdam) as well as several other small locations within Amsterdam. Additionally, it needs to be stated that soil health is a small and hidden part of the topics covered within the LL. The main overarching topics are urban sustainability and circularity. However, this is something that occurs more often within urban living labs due to the plethora of issues affecting such areas.

⁴⁸ The information for this Living Lab was obtained from the website of the Living Lab (<https://www.ams-institute.org/how-we-work/living-labs/>).

The following topics can be related to soil health: Metropolitan food systems (regarding city-based solutions and locally produced food), climate resilient cities (due to the role that the subsurface plays) and circularity in urban areas (due to the focus on sustainable ecosystems that also include the soil).

Finally, regarding the participants, the LL involve a wide variety of different types of stakeholders (e.g. knowledge institutes, governmental partners, private partners, citizen groups, etc.).

The AMS LL consider the following central aspects:

Figure 1: Overview of the different aspects that play a central role within the Living Labs organized by the Amsterdam Institute for Advanced Metropolitan Solutions (Source: <https://www.ams-institute.org/how-we-work/living-labs/>)

The Living Lab principles

Continuity

It is not completely clear, what the overall continuity is of this LL, this seems to vary between sites, due to the fact that the LL locations are used for a variety of different projects/experiments with different stakeholders. The active involvement of stakeholders seems to be dependent on available budgets for activities. The collaboration that facilitates the Marineterrein LL seems to be stable, based on the online data sources.

Openness

The openness principle is unclear while there is insufficient information on the website about this. In figure 1, above, openness is mentioned implicitly in the aspect that the LL makes use of co-creation (participants are involved in the process) and that decision-power is mentioned as an important factor.

Realism

Also, in this LL realism can be considered to be an important factor, while it develops tools and services for end-users to use in their day-to-day practice. The experiments and projects have as aim to create (scalable) experiments that can be tested in the LL and then applied in urban environments.

Empowerment / Influence

Because of lacking information, not much can be said about empowerment/ influence, as is the case with openness.

Value

On value, the LL scores high as it provides room to experiment with urban solutions that can be further upscaled within the urban context and as there is a direct connection between the value of the LL and practice / practical implications for the experiments.

Conclusions

The AMS LL is difficult to score due to a lack of information on the website. However, it is a good example of a LL covering the complex situation within urban areas. As mentioned earlier, the urban environment is home to a large amount of different challenges. Soil health is implicitly present within the larger umbrella of urban sustainability and circularity. Moving forward in the future on the topic of soil health, attention needs to be given to this position of the topic.

ANNEX VII: WORKSHOP RESULTS

AquaConSoil workshop June 16, 2021

Soil Mission Support

Co-creating the European Roadmap for Land and Soil Related R&I

AquaConSoil 1aSpS2
Wednesday 16 June 2021, 13.30-15.00 h

Partners: Bundesanstalt für Landwirtschaft und Ernährung, zalf, INRAE, Deltares, umweltbundesamt, ATK, eagasc, eco logic, INIA, WAGENINGEN UR.

Funded by the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme of the European Union.

Soil Mission Support

SMS Towards a European Research and Innovation Roadmap on Soil and Land Management

H2020 CSA

Linda Maring¹, Jos Brils¹, Sandra Naumann², Sophie Ittner², Michael Loebmann³
¹ Deltares (NL), ² ECOLOGIC (DE), ³ ZALF (DE)

Partners: Bundesanstalt für Landwirtschaft und Ernährung, zalf, INRAE, Deltares, umweltbundesamt, ATK, eagasc, eco logic, INIA, WAGENINGEN UR.

Funded by the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme of the European Union.

SMS Objective: Develop a European R&I Roadmap for sustainable soil and land management

4

The SMS Approach of R&I roadmap co-creation

Co-creation covering all relevant actors, sectors and policy fields:

- Co-analyse R&I knowledge and activities on soil systems and land management
 - **Mapping and assessment** of the state-of-the-art of R&I in soil and land management
 - Proper definition and stock-taking of Living Labs and Lighthouses
 - Identification of R&I gaps & needs for soil and land management
- Co-develop a R&I **roadmap** on soil systems and land management
 - Integrates thematic (what) with procedural (how) recommendations
 - Identifies strategic criteria for future R&I
- Co-design an **active platform** for R&I roadmapping:
 - Facilitate the coordination of R&I activities
 - Promote good practices for land and soil management research using Living Labs and Lighthouses
 - Assist in continuous co-design of the R&I roadmap together with researchers, practitioners, young professionals, policy makers, and informed citizens.

Stocks

Needs

Gaps

Actions

6

SMS Group

Cover all land use sectors
Cover all land use actors
Cover all soil functions

5

The role of soil and land management for sustainable development

- Increased provision of biomass for **food, feed, fibre, and bioenergy** (SDGs 2 and 7)
 - Mitigation of and adaptation to **climate change** (SDG 13)
 - Mitigation of land take by **urbanisation** (SDG 11)
 - Improved provision of **ecosystem services & biodiversity and disaster control** (SDG 15)
- This progress can only be achieved with a multi-actor **partnership** across locations and sectors (SDG 17)

Mitigation of trade-offs between SDGs

7

The SMS Knowledge Matrix

Interaction

- SMS is about co-design with actors / European actor networks
- Strong interaction with other initiatives formalised and non formalised
- Dynamic situation: Horizon Europe; Mission on Soil Health and Food, Soil thematic strategy

Urban or industrial soil management is relevant for achieving these Soil Mission targets

Urban or industrial soil management is relevant for achieving these Soil Mission targets

SMS identified Soil and Land related R&I gaps:

R&I needs in the urban sector:

- Understand and apply soil multi-functionality
- Indicators and regular monitoring
 - Standard procedures for quantification and evaluation
 - Short- and long-term effects
- Frameworks for reducing land take and soil sealing
 - Promote suitable innovations (architecture, landscape planning, ...)
 - Raise awareness and involve stakeholder
 - Reuse/remediation of Brownfields

→ Create opportunities

SMS identified Soil and Land related R&I gaps:

General needs:

- Develop site specific, integrated, environmentally friendly and socially sensitive approaches
 - More stakeholder involvement
 - More inter- and trans-disciplinary research across spatial scales
 - More targeted efforts (research, decision making, practice)
- Free access of public research results, publications and reports
- Process research results into practically usable forms
 - Gain a systemic overview
 - Outreach

Soil Mission objectives

Objective

1. Reduce land degradation, including desertification and salinization
2. Conserve (e.g. in forests, permanent pastures, wetlands) and increase soil organic carbon stocks
3. No net soil sealing and increase the re-use of urban soils for urban development
4. Reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration
5. Prevent erosion
6. Improve soil structure to enhance habitat quality for soil biota and crops
7. Reduce the EU global footprint on soils
8. Increase soil literacy in society across Member States

What key R&I gaps missed? (start by typing the # to which Soil Mission objective your gap relates. For # see previous slide and chat box)

#4 #7 unknown fate and transport of pollutants in soil, fe degradation rates

for example = fe

8. Missing links between social economic and soil, environmental studies

6. Improve soil structure to 3. No net soil sealing 4. Reduce soil pollution

7 market chains are not designed to promote PP&P

#7 #8 education about soil, give insight

People planet profit

Stop soil sealing by new infrastructure

1 regulation and subsidies should be designed to avoid negative tradeoffs

Tune regulation, subsidies, (financial) incentives between sectors that affect land use to avoid adverse effects

Where to start / what R&I gap first to be addressed? (what ever comes in your mind first)

pollutant behaviour

Tune regulation, subsidies and (financial) incentives that affect land use to avoid adverse effects

Ripe fruit first to achieve results that motivates others

Knowledge the soil. Map the soil to categorize it and protect it

Our assumptions

- Soil Mission and its related objectives can only be achieved through healthy soils and for that it is needed to engage stakeholders
- You (as actor) will only engage if you recognize benefits in that engagement (what can you propose to me ...)

Value Proposition

Gain creators

Products & services

Pain relievers

→

Customer Profile

Gains

Customer jobs

Pains

Our proposition

What we offer to facilitate your job

Your need

Job to do, and related 'pains' and 'gains'

Picture source: B2B International

Soil Mission actor groups

Actor group

1. Policy maker and government
2. Research community
3. Research funder
4. Land user / manager / owner and related associations
5. Private sector and industry
6. Service provider
7. NGO (a.o. nature protection)
8. Other

Please remember your #

What would you gain (is your benefit) from sustainably managed soil? (type first your actor group type #. For # see previous slide and chat box)

8. Citizens: Long term life on this planet	#8 as citizen: a healthy soil now and for future generations	#8 healthy environment
2: researchers we want to achieve goals such as sustainable use. So we make impact if we reach this	#2 we could produce healthy foods	#2 mission clean soil and water is realistic goal
4. Land users & 5. Industry long term production potential	#6 every advice must have an environmental benefit	#2 increase soil health, increase human health

What would you gain (is your benefit) from sustainably managed soil? (type first your actor group type #. For # see previous slide and chat box)

#2 sustainably managed means system approach	7.ngo very direct benefit when talking on protection as a goal	4. 5. 6. 8. mitigation of climate extremes (droughts, heat waves, heavy rains)
4&5 less money to spend on cleanup mitigation	#6 room for new innovations	8. Citizens less tax money needs to be spend on protection and clean up. More for other objectives :-)
#2 fertilizer and pesticides reduction	#1 eternal fame	2 researchers. No work anymore

What pains (headaches) do you fear when soil is sustainably managed? (type first your actor group type #. For # see previous slide and chat box)

2. Researcher. No work anymore	#8 reduced space for housing	#6 search for good people
5. Limited possibilities to do their work. More costs to make	#2 new behaviour of the soil microbioma	All: less opportunities for human activities when nature goes first
It would be great if we become unconsciously competent		

Your one word evaluation of this session (by typing a word already at the screen it will grow)

Soil Expert Group workshop June 22, 2021

Summary of the main points of the first expert workshop:

Co-creating a European research and innovation roadmap on soils and land management

22 June 2021, 09.00-12.30, Online

Results are visualised in the Miro Board:

<https://miro.com/welcomeonboard/SjM3NmJQV1o5akJ2OWtDU21yeFYyWEFWWmVYdTJhZDk1Qm1Gb0Zpa0hYY0x1ZW1GRG02MFNSSDNTNjdFNWxpTnwzMDc0NDU3MzQ5OTAzMTY4NDE3>

Expectation from the group on the R&I Roadmap for Land and Soil Management

- Most actors are specifically interested in contributing to the mission on soil health and food, so it is important to communicate clearly how exactly the project and the roadmap will contribute to the implementation of the mission
- Explore how Horizon Europe can better contribute to research and policy
- Improve connection of different land use sectors and knowledge and break existing sectoral silos
- Make scientific knowledge available to put action into place, e.g. getting the knowledge to the farmers
- address also the urban-rural and local/regional nexus

Step 1: Vision of the Roadmap

Figure 1: Vision of the Roadmap

- There was no feedback on the vision of the roadmap
- But also no rejection, so this overarching vision of the roadmap can be accepted for now.

Step 2: User needs and benefits

- There are clear benefits for every sector (table 2 underneath), it seems that it is very intuitive to name the benefits, while R&I needs are more complex and detailed
- There is a long list of research gaps from e.g. the EJP SOIL roadmap according to agriculture
- Needs are very different from region to region
- The question is how we can get a complete list of needs, especially in relation to industry, urban and protected areas where the database is currently weaker?

Step 3: Prioritise needs

- Results can be found in table 2 underneath.
- The identification/prioritisation of the most important needs and gaps should be, for example, an "informed process"
- Identification of trade-offs & synergies should be an important part of the prioritisation process.
- Prepare synthesised knowledge basis to prioritise key needs (+ actions) for the roadmap
- Suggested criteria to prioritise needs:
 1. Urgency and timing (windows of opportunities)
 2. Where are the main synergies between different soil mission objectives?
 3. Need for balancing interests and mitigating trade-offs

Step 4: How to address the needs (informing the Soil mission R&I roadmap)

- Results can be found in table 3 under the Detailed Results from the workshop underneath.
- In order to address the needs, it seems that the different knowledge types are useful overarching categories to structure specific actions to address the needs
 - There is a strong need for training, exchange, demonstration and awareness raising
 - Improved soil monitoring, create official standards
 - Develop policy frameworks
 - Define goals

Step 5: Structure, Format and elements of the roadmap

- Use of the mission goals and societal challenge as a starting point to structure the roadmap?
- The roadmap should include following elements/provide information on:
 - Linking measures clearly to the targeted end-users
 - Address the soil-science -society interface
 - Outline the route from needs/gaps to solutions/improved soil and land management
 - Highlight synergies
 - Provide recommendations tailored already for Horizon Europe topics (with a strong focus on impact)
 - Address also the enabling conditions for improved implementation of sustainable soil and land management
 - Milestones? Indicators to measure progress achieving targets?
 - From theory to practice - Recommendations on how to bring knowledge to "end-users" based on good practice (living labs, light houses, multi-stakeholders platforms,...)
 - Megatrends; climate change, urbanisation, bio-economy etc. crossing the SM objectives

Overarching issues emerging from the discussion:

- It is also important to communicate clearly how exactly we are already building on existing work (e.g. roadmap of EJP Soil)
- Especially with regard to agricultural, there is already a lot of knowledge, so the focus of the SMS project should be strongly on the other sectors.
- What is the scope of the roadmap? Balancing between being as short as possible but detailed enough
- Formulate clearly the timeframe for which the roadmap is intended.
- A lot of knowledge is there but how to transfer the knowledge from science to practice?
- consider local contexts impacting whether measures are effective and feasible

Participants

Table 1: Participants (Names undisclosed)

Organisation
JPI FACCE Scientific Advisory Board
representative of the Ecosystem Service Partnership
Local Governments for Sustainability (ICLEI)
NICOLE network
Copa-Cogeca
The Common Forum on contaminated Land
European Forest Institute (EFI)
The European Environmental Bureau (EEB)
European Landowners Organisation (ELO)
IFOAM
EJP Soil
2 SMS project members from Ecologic, 1 from Deltares and 1 from ZALF

Detailed Results from the workshop

Table 2: Users' needs in order to manage soils more sustainable and benefits from sustainable soil management

Sector	Needs	Benefits
Agriculture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Translation of conceptual frameworks on SOM into practical advice to farmers • Creation of Communities of Practice • Increase used of perennial crops in agriculture • Implementation of conservation tillage without pesticides • Ecosystem services-based management (looking at trade-offs and synergies) • Practical advice for intercropping and mixed cropping, and more use of leguminous crops • need of clear conceptual framework (definitions) • Analysis of the improvement potential (baseline) • Lacking management and soil type specific emission factors • Impact analysis in economic terms • Non-exhaustive list of applicable practices and their impact on improvement potential • Cost efficient MRV 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced GHG emissions and lower nutrient loadings to the aquatic ecosystems • Organic and agro ecological practices, protecting soil and biodiversity • Improved image and societal perception of the agricultural sector • Payment for delivering ecosystem services • nature-based solutions (economically feasible and environmentally friendly) • Measurement of impact of co-benefits of carbon farming = potential for future rewarding • Soils are again at the centre of agriculture

Sector	Needs	Benefits
Agriculture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effective policy incentives directly rewarding farmers for good soil management and carbon sequestration (not carbon markets with high transaction costs where consultants make most profit) • Decision support tools for designing crop rotations • Site-specific implementation of soil improving management practices. • Importance to underpin circularity • Develop and implement biodiverse cropping systems that support soil quality • Improved nutrient retention in agriculture and the landscape linked to water management • Reduced use and dependence on P fertilizers • To ensure right assessment of cultivation and soil management measures' environmental impacts we need accurate measurement of cycles and flows in-situ conditions • Farmer-oriented approach • Funding - How to optimise practices in function of funding (CAP subsidies, other public funding, private funding) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A central practical expertise centre • More stable yields • Resilience against climate change (water stress and flooding) • Clear unique definitions • Natural soil fertility (no need for adding artificial fertiliser)
Forestry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved Inter-rotation period management • Site-specific implementation of soil improving management practices. • optimised road layout and maintenance (minimal impact, optimal logistics) • Ecosystem services-based management (looking at trade-offs and synergies) • Analysis of the improvement potential (baseline) • shared visions on desired objectives • Importance to underpin circularity • Soils underpinning forest biodiversity • Increased awareness and knowledge uptake • Non-exhaustive list of applicable practices and their impact on improvement potential • mix of regulatory and PES type tools to facilitate improved management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measurement of impact of co-benefits of carbon farming = potential for future rewarding • A central practical expertise centre • Payment for delivering ecosystem services • more profitable forestry (provision of wood, non-wood, maybe also through ES if PES) • nature-based solutions (economically feasible and environmentally friendly)
Industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cleaning heavy polluted areas • Ecosystem services-based management (looking at trade-offs and synergies) • Monitoring diffuse pollution at regional scale and connect/validate by biomonitoring • Solutions in managing pollution of forever chemicals • Facing aridification, understanding the potential of NBS (forest and land management) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • improved societal recognition, respect and license to operate • nature-based solutions (economically feasible and environmentally friendly) • halt/revert desertification and cope with aridification in Mediterranean ecosystems • Improved image and societal perception of the industrial sector" • improved (mid and long term) productivity and resilience
Urban areas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-creation processes for soil restoration, regenerative urban agriculture, sustainable soil mgt • Ecosystem services-based management (looking at trade-offs and synergies) • How can soils underpin urban biodiversity (action)? • Safe and strict standards for soil contamination in urban (& nature and agricultural) areas • Ambition on no soil pollution in 2050 necessary? • Ecosystem services of urban soils incl carbon sequestration, pollutant sinks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • nature-based solutions (economically feasible and environmentally friendly) • Healthy citizens • Citizens can grow healthy food in kitchen garden • Air purification • Safe spaces to raise kids" • Carbon Sequestration

Sector	Needs	Benefits
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How does urban soil pollution/ contamination impact peri-urban and rural areas? • What functions do soils (have to) fulfil in urban NBS? • What level of priority should soils have in urban planning/ sustainable development? • How can urban soil pollution/ contamination and its impact on peri-urban and rural areas be reduced/ avoided? • Also, increased efficiency, competitiveness,... • Impacts on biodiversity central? Impact on biodiversity mitigations? Roadmap to become non-impact in 2050? • Soil neutrality goal? • How can sustainable soils management be reconciled with all the competing interests in cities (e.g., lack of space) 	
Protected areas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ecosystem services-based management (looking at trade-offs and synergies)", "protect biodiversity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Restoration of wetlands • (additional) arguments for nature protection • Combat desertification"

Table 3: How to address the needs

Needs	R&I action and other measures to address the needs
Agriculture: Effective policy incentives directly rewarding farmers for good soil management and carbon sequestration (not carbon markets with high transaction costs where consultants make most profit)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Update Inventory and Assessment of Soil Protection Policy Instruments in EU Member States https://ec.europa.eu/environment/soil/pdf/Soil_inventory_report.pdf • Organise standard owners on a non-profit base • Provide good advice to farmers willing to change soil management • Foster independent advise • Define regulatory framework ASAP • Create CoPs (exchange of best practices) • What policy measures create impact on the ground? • Identification of trade-offs of certain practices to implement the do no harm principle • Better understanding of the dynamics around permanence/reversibility of C sequestration + what policies to ensure permanence (ratchet mechanism, polluter pays principle,...?)
Forestry: Analysis of the improvement potential (baseline) + overview of impact of potential measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • develop region specific post-fire management strategies (adapt species according ecological setting) • Foster independent advise • Agree on goals for soil condition and stablish governance approaches that actually work! (ahahah) • Develop the policy science interfaces • Increase awareness and knowledge transfer • Create CoPs (exchange of best practices) • Improve soil monitoring • Demonstrate de links between soil condition and provision of private and public goods and services • Organise standard owners on a non-profit base"
Urban areas: Safe and strict standards for soil contamination in urban (as well as soils in nature and agricultural area)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prioritise public health when setting standards, not needs of industry • find viable land uses for peri-urban areas to avoid soil sealing by industrial development areas • Set up integrated monitoring schemes (incl. standardized KPIs, co-monitoring concepts) that continuously monitor ecosystem services • Create official standards (e.g., through ISO/CEN/CENELEC) on sustainable soil mgt in urban areas • understanding health-related issues (e.g. epidemiological studies) regarding dust inhalation (fine particles of contaminated soil)"

Needs	R&I action and other measures to address the needs
Industry: Ecosystem services-based management (looking at trade-offs and synergies)	-
Protected areas: Ecosystem services-based management (looking at trade-offs and synergies)	-

Table 4: First ideas on the structure and elements of the roadmap

Further potential elements of the roadmap	<p>Short-term, mid-term, long-term targets</p> <p>From theory to practice: Recommendations on how to bring knowledge to "end-users" based on good practice (living labs, light houses, multi-stakeholders platforms,)</p> <p>Megatrends; climate change, urbanisation, bioeconomy etc. crossing the SM objectives</p> <p>Linking measures clearly to the targeted endusers</p> <p>Mission objectives as starting point?</p> <p>Milestones? Indicators to measure progress achieving targets?</p> <p>Address the soil-science -society interface</p> <p>Outline the route from needs/gaps to solutions/improved soil and land management</p> <p>Address also the enabling conditions for improved implementation of sust. soil and land management</p> <p>Highlight synergies</p> <p>First generation FTPs were very successful</p> <p>Provide recommendations tailored already for HEurope topics (with a strong focus on impact)</p>
Overall Considerations	<p>How to include soil scientists in soil literacy</p> <p>Transfer /translation from science to practice (also incl. social science)</p> <p>Build on available results (in part. EJP for agriculture and relevant research projects)</p> <p>Learn from failures in the past, drivers of mistrust (e.g. engaging land managers) - start a dialogue!</p> <p>Take an adaptive/ flexible approach? Looking also at experiences from other sectors (e.g. water)</p> <p>Intersections of soils with climate and biodiversity crises</p> <p>Priorisation criteria:</p> <p>Urgency and timing (windows of opportunities) are key!</p> <p>Need for balancing interests and mitigating trade-offs</p> <p>Where are the main synergies btw. different SM objectives?</p> <p>Which objectives/ targets are the most challenging?</p> <p>Soils should play a key role in the Urban Greening Plans called for by the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030</p> <p>consider local contexts impacting whether measures are effective and feasible</p> <p>Identify different barriers to implementation (economic, but also social etc.)</p> <p>Helpful reference: http://www.openness-project.eu/sites/default/files/OpenNESS_brief_03.pdf Again, soil health is not the primary focus but it includes a number of interesting examples of applied soil health measure,"http://www.openness-project.eu/sites/default/files/OpenNESS_brief_03.pdf"</p> <p>CIRCASA project</p>
The Expert group collaboration process	<p>Prepare synthesised knowledge basis to prioritise key needs (+ actions) for the roadmap</p> <p>Room for in-depth discussion in the expert group?</p> <p>Include Horizon 2020 NBS Task Forces</p> <p>https://networknature.eu/network-nature/nature-based-solutions-task-forces</p>

ANNEX VIII: SURVEY ON ACTOR NEEDS

See section 2.1 for explaining text

Survey on how the EU Soil Mission objectives may affect soil stakeholder interests

Dear soil stakeholder,

We estimate that you have an interest in soil and its management. If we are right, we would be very pleased if you would be willing to fill out our short survey and thus provide us your valuable input. With this survey – which will take approximately 20 minutes to fill out – [The Soil Mission Support project](#) wants to gain insight in your view on the objectives identified by the EU mission on soil health and food (see below) and how they relate to your soil stakeholder interests.

EU missions and the Mission on Soil health and food

The EU has set 5 missions for the future of the EU. These missions are commitments to solve some of the greatest challenges facing our world: fighting cancer, adapting to climate change, protecting our oceans, living in greener cities and ensuring soil health and food. More information can be found on the [EU missions website](#).

The Mission on Soil health and food states that land and soil are essential for life on Earth. Soil supplies the food we grow and eat, as well as other goods such as feed, textiles, or wood. Soil also provides a range of other ecosystem services, which are important for clean water, supporting biodiversity or for cycling nutrients and regulating climate. Soil is a highly dynamic and fragile system, and it is a finite resource. It can take up to 1,000 years to produce 1 cm of soil. Soil is facing pressures from an increasing population that demands more land for production, settlement and industries. Soil is also heavily affected by climate change, erosion and sea level rises. Approximately 33% of our global soil is degraded and in the EU erosion is affecting 25% of agricultural land.

The goal of the Mission on Soil health and food is to achieve that by 2030 at least 75% of soils in each EU Member State are healthy, or show a significant improvement towards meeting accepted thresholds of indicators, to support ecosystem services.

The Soil health and food mission will be achieved through a portfolio of actions – such as research projects, policy measures or even legislative initiatives – thus to achieve a measurable goal that could not be achieved through individual actions. For more information on the Soil health and food mission see [the soil mission's website](#).

What will be done with my answers?

Your answers will be processed anonymously and in accordance with the Soil Mission Support data protection notice which can be downloaded [here](#). They will be used as valuable input to support the achievement of the EU mission on Soil health and food.

Note: you can ignore the "OK" button during the survey

4. In what actor group would you place the organisation that you are working for? (multiple answers are possible)

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Policymakers and governmental organisations | <input type="checkbox"/> Private sector and industry |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Research funding organisations | <input type="checkbox"/> Service provider/Consultant |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Research community (university, knowledge institutes) | <input type="checkbox"/> Non-governmental organisation |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Land users/managers/owners and related organisations | |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify) | |

2. In which country/countries is your organisation most active?

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Albania | <input type="checkbox"/> Lithuania |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Andorra | <input type="checkbox"/> Luxembourg |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Armenia | <input type="checkbox"/> Malta |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Austria | <input type="checkbox"/> Moldova |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Azerbaijan | <input type="checkbox"/> Monaco |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Belarus | <input type="checkbox"/> Montenegro |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Bosnia and Herzegovina | <input type="checkbox"/> The Netherlands |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Bulgaria | <input type="checkbox"/> North Macedonia |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Croatia | <input type="checkbox"/> Norway |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Cyprus | <input type="checkbox"/> Poland |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Czech Republic | <input type="checkbox"/> Portugal |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Denmark | <input type="checkbox"/> Romania |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Estonia | <input type="checkbox"/> Russia |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Finland | <input type="checkbox"/> San Marino |
| <input type="checkbox"/> France | <input type="checkbox"/> Serbia |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Georgia | <input type="checkbox"/> Slovakia |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Germany | <input type="checkbox"/> Slovenia |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Greece | <input type="checkbox"/> Spain |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Hungary | <input type="checkbox"/> Sweden |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Iceland | <input type="checkbox"/> Switzerland |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Ireland | <input type="checkbox"/> Turkey |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Italy | <input type="checkbox"/> Ukraine |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Kazakhstan | <input type="checkbox"/> United Kingdom |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Kosovo | <input type="checkbox"/> Vatican City |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Latvia | <input type="checkbox"/> European Union |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Liechtenstein | |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify) | |

3. Which of the following areas or sectors relate to your organisation? [multiple answers are possible]

- | | |
|---|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Agriculture/Horticulture | <input type="checkbox"/> Urban areas |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Forestry | <input type="checkbox"/> Industry |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Protected areas (such as National parks) | <input type="checkbox"/> Infrastructure |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify) | |

"By 2030, at least 75% of soils in each EU Member State are healthy, or show a significant improvement towards meeting accepted thresholds of indicators, to support ecosystem services."

Below you find an overview of the objectives and targets related to the Soil health and food mission's goal:

Mission Goal: 75% of all soils healthy by 2030 as indicated by no decline in any of 6 soil health indicators according to benchmarks for healthy soils for each local context			
Specific Targets and Indicators			
Objectives	Land Management Targets	Soil Health Targets	Six Soil Health Indicators
Land degradation and desertification	<i>50% degraded land restored</i>	<i>Strong reduction in degradation and desertification</i>	<i>All 6 soil health indicators</i>
Soil organic carbon	<i>Conservation of high carbon soils and a reverse of carbon loss in croplands.</i>	<i>A switch from a 0.5 % loss per year to a 0.1-0.4% increase in SOC concentration in cropland soils</i> <i>30-50% reduced area of peatland losing carbon</i>	<i>Soil organic carbon stock</i> <i>Vegetation cover</i>
Soil sealing and net land take	<i>Urban recycling of land from 13 to 50%</i> <i>No net land take by 2050</i>	<i>Switch from 2.4% to no net soil sealing</i>	<i>Soil structure including soil bulk density and absence of soil sealing and erosion</i> <i>Vegetation cover</i>
Soil pollution	<i>25% of land under organic farming</i> <i>Doubling of rate of remediated sites prioritising brown field sites</i>	<i>5-25% additional land (i.e. over and above the 25% in full organic) with reduced risk from a range of pollutants</i>	<i>Presence of soil pollutants, excess nutrients and salts</i>
Erosion	<i>50% degraded land restored</i>	<i>Prevention on 30-50% of land with unsustainable erosion risk</i>	<i>Soil structure including soil bulk density and absence of soil sealing and erosion.</i> <i>Vegetation cover</i>
Soil structure	<i>50% degraded land restored</i>	<i>Reduction by 30-50% of soil with compaction</i>	<i>Soil bulk density and other measures of soil structure</i>
<i>While not being a soil indicator in the strict sense, mission activities will be assessed against their impact on the health of soils outside Europe</i>			
Global footprint	<i>Strengthened international cooperation; trade regulations, including carbon tax</i>	<i>20-40% reduction of current global footprint</i>	<i>Food, feed and fibre imports leading to land degradation and deforestation</i>

Please point out how important (of great significance or value) you perceive each of the different objectives identified by the EU mission on soil health and food for your organization and why this is the case.

For each of the 8 above objectives the following questions were asked, for the sake of space, the similar follow up questions are not all repeated for each objective (table underneath) here.

4. Please point out how important (of great significance or value) you perceive the objective "Reduce land degradation, including desertification and salinization" for your organization.

9. Please point out how important (of great significance or value) you perceive the objective **"Conserve (e.g. in forests, permanent pastures, wetlands) and increase soil organic carbon stocks"** for your organization.

14. Please point out how important (of great significance or value) you perceive the objective **"No net soil sealing and increase the re-use of urban soils for urban development"** for your organization.

19. Please point out how important (of great significance or value) you perceive the objective **"Reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration"** for your organization.

24. Please point out how important (of great significance or value) you perceive the objective **"Prevent erosion"** for your organization.

29. Please point out how important (of great significance or value) you perceive the objective **"Improve soil structure to enhance habitat quality for soil biota and crops"** for your organization.

34. Please point out how important (of great significance or value) you perceive the objective **"Reduce the EU global footprint on soils"** for your organization.

39. Please point out how important (of great significance or value) you perceive the objective **"Increase soil literacy in society across Member States"** for your organization.

- | | |
|----------------------------------|--------------------------------------|
| <input type="radio"/> Not at all | <input type="radio"/> Very |
| <input type="radio"/> Slightly | <input type="radio"/> No opinion |
| <input type="radio"/> Neutral | <input type="radio"/> Not applicable |
| <input type="radio"/> Fairly | |

5. Why is this the case? [multiple answers are possible]

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Legislation/regulation | <input type="checkbox"/> Demands from your funders |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Current activities of your organisation | <input type="checkbox"/> Demands from your members/supporters |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Ambitions of your organisation | <input type="checkbox"/> Demands from the soil user(s) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Demands from your customers | <input type="checkbox"/> Social and environmental responsibility |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Demands from the general public | <input type="checkbox"/> High costs for restoration or irreversibility of the matter (and related costs) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Other, namely: | |

6. Please point out how urgent (requiring immediate action or attention) you perceive this objective for your organization.

- | | |
|----------------------------------|--------------------------------------|
| <input type="radio"/> Not at all | <input type="radio"/> Very |
| <input type="radio"/> Slightly | <input type="radio"/> No opinion |
| <input type="radio"/> Neutral | <input type="radio"/> Not applicable |
| <input type="radio"/> Fairly | |

7. Why is this the case? [multiple answers are possible]

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Legislation/regulation | <input type="checkbox"/> Demands from your funders |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Current activities of your organisation | <input type="checkbox"/> Demands from your members/supporters |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Ambitions of your organisation | <input type="checkbox"/> Demands from the soil user(s) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Demands from your customers | <input type="checkbox"/> Social and environmental responsibility |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Demands from the general public | <input type="checkbox"/> High costs for restoration or irreversibility of the matter (and related costs) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Other, namely: | |

8. What does your organization need in order to be able to help reaching this objective (e.g. R&I, knowledge, technology, legal support, forms of organization, etc.)?

SECTION 3: Your envisioned role as a stakeholder when it comes to reaching the EU mission objectives

44. What level of engagement would you desire for your organisation when it comes to reaching the EU mission objectives on soil health and food?

- | | |
|---|---|
| <input type="radio"/> Our organisation does not want to be engaged in reaching the EU mission objectives on soil health and food. | <input type="radio"/> Our organisation wants to be involved in reaching the EU mission objectives on soil health and food. |
| <input type="radio"/> Our organisation wants to be informed about reaching the EU mission objectives on soil health and food. | <input type="radio"/> Our organisation wants to collaborate with the EU to reach the EU mission objectives on soil health and food. |
| <input type="radio"/> Our organisation wants to be consulted about reaching the EU mission objectives on soil health and food. | |

45. Could you please elaborate a bit your response to the previous question (i.e. how you would like to engage; why do you not want to engage).

SECTION 4: The influence of the EU Soil Mission objectives on soil stakeholder interests

46. If the EU Soil Missions objectives would be reached overnight, how would this positively affect your own organization?

47. If the EU Soil Missions objectives would be reached overnight, how would this negatively affect your own organization?

48. How would you estimate the relationship between the previously mentioned positive and negative effects? (would the positive effects outweigh the negative effects, or vice versa?)

49. What can be done, in your opinion, to maximize the positive effects that you expect for your organization if the EU Soil Missions objectives would be reached overnight?

50. What can be done, in your opinion, to reduce or solve the negative effects that you expect for your organization if the EU Soil Missions objectives would be reached overnight?

SECTION 5: Thank you and follow up

51. If you have any questions or comments concerning the survey please leave these below.

52. Can we contact you for follow-up questions or engagement in activities (e.g. workshops) in our H2020 Soil Mission Support project?

- Yes
 No

Your answers will be processed anonymously and in accordance with the Soil Mission Support data protection notice which can be downloaded here. They will be used as valuable input for the further development of the portfolio of actions – such as research projects, policy measures or even legislative initiatives of the EU mission on soil health and food.

53. Please provide your name and email address if you can be approached for follow up (on) questions and activities.

Name

Email Address

Thank you for filling out our survey!

ANNEX IX: SURVEY ON ACTOR NEEDS - RESULTS

Population and Response

See section 2.1 and 3.1 for explaining text. In addition:

Sectors that were defined as other were:

Marginal land, brownfields, contaminated sites / areas (2X)	Regional development
Environment (2X)	Living labs
Water management	GIS & Remote Sensing
Municipalities, regional authorities	Coastal areas
NGO: National Soil Protection	Nutrients
Climate change (2X)	River-delta-lagoons-seas systems
Food (2X)	Natura 2000 areas
Aquaculture (2X)	Permafrost/wetlands

Objectives of the soil mission – important/urgent

The survey was based on the objectives of the Soil Mission. Per objective the respondents were asked to indicate the importance of this objective for their organization and what the main reason for that is. Next, the respondents were asked how urgent they perceived the objective and what their needs were when it came to help reaching this objective. The results are displayed on the next page (table 1).

Table 1: objectives 1-5 - important/urgent

Objective	Importance (%)	Reason	Urgent (%)	Reason
1) "Reduce land degradation, including desertification and saliniza	Fairly: 15%	Demands from your members/supporters 12%	Fairly: 25%	Demands from your members/supporters 9,21%
	Very: 67%	Demands from your customers 13%		Demands from your customers 14,47%
		Other, namely: 15%	Very: 57%	Demands from your funders 14,47%
		Demands from your funders 19%		Other, namely: 14,47%
		Legislation/regulation 26%		Legislation/regulation 26,32%
		Demands from the general public 26%		Demands from the general public 26,32%
		Demands from the soil user(s) 29%		Demands from the soil user(s) 26,32%
		High costs for restoration or irreversibility of the matter (and related costs) 31%		High costs for restoration or irreversibility of the matter (and related costs) 27,63%
		Ambitions of your organisation 47%		Current activities of your organisation 42,11%
		Current activities of your organisation 51%		Ambitions of your organisation 50,00%
		Social and environmental responsibility 60%		Social and environmental responsibility 55,26%
2) "Conserve (e.g. in forests, permanent pastures, wetlands) and increase soil organic carbon stocks".	Fairly: 23%	Demands from your members/supporters 11,59%	Fairly: 25%	Demands from your customers 14,49%
	Very: 70	Demands from your funders 14,49%		Demands from your funders 14,49%
		Other, namely: 14,49%	Very: 61%	Other, namely: 14,49%
		Demands from your customers 17,39%		Demands from your members/supporters 17,39%
		High costs for restoration or irreversibility of the matter (and related costs) 23,19%		High costs for restoration or irreversibility of the matter (and related costs) 20,29%
		Legislation/regulation 26,09%		Legislation/regulation 23,19%
		Demands from the general public 26,09%		Demands from the soil user(s) 27,54%
		Demands from the soil user(s) 34,78%		Demands from the general public 31,88%
		Current activities of your organisation 55,07%		Ambitions of your organisation 47,83%
		Ambitions of your organisation 56,52%		Current activities of your organisation 52,17%
		Social and environmental responsibility 62,32%		Social and environmental responsibility 57,97%
3) "No net soil sealing and increase the re-use of urban soils for urban development".	Fairly: 17	Demands from your funders 7,58%	Fairly: 25	Demands from your funders 6,06%
	Very: 45	Demands from your members/supporters 7,58%		Demands from your members/supporters 6,06%
		Demands from your customers 12,12%	Very: 41	Demands from your customers 12,12%
		Demands from the soil user(s) 16,67%		Demands from the soil user(s) 15,15%
		Other, namely: 18,18%		Other, namely: 19,70%
		Legislation/regulation 25,76%		High costs for restoration or irreversibility of the matter (and related costs) 21,21%
		High costs for restoration or irreversibility of the matter (and related costs) 25,76%		Legislation/regulation 25,76%
		Demands from the general public 30,30%		Demands from the general public 27,27%
		Current activities of your organisation 43,94%		Current activities of your organisation 31,82%
		Ambitions of your organisation 43,94%		Ambitions of your organisation 36,36%
		Social and environmental responsibility 56,06%		Social and environmental responsibility 60,61%
4) Reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration	Fairly: 23	Demands from your members/supporters 9,72%	Fairly: 24	Demands from your members/supporters 9,72%
	Very: 63	Demands from your funders 12,50%		Demands from your funders 11,11%
		Other, namely: 13,89%	Very: 57	Other, namely: 11,11%
		Demands from your customers 25,00%		Demands from your customers 20,83%
		Demands from the soil user(s) 27,78%		Demands from the soil user(s) 20,83%
		Demands from the general public 34,72%		Demands from the general public 30,56%
		High costs for restoration or irreversibility of the matter (and related costs) 34,72%		High costs for restoration or irreversibility of the matter (and related costs) 30,56%
		Legislation/regulation 40,28%		Legislation/regulation 43,06%
		Current activities of your organisation 54,17%		Current activities of your organisation 44,44%
		Ambitions of your organisation 55,56%		Ambitions of your organisation 55,56%
		Social and environmental responsibility 63,89%		Social and environmental responsibility 61,11%

Objective	Importance	Urgency		
5) Prevent erosion	Fairly: 18	Fairly: 30		
	Very: 59	Very: 49		
	Demands from your members/supporters	7,14%	Demands from your funders	7,35%
	Demands from your funders	10,00%	Demands from your members/supporters	7,35%
	Other, namely:	14,29%	Other, namely:	11,76%
	Demands from your customers	15,71%	Demands from your customers	20,59%
	Legislation/regulation	20,00%	Legislation/regulation	23,53%
	Demands from the general public	28,57%	High costs for restoration or irreversibility of the matter (and related c	26,47%
	High costs for restoration or irreversibility of the matter (and related c	31,43%	Demands from the general public	27,94%
	Demands from the soil user(s)	38,57%	Demands from the soil user(s)	33,82%
	Ambitions of your organisation	40,00%	Current activities of your organisation	39,71%
	Current activities of your organisation	45,71%	Ambitions of your organisation	44,12%
	Social and environmental responsibility	64,29%	Social and environmental responsibility	58,82%

Concerning the category “other” for objective 1-5, the following reasons for importance and urgency were mentioned by the respondents (table 2)

Table 2: objectives 1-5 - reasons for importance and urgency category “other”

Objective	Other -Important	Other- Urgent
1) "Reduce land degradation, including desertification and salinization"	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Land degradation is a critical topic in urban areas, in particular in the context of urban sprawl and unsustainable development. Soil sealing, contamination and removal as well as a decrease in vegetation are examples of common issues impacting the biophysical environment in urban areas. Through a number of our sustainable development pathways (i.e., Nature-based development pathway, Equitable and people-centered development pathway, Circular development pathway, Resilient development pathway) we are supporting our members in addressing urban land degradation. Need for sustainable redevelopment of brownfields in urban areas Salt water in deeper layers can come to the surface No good water status without good soil status the role of soils in climate change mitigation the importance of soils for climate change mitigation and also adaptation including NBS corrosion, Human health issues not an issue in Denmark Land degradation is an issue (e.g. erosion), but not desertification and salinization Consequence of degradation is nutrient loss and impacts on water bodies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Energy transition can become coupled driver to reduce soil and groundwater pollution Other stakeholders are responsible desertification and salinization are not a problem nowadays in France. But it will be a problem with climate change. our institution is not directly responsible and has got not direct responsibility. As the state institution can act just in the frame of given responsibilities We lack knowledge about it. As above, nutrient loss, water quality impacts Overwhelming evidence that action is needed urgently to tackle the biodiversity and climate crises which are both related to this objective

Objective	Other -Important	Other- Urgent
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Desertification is not a pressing issue in Flanders, salinization will be in the long run but does not yet receive adequate attention • Moral imperative to preserve precious natural resources for future generations 	
<p>2) "Conserve (e.g. in forests, permanent pastures, wetlands) and increase soil organic carbon stocks".</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SOC includes carbon from plant remains in the form of humus which stores and provides readily available nutrients and water. Healthy, nutritious soils are the foundation of resilient NBS. More recently, nature-based carbon removal in urban areas is gaining interest for climate mitigation and to achieve cities' net zero goals. • The same needed for water management • carbon stocks crucial for climate neutrality ambitions - role in adaptation • Importance to protect soils and soil biodiversity because soil organic matter has a central role. Also importance to combat climate change (mitigation and adaptation). • This objective is not directly applicable to JPI Urban Europe / Driving Urban Transitions thematic orientation. However, there are potentially interesting links to explore regarding nature-based solutions, mitigating risks of extreme weather events, develop climate resilient, weather proof, healthy, safe, accessible, attractive, and inclusive urban environments. • SOC is linked to nutrient use efficiency, nutrient loss reduction • Central to addressing the climate and biodiversity crises • links to climate change issue 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The IPCC's Sixth Assessment Report warns that for cities, some aspects of climate change may be magnified, including heat, flooding from heavy precipitation events and sea level rise in coastal cities. Stabilizing the climate will require strong, rapid, and sustained reductions in greenhouse gas emissions, and reaching net zero CO2 emissions. Limiting human-induced global warming to a specific level requires limiting cumulative carbon dioxide emissions, reaching at least net zero CO2 emissions, along with strong reductions in other greenhouse gas emissions. Through conserving and increasing SOC stocks in urban areas, cities can do their share in the small remaining window for limiting global warming to well below 2° C by atmospheric carbon removal. • The NL main Ecological structure was broken down by short visionary politics. This should be redeveloped a.s.a.p. • Urgency to mitigate climate change • Demands from local public administration • Lacking clarity on R&D goals; poor leadership and overall management... • The NL is very crowded and have to face huge challenges on climate change, biodiversity, food transition, water quality and energy transition • Remaining sinks must be urgently protected to stop further degradation
<p>3) "No net soil sealing and increase the re-use of urban soils for urban development".</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The greatest impacts of soil sealing in Europe are observable in urban and metropolitan areas. Economic benefits such as local jobs, tax revenues and political advantages are incentivising and driving urbanization and soil sealing (e.g., development of new industrial & residential areas). Regional and local governments are often competing for economic development while there is little economic incentive for the conservation and restoration of urban and semi-urban ecosystems. Urban soil sealing and a lack of green infrastructure for water retention in both urban and rural areas can lead to catastrophic flooding of cities. Also, the prevention of land take and soil sealing is a crucial component of municipal efforts to bend the curve in biodiversity loss. Re-use of urban soils is often thought only in terms of re-using for a different type of soil sealing, but not in terms of re-using to de-seal for public green spaces, SUDs, etc. and promotion of biodiversity above and in soils. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The prevention of soil sealing and the re-use of urban land for development are of high urgency due to the increasing risk of urban flooding amplified by climate change and due to the current biodiversity crisis. At the same time, increasing need for urban housing, industrial zones and job opportunities is amping up the pressure on the development and sealing of remaining green areas adjacent to cities. • Demands from NGOs • not applicable • ...not an issue at my organisation

Objective	Other -Important	Other- Urgent
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It saves cost • Renaturalization of urban spaces as a natural-based solutions • Demands from NGOs • It is essential that the protection of agricultural land, which is naturally rich in carbon sequestration activities, should be protected from being continuously overtaken by the urban sprawl inherent across the Union. The decrease in agricultural land due to continuous urban expansion and land sealing prevents a genuine solution to carbon sequestration on a large-scale; and also increases the price of land year on year for those who wish to perform such activities on a larger scale than currently or to get into the agricultural and forestry sectors for the first time. • ...not an issue at my organisation • organization has focus on agricultural soils, soil sealing as such no issue in the NL • As rural entrepreneurs, we are in favour of the no net soil sealing • not an issue for the moment • Not a big topic for our organisation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • organization has focus on agricultural soils, soil sealing as such no issue in the NL • not involved in this type of activities • Access to soil is one of the most important barriers for young farmers. Flanders has very limited open space, that is under immense pressure. • Urbanisation is a threat to rural development • not an issue for the moment • In the NL there is a shortage of land to fulfil all the societal challenges. So every piece of land is needed and should be restored. • Trends in urban sprawl and inner-city development • Not a big compared to other issues we work on
4) Reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soil pollution and contamination plays a major role in urban areas and in industrial sites in particular, often limiting the way land and soil can be re-used due to negative public health impacts. Soil pollution also significantly impacts supply chains of essential resources such as drinking water and healthy agricultural products for cities. • Protect future drinking water wells • Demands from local authorities, administration, NGOs • shareholders • Nutrient content of soil core to our aims and actions • falls within other government entities' responsibilities • Contaminated land reduces a lot of other functions. As said before we need all the land there is to fulfil our societal needs. • Moral imperative to not degrade precious natural resources for future generations + Imperative to address the biodiversity crisis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reducing soil pollution and enhancing restoration is a very urgent issue since rural and urban soil pollution already impacts essential supply chains for cities. Urban soil pollution poses a threat to public health and makes the re-use of urban soils more challenging and costly. • In NL over 550 IBC locations suffer from endless measures to monitor these locations. There is a need to stimulate Nature Based Solutions to come to a finite treatment. • Demands from local authorities, administration, NGOs • Nutrient content of soil core to our aims and actions • It is much cheaper to reduce pollution at source than to clean it up later. Concern for the potential health impacts linked to soil pollution (eg by heavy metals) • there are only spots where the pollution is a challenge

Objective	Other -Important	Other- Urgent
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The pollution is not the main challenge in the country 	
5) Prevent erosion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Soil erosion can be a major issue for cities. Intensive use of land can affect soil and its functions significantly and in several ways, including through soil sealing, erosion, compaction and contamination. When sealed — covered by buildings, asphalt or concrete — soil loses, among others, its ability to absorb and retain water or to produce food. Use of heavy machinery can change soil structure and make it more compact, reducing air and water in the parts of the soil where plant roots take up water and nutrients and where soil animals and microorganisms decompose organic material. Sealed or heavily compacted soil absorbs less rain water, which in turn increases surface run-off, soil erosion and the risk of flooding. Erosion can also affect biodiversity as top soils tend to shelter the highest diversity and density of soil organisms. Through soil erosion or flooding, pollutants can enter water streams, leach into groundwater and spread farther. Rural soil erosion can significantly impact supply chains of essential products such as agricultural products for cities and cause pollution of water bodies of downstream cities. In a delta area erosion is less important status of surface water is threatened by erosion climate change current operations coastal erosion Soil erosion implies nutrient losses, nutrient inputs to surface waters Erosion is relatively small issue in NL The NL is rather flat and there is hardly any erosion. Local provincial legislation is mostly sufficient. Moral imperative for future generations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It is a minor topic in NL with climate change, erosion will be enhanced, and the impacts will be more and more important some current locations are under threat Erosion is relatively small issue in NL recent overflow focus the issue for the general public Hardly any problem Need to adapt to climate change and make agriculture more resilient to safeguard farmers livelihoods and food production.

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Table 3: objectives 6-8 - important/urgent

Objective	Importance (%)	Reason	Urgent (%)	Reason
6) Improve soil structure to enhance habitat quality for soil biota in crops	Fairly: 21	Legislation/regulation 6,94%	Fairly: 53	Other, namely: 5,71%
	Very: 58	Demands from your members/supporters 6,94%		Very: 24
		Demands from your funders 8,33%		Demands from your members/supporters 8,57%
		Other, namely: 9,72%		Legislation/regulation 12,86%
		Demands from your customers 18,06%		High costs for restoration or irreversibility of the matter (and related c 18,57%
		Demands from the general public 20,83%		Demands from your customers 21,43%
		High costs for restoration or irreversibility of the matter (and related c 23,61%		Demands from the general public 22,86%
		Demands from the soil user(s) 29,17%		Demands from the soil user(s) 28,57%
		Current activities of your organisation 47,22%		Current activities of your organisation 44,29%
		Ambitions of your organisation 48,61%		Ambitions of your organisation 51,43%
		Social and environmental responsibility 66,67%		Social and environmental responsibility 61,43%
7) Reduce the EU global footprint on soils	Fairly: 19	Demands from your customers 10,45%	Fairly: 21	Demands from your funders 8,06%
	Very: 47	Demands from your funders 10,45%		Very: 50
		Demands from your members/supporters 11,94%		Demands from your members/supporters 9,68%
		Demands from the soil user(s) 13,43%		Demands from the soil user(s) 11,29%
		Other, namely: 14,93%		Demands from your customers 16,13%
		Legislation/regulation 19,40%		Legislation/regulation 20,97%
		High costs for restoration or irreversibility of the matter (and related c 23,88%		High costs for restoration or irreversibility of the matter (and related c 22,56%
		Demands from the general public 32,84%		Demands from the general public 33,87%
		Ambitions of your organisation 43,28%		Current activities of your organisation 37,10%
		Current activities of your organisation 44,78%		Ambitions of your organisation 43,55%
		Social and environmental responsibility 59,70%		Social and environmental responsibility 66,13%
8) Increase soil literacy in society across Member States	Fairly: 34	High costs for restoration or irreversibility of the matter (and related c 6,25%	Fairly: 36	Other, namely: 4,76%
	Very: 44	Other, namely: 9,38%		Very: 41
		Legislation/regulation 12,50%		Demands from your funders 12,70%
		Demands from your members/supporters 12,50%		Demands from your members/supporters 12,70%
		Demands from your funders 14,06%		Legislation/regulation 14,29%
		Demands from your customers 15,63%		Demands from your customers 17,46%
		Demands from the general public 21,88%		Demands from the soil user(s) 17,46%
		Demands from the soil user(s) 25,00%		Demands from the general public 30,16%
		Ambitions of your organisation 46,88%		Current activities of your organisation 44,44%
		Current activities of your organisation 50,00%		Ambitions of your organisation 52,38%
		Social and environmental responsibility 54,69%		Social and environmental responsibility 55,56%

Table 4: objectives 6-8 - reasons for importance and urgency category "other"

Objective	Answers in the category <i>Other</i> -Important	Answers in the category <i>Other</i> - Urgent
6) Improve soil structure to enhance habitat quality for soil biota and crops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soil structure that enhances habitat quality for soil biota and crops is essential for biodiversity action in cities and is often the foundation of resilient nature-based solutions. • I am not involved • Strong links to regenerative urbanisation: urban agriculture; nature-based solutions, urban biodiversity, urban food security • Soil biological activity important for nutrient use and retention, in particular in context of climate change • needed basis for agriculture • Links to the climate and biodiversity crises, imperative to act on those + to adapt to climate change 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • not active in this field • Ensure high crop levels and productivity of food for supply
7) Reduce the EU global footprint on soils	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ICLEI is working with cities around Europe on implementing circular economies to separate economic growth from resource depletion and land as well as environmental degradation, replacing the linear "produce, consume, discard" model and decrease the footprint on soils both in Europe and beyond. • NL imports Soya from south America leading to disruption of the Amazone. A global change in farming is essential. At national level a shrinkage of more than 50% cattle is a first good step. • Climate program • Think globally act locally, the soil is a local resource cannot be dragged to another country, everyone has to act in their own territory • to enable the preservation of the carbon stock capacities • Demands from NGOs • Links to topic in JPI Urban Europe / Driving Urban Transitions such as urban, sub-urban development issues beyond soil sealing • Focus of work on the NL • The Earth overshoot day for NL is May 3rd. So we need to decline our footprint 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The nitrogen excess is a strong national driver to reduce EU soil footprint on the globe. • Demands from NGOs • Significant import of phosphorus in food and animal feed crop products, results in high exported impact • focus of work on NL

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moral imperative to bring our footprint within planetary boundaries for the sake of vulnerable populations outside the EU affected by our consumption patterns and future generations 	
<p>8) Increase soil literacy in society across Member States</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge on polluted soils at universities is declining, however the soil pollution is increasing... • general public awareness of role of soils • examples of demands from local authorities, teachers... • Strong link to behaviour change which is required for sustainable urbanisation; for example, urban sprawl (green field developments) has immense environmental and therewith societal consequences. Yet, there is a lack in public awareness. • I see this as a result of all the other themes to work on • Soil literacy in the general public would be beneficial to build pressure for change, but it is not a prerequisite for policy action. Literacy in the main soil users, ie farmers and foresters, is a bigger priority. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • University managers lost interest due to lack of societal interest (which is inherent to project financing, which is max 4 years)) • Kind of vector from all the earlier themes • The general public is not the priority

If we plot the above using the scores of very important and very urgent as input, this results in the scatterplot as displayed in the figure 3-12 in chapter 3.

This shows that there is a perceived difference between the importance and the urgency of the objectives of the soil mission. Resulting in the following order of importance X urgency:

- nr 1. Objective 2 - Conserve (e.g. in forests, permanent pastures, wetlands) and increase soil organic carbon stocks.
- nr 2. Objective 1 - Reduce land degradation, including desertification and salinization
- nr 3. Objective 4 - Reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration
- nr 4. Objective 5 - Prevent erosion
- nr 5. Objective 7 - Reduce the EU global footprint on soils
- nr 6. Objective 3 - No net soil sealing and increase the re-use of urban soils for urban development.
- nr 7. Objective 8 - Increase soil literacy in society across Member States
- nr 8. Objective 6 - Improve soil structure to enhance habitat quality for soil biota and crops

Below (table 5) we have displayed the scores *per* actor group. These show some differences

Table 5: Overview of importance and Urgency of the different objectives of the soil mission per actor group (see explaining text below the table)

		Soil Mission Objectives															
		1		2		3		4		5		6		7		8	
User category		I-Q4	U-Q6	I-Q9	U-Q11	I-Q14	U-Q16	I-Q19	U-Q21	I-Q24	U-Q26	I-Q29	U-Q31	I-Q34	U-Q36	I-Q39	U-Q41
Land users/managers/owners and related organisations	N = 4	V75	V50	V75	V75	V50	V25	V75	V75	V50	V33	V75	V75	V75	V67	V50	V67
		F25	F50	F25	F25	N25	F50	F25	N25	N25	N33	SL25	SL25	N25	N33	F25	SL33
Policymakers and governmental organisations	N=9 (8)	V67	V55	V67	V44	V44	V22	V56	V67	V78	V67	V78	V67	V67	V63	V44	V50
		F33	F34	F33	F44	F44	F33	F33	F33	F11	F22	F22	F22	F22	F11	F12	F44
Researchers/ research communities	N=31	V81	V55	V75	V73	V43	V36	V68	V57	V71	V50	V61	V56	V41	V41	V34	V27
		F10	F29	F14	F15	F11	F21	F21	F29	F11	F32	F18	F24	F30	F33	F44	F42
Research funding organisations	N=11	S3	S6	S4	S4	S11	S7	S4	S4	S14	S7	S11	S4	S15	S7	S11	S12
		N6	N10	N7	N8	N25	N25	N7	N11	N4	N7	N11	N16	N11	N15	N11	N19
Private sector and industry	N=5	V40	V40	V100	V75	V25	V33	V75	V75	V50	V67	V50	V50	V75	V75	V50	V50
		F20	F20		F25	F25	F33	F25	F25	NO50	NO34	F50	F25	S25	S25	NO25	N50

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		NA20 NAA20	NA20 NAA20			NO25 NAA25	NAA34						N25			N25	
Service provider/Consultant	N=8	V88	V75	V63	V63	V63	V63	V63	V63	V38	V38	V63	V50	V63	V57	V63	V57
		F22	F25	F37	F37	F13 N25	F13 N25	F13 N13 S13	F13 N13 S13	F37	F25	F12 N13 S12	F13 N25 S13	F12 S13 NO12	F14 N14 NAA14	F25 NO12	F29 N14
Non-governmental organisation	N=9	V67	V56	V67	V44	V33	V22	V56	V68	V78	V68	V67	V67	V67	V63	V44	V50
		F23	F34 N11	F23	F44 N11	F11 N44 NAA11	F33 N33 NAA11	F33 S11	F11 N11 S11	F22	F22	F33 S11	F22 N11	N11 S11 NAA11	F12 NAA25	F44 N11	F50
Other	N=8	V100	V87	V75	V63	V50	V63	V63	V63	V88	V88	V88	V83	V57	V50	V86	V71
			F13	F25	F25 N12	F25 N25	F25 N12	F25 N12	F13 N25	F12	F12	F12	F17	F29 SL14	F17 N17 NO17	F14	F29

The numbers 1-8 correspondent with the following soil mission objectives:

1. Reduce land degradation, including desertification and salinization
2. Conserve (e.g. in forests, permanent pastures, wetlands) and increase soil organic carbon stocks.
3. No net soil sealing and increase the re-use of urban soils for urban development.
4. Reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration
5. Prevent erosion
6. Improve soil structure to enhance habitat quality for soil biota and crops
7. Reduce the EU global footprint on soils
8. Increase soil literacy in society across Member States

The numbers I-Q[X] refer to the question numbers when it comes to importance of the specific soil mission objective. The numbers U-Q[X] refer to the question numbers when it comes to urgency of the specific soil mission objective.

The following abbreviations are used in the table:

- V: Very
- F: Fairly
- N: Neutral
- SL: Slightly
- NAA: Not at All
- NA: Not Applicable
- NO: No Opinion

If we look at the needs of the respondents when it comes to the different objectives, we see that there are a lot of similarities. For example, policy, legal support, funding, knowledge is mentioned for each objective (Table 6).

Table 6: Overview of needs related to the different objectives of the soil mission per actor group. Please note that this table contains some identical responses at different places because the respondents have repeated their needs for the different objectives

Objective 1) "Reduce land degradation, including desertification and salinization"

Q8 What does your organization need in order to be able to help reaching this objective (e.g. R&I, knowledge, technology, legal support, forms of organization, etc.)?

land legal framework EU environment legal support need
knowledge good soil support policy
research funding funding develop research knowledge technology
financial support

Needs: Reduce land degradation, including desertification and salinization

- To reduce land degradation, we need:
 - 1) Soil protection and restoration requires a whole-of-government approach in relevant policies
 - 2) Strong linkages of soil management with other major goals of the EU Green Deal etc require a convergence and alignment of soil policies with the connected policy areas.
 - 3) EU endorsed key performance indicators (e.g., for NBS, Green City Accord (GCA), EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, Urban Greening Plans) should take into account soil and land degradation
 - 4) Strive for mainstreaming Land Degradation Neutrality (LDN) in territorial planning in EU via EU Goal on LDN and policy alignment + multi-level governance structures + EU standards + integration in EU commitments e.g. Green City Accord, Local Green Deals.
 - 5) Legislative mandate and budgetary capacity for local and regional governments do make decisions related to soil health and land-use without having to give way to powerful (real-estate) developers or other urban development priorities."
 - Access to collaborative research, development and demonstration, more coherent access to international markets
 - further legal support and funding mainly for brownfields and orphan sites
 - knowledge sharing, communication and dissemination
 - Adequate funding of research and innovation activities
 - EU transboundary cooperation
 - A general shift from ""Business as Usual"", with economic growth as an excuse to not take the measures needed (#MindTheGap)
 - Encourage society to be a vector of environmental and social trends"
 - Acceptance of innovation and reduce reluctance from regulatory bodies
 - Political drivers from legislators
 - "Support for first full-scale application of the combination ATES and stimulated bioremediation after several successful pilots (Hammerbakken, Copenhagen, DK; Nieuw Welgelegen, Utrecht, NL).
 - Broader: Many research topics stop after lab research. The society needs success stories to develop success in the lab to full scale implementation. An important hick up in implementation of new technologies is the lack of an integral approach in organizations as municipalities.
 - The Living lab approach (See AMS Institute NL) may overcome part of this organizational aspect. There is a need of inspiring stories like in NL the project: 'Holwerd at sea'. We tried to develop such story with AMS students for the major Amsterdam dump site 'De Volgermeer'. However, it takes longer time, although you think it will take long time "
 - Not yet an issue
 - legal support
 - Awareness raising on the topic in current policy tools
 - knowledge and technology transfer of good practices
 - JPI supports and will continue to support on soil as related to agriculture and climate change. There is a need for an enabling environment both at the policy and the research funding levels. FACCE has contributed to the initiation of and/or participated in the EJP Soil, Circasa and its successor, SMS...
 - Our organisation puts in place research addressing questions related to land use and land use change with relation to agriculture under climate change. Continued national and EU funding is needed to continue and reinforce this research. Better monitoring of soil quality and soil biodiversity is also needed
 - involve to EU programs and more modern equipment
 - interdisciplinarity of the research communities on climate change; alignment of Ministries in the ERA across climate, agriculture, environment
 - partnerships and coordination, including in mobilization of resources for research
 - Research funding
-

Needs: Reduce land degradation, including desertification and salinization

- knowledge: identification of areas concerned by desertification and salinization (where and when?), including oversea territories.
 - link the research communities on the interfaces; collaboration between ministries for research, climate and environment for better alignment of poli
 - Exchange of knowledge, experience not just on a scientific level, but from the real implementation level
 - Legislation, consciousness of politics and citizens and not to forget the large multinational industry and their stakeholders to come into action (they have large influence and huge leverage)
 - sufficient funding and good science communication
 - legal and financial support in order to allow farmers and farming cooperatives to actively work on this issue; preserving the resource most precious and essential to their activities. Without genuine support and guidance, then change cannot occur as the farming community cannot put their own livelihoods at risk and impoverish themselves.
 - legal support, a legislative approach in soil
 - legal framework
 - international collaboration
 - R&I, knowledge, legal support, funds (2X)
 - level playing field
 - R&I, continuous research funding and transfer infrastructure
 - Financial support to keep alive existing projects and to research and develop new tools to assess and fight land degradation
 - More knowledge about the pains of land degradation. The biochar coming from our plants can help against desertification by its water holding capacity Good legal framework
 - Knowledge and legal support
 - long-term (because soil processes are slow) research funding
 - R&I, applied science, bridging the gap between policy makers, land owners and scientists
 - Facilities are fine, but management is poor => lacking rand/or less competent leadership and incomplete impact pathways (...just some bullet points that are lacking in clear and SMART goals). Thus, researchers just look for projects they are interested in and try to cover their working hours with any type of project funding...
 - Research funding, R&I projects
 - R&I project possibility, financial support
 - R&D, legal support (EU and national soil policies), financial support
 - R&I, legal support (EU/National policies), financial support, citizen demand
 - Regulatory and financial action to re-orientate agricultural and land management practices
 - "Regulation
 - Funding"
 - Improve knowledge by advices who is based on adequate legislation
 - R&I funds, knowledge, recognition of the problem, cooperation with stakeholders
 - Easy to measure and cost-effective indicators. Digital platform for follow-up
 - financing of surveys, sharing knowledge with land/soil users
 - R&I, legal support
 - Research and advisory services, in particular within liming to increase crops and especially root development of plants, carbon sequestration, further biochar incorporated as a soil amendment and carbon sink.
-

Needs: Reduce land degradation, including desertification and salinization

- Funds for R&I
- From theory into practice: independent advice based on scientific results, appropriate rewarding mechanisms, both integrated in an adequate policy framework.
- R&I, legal support
- Research & Innovations, ICT technology, government support
- Funding guarantee on the long term to open position and manage field trials
- "There are several issues: the infrastructure budget must be used for infrastructure and not other beneficial goals in the infrastructure.
- Most of the stakeholders must get more awareness about the value of land and the services it can provide.
- The leading role should be at the ministry, but they are not capable to do this. The soil and water roles of the different public organizations should be clear (decentralization in the NL)."
- Scientific knowledge summarised and translated to be easily "digestible" and usable in a policy context (e.g. as done by the European Court of Auditors in their report on desertification). I don't know if more knowledge is needed, there may already be sufficient knowledge in the scientific community which just doesn't reach NGOs/policy-making circles.
- "Controlled environment agriculture:
 - -free up land toward soil restoration goals, while relocating specific crop productions into intensive food production systems indoors. Compared with conventional agriculture, CEA produces more with less
 - -be developed on brownfields and severely/irreversibly soils as it uses growing practices that are soil independent. This is crucial to secure food supply despite high share of degraded soil in the EU"
- funding for studies, sharing knowledge with land/soil users
- Legal support, awareness raising of land owners
- R&I, knowledge, technology, legal support, forms of organization
- Knowledge about indicators for soil health and about management options to manage these indicators. Especially the biological parameters
- Political focus on monitoring soil degradation and soil health
- knowledge, R&I, technology
- Will from the land and forestry owners
- Binding, comprehensive and integrated legal framework (EU and national policies and programmes, e.g. CAP) to provide incentives for farmers to practice (adopt/maintain) regenerative agriculture, including organic farming and agroecology, while disincentivising harmful forms (methods, techniques, practices) of land management; financial support for advocacy activities to further advance organic farming and agroecology in Europe, build capacity of the organic sector to engage in R&I and enable knowledge exchange, e.g. through digital knowledge reservoirs, farmer-field schools, demo farms, innovation hubs, peer-to-peer learning etc.

Objective 2) "Conserve (e.g. in forests, permanent pastures, wetlands) and increase soil organic carbon stocks".

Q13 What does your organization need in order to be able to help reaching this objective (e.g. R&I, knowledge, technology, legal support, forms of organization, etc.)?

farmers EU national research organization funding legal practices
 management soil financial policy framework knowledge
 project support legislation need research funding
 legal support technology action agriculture organic carbon stocks
 financial support

Needs: "Conserve (e.g. in forests, permanent pastures, wetlands) and increase soil organic carbon stocks".

- "The increase in urban SOC stocks has not been a focus of municipalities so far and necessary capacity is limited. To address this, cities need:
 - 1) Mobilisation of adequate financial resources and effective incentive mechanisms
 - 2) Technical knowledge: municipal capacity for SOC management and monitoring (i.e., human resources, technical knowledge and efficient tools)
 - 3) Standardised key performance indicators and monitoring protocols as well as easily accessible and affordable monitoring technology
 - 4) Evidence to support decision-making and priority setting for SOC stocks in view of many other development priorities
 - 5) Best practices in urban SOC stock restoration and management
 - legal support, funding
 - communication and dissemination
 - Raising awareness followed by political action to steer in a more sustainable direction
 - R&I, business model
 - forms of organisation
 - Awareness raising through policy tools - setting up own project
 - R&I; actualisation of legal instruments
 - not only protected areas have to do soil protection but on arable land it is much more important
 - JPI supports and will continue to support on soil as related to agriculture and climate change. There is a need for an enabling environment both at the policy and the research funding levels. FACCE has contributed to the initiation of and/or participated in the EJP Soil, Circasa and its successor, SMS...
 - JPI is involved or was instigator in a number of research actions supporting soil conservation and increasing soil C sequestration (EJP Soil, CIRCASA and its successor....). This type of research will continue in our-JPI. Policy support and research funding are required
 - legislative framework, collaboration between climate, environment and agriculture ministries
 - Open and participative research networks and access to research finance
 - "-legal support (incentive to change practices that could decrease the soil organic carbon stock). For example, more ambitious CAP, European soil directive and national soil framework.
 - -human and financial resources"
 - KIT (Knowledge, Innovation and Technology), supported by legislation and coming into action of the large industry and their stakeholders
 - funding and awareness raising
 - protecting wetlands and peatlands is important and the promotion of the use of alternative recycled resources for horticultural purposes (manufacturing growing media is needed. Increase carbon stocks in arable soils is needed in several regions in Europe to keep our soils healthy, the application of carbon farming practices including the use of organic soil improvers and organic fertilisers should be supported
 - legal framework
 - legislation to oblige
 - awareness
 - R&I, knowledge
 - R&I, continuous research funding and transfer infrastructure
 - policy choices, now contradiction between manure legislation and soil protection (OM)
-

Needs: "Conserve (e.g. in forests, permanent pastures, wetlands) and increase soil organic carbon stocks".

- Knowledge and legal support
 - long-term (because soil processes are slow) research funding
 - financial support
 - ...well designed R&D strategy; reliable and consistent leadership as well as reliable HR policy supporting scientists instead of building up bureaucratic administration consuming between 10 to 20 % of the scientist working time...
 - R&I dedicated projects
 - National R&I project possibility, financial support
 - legal support (EU and national soil policies), financial support, knowledge
 - R&I, legal support (EU/National policies), financial support, farmers demand
 - Regulatory action (CAP requirements) or financial incentives to agriculture
 - "Regulation
 - Funding"
 - Improving promotion of project results and implementing them in area of soil protection
 - R&I funds, knowledge, recognition of the problem, cooperation with stakeholders
 - Cost-effective and accurate MRV system
 - financing of surveys, sharing knowledge with land/soil users
 - dedicated research programmes that put in place a strategy and action plans, fund activities to reach the goal
 - Financial and professional (scientific) support from our authorities and industrial partners (supplying agricultural customers)
 - Improved monitoring + knowledge transfer to farmers
 - legal support, cooperation between farmers and other institutions
 - From theory into practice: independent advice based on scientific results, appropriate rewarding mechanisms both supported by an adequate policy framework
 - R&I, legal support, funding
 - Database and ICT tools, research & innovations
 - I think several technical options exist to increase soil carbon but some legal support are needed
 - My organization works for the ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management and other stakeholders. We are an executive organization between policy and practice. Our organization has the network and knowledge to a key player. But the shortage of money from the Ministry is the problem.
 - Scientific knowledge being brought to policy circles. Research demonstrating the multiple co-benefits (and estimating the economic benefits). Better knowledge extension to farmers to convince of the need and benefits of action.
 - "We need an integrated soil management strategy that identifies severely or irreversibly polluted soils, so as to make full use of them with CEA towards Food Security.
 - More practically, we want to put in place a pilot project relocating specific crops in CEA, and assess the restoration performance of former farmed soil, and carbon footprint of CEA. We need more data as to how in some circumstances, CEA can give nature the change to repair itself and also have more performing restoration practices, due to no more farming, while preserving food security"
 - funding for studies, sharing knowledge with land/soil users
 - Financial support to land-owners and knowledge on practices and measures of soil conservation
 - R&I, knowledge, technology, legal support, forms of organization
 - Better information about 'behaviour' of different pools of organic matter and organic inputs in the soil
-

Needs: "Conserve (e.g. in forests, permanent pastures, wetlands) and increase soil organic carbon stocks".

- It is already a focal objective
- knowledge, technology, R&I
- Stronger legislation
- Legal framework (EU and national policies and programmes, e.g. CAP) to provide incentives for farmers who maintain and/or increase soil carbon by practicing sustainable agriculture (such as organic farming and agroecology) while disincentivising practices that deplete soil carbon stocks; financial support for advocacy activities to further advance organic farming and agroecology in Europe, build capacity of the organic sector to engage in R&I and enable knowledge exchange amongst all farmers in Europe and beyond, e.g. through digital knowledge reservoirs, farmer-field schools, demo farms, innovation hubs, peer-to-peer learning etc.

Objective 3) "No net soil sealing and increase the re-use of urban soils for urban development"

Q18 What does your organization need in order to be able to help reaching this objective (e.g. R&I, knowledge, technology, legal support, forms of organization, etc.)?

Needs: "No net soil sealing and increase the re-use of urban soils for urban development"

- " Adequate frameworks to account for the ecological impacts of soil sealing and mitigation actions (natural capital accounting, "eco budgeting Ökokonto")
 - Effective incentive programmes that local and regional governments can use and offer to urban actors to prevent soil sealing
 - Policies that encourage municipalities to commit to goals for soil sealing. For example, the goal of land degradation neutrality could be made operational for local and regional governments.
 - Capacity building to scale up adequate replacement options for soil sealing (e.g., nature-based solutions, permeable surfaces, etc.)
 - "stricter regulations and more funding
 - awareness raising
 - mobilisation of politics and politicians "
 - communication and dissemination
 - " - Adequate funding of research and innovation activities
 - Acceptance of innovation and reduce reluctance from regulatory bodies
 - - Political drivers from legislators
 - - EU transboundary cooperation
 - - A general shift from ""Business As Usual"", with economic growth as an excuse to not take the measures needed (#MindTheGap)
 - - Encourage society to be a vector of environmental and social trends"
 - " - Adequate funding of research and innovation activities
 - - Acceptance of innovation and reduce reluctance from regulatory bodies
 - - "Stimulation of Living labs.
 - development of Societal Business cases in which 'green inclusive' measures are not hindered by bureaucracy"
 - R&I
-

Needs: "No net soil sealing and increase the re-use of urban soils for urban development"

- legal support
 - Guidelines for dehardening - targets for dehardening - recycling land
 - legal support, economic instruments
 - integrated planning
 - This area is somewhat marginal for FACCE-JPI although we do consider urban agriculture
 - Open and transparent platforms to share knowledge and support to explore existing successful stories
 - Research funding
 - "-legal support (European Soil Directive, national Soil framework).
 - - human and financial resources."
 - KIT, legislation and pro-active approach of large industry (supported by their stakeholders)
 - funding
 - legal support on green public procurement
 - change in the EU agricultural policy, which determinates and deforms national policies and how the actors behave
 - toolbox
 - R&I, knowledge
 - Financial resources and data
 - Knowledge and legal support
 - none
 - ...a strategy that addresses sealing and urban soils.
 - R&I dedicated projects
 - Technology, legal support
 - R&I
 - R&I, citizen demand
 - Regulation
 - nothing
 - legal support
 - soil quality should be considered as an essential factor in the spatial planning processes
 - Support to actions preventing soils from sealing by human construction work: living und business estates, roads etc.
 - Legal basis, knowledge on soil quality after de-sealing urban soils,...
 - An adequate policy framework safeguarding rural areas
 - Legal support from the ministry,
 - Legal support is the key I think to stop urbanization. Several aspects can be modified. For instance, we reduce taxes for people who invest in existing building to install a new shop and increase taxes for those who prefer to build new installations.
 - Budget from the government to build awareness and to show good practical instruments and demonstrate these in lighthouses
 - This is not something we are working on directly (as we do not work on urban planning or soil policy as such), although we believe it is a very important matter
-

Needs: "No net soil sealing and increase the re-use of urban soils for urban development"

- CEA takes places in urban and peri-urban environments mostly so as to create local food supply chains. We need to map out urban environments to see where the opportunities are and allow for more food security, resilience, sustainability and economic growth in urban environments. CEA can take place on very to irreversibly degraded soil due to soil-independent growing practices
- sharing knowledge with land/soil users
- Funding to support implementation of green measures in cities, legal support.
- Activity / Objective out of reach
- no interest
- Legal support (urban planning policies)

Objective 4) Reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration

Q23 What does your organization need in order to be able to help reaching this objective (e.g. R&I, knowledge, technology, legal support, forms of organization, etc.)?

EU research funding Soil pollution National policy Adequate need
 framework knowledge technology soil legal support
 funding reduce Support pollution land pollute soils financial support
 water

Needs: Reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration

- "Substantial capacity building for cities. This includes:
 - - Adequate financial resources and investments in the remediation of polluted sites.
 - - Effective toolkit to build technical capabilities for municipal staff.
 - - Urban, landscape and architecture planning expertise to consider and reduce soil sealing
 - "targeted funding
 - reducing barriers and psychological fears"
 - communication and dissemination
 - " - Adequate funding of research and innovation activities
 - - Acceptance of innovation and reduce reluctance from regulatory bodies
 - - Political drivers from legislators
 - - EU transboundary cooperation
 - - A general shift from ""Business as Usual"", with economic growth as an excuse to not take the measures needed (#MindTheGap)
 - - Encourage society to be a vector of environmental and social trends"
 - Support from the National government to transfer IBC locations to finite measure in which the groundwater is safe for human consumption as intake for drinking water preparation.
 - Make New programmatic combinations
 - technology; training
 - Core business
 - legal support; R&I, support to stakeholders
 - knowledge and technology transfer
-

Needs: Reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration

- FACCE-JPI supports and will continue to support on soil as related to agriculture and climate change. There is a need for an enabling environment both at the policy and the research funding levels. FACCE has contributed to the initiation of and/or participated in the EJP Soil, Circasa and its successor, SMS... FACCE has collaborated with Water JPI to fund projects on water and soil pollution
 - FACCE-JPI has and will continue to support research on soil and water pollution together with the Water JPI through the funding of research projects.
 - Research funding
 - "-organization in charge of orphaned contaminated site management, human and financial resources oriented on security, increasing means could allow to fully restore polluted sites and develop prevention actions.
 - -legal support to harmonize prevention of soil pollution, integrative legal framework to prevent soil pollution and define a national soil quality target. European Soil Directive."
 - KIT, EU soil strategy embed in every EU country, legislation and pro-active approach industry and their stakeholders
 - funding
 - we call for an EU Soil protection framework
 - change of the EU agricultural policy
 - toolbox with solutions and more insight
 - R&I, knowledge
 - R&I, continuous research funding and transfer infrastructure
 - Detailed soil data
 - We need better legislative framework around biosolids pyrolysis which eliminates soil pollution from spreading sewage sludge
 - Knowledge and legal support
 - R&I, financial support
 - R&I
 - National R&I project possibility, financial support, technology, legal support.
 - R&I, financial support, citizen demand
 - Implementation of Nitrates Directive, and implications of EU Water Framework Directive implications for agriculture
 - Regulation
 - Technology
 - Transfer of knowledge
 - R&I funds, knowledge,
 - share knowledge with land/soil users
 - dedicated programmes
 - Financial support to our R&D projects to highlight and develop technology and knowledge, to avoid and to remediate this soil pollution, legislative actions from the authorities to prevent this deterioration.
 - Funds for R&I, as well as for Dissemination of knowledge
 - From theory into practice: independent advice based on scientific results, appropriate rewarding mechanisms, both supported by an adequate policy framework
 - funding
 - Support monitoring activities by the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development
-

Needs: Reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration

- Some funding for research is needed here. In particular how pollutants will affect human health or ecosystem health in the context of global change is not well known.
- Because of the decentralization of soil tasks, we need to work on capacity building. There for we need budget from the government. Practical instruments to demonstrate how contaminated land can be controlled/managed or remediated.
- Independent research being carried out and its findings brought to policy circles. Awareness raising among farmers to convince of the need to act.
- FarmTech Society fully endorses the goals of the Green Deal. But we believe that the equation will reduce the land available for farming while there is need for food security. CEA bridges this gap by freeing up former farmland for restoration while relocating food production in intensive indoor systems that are optimized for resource-efficiency, nutrient usage, and land use
- funding for studies, sharing knowledge with land/soil users
- new cost-effective technologies in treating polluted soils and funding to implement the action.
- R&I, knowledge, technology, legal support, forms of organization
- knowledge, technology, R&I, legal support
- only legislation can force stakeholders to improve the situation
- Binding, comprehensive and integrated legal framework (EU and national policies and programmes, e.g. CAP) to provide incentives for farmers to practice (adopt/maintain) sustainable agricultural methods that foster restoration/regeneration rather than polluting soils, such as organic farming and agroecology, while disincentivising harmful methods like heavy machines, chemical pesticides and nitrogen fertilisers that lead to compaction and pollution of soils; financial support for advocacy activities to further advance organic farming and agroecology in European and enable knowledge exchange among all farmers, e.g. through digital knowledge reservoirs, farmer-field schools, demo farms, innovation hubs, peer-to-peer learning etc.

Objective 5: Prevent erosion

Q28 What does your organization need in order to be able to help reaching this objective (e.g. R&I, knowledge, technology, legal support, forms of organization, etc.)?

Needs: prevent erosion

- See answer to question #23.
 - "awareness raising
 - funding and supporting of measures, agricultural practices"
 - communication and dissemination
 - " - Adequate funding of research and innovation activities
 - - Acceptance of innovation and reduce reluctance from regulatory bodies
 - - Political drivers from legislators
 - - EU transboundary cooperation
 - - A general shift from ""Business As Usual"", with economic growth as an excuse to not take the measures needed (#MindTheGap)
 - - Encourage society to be a vector of environmental and social trends"
 - --Pilot project with nature based solutions
-

● **Needs: prevent erosion**

- R&I, legal support
 - support to manage river basin integrated way and cooperation with farmers, land users.
 - FACCE-JPI supports and will continue to support on soil as related to agriculture and climate change. There is a need for an enabling environment both at the policy and the research funding levels. FACCE has contributed to the initiation of and/or participated in the EJP Soil, Circasa and its successor, SMS... FACCE-JPI is actively contributing to the future partnership on Agroecology LLs and RIs which aims, among other things, to protect soil
 - FACCE-JPI has and will continue to support research on sustainable agriculture which reduces soil erosion
 - Research funding
 - "- human and financial resources, organization not able to cover these actions meanwhile our organization is in charge of soil protection
 - - knowledge: identification of areas concerned
 - - legal support: national soil framework and European Soil Directive"
 - EU Soil strategy embedded in every country, balance strategies with agricultural and nature sectors
 - funding, awareness raising
 - support of carbon farming practices
 - change in the EU agricultural policy, legal support, finances
 - legal support at local or regional scale
 - dialog with & awareness at land owners and authorities
 - R&I, continuous research funding and transfer infrastructure
 - Detailed soil data
 - Legal support
 - R&I
 - National R&I project possibility, financial support, legal support
 - more accurate soil data and soil maps
 - R&I, legal support (EU/National policies), financial support
 - Regulatory and financial action towards farming, including via EU Water Framework Directive quality objectives and in the CAP
 - "Regulation
 - Funding"
 - Continue with supporting
 - nothing
 - Continuous funding for working with farmers to test small and larger improvements to their management and machinery to prevent erosion. We have had an interesting project, but then the funding ends and the work with farmers cannot be continued anymore. These matters need continuous action and attention.
 - sharing knowledge with land/soil users
 - dedicated programmes
 - Research and development projects, participating in European and Global soil research organisations (IUSS, and the Norwegian and the British Soil Science Society.
 - technology implementation
 - From theory into practice: independent advice based on scientific results, appropriate rewarding mechanisms, both supported by an adequate policy framework
-

• **Needs: prevent erosion**

- R&I, technology, funding
- Legal support from the Ministry
- Some technical solutions exist already to reduce erosion, they must be promoted through legal support
- Hardly any problem
- Detailed knowledge (eg of the hotspots and drivers of erosions) bring brought to policy circles
- Soil health is critical to adapting and mitigating climate change. As said before, to unlock CEA's potential with regards to integrated management we need a mapping out of urban, and peri-urban soils as well as assistance in launching pilot projects
- funding for studies, sharing knowledge with land/soil users
- legal support
- R&I, knowledge, technology, legal support, forms of organization
- R&I, knowledge, technology
- not concerned
- Legal framework (EU and national policies and programmes, e.g. CAP) to provide incentives (subsidies etc.) for farmers to practice (adopt/maintain) sustainable forms of agriculture that prevent erosion, such as organic farming and agroecology, while disincentivising harmful forms (methods, techniques, practices) of land management; financial support for advocacy activities to further advance organic farming and agroecology in Europe and enable awareness raising and knowledge exchange among all farmers, land owners and managers, e.g. through digital knowledge reservoirs, farmer-field schools, demo farms, innovation hubs, peer-to-peer learning etc.

Objective 6) Improve soil structure to enhance habitat quality for soil biota and crops

Q33 What does your organization need in order to be able to help reaching this objective (e.g. R&I, knowledge, technology, legal support, forms of organization, etc.)?

financial support policy improves biochar legal support
 framework knowledge agriculture soil practices funding
 land research research funding farmers supporting

Needs: Improve soil structure to enhance habitat quality for soil biota and crops

- See answer to question #23.
 - as previous answer
 - "awareness raising
 - funding and supporting measures"
 - communication and dissemination
 - Information/data about compaction etc
 - Raising awareness
 - R&I
 - dissemination of knowledge
 - FACCE-JPI supports and will continue to support on soil as related to agriculture and climate change. There is a need for an enabling environment both at the policy and the research funding levels. FACCE has contributed to the initiation of and/or participated in the EJP Soil, Circasa and its successor, SMS...
 - FACCE-JPI has and will continue to support research on sustainable and resilient agriculture for providing European food security. Research funding
-

Needs: Improve soil structure to enhance habitat quality for soil biota and crops

- "- human and financial resources, organization not able to cover these actions meanwhile our organization is in charge of soil protection
 - - knowledge: identification of areas concerned
 - - legal support: national soil framework and European Soil Directive"
 - More awareness of the importance of Soil As Natural Capital by all stakeholders (policy - industry - citizens). Align with agriculture and nature sector (from the perspective of environmental and infrastructure approach)
 - funding and awareness raising
 - EU soil protection framework and linkages to other EU initiatives Farm to Fork CAP reform
 - responsibilities to act
 - pilot areas
 - no needs
 - R&I, knowledge
 - R&I, continuous research funding and transfer infrastructure
 - Crop detailed data to develop models able to evaluate best practices
 - Biochar improves soil habitat for microorganisms and improves soil conditions for crops
 - We need legislative support to favour use of biosolids and manure biochar for soil applications and more research into using well defined types of biochar and biochar manufacturing processes (in our case 650 C for 20 min) for improving biota and crop yields.
 - knowledge, funding for research
 - Legal support
 - financial support (expensive lab measurements)
 - R&I
 - National R&I project possibility, financial support, legal support
 - R&I
 - R&I, legal support (EU/National policies), financial support
 - "Regulation
 - Funding"
 - all of them
 - R&I funds, knowledge, cooperation with stakeholders
 - continuous R&I and work with farmers. Cost effective and accurate indicators (eg based on remote sensing) to detect problems with soil structure and compaction
 - share knowledge with land/soil users
 - no expertise
 - Running research and promoting remedial measures in agriculture: liming, recycling of residual materials from society as plant nutrients and organic substances, promoting increased biological life in soils.
 - Improved monitoring, more knowledge on the effect of current practices on soil life, knowledge transfer to farmers...
 - Funds for R&I, and for Dissemination of knowledge, as well as for cooperative research
 - From theory into practice: independent advice based on scientific results, appropriate rewarding mechanisms, both supported by an adequate policy framework
 - funding
-

Needs: Improve soil structure to enhance habitat quality for soil biota and crops

- Soil Monitoring and guidelines for farmers
- Generally, increasing soil organic carbon and reducing soil pollution have positive effect on soil biodiversity, more funding for research to better understand the mechanism must be allocated. Moreover, the legal support to increase soil carbon and reduce erosion might also cover some biodiversity aspects
- Operational instruments, budget and a reduction of the total nitrogen deposition on nature areas. Also in agricultural land the benefits of biodiversity are clear.
- knowledge brought to policy-makers
- Same as previous replies
- sharing knowledge with land/soil users
- Knowledge and financial support to implement the good practices
- R&I, knowledge, technology, legal support, forms of organization
- R&I, knowledge, technology
- New technologies can help improving the situation
- Binding, comprehensive and integrated legal framework (EU and national policies and programmes, e.g. CAP) to provide incentives for farmers to practice (adopt/maintain) regenerative agricultural practices that enhance soil structure, including organic farming and agroecology, while disincentivising harmful forms of land management; financial support for advocacy activities to further advance organic farming and agroecology in Europe and enable awareness raising and knowledge exchange among farmers, e.g. through digital knowledge reservoirs, farmer-field schools, demo farms, innovation hubs, peer-to-peer learning etc.

Objective 7) Reduce the EU global footprint on soils

Q38 What does your organization need in order to be able to help reaching this objective (e.g. R&I, knowledge, technology, legal support, forms of organization, etc.)?

international programmes awareness carbon EU climate framework land
 knowledge emissions SOIL set need footprint policy actions
 legal support financial support supports

Needs: Reduce the EU global footprint on soils

- Capacity building in the areas of R&I, knowledge and technology is needed for cities to identify pathways towards developing circular economies.
 - "legislation
 - funding
 - enhancing attractivity for measures"
 - communication and dissemination
 - Knowles and integrated vision
 - Awareness raising - set up indicators - set up holistic framework
 - Soil Framework Directive
 - JPI supports and will continue to support on soil as related to agriculture and climate change. There is a need for an enabling environment both at the policy and the research funding levels. Our JPI has contributed to the initiation of and/or participated in the EJP Soil, Circasa and its successor, SMS...
 - Research funding
 - "- human and financial resources
 - - knowledge: methodologies to assess, international standardization
-

Needs: Reduce the EU global footprint on soils

- - legal support at an international level, WTO"
 - We operate in a European context, so our aim is also to reduce the EU global footprint on Soils. There's a need for an overall approach (policy - industry - citizens).
 - more knowledge
 - soil framework, carbon removal and certification schemes
 - action oriented and intersectoral coordinated EU policy, in many aspects the EU policies are in contradiction
 - "international collaboration"
 - awareness & sense of urgency
 - R&I, knowledge
 - Knowledge
 - Better quantification of GHG emissions from manure and sewage sludge when stored and when spread on farmland can help us quantify climate savings when drying and pyrolyzing wet biomasses
 - Spreading of manure and biosolids on farmland has a large climate gas emission. We can eliminate emissions and on top store carbon in the ground via biochar. More research is need to quantify current emissions precisely to be able to calculate the precise benefits of converting the biomass to biochar for soil application
 - Legal support
 - R&I, knowledge
 - ...global footprint of what exactly? Soil degradation is a complex issue; I am convinced that a footprint system can be developed and set up, but what is the baseline (SOC, erosion, soil microbiome, infiltration, etc.)?
 - R&I
 - National and international R&I project possibility, financial support, legal support
 - R&I, knowledge
 - R&I, legal support (EU/National policies), financial support, citizen awareness/demand
 - Border Taxes on Carbon should be extended to nutrients (P, N)
 - Regulation
 - Use of results from R&I
 - nothing
 - sharing knowledge with land/soil users
 - dedicated programmes for implementation
 - R&D, advisory actions to reduce this deterioration of the soils we live from.
 - Technology
 - From theory into practice: independent advice based on scientific results, appropriate rewarding mechanisms, both supported by an adequate policy framework
 - funding
 - Not noted
 - Practical information to build awareness at the general public and other stakeholders. Budget from the government to execute such a program.
 - More and easily accessible data about our land footprint outside the EU, what is driving it (what is that land being used for), how is it affecting local populations in those countries...
 - By relocating certain food production indoors (greenhouses to vertical farms) CEA can greatly lessen farming's footprint on soils. Not only do we need to get recognized for this argument but also as a sustainable production method
-

Needs: Reduce the EU global footprint on soils

complementary to conventional and organic farming. CEA has the potential to speed up restoration of soils, while preserving food security for the EU

- Support to be involved in global actions
 - R&I, knowledge, technology, legal support, forms of organization
 - i am not sure this can be measured
 - Legal framework (EU and national policies and programmes, e.g. CAP, trade regulations/agreements) to provide incentives for European farmers to practice sustainable agriculture, including organic farming and agroecology, while prohibiting imports leading to land degradation and deforestation; financial support to further advance organic farming and agroecology in Europe and beyond through advocacy and enabling knowledge exchange
-

Objective 8) Increase soil literacy in society across Member States

Q43 What does your organization need in order to be able to help reaching this objective (e.g. R&I, knowledge, technology, legal support, forms of organization, etc.)?

stakeholders importance soil funding etc knowledge industry
 communication policy SOIL EU support awareness
 need climate change forms organization

Needs: Increase soil literacy in society across Member States

- Communication, education and public awareness raising initiatives should highlight the underestimated importance of soils and their functions to drive soil conservation and restoration action with concrete messages and options for action for the diversity of stakeholders (e.g. from developers, to local policy-makers, to planners and architects as well as local CSOs).
 - "projects
 - reports
 - support"
 - communication and dissemination
 - "Awareness of the topic. Integration into the Energy transition.
 - The environmental engineers dealing with soil contamination are between 55 and 65 years old. In 10 years lot of knowledge will leave the societal memory."
 - Soil + Land stewardship approach
 - events on world soil day, lectures, R&I, stakeholder involvement
 - dissemination materials, support for dissemination
 - Our JPI supports and will continue to support on soil as related to agriculture and climate change. There is a need for an enabling environment both at the policy and the research funding levels. Our JPI has contributed to the initiation of and/or participated in the EJP Soil, Circasa and its successor, SMS... Our JPI is also contributing to a new proposal to increase soil literacy in the context of the soil mission
 - collaboration between the soil and climate research communities towards joint communication
 - forms of organization
 - "- human and financial resources
 - - knowledge transfer
 - - legal support: a national and integrated policy to enhance soil literacy in society (education, communication, training, awareness, participative science and observatories...)"
 - It all starts with insight/ understanding of the importance of a healthy soil. There's a need of a long-term vision. There is a must of a wholeheartedly support by the politicians (policy > legislation > enforcement) as well as a pro-active
-

Needs: Increase soil literacy in society across Member States

industry. A dialogue is vital in order to change the ESG course of companies (dialogue between industry and politicians and between industry and their stakeholders).

- harmonizing soil data and access to data
 - A genuine education of the importance of soil and their properties at primary, secondary, and university levels in all EU member states. The understanding of the role of soil in the future of adapting and mitigating climate change is not adequately provided, and as a result can be the cause of regular misunderstanding and propaganda. While the role of soil has been lauded only recently as one of the main saviours from climate change; there is still a large-scale miss appreciation for the importance of this natural resource.
 - EU wide awareness raising campaigns for soil
 - societal demand
 - international collaboration
 - no needs
 - R&I, knowledge
 - Resources to keep alive existing projects and to create targeted activities
 - Would also be great for us to understand in more detail how our biochar can help soil improvement - what are all the problems soils in Europe have and where do what problems need to be addressed?
 - Forms of organization
 - Not clear what the citizen should be aware of; soil classification and such bring things like soil chemistry, biology, physics etc. may not attract. Involve social scientist to assess how to reach them and what to disseminate by explaining the why is affect their life and welfare => thus, a matter of communication (communication experts are needed...).
 - R&I
 - National project possibility
 - communication tools
 - Communication tools and skills
 - "Regulation
 - Funding"
 - Use of knowledge, R&I
 - Cooperation with stakeholders, funds
 - sharing knowledge with land/soil users on how soils and humanity depend on each other
 - Improve knowledge level of soil health and food productivity conditions throughout whole society.
 - forms of organization, change/exchange technology knowledge
 - A comprehensive story
 - forms of organization
 - Working seminar. media PR
 - Some funding to improve the communication between the research agencies/university, etc and the general public is key.
 - **PraCTICAL FACTSHEETS AND ORGANIZATION TO EXECUTE SUCH A PROGRAM**
 - sharing knowledge with land/soil users
 - Soil literacy is important cause it highlights the fact that we need non-soil-based practices to complement soil restoration within the EU—which is what CEA can do. If we follow the provisions of the EU Green Deal soils are at the center of many strategies and there might be enough of it. We must reconsider the fabric between rural and urban areas, by means of urban agriculture and CEA, to lessen the pressure on rural land and see the opportunities of urban areas. Even if the latter are small in scale, CEA can make great use of it with intensive crop production practices
-

Needs: Increase soil literacy in society across Member States

- Tools and funding to implement educational activities.
 - knowledge, legal support, forms of organization
 - not directly concerned
 - Financial support for advocacy and communication activities to raise awareness among policy makers, farmers, industry and civil society/citizens in general of the importance of soil and sustainable soil management for food, environmental services etc. through (social) media, knowledge platforms, events, workshops, personal meetings etc.
-

Although we indicated also based on previous projects that there are significant differences between the different actor groups, there does not seem to be a large difference when it comes to the needs, at least not based on this survey. As described in the methodological section there can be different reasons why this is the case.

Involvement

Finally, we asked the stakeholders *What level of engagement would you desire for your organisation when it comes to reaching the EU mission objectives on soil health and food?*

Figure 1: What level of engagement would you desire for your organisation when it comes to reaching the EU mission objectives on soil health and food?

To make sure that there was no bias in these answers based on the diversity in actor groups, we also present the answers *per actor group* in the table below. This shows that there are some differences, especially when it comes to the actor group of private sector and industry we can see that 100% of the (4) respondents want to collaborate with the EU on reaching the EU mission objectives on soil health and food.

Table 7: Level of involvement for reaching the EU mission objectives on soil health and food of the respondent’s organisations per actor group

Actor group	n*	Our organisation (% of n)				
		does not want to be engaged	wants to be informed	wants to be consulted	wants to be involved	wants to collaborate with the EU
Land users/managers/owners and related organisations	4			25	25	50
Policymakers and governmental organisations	9				40	60
Researchers/ research communities	27		4	7	26	63
Research funding organisations	8			13	25	62
Private sector and industry	4					100
Service provider/Consultant	8				44	55
Non-governmental organisation	9				40	60
Other	7			14	29	57

* Please note that respondents had the option to tick more than one actor group

Some of the reasons for the given scoring for collaboration are given below:

- "Soils and land play a central role in sustainable urban developments for the reasons stated above. Org X is committed to provide the urban perspective for a successful development and implementation of soil-related policies across European landscapes".
- As part of the EU Soil Mission, it is essential to propose a continuum on soils, ranging from agricultural soils to forest, wetland, urban, etc. soils, for more efficient soil preservation. Better trans-European cooperation on soil databases, soil monitoring, soil remediation is required to harmonize good practice and increase the availability of scientifically robust data on soil quality. Such data are essential for developing decision making tools, prediction models in order to reach efficient soil restoration and land management options. It is also essential to address the quality of urban soils. These soils should be managed in line with the objectives of the Circular Economy Action Plan to promote, e.g., the reuse of excavated urban soils, the refunctionalization of soils (degraded or not) or the creation of technosoils, while addressing risks regarding environmental and/or health impacts. Such recycling principles, which also apply to brownfields in urban and suburban areas, are essential in order to reduce the pressure on more pristine soils, which could be used for e.g. agricultural purposes. For the application of circular economy principles to soils, it is necessary to identify soil quality criteria considering soil multifunctionalities and ecosystem services for improved land management (in order to reach net land take, improved citizens well-being, mitigation climate change...)
- through integration of water policy and soil policy
- As a mission-driven organisation, our purpose is to enable farmers to use farming methods that increase soil health. We are already assisting the EU in measuring and incentivising this evolution as part of our core business. We would be happy to do more of it!
- Ensuring our knowledge and tools (models etc) are used in the context of the research and knowledge transfer efforts to policy makers and stakeholders as part of a broad European efforts to protect and restore our soils, including their biodiversity.
- we are missing a comprehensive legislative approach on soil health and protection since several years. There is a need for an integrated approach on soil protection with regard to circular economy and climate change.
- the ministry is responsible for regional development policy which is integrative policy and creates a base for integrated approach, but is confronted with the responsibilities of the ministry of agriculture and EU agricultural and other policies, not in every case "soil friendly"
- International collaboration in establishing pilot areas. Soil quality affects environmental health and human health.
- We want to engage on how biochar from biomasses can be applied to/in soil, what problems should we help to solve where, etc
- We see a very strong link to our thematic priority 'Circular Urban Regenerative Economies (CURE)'. The topics of CURE link to many of the objectives presented by the Soil Mission. We would be very interested in contributing to the objectives and assessing thematic links further to eventually bring together efforts.
- Soil data exchange. Sharing good practices in the management and protection of soil resources, including IoT, AI, ML
- As a stakeholder, we actively participate in policy discussions at the European and national level (through our member organisations) and programmes funded by Europe and the Member States on soil issues.
- Agriculture and forestry contractors implement work contracted by farmers and forestry owners, so the work performs depends very much own what our customers are asking. We can implement it if they wish!

Asking further on what the soil objectives means for the organisation

To get more insight in the meaning of the soil mission for organisations of the different actor groups we also asked the respondents the following questions:

Question 46: If the EU Soil Missions objectives would be reached overnight, how would this positively affect your own organization?

Question 47: If the EU Soil Missions objectives would be reached overnight, how would this negatively affect your own organization?

For the respondents this turned out a difficult question to answer. 7 respondents answered Q46 and 5 respondents answered Q47. The majority pointed out that they did not know the answer. Below are the other answers

Q46:

- Land degradation would be minimal and even more localized. Greenhouse gases emission and carbon loss from agricultural lands will be decreased, because the most vulnerable areas (peatlands, organic soils) will be under permanent plant cover.
- It would fulfil the main goals of our organization - a healthier population, enough quality and safe food

Q47:

- Less Jobs
- Considering in our country there is a great share of peat soils and organic soils in agricultural land a significant area is under (permanent) grasslands. At the same time pressure on North-Europe to grow crops is increased due to climate change.

Next, we asked: *How would you estimate the relationship between the previously mentioned positive and negative effects? (would the positive effects outweigh the negative effects, or vice versa?)* this gave a response of 5 of which the majority pointed out that they could not answer the question.

Finally, we asked what could be done to maximize the positive effects (Q49) and minimize the negative effects (Q50)

When it came to maximizing the positive effects the respondents pointed out that:

- *Continuous dialogue between the different actors and between the different disciplines and data sharing*
- *Soil protection and restoration requires a whole-of-government approach in relevant policies Strong linkages of soil management with other major goals of the EU Green Deal etc require a convergence and alignment of soil policies with the connected policy areas. EU endorsed key performance indicators (e.g., for NBS, Green City Accord (GCA), EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, Urban Greening Plans) should take into account soil and land degradation. Strive for mainstreaming Land Degradation Neutrality (LDN) in territorial planning in EU via EU Goal on LDN and policy alignment + multi-level governance structures + EU standards + integration in EU commitments e.g. GCA, Local Green Deals"*
- *"EU soil objectives are drivers for soils if they reached. They should increase common soil interest and integrated approach among soil stakeholders,*
- *Promote Human and Financial resources for R&D activities*
- *This shall provide additional resources to our organization and enhanced soil R&D aims."*
- *As a public organisation, EU soil Missions objectives may significantly increase soil activities which will be performed by laboratories, private companies, contractors. Public bodies may require more help for the public organization for technical advice without additional resources.*
- *"Develop a clearer vision upon circular economy.*
- *Part of this can be: a stop on the release of new chemicals. A second step needs to be a proof that chemicals are part of the short term (10 year) 'biological cycle'.*
- *This is much more intelligent than the design of 'for-ever' chemicals"*
- *Involvement of stakeholders (NGOs as well as farmers [associations])*
- *transfers of relevant information*

- *If the objectives were reached overnight, we could invest research funding on other pressing issues*
- *substantial learning about the accomplishment of the Missions (role of legislation, stakeholders, all actors)*
- *Joint projects, open access networks to share knowledge and data, and built upon existing integrated modelling efforts (in particular bottom up)*
- *Improving research and knowledge on Soil health and food for future generation*
- *The integration of the ambitious targets from EU Soil Mission Board in EU policies could help Member States to engage more ambitious strategies and actions on Soil. This could lead to increase and consolidate human and financial resources dedicated to Soil for our organization.*
- *A bold move by implementing an ambitious EU Soil Strategy on short term*
- *Enforce the knowledge dissemination and outreach. better ways to bring the developed knowledge to the end-users is one element that needs to be improved next to developing new knowledge that is needed*
- *Change in EU agricultural policy is crucial. The support of the development of rural areas should be not focused on direct payments to the farmer, but on environmental dimension of soil management and agricultural production, distribution and consumption and integrated development of rural areas harmonizing agriculture and different ecosystem services in these areas*
- *uniform objectives; integral approach, i.e. industry/urban/biodiversity & agriculture*
- *reconsider EU subsidy policy, reduce biofuels*
- *Soil threats and benefits should be communicated much more, both to a specialist audience but also to the broader public*
- *strengthen farmers' opportunities to select practices that promote soil health using incentives (for the good practices) AND disincentives (for the bad practices).*
- *communication between stakeholders*
- *Intensified implementation of new technologies and digitalization of the collected field soil information for efficient use.*
- *...Impossible over night as we talk about behavioural changes => develop a theory of change => helps to assess how to proceed (...what and for whom, when what and why...).*
- *Increased funding for national projects and substantial quota for Eastern EU countries in international projects related to the EU Soil Mission objectives.*
- *more data on soils available and a greater demand for information which would make it possible to release financial and human resources to strengthen our transfer and communication action*
- *Recruit new staff - develop new devices (soil app, web platforms) to be able transfer / inform / increase access to soil data / soil information*
- *Collaborate with private actors like us, who are already working in the same direction. Rather than reinventing the wheel, use private enterprise to further your goals*
- *Soil legislation o EU level*
- *There might be an agreement that food security and EU Soil Mission goals would be reached at the same time e.g. to compromise in which areas to focus on food production or restoring degraded land.*
- *More professional endeavour to achieve results to ensure our soils, more research to develop further actions and technologies, awareness of the need of soil health improvements.*
- *Funds for allow experienced professionals to disseminate the objectives and the ways to accomplish the objectives*
- *Coordination, harmonisation of the different fora dealing with the issue at European, National and Regional level.*
- *The development of economically, socially and environmentally sustainable, responsible and resilient agriculture*
- *We expect the governmental support and general awareness of stakeholders*
- *Improve communication, reduce administrative work to spend time of concrete aspects.*
- *"Facilitate budget and calls to exchange international knowledge in the Horizon program 2021-2027.*
- *A strict biodiversity, climate and soil EU policy.*
- *The challenges we face are too big to find the solutions as a member state itself. We need to cooperate international.*
- *Our organisations wouldn't draw benefits from reaching the Soil Mission's objectives as our interest in them stems from our objective to build a better future where people and nature thrive together, in the public interest, not for our own gain.*

- *"- recognize CEA as a sustainable crop production method complementary to the F2F strategy (organic and conventional farming) map out the rural, urban and peri-urban soils across Europe to see where opportunities are for CEA (several to irreversibly degraded soils) integrated soil management strategy including a role for CEA"*
- *There is a need for targeted public campaign on the subject.*
- *Increase resource support (funding, organisational issues) and strong collaborative commitments, improve participation level of farmers, foresters and citizens*
- *Changes in soil management need to take place in practice, but the topic needs to be taken serious in the whole value chain. Farmers need a fair share to make these changes possible. EU wide and not only the good examples, farmers that operate in niches.*
- *If the objectives are met, then a second step must be taken to increase the level of protection intended for by the goals*
- *it will depend on what farmers and land owners want*
- *Comprehensive legal framework that leads to the rapid adoption of sustainable soil and land management practices by all farmers and land managers and phase-out of unsustainable practices through a combination of binding measures including (redirecting of) subsidies, to be applied in all Member States*

When it came to minimize or solve the negative effects that the respondents expected for their organization if the EU Soil Missions objectives would be reached overnight. The following answers were given:

- *less work and shift our work somewhere else*
- *communication*
- *"positive effects shall impact more than negative effects Maximise RDI transfer towards practical implementation.*
- *Promote soil science at training and education levels.*
- *Distribute adequate resources"*
- *Positive effects shall impact more than negative effects*
- *I do not expect negative effects*
- *None*
- *to stop current EU agricultural policy and limit national subvention into the agriculture as they are today, e.g. without environmental dimension*
- *If that is the case, then we will have to adapt.*
- *Development and adoption of specific tools to assess and combat soil degradation*
- *International collaboration and knowledge transfer*
- *"Due to urban complexities, there will be trade-offs (dilemma situations) which need to be addressed.*
- *However, this is negative per se, but something JPI Urban Europe / DUT aims to address. Identifying these dilemmas and working with the complexity is a central element of our work. "*
- *Not a drama, but an overnight change would affect the success rate of getting third party funding (calls addressing topics of the EU Soil Mission) => reasoning: lack of experts required so tackle such challenges (getting the best requires a supportive working environment and a clear understanding at the organization where to go (reliable R&D management, strategic HR and facility management,..)*
- *The legislation includes the requirement (or at least recommendation) to attain higher agricultural education for those wishing to start farming in more than 50 ha areas of arable la*
- *a crisis situation would have to be managed if the demand becomes too great and we do not have enough qualified people to meet it (current lack of training of soil specialists in France)*
- *Recruit new staff to be able to answer to the demand on soil data/soil information and to collect/manage new data*
- *"Avoid re-inventing the wheel.*
- *Make sure you synchronise your finger on the pulse with the activities entrepreneurs are doing, working in the same direction, and focus on funding and supporting those efforts, rather than supplanting.*
- *For example, if you want farmers to capture more carbon in their soils, do not create a single EU standard for measurement and incentive; rather focus on vetting existing initiatives that do a good job, and lead farmers to those initiatives.*

- *Biological diversity is the key to better soil health. In the same sense, enterprise diversity is the key to achieving the EU Soil Mission objectives.*
- *Soil legislation o EU level*
- *If the mission is reached no research on soils would be needed. This is a purely hypothetical question.*
- *There might be an agreement that food security and EU Soil Mission goals would be reached at the same time e.g. to compromise in which areas to focus on food production or restoring degraded land.*
- *There scarcely would be any negative effects for our soils promoting endeavours.*
- *Develop more applied research providing practical and viable solutions for farmers. Increase funding for research and development*
- *The role of the EU to be stronger and force countries for Soil Mission objectives achievement*
- *CEA faces one major hurdle which is the energy footprint. Its carbon footprint is very low if CEA clusters are linked to renewable energies and/or reusable heat waste streams. Hence its appropriateness in urban and peri-urban environments*
- *Reduce all administrative and bureaucratic burden for all actors involved*
- *I don't expect negative effects for our organization*
- *I do not expect negative effects*
- *No negative effects expected (other than that our organisation would not be needed as much anymore, or would refocus its activities, e.g. on services for producers such as making knowledge and information available and building capacity for R&I)*

The final question (Q51) was if respondents could be approached for additional involvement/questions. In this case 100% of the 62 respondents answered positively.

Comments and further involvement

- *In practice it's often more complex. An integrated approach with flexible instruments is needed to tackle the challenges.*
- *We believe, along with many other stakeholders, that EU Green is reachable only if EU goes away from a strong urban -rural divide in its approach to agriculture, land planning and soil management. It is a continuum, with each its specific opportunities. CEA complements a soil restoration strategy by highlighting the potential for food security of urban and peri-urban areas.*

ANNEX X: RELATIONS BETWEEN THE OBJECTIVES AND BUILDING BLOCKS OF THE MISSION FOR SOIL HEALTH AND FOOD AND THE SMS KNOWLEDGE MATRIX

Draft figure: Please note that some connections are stronger than other, some can be missing, and some can be obsolete